

Ramon's Articles PRE and NON-EPEMC

-These are NOT science articles, and are NOT held to EPEMC standards-

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Why Spiritual Pursuit?

Your emotional self belongs to the spirit, and your emotions guide the greater half of your health and your lifestyle, and thus your happiness. I believe in helping someone become strong spiritually, then they can handle almost anything else.

How can I help you become spiritually and emotionally healthy?

I teach according to your needs and your point of view by using these eastern methods.

- Teaching **Daoism (Taoism)** - yang - and **Buddhism** - yin - so that you get a comprehensive perspective
 - May also draw from aboriginal/native cultures, Christianity, and certainly from science.
- Helping you to understand the **8 Universal Laws or "Bagua Dharma"**
 - Using the Bagua Dharma to guide your Destiny ; empower YOU

- Achieve the "meaning of Life" whatever that may be for you.
- Utilizing **Chinese Medical** theory about the psyche and spirit to help you find the root causes of unhealthiness and unhappiness in your life.
- Providing **Chinese Metaphysical Consults**:
 - I Ching
 - BaZi - Four Pillars of Destiny
 - Feng Shui
 - Mian Xiang
 - Tong Shu
 - Bing Fa
- Using physical activity to strengthen the body, exercise the spirit, and calm the mind
 - **Gung Fu**
 - **Tai Ji Quan (Tai Chi) or other Nei Jia**
 - **Qi Gong (meditation)**
- Enhancing your basic Life Vibration so you can move from your current station in life - job, social , intellectual, financial status - to the one which you wish to achieve and inhabit.
- Helping you (by aiding you) to find your Purpose in life, and develop your Mission, without which no one can say they are fulfilling their basic potential and achieving lasting success in this life.

Recommended Readings

Title	Genre/Subject	Main Reason	Buy, Borrow, Download
<u>Art of War</u>	Chinese Classic	THE definitive masterpiece of strategy...	Download
<u>Lotus Sutra</u>	Buddhism	You will attain enlightenment.	Download
<u>Desiderata</u>	European Mysticism	Supplemental to Tao Te Ching	Download
<u>Musashi's Book of 5 Rings</u>	Japanese Classic	Musashi was THE eminent swordmaster... learn from the source.	Download

<u>Tao Te Ching</u>	Chinese Classic	the way that can be walked is not the Way.	Download
<u>Musashi</u>	Japanese Classic	The Gone with the Wind of Japan, Yoshikawa's timeless masterpiece	Buy
<u>How to Multiply Your Baby's Intelligence</u>	Self-help	break unsaid paradigms that hold your family back.	Buy
	Health & Longevity	a 1600s Samurai gives the key to correct living	Buy
<u>Taoist I Ching</u>	Chinese Classic	Most expedient means to attain the Meaning of Life and accomplish all goals/dreams	Buy
<u>Shaolin-Do: Secrets from the Temple</u>	Shaolin	A classic in the genre	Buy
<u>Think and Grow Rich</u>	Self-help	one of 4 main classics in the genre	Buy
<u>In Defense of Food</u>	Truth Movement	Do you not eat real food? How do you know, and what can you do to change this?	Buy
<u>Rich Dad, Poor Dad</u>	Self-help	One of 4 classics in the genre	Buy
<u>Silmarillion, The</u>	Fantasy	Just reading this will enhance your English vocab and give you wisdom	Buy
<u>Science and Art of Tracking</u>	Survival-awareness	Learn the secrets of master trackers	Buy
<u>See You at the Top</u>	Self-help	one of the 4 main classics of the genre	Buy

The I Ching

Spirituality & Divination

The foreward in this book by Carl Jung is excellent.

Borrow

Eat This, Not That (series)

Truth Movement

most people need help getting started changing their diet... it's a good guide.

Borrow

Fast Food Nation

Truth Movement

an instant classic, goes well with Super-size Me, the movie

Borrow

Web That Has No Weaver

TCM

classic book for newbies

Borrow

5 Universal Constants

Nothing has perplexed scientists and mathematicians as long as why pi, for instance, is set to its particular value.

Pi, discovered in the time of ancient Greece was a particularly intriguing constant. First it is irrational, and never repeats unlike $1/3$ or 0.3333333 etc... Secondly, it goes on like this forever, unlike say $1/4$ which is 0.25 . Finally, it is associated with the most perfect shape known, the circle.

The circle is the symbol of perfection, emptiness (zero, wu), completeness, cyclical things like seasons, it is useful for forming balls, wheels, storage containers, etc... and portions of it, used as arcs, are incredibly strong.

For the longest time, in fact, because of the assumption of Heaven's perfection it was assumed not just that the sun and stars went round the Earth but also that they did so in a perfect circle, which later turned out not to be true.

This error was later repeated in the formation of the atomic model, which had perfect circular rotations of the electrons around the nucleus.

Pi even became the subject of a cult classic film, in which the eccentric mathematician and main character uses Pi to start predicting things like the stock market¹, and is accosted by people who want to know the number because it is the true name of God. (Thus pi-worship has not ended).

Later in mankind's history, during various movements, four more important numbers came to be known as "holy" numbers.

- i - the imaginary number or root of -1, which was for a time assumed to be akin to an endless staircase, something conceivable in mind only, but not "real", hence the name.
 - As it turns out i is absolutely necessary for explaining myriad things in modern engineering, not the least of which: electricity and magnetism which are completely dictated by Euler's formula
- e - Euler's² number, which is slightly smaller than pi. This number has to do with what are called "**natural logarithms**" which are derivatives of exponential functions. e is the special number (he discovered) such that $\ln[e] = 1$
- c - the speed of light. Known as "the" constant due to Einstein's cultural influence of his famous formula $E=mc^2$. However, he did not discover the speed of light... that had been reasonably well calculated since the mid-19th century. What Einstein did was to discover that space and time were part of the same fabric and that c acted as a constant observer and cosmic speed barrier for massive objects (though now we know the Universe itself expanded faster than light in its beginning). It is a whopping 300,000,000 or three hundred million meters per second, roughly 586,000 miles per second. Be sure to review the last article about Relativity.
- h - Planck's constant is a different sort of number. It is quite small, 6.626×10^{-34} Joule-seconds and is a number which is used to discover the ultimate vibration frequency and wavelength of a mass, be it particle or planet.

What is interesting about these irrational numbers (and i) is not that they exist, but that they keep showing up in simple, elegant formulas.

From wikipedia

As quantum mechanics was developed, it was found that very often when h appeared in equations, it was divided by 2π . The reduced Planck constant,

$$\hbar = \frac{h}{2\pi}$$

There is the ever amazing Euler's formula

$$e^{ix} = \cos x + i \sin x$$

Where x is frequently replaced with radians (theta) or 180 degrees/ 2π .

Here's a funny little dandy

$$e^{i\pi} = -1$$

Which immediately you see the connection to i , π , and e .

Ultimately, of course, h and c can also be tied together... from physics.nist.gov...

The quantity α was introduced into physics by A. Sommerfeld in 1916 and in the past has often been referred to as the Sommerfeld fine-structure constant. In order to explain the observed splitting or fine structure of the energy levels of the hydrogen atom, Sommerfeld extended the Bohr theory to include elliptical orbits and the relativistic dependence of mass on velocity. The quantity α , which is equal to the ratio v_1/c where v_1 is the velocity of the electron in the first circular Bohr orbit and c is the speed of light in vacuum, appeared naturally in Sommerfeld's analysis and determined the size of the splitting or fine-structure of the hydrogenic spectral lines. Sommerfeld's theory had some early success in explaining experimental observations but could not accommodate the discovery of electron spin. Although the Dirac relativistic theory of the electron introduced in 1928 solves the main aspects of the problem of the hydrogen fine-structure, α still determines its size as in the Sommerfeld theory. Consequently, the name "fine-structure" constant for the group of constants below has remained:

$$\alpha = \frac{e^2/\hbar c}{4\pi\epsilon_0} = \frac{\mu_0 c e^2}{2h}$$

The fine-structure constant α is of dimension 1 (i.e., it is simply a number) and very nearly equal to 1/137. It is the "coupling constant" or measure of the strength of the electromagnetic force that governs how electrically charged elementary particles (e.g., electron, muon) and light (photons) interact.

This elegant little formula has a yin yang relationship wherein it contains so many irrational/infinite numbers, and yet is simple and self-contained... truly the very example of the Law of Conservation. Or if you like, the Buddhist concept that the universe exists but does not exist, is void but has form, etc...

Take what you will from it... you probably already have your opinion. But to keep it lively, let's take a look at a particularly [bizarre gnostic story about math](#):

Ed Leedskalnin, the strange man who built the Coral Gables castle in Florida had a plaque in his bedroom that referred to a Theory of Everything as a ratio between two integers...7129 / 6105195...as quoted at the bottom of the following article:3

One final note: A plaque was found in Ed's bedroom. It read: THE SECRET TO THE UNIVERSE IS 7129 / 6105195. To those of you interested in deciphering this additional mystery: Good Luck!.....end quote.

The integer 37 solves this mysterious ratio...cosine in radians

$$((7129 / 6105195 / -37) - 3) / 10 = \cos (6105195 / 7129)$$

$$-0.30000315593 = -0.300003156397$$

The integer 37 also cracks the ratio to the Feigenbaum constant, ruler of the mandelbrot fractal, chaos to order phase transitions... $F=4.669201609 = \text{Feigenbaum constant} \dots$ tangent in radians

$$(\tan^{-1}(6105195 / 7129 / 37)) + \pi = 4.6692\dots$$

The Leedskalnin ratio also clicks to the Cheops constructs through the amplitude for an electron to emit or absorb a photon, the fine-structure constant... $a(\text{em}) = 137.03599976\dots$ 1998 NIST

$$(6105195 / 7129 / 37)^{-1} - (ht / 2 / bl) = \cos 137.0359815$$

when $ht = \text{height of Cheops pyramid} = 486.256 \text{ ft}$
 $bl = \text{base leg Cheops pyramid} = 763.81 \text{ ft}$

reference Churchill/Massey 1910 expedition to Egypt

$1/137.0359815$ is 99.9999867% of 1998 NIST value

Interesting to note that when Leedskalnin died (1951) the value of the fine-structure was thought to be $\dots a(\text{em}) = 1/137.035978\dots$

Another interesting Cheops constructs form is as follows:

$$6105195 / 7129 / (37^{17}) * (10^{25}) = 10^{(2*ht/bl)}$$

if $ht = 486.2573394\dots$
 $bl = 763.81$

following is the complete article....J.Iuliano

Within the continental United States, there are no pyramids or great stone circles. Surprisingly, the most impressive STONE site in America was built in the 20th Century. Coral Castle, near Homestead Florida, is a mind-blowing mystery. It has been called 'the 8th Wonder of the World.' This 'engineering marvel' contains over 1100 tons of cut and trimmed, dense, coral blocks. The interlocking stones form a castle that were set in place without mortar. Twenty-five miles from Miami, these elegantly carved stones have astronomical alignments.

What amplifies the enigma is that Coral Castle was built SINGLE-HANDEDLY by a small, sickly man named Edward Leedskalnin. Ed only weighed 100 pounds and stood no more than 5 feet tall. How could such a small man, alone and without any equipment, have accomplished this engineering feat? Over 3 million pounds of rock were cut, lifted, transported and set with incredible precision?

In 1919, a young Leedskalnin searched remote areas in Florida for a particular spot of land. He had advanced tuberculosis and was nursed to health by a Mr. Moser and his family. Soon, Ed recovered. He rode his bike and eventually found the place he was looking for. Ed picked the worst acre of land in the state. It was solid bedrock; nothing could grow on it. Mr. Moser gladly gave Ed the land. Later, the Mosers could not believe their eyes. Little Ed had cut and lifted a 10 ton block right out of the bedrock.

Modern engineers were asked: What would it take, with large diamond tools and state of the art machinery, to duplicate Coral Castle? Their answer was: 'It couldn't be done.'

Ed was asked: How did you do it? He would reply: 'It's not difficult, really. The secret is in knowing how.' He was asked: Why did you do it? 'Someday, my Sweet 16 will come,' was always his response.

The hermit constructed his castle in tribute to his Sweet 16. Curious locals came to see what Ed was doing. Leedskalnin had a sixth sense and knew when neighbors approached. He stopped work every time. No one ever saw exactly how the stones were cut and moved. There were a few reports that the rocks moved themselves. (There are similar legends about Easter Island; that the statues moved themselves).

In the 1930s, a gang of thugs thought Ed had hidden riches. They beat him up and tried to rob him. Ed was shocked at this invasion into his private world. The attack motivated Leedskalnin to move Coral Castle! He picked up every megalith (some stones weighed up to 30 tons) and transported his entire castle. He hired a local trucker, but the driver was always directed to look away as Ed loaded the truck. All 3 million pounds of hard coral was moved 10 miles to its present location near Homestead Florida.

Coral Castle took 28 years to complete. Sixty years ago, Ed Leedskalnin would have taken you on a guided tour and only charged you 10 cents. Each piece of his wonderful rock garden would have been explained...with the exception of precisely how it was levitated.

The inspiration for all of Ed's efforts was his Sweet 16. Billy Idol even wrote a song pertaining to this 'lost love.' If you go to Internet sites on C.C., headlines read: 'ONE MAN'S MONUMENT TO UNREQUITED LOVE.' When Ed was 26, Agnes Scuffs rejected him one day before they were to be married. But, she might not have been the real Sweet 16. When asked about Sweet 16, Ed would look to the sky with a glazed expression on his face.

Coral Castle contains amazing stone towers in harmony with nature; the sun; the Moon and the planets. A huge, 9-ton rock that functions as a door is perfectly balanced. One push from a small child can open it. Children are known to be particularly attracted to the castle in the same way they are fond of dinosaurs. Ed shared their same sense of playfulness.

How did Ed construct Coral Castle? The little man only had a fourth grade education back in Latvia. Yet, he possessed the secret of anti-gravity! Ed was very intelligent and a skilled electrical engineer. He experimented with electromagnetism. Leedskalnin demonstrated to neighbors his strange machines. He was able to generate his own electricity. Ed wrote a

total of 5 pamphlets; one called 'Magnetic Current' is as incomprehensible as Einstein's Unified Field Theory. He admitted that he could produce anti-gravity and knew how the ancient pyramids were built.

When Ed lifted the many-ton stones onto the truck away from the driver's view...this probably was done with a small (hand-held) device that created a strong, magnetic field. The apparatus, on the order of a tuning fork, might have vibrated at just the right frequency.

If you see photos of Ed Leedskalnin, you will notice a physical resemblance to Nikola Tesla. He was a small version of Tesla. There are many parallels between the two: Each were thin; had similar faces with drawn-in cheeks; each were European immigrants; they experimented with electromagnetism; each were obsessed with celestial bodies and often seen in formal suits. Were they related? Leedskalnin was a bit younger than Tesla. Tesla said that anti-gravity can be created by a 'rotating magnetic field.' Also, Ed's idea of a special land conducive for his purposes is not different than the Tesla/Matthews concept that the energy is already in the ground; waiting for someone to tap into it. There is no known connection to these two mystery men. But, the similarities are too coincidental to doubt.

Bruce Cathie is a researcher who also has a world map of harmonic grid points. {His map has many more components than my 13-point map. Looking at his map, many of our locations coincide}. He believes that the 'special land' that Leedskalnin searched for and found was positioned on one of these EM vortexes. These power-point, ley lines could have made possible the construction of Coral Castle.

In 1980, a home movie was discovered at C.C. that shows an animated Ed. He was a simple man for all of his advanced intelligence. His neighbors knew him as a kind and gentle soul. In 1951, he died at the age of 64 from malnutrition. Was Sweet 16 a female alien from Venus? Is he with her now?

One final note: A plaque was found in Ed's bedroom. It read: THE SECRET TO THE UNIVERSE IS 7129 / 6105195. To those of you interested in deciphering this additional mystery: Good Luck!

Reincarnation... a scientific perspective

As promised... a supplementary article to develop your understanding of physics and reality.

The subject of the afterlife is a subject no one alive (if indeed only Christ and Buddha did) have the authority to render a decision about. However, perhaps through looking at the various perspectives, we can come to some understanding of one likely possibility of billions of possibilities.

The reason this subject attracts me so much is that so many forms of reincarnation theory exist. It wasn't, in fact, until the Aryans and their nomadic views of Hell - which were very different from current beliefs common today - invaded the valleys of Mesopotamia and Ganges that non-reincarnation became the standard western view.

Though it is true the Egyptians had their views of afterlife being a judgment, the concept still remained a form of "life after death." Even the far north Norsemen, before believing in Valhalla (Heaven) believed in an after-life.

Reincarnation, or the after-life, has some form almost anywhere on Earth. Modern research seems to indicate that the concept of eternal judgment seemed to have started in the Greek and Aryan societies and entered Hebrew and later Arabic philosophy around the time of the agricultural revolution¹ when great heaping piles of human refuse, which did not rot away but lay in stinking mounds outside the cities, became the human model for poverty and Hell.

Indeed the concept around the world, of a Hell and therefore, hopefully, a Heaven seemed to have emerged from the result of economics and city-life... the stratification of human existence² that formed when the tribe was replaced by the clan and then by the castes and

classes of nobility, priests/monks, warriors, farmers, and un-touchables (widows, disabled, filth cleaners, butchers, minorities, gays and other "unmanly men", prostitutes, etc....). This was between 3,000 and 5,000 years ago depending on the area you look at.

So why was reincarnation the primary world-view before that, and why was it replaced - in some places - with Heaven and Hell unending? The answers are easy, if you look at it the right way (in a quantum sense of right)³. Prior to civilization, mankind lived in accordance with nature, in its cycles of birth and death. Energy/Qi came to a being or plant, thrived for a time on the arc of life⁴, then passed away. If an animal, it was eaten. If a plant, it shriveled, rotted, and turned to dirt. Ashes to ashes, dust to dust as the 'Good Book' says.

People literally saw life as a gift that was repeatedly given and taken away, obviously to be given again. But when mankind started to manipulate the laws to suit himself, human conditions arose and life, for most people, became a struggle of work, toil, sickness, loss, and death⁵... and this negative outcome created a negative worldview... Eternal Hell.

But without hope, life is not worth living, and not worth living well; hope springs eternal and if you've had a child, you'd know why. In proof that deep down, Man is good, he also created eternal Heaven and gave specific rules to get there. For the Norsemen it was being a worthy and honorable warrior. For the Hebrews it was reverence for the One God and sacrifice. For the Christians, it became Christ. For the Egyptians, it was a judgment of sins levied on a scale (and this concept was very popular everywhere).

Only in places of aboriginal culture did the previous view of shifting Spirit forms and transference of energy, remain, and in India, where the Aryans mixed with the Indians and Hinduism was born with its many gods (or Krishna) and reincarnation became a tool of punishment or reward, based on quality of life.

But in the "Far East" the view of the After Life remained an interesting mixture of shaman Spiritualism, (like Shintoism), immortality and heavenly realm(s) that are all over, above and below, and on either side, and also Hell for those that were bad, but it was not eternal necessarily.

When Buddhism arrived, Buddha succinctly combined - and this is to his credit - people's understandings of reincarnation with these multi-varied realms, dimensions, etc... so that 1) people would not be turned away by non-existence and 2) they would understand that no matter WHAT the circumstance of the after-life, it led to suffering, and therefore Nirvana was the escape⁶. Later schools were divided as to how this was exactly achieved, but the result was tremendous for the East... wherever Buddhism went it successfully mixed with the cultures there. There is some speculation its influence spread even to Jesus in Jerusalem, and it certainly is known to have spread as far west as Persia by the 4th century CE.

In China, Nirvana was a matter of the Void, or Wu... and attainable for the Sages... and yet Chinese philosophy had an emphasis on longevity and reaching immortality. This created a very interesting dichotomy of yin/yang, which proved to the Chinese both were possible/probable.

Meanwhile in the West and in Africa, where Christianity and Islam, its cousin in combat but also in background had long embraced the idea of permanent Judgment and Salvation rather than Enlightenment as a form of escape. For them, after-life was a goal (unlike Buddhism=non-existence or Daoism=immortality) and a GOOD afterlife was **the** goal. Each has its paths there.

More importantly for our discussion, later the science arrived and biology, chemistry, and Newtonian physics began to show that our bodies were not spiritual, but mechanical and when we died... they just died. So after-life was permanent after all... permanently black and non-real. Swaths of scientists and their convinced high class (re: rich) believers bailed from spirituality and became atheists, saying that without "proof" the only opinion that made sense was that you just died, and that was it. This negative world-view had an

immediate, lasting, and devastating impact.

Our western culture forgot the Tree of Life and embraced money as a "god" and the economy of technology and war. Steadily, as human life has become less important, less unique, less spiritual, civilian deaths have made up ever increasing percentages in war until now, soldiers don't even have to die... they can bomb from remotely operated vehicles and then go home and kiss their wives, safely away from combat by half the world.

Yet, we all now live under the consistent, dominant threat of Total Annihilation - a true Judgment Day or Armageddon... not God's, but our own 'misjudgment' of what's valuable in life. I am reminded of the lines from Genesis, spoken some 5,000+ years ago around campfires warning children not to engage in judgment of each other: God said to Adam (Man),

*"You are free to eat from any tree in the garden;
but you **must not eat from the tree of the knowledge** of good and evil⁷,
for **when you eat of it you will surely die.**"*

So now, the ultimate irony is this. In the 20th century Einstein, a giant among men, and thousands of others who discovered Quantum theory have found that indeed the Universe is not "mechanical" at all.. that we really don't know how space-time works thoroughly. That in fact more dimensions, stranger than thought do probably exist. That there are 100 billion **known** galaxies in our single Universe, which is larger than can be seen and is accelerating apart even as we speak. That there are thousands of Earth-like planets in our own galaxy, each capable of life.⁸

That there is such a thing as anti-matter and Dark Energy/Matter. That in fact, without the imaginary number i (root of -1), you could not even explain something as simple as

electromagnetism! That all of these findings have deep, **profound** meaning behind our understanding of consciousness, existence, and how we treat the world and others.

That in fact our very 3D/4D view may be simply a holographic projection from the edge of the Universe itself... not even experienced as it really is.⁹

Western gurus, versed in this new quantum-relativity or "**string**" like view of the Universe are coming to the SAME conclusions as Buddhists and Daoists and other mystic systems came to long ago... that we are empty in form, unique in essence, products of a special evolutionary law that creates order from Chaos and binds humanity and living things together in a complex web known as an ecosystem,¹⁰ and may in fact be part of a larger neural network of some higher-dimensional God.¹¹ That if you know how, you can in fact totally alter your outcomes, **health**, happiness, existence ***with mere thought alone...***

They've discovered all of that only in the last 50 or 60 years in the West, so we are still bridging the gap to the East.

And then I am reminded of the old views of Reincarnation. Is it then possible... just maybe... that there is a scientific view?

I posit to you, reader, that it's not just possible, scientifically speaking it's a probability. Did you know that the atoms within you right now are nearly as old as the Universe itself? They were not created in our sun, but in a giant star after the Big Bang, when a super-**supernova** exploded and shot these heavy elements out into the Void and they congealed over aeons of time, indeed as Buddhists say Asamkayas of Kalpas, beyond count or reckoning, and when the time was right, the essence correct, and the 5 Elements were in balance on our planet, life spontaneously formed and 3 Billion years later here you are reading this.

Do you know that amount of time is relatively the same as the passage of time, relative to an atom's rotation time, that it will take light to leave your screen and pass into your brain and be evaluated as a thought... and that this distance covered is practically zero to light, yet is still long enough, far enough for light to appear as eons of time to a rotating atom of hydrogen floating around??

Literally you are the reincarnation of dead stars, dead microbes, dead animals and plants, things you've eaten, Entangled energy and Qi from the essence of things you've absorbed... even this text, which after I've died leaves my Spirit within you...

In fact, if you understand the Law of Conservation rightly... there is no passage of Time, only Nowness and your observation of it is a matter of Relativity... meaning that eons have passed since you began reading it... and you and I have died and been reborn with each Universe already countless asamkya of times... continuously sitting here, reading that which we already know - which defines ourself, the one Source, and binds us to existence... repeating information which causes Creation to exist at all, simply because that is the function of our function.

Indeed, this is the inexorable result of all the research, all the spiritual pursuits and philosophers... that in the end we are that unique a being and we are meant to discover this... even if we have to do it the hard way and ignore that which was already understood long before.

This is the form of Reincarnation that science has revealed... and is verified in the 8 Laws, especially in Evolution and Conservation.

As for Heaven and Hell, I want to the reader to understand that this does not invalidate any belief system at all.. indeed it is all a greater subset of the larger knowledge.¹² That if you are even miserable, even for a moment, this is Hell for eternity... and if you are in ecstasy or feeling "saved" or "enlightened" this is Heaven for an eternity... such is the Law of Conservation. Its wonder and amazement is without calculation in meaning or profundity. Even if I tried I could not cease to extol its amazing virtues. Indeed as we sit here together, reader, you understanding and absorbing this and assimilated these thoughts, we are reaffirming this amazement for all time, fulfilling the function of creating order where there is Chaos.

It is my personal religious belief that when we share these understandings, new Universes are created and the Dark Energy needed is in fact just thought energy... and that the anti-matter and matter formed are the counterbalances that serve to keep Conservation together... and the "taxes" paid to do this creation is the subsequent death of other Universes like ours which have fulfilled their end of the reincarnated cycle... their beings having JUST now... no JUST now, etc... completed their path to evolving to this profound understanding as one great Being that is all encompassing... that is defined by the very Laws that underwrite him/her/it.

I want to you understand it is not important to dwell on this, or run around in awe of the Nowness, unless that is your function in this incarnation... to be the weirdo in society. **It is only important that you find the Way and the Meaning of Life**, as it pertains to your "department" in this great "government."

Go now and when you step outside, breath fresh air (while you can), and feel the grass... see the trillions of unconscious life forms with your mind's eye and how they move and wiggle in Nowness... in the **Life Aquatic**, and realize only your mind and spirit, among all these trillions, can move forward and backward in time, move matter as it wills, change destiny and shake the world, literally... that you are the incarnation of God as God wants and needs you to exist at this level... whatever you do in life, whether remain lowly or ascend.

I will explain various aspects of the Universe as it pertains to the harder to understand concepts in the Metaphysics section in a separate article. Go there if you wish to understand a little more thoroughly the concepts of folded space and time, inter-dimensions, anti-matter, dark energy, imaginary numbers, light, relativity, etc... They aren't important, what's important is APPLICATION of knowledge and wisdom, but if you WISH to, that's where to learn more.

1. Agricultural Revolution - when man began to sow and reap, rather than hunt and gather... the beginning of city life began humbly as a means to protect the tribe. It was frequently abandoned in America, but took firm root in the other "cradles" of civilization. Prompting the story of Cain and Abel from Genesis Chapter 4.
Now Abel kept flocks, and Cain worked the soil. 3 In the course of time Cain brought

some of the fruits of the soil as an offering to the LORD. **4** But Abel brought fat portions from some of the firstborn of his flock. The LORD looked with favor on Abel and his offering, **5** but on Cain and his offering he did not look with favor. So Cain was very angry, and his face was downcast.

6 Then the LORD said to Cain, "Why are you angry? Why is your face downcast? **7** If you do what is right, will you not be accepted? But if you do not do what is right, sin is crouching at your door; it desires to have you, but you must master it."

8 Now Cain said to his brother Abel, "Let's go out to the field." ^[d] And while they were in the field, Cain attacked his brother Abel and killed him.

9 Then the LORD said to Cain, "Where is your brother Abel?"

"I don't know," he replied. "Am I my brother's keeper?"

10 The LORD said, "What have you done? Listen! Your brother's blood cries out to me from the ground. **11** Now you are under a curse and driven from the ground, which opened its mouth to receive your brother's blood from your hand. **12** When you work the ground, it will no longer yield its crops for you. You will be a restless wanderer on the earth."

13 Cain said to the LORD, "My punishment is more than I can bear. **14** Today you are driving me from the land, and I will be hidden from your presence; I will be a restless wanderer on the earth, and whoever finds me will kill me."

15 But the LORD said to him, "Not so ^[e] ; if anyone kills Cain, he will suffer vengeance seven times over." Then the LORD put a mark on Cain so that no one who found him would kill him. **16** So Cain went out from the LORD's presence and lived in the land of Nod, ^[f] east of Eden.

2. Here i am making a specific reference to the Buddhist concept of the 10 Worlds or Realms of cosnsciousness
 1. Hell - lowest form... misery and suffering unending
 2. Animals - pure aggression and lust, but at least animals don't know they are miserable
 3. Hungry Ghosts - pure greed, nothing is enough, no matter what goes into the Void inside... like a black hole consuming light even. Think of drug addicts or sex addicts, corrupt politicians, etc...
 4. Anger - rage, hatred, doubt, cynicism, etc...
---end of lowest four realms of most unhappy souls
 5. Tranquility - serenity, peace, calmness... too often short and fleeting in life
 6. Heaven - joy, love, any form of happiness, also fleeting or subject to changes. Love is very great, but for people of the lower six realms, it too has no permanence... only those of the upper 4 realms find lasting true love as they harmonize with the love of God, which has no end nor source separate from itself.
---end of lower six realms, the 95% of human existence and 95% of the population are here 95% of the time
 7. Student or "voice hearer" - easiest of the upper four to get into, easiest to fall out of or lose one's motivation

8. Self-realized or "pratyekabuddha" - good as a lower vehicle, will end outflows, give one satisfaction, but it self-centered, and without ability to aid others, nor even compassion to do so. Often leads to remoteness, isolation, cynicism, and acceptance of not attaining the Meaning of Life
9. Teacher or "bodhisattva" - literally the teachers of the Law, their compassion requires more dedication than others... and they forsake the bliss of being alone and "without sin, like an elephant wandering in the forest," not because they want fame and success, but because of love and compassion.
---end of 9 realms of "angels" or spirits of various service to God; the lowest four were demons/devils, the upper 5 were servants of God and the Buddhas who spin their "wheel of Dharma" for others.
10. Enlightenment/Salvation or "buddhas" - the realm of those that understand the laws/ singular Law, perceive phenomena of existence and non-existence equally, and can describe it for others... they are full of love and compassion. Guatama, Jesus, Ghandi, Martin Luther King Jr., Nelson Mandela, Mother Theresa, the Dalai Lama, etc...
---end of 10 worlds of human consciousness
11. "I am"

It must be understood that each of these exists within the other, and each again, and in the three-fold world of Heaven, Earth, and Man, this makes 3,000 realms... or more. This means at any moment, for example, you may feel awful (1) but see Heaven(6), and know peace and compassion (9) because of it... and this energy is felt everywhere and shared everywhere (11).

You resonate in one or two levels, but you experience them all.

3. Meaning without judgment, more about how you ask the question than what the result is. Innocently seeking answers, not with an agenda except to know and hear Truth.
4. The "arc of life" refers to the bell curves [of the 95/5 rule] which explain how things have a beginning, middle, and an end. These curves follow sinusoidal patterns, which are, as a rule in every mathematical formulation of physics and chemistry because of the Law of Rotation and Law of Vibration.
5. The **Four Noble Truths** and **Eightfold Path** to extinguishing the cycle of suffering was the first sutra/sermon Shakyamuni Buddha gave after achieving a homeostasis (stability) of the 10th World.
It is important to point out that as soon as one realizes this... and has even a moment of enlightenment to its truth, whether you continue on in that view or not, you have had a moment of clarity and Truth... and thus achieved extinguishment or Nirvana. Parinirvana would be if you had this thought *even as you died... **and hopefully your whole life remembered it before that.***
6. Nirvana, as a goal, is rather a pointless pursuit. In fact the more sought/grasped for, the harder to get. This much was revealed later to the voice hearers and pratyekabuddhas in the end of his life Mahayana sutras of Heart, Diamond, and Lotus of the Wonderful Law. Nirvana is a state of mind... a choice that takes advantage of the Law of Rotation.

Living in Nirvana and achieving Parinirvana at the end of life, is however, a matter of raising one's energy state, or Vibration to a level... and usually the final jump requiring some form of emotional shock. The shock that enables one to receive this Dharma and know its truth is the Bodhicitta.

The Bodhicitta, however, does not enable one to remain permanently in Buddhahood. That method is, for most of us, a matter of just remembering to choose it. But for some... they have **Satori** and achieve this energy state. They are known around the world as gurus and self-help experts (the real ones at least) and they are a joy to be around.

7. The only Tree in the "garden" that was forbidden. Why? Typically it's taught that this was a test of loyalty. For a child, this is a good moral, but it isn't obviously, accurate.

It was forbidden because it wasn't a real tree, but a figure of speech for a body of knowledge about judging the good and evil of people and our worlds... which was supposed to belong to the Divine. Or so sayeth the creators of the story.

Ironically, the people who wrote the story down were not the creators, but their conquerors, which had long ago learned the life of Cain and been judging what was good and evil daily. They had human laws and grew crops and waged war. And all of these people either died out - as a people - or were absorbed by more aggressive such cultures... thus Vengeance for slaying of Cain was sevenfold.

- 8.

9. **Yes, just like the baseball cards of the 1990s... a hologram.**

10. Much akin to the "jeweled net" of Buddhism wherein each net is bound at the knot with a jewel that reflects all other jewels. Much like the image of the Universe forming...

11. 100 billion galaxies in a Universe... 100 billion stars in a galaxy... 100 billion neurons in a brain... what will happen when there are 100 billion sentient beings in our "department"? Who knows.

12. Like this image, please understand that our "massiveness" dictates we haven't omnipotence of Light Perspective. Therefore we can only have a finite amount of the Matrix of Knowledge overall, which extends to infinity and has infinite dimensions.

Advanced Bagua Dharma Theory

Preface

It will be difficult to understand any of this without a thorough working knowledge of the language of the Bagua Dharma and *nearly visceral knowledge of it*.

Theoretically speaking, this article could be understood, but the exercise of doing it would only be to 'study ahead' or perhaps further understand the basic concepts themselves.

If you choose to go ahead in reading this without having truly studied the BD til you know it like the back of your hand, then do so at your own risk. Worse than not understanding something is in discarding or disregarding it out of contempt, so guard against your hypothalamic instincts.

"Abandon all hope ye who enter here."

How the Laws Govern The Universe

In the beginning, I tell students, **"Study the Law of Harmony, know it well, and change karma this way."**

When they are a bit learned, I tell them, **"Know the vibrations, and set your vibrations as often as possible to the 11th Realm or to your environment."**

When they are in the intermediate stages I tell them, **"Study the Law of Relativity, see the yin and yang in all things, and know all things are possible."**

This, for the most part will suffice to get anything you want in life. For the icing, heck learn the 95/5 Rule and you're set.

But the big kicker is, this is only good for getting what **you** want. But what about the great things: what the Universe wants and what you need and what your environment needs?

Normally I would say the Law of Harmony solves that but the thing is people can choose to be out of harmony when it feels good. When you want to be unhappy and angry, you can sever yourself... that is allowed. Believe me it's a fun choice, for the time being.

But as you mature you're not supposed to want to be like a rebellious teenager with your parents... you are supposed to be steadfast and stalwart. We are tested upon our forbearance, patience, and forgiveness. We can pretend to have these things in plenty supply but all the time we lose 'control' and act like children: and **that's when the trouble comes**.

You do NOT have to be perfect and never lose your cool in order to study the advanced subjects. Rather, studying the advanced subjects will help you overcome that tendency - over time, of course.

The way I teach I divide everything into two groups of knowledge: basic and advanced. Basic means essential. Many times students wonder why I teach the 'practical' after the 'theoretical'.

Why? Because it is principle that matters and what good is practical skill if you don't know why it works: that's just living off a myth. Hey myths work great, but it wouldn't be the science of Bagua Dharma if you had to just apply some tools and get results.

Develop skills, then get more tools. Would you give a wet-behind-the-ears carpenter a rotating saw? He'd cut off his fingers and then blame you!

I don't want to be blamed for student's lack of success. I say, **"Learn the principles to give you the skill, then learn some techniques to hone your abilities."**

One of the new principles that will enable honing of skills (taught in the course) is that of how the Laws actually go about governing, besides just being formulas and whatnot.

The way the Laws govern is through interdependence, much as a mother and father raise a child. Through the Law of Polarity itself, each of the eight laws makes up half a pair, making four basic inter-relationships. This is similar to their being four basic forces in the Universe.

1. **Karma - Vibration (Strong)**

The Law of cause and effect takes causes and produces the synchronistic and multi-varied effects by continuing the vibrational outflows of the cause (intention, orientation, impact, energy, extent, follow-through, etc...). The Law of vibration receives the directive of the heavenly principle of Karma and the physical matter of the Universe (yin) attunes to the effects to produce causes at the particular moment set. There are dampened or latent effects or instant, inherent effects. The way these two interact forms the very basis of the human psyche and the entire Karmic process within the mind.

2. **Evolution - Rotation (Weak)**

Wind penetrates, Thunder moves. Nothing moves more universally than wind and nothing faster than Thunder (here represented by Lightning, which the Chinese considered one principle). Where the Law of Evolution governs changes in the physical plane, the Law of Rotation governs action in the physical plane. You perceive and then you react.

Also the Law of Evolution may govern change in say biology or seasons or even lives, but it is the Law of Rotation that makes them karmically cycle and provides the basis for scientific observation. While the Law of Rotation may govern activity it is the Law of Evolution, informed by Karmic precision that determines the expression of the activity (aka timing). One word said the same way but at different times can have totally different impacts. This is the subtly of Wind.

3. **Relativity-Polarity (Electromagnetic)**

The classic case of left vs. right, liberal vs. conservative, black/white vs. gray areas (or the rainbow!) On the one hand the Law of Polarity gives us dual expressions of reality, while on the other hand it is always divisible and changes so effervescently that realistically we can only experience it in our own relative terms. While one side begs to see the whole the other side begs to see the difference.

The existence of both does not negate the existence of either. There is good and evil and yet some will see good and perceive evil and others see evil and perceive good, for

example. This is why it is important to know karmic principle because only a King can decide.

If something is evil the outcome will produce evil, and if good it will produce good. There may always be a person who protests on their behalf, but compared to the 95%, the 5% must have a very strong argument to be able to overcome the solidity of true yang and true yin. Meanwhile the dualist perspective must simply allow for a relative viewpoint, thus enabling the true yin principle and it will soften the Law of Relativity instantly. It is like the case of a wife and husband... if he can but put things in the right way she will agree, but the principle must be observed!

4. **Conservation-Resonance (Gravity)**

Stillness matched with stillness. One lonely, one nurturing and forthgiving. One Law states that all things exist, the other determines what they exist with, stating that nothing can remain in harmony with that which is not the same vibrational 'tune.'

It is the principle of the idea of possibility that gives resonance opportunity (and governs the 95/5 rule). If there were fewer possibilities, say only a finite number, then the choices we had would be limited, and out would go free-choice and destiny guidance. But also if not all possibilities existed then there wouldn't be the fate of Karma either.

Conservation states that there is no flow of time, only perception of its passage via momentum. Resonance says that without momentum nothing could tune with anything else (no rotation, no vibration, no evolution, and no Karma!). This 'cosmic glue' draws together aspects as abstract as a Picasso painting and certainly more bizarre and useful. It is for that reason that I recommend study of Conservation even though it is the most difficult to believe.

These four primary relationships are further combined into the interaction of four primary Laws and four secondary Laws.

- **Karma+Vibration+Polarity+Relativity govern the activity of the internal environment**
- **Evolution+Conservation+Rotation+Resonance govern the activity of the external environment**

So within the primal yin/yang relationship taught at the basic level (yin right, yang left), we see also there is yin and yang between individual laws and then also between internal and external tendencies.

Then again there are the Six levels (according to Chinese Philosophy) that govern the fruition of influence of laws upon the situation and the body and spirit:

1. **Taiyin - Karma-->Evolution**
2. **Shaoyin - Relativity->Conservation**
3. **Jueyin - Vibration**

4. **Taiyang - Rotation**
5. **Yangming - Polarity**
6. **Shaoyang - Resonance-->Karma**

This order is **the order that most represents the procession from birth to death and from ignorance to wisdom**. The fact is of course that the greatest yang is in youth and so it is of course better to acquire wisdom young and come to fruition over a lengthy period. But the movement of the body towards decline (from Heaven to Earth) is nevertheless that realization which gives us the power to complete the cycle, attain the Meaning of Life, and use these Laws to advance the spirit back to Heaven.

There are also the Five Elements to consider

- **Fire - Polarity and Karma**; this element represents clinging and yet also illumination/enlightenment. One must know the dualities and choose the yang principle, and yet also know the singular principle of Karma and the truth of oneself to overcome clinging and attain mastery.
- **Earth - Conservation, Vibration, and Harmony**; These three Laws govern all that nourish in stillness and provide tranquility and disseminate the Heavenly Principle in the Universe. It is Conservation that makes all things possible, Vibration that sets them in their places, and Harmony that keeps the order amidst the chaos
- **Metal - Rotation**; the cutting, decisive nature of activity which is best summed up in the relationship of the metal organs: one takes in the heavenly Qi (lungs), one rids the body of the turbid, earthly yin waste (colon). The Law of Rotation is often about letting go of previously held beliefs or other views that are no longer valid for the present situation. After all, most things in our life have daily or even hourly changing hexagrams to govern them. But even tense long standing situations will change. Rotating with the Dao is all important to keeping up with the present. The reason the Law of Karma is so brutal is so few people keep up with the changing energies.
- **Water - Relativity and Harmony**; These two laws represent polar differences in their functions. One causes difference amongst people to become obvious and gives us our free will; the other causes divisions to cease and restore heavenly unification and enable the righteous man/woman to complete one's purpose in life and attain earthly desires through Karmic reward. These are the Kidney Yin and Kidney Yang in the medicine; one the ultimate source of nourishment and one the ultimate source of movement. Though it seems things may not move unless they are in Harmony, in fact the Universe/God always moves things in Harmony. If they are not in Harmony they simply remain separate in form. If they can harmonize then they will morph into new substances, situations, relationships, etc... this is the truth of the Law of Harmony. Our misperceptions of it are indeed only due to the Law of Relativity which is wisely set to keep us ignorant of the Divine Order in every little detail. This is how we are nourished by our relative ignorance. Though it does not remain an excuse to be ignorant, the more one knows these laws and It All, the more the ignorance becomes a comfort from the increased responsibilities.

- **Wood - Evolution**; the precise mystical coupling of the Law of Harmony and Law of Karma produces the physical output of changes in all that we see. It is through the activities taking place in the chaotic computational data field of the Law of Conservation that different outcomes chosen from the Law of Vibration, Rotation, and Polarity come to be for us to perceive them in the Law of Relativity. This Element is the executor, and unlike a human minister **it is always filial to the precise order of Laws**. It is not like Greek Gods or other deities that may defy natural order... it always obediently produces the results, across all dimensions, in every existence, on all planes, and in all realms. Thus the mistakes we see are not faults of the computational engine of Reality, but rather faults in our sensation and perception meant to teach us something we did not remember from before (or know before?)

These are the various ways in which the laws enact and enforce the Tian-Ren-Di mandate.

The Heavenly Mandate

Tian-Ren-Di or Heaven-Man-Earth or more scientifically Universe-Sentience-Existence or more religiously God-Adam-Eden or more pagan Great Spirit-spirit world-Great Mother (Gaia), etc... is the original holy trinity.

These three planes are not merely that which gives shape, hue, and texture to our Universe via the 3 Axes, but they form a cohesive function with the 8 Laws.

Firstly the Mandate forms the precise mathematical alignment of the Laws, represented most conveniently by using the trigram method (yin=broken line, yang=unbroken line). There are only 8 combinations possibly in using the 3 Planes of existence; hence there are only 8 primary Laws, not 7 nor 9. They are of course all subdivisions of the Grand Law - Law of the Lotus or God - which of course is beyond our capacity to perceive directly. As shown above the laws may be combined in different ways, but ultimately the trigram method best delineates why there are 8 and not any other number. Note: in Buddhism you may hear of '3 laws', this is the Mandate in a different translation, but **this is what the Buddha meant: Dharma-Buddha-Nirvana**.

Secondly the **Mandate forms a bridge between the 4 Yang or Heavenly Laws and the 4 Yin or Earthly Laws**. That bridge is the Qi Ji (Qi machine) or human spirit, mind and body, itself a fractal representation of the Mandate. This means $4+3+4 = 11$ 'units' on the Spiritual Axis.

Finally this third 11, in completing the triple axis (making the Universe Spherical in concept rather than flat and circular) **unites the Lotus Law in its supreme concept**.

- 11 Dimensions of Physical Reality (String Theory)
- 11 Vibratory Realms of Mental-Spiritual psyche (Shen-Hun)
 - **The 11th is also known as the "Singularity" or 11:11:11**
- Evolution+Relativity+Conservation+Vibration+Earth+Man+Heaven+Rotation+Polarity+Harmony+Karma

- 11 Spiritual 'units' in the governing axis

This is the Tian-Ren-Di Mandate or God's Purpose which is to say the Singularity as expressed for sentience to discover.

A side effect of the Mandate is that any being that exists in harmony with this Mandate will be karmically rewarded (maybe over lifetimes or right away, though we may for a time seem punished for knowledge). This is known as attaining the **Meaning of Life** and leads directly to **attaining one's purpose to exist**. This means completing the three bodhis and returning in death to the Source having done all that one could do with what one was given. Failure or success, there is no blame in this, and knowing this and **attaining first bodhi is also known as "the place of security."**

Security means safety, health, and happiness. There is no greater security than the comfort of one's home. When one knows and investigates the Mandate down to the deepest truth of the matter, knowing that above all business, pleasure, and other individual caprices in life **this Mandate comes foremost is the greatest thing anyone can do**. This is called true Faith, *for it is not blind in ignorance nor foolish in acceptance*, it is based in self-evident design, admiration, humility to the Heavenly principles, and cessation of slander: the greatest karmic sin according to the Shakyamuni Buddha and the Christ Buddha - the two foremost bodhisattvas of East and West.

Becoming a Sage Equaling Heaven

The Chinese had a strange concept wherein if one perfected oneself and became like a Daoist Immortal, one could become a great sage equaling Heaven itself. Now practically speaking we know *this is not possible*, for the two greatest Buddhas that ever walked this Earth both demonstrated that only at a high level does the 10th Realm come close enough to touch the 11th (Beyond) Realm, **but still they died to finish this task**.

So we know that we live under Law and not above it.

However, there are 8 Laws and the knowledge of them will automatically ensure not only salvation but extinction because Extinction is the fruit of an Arhat who can perceive the Wu-Void and can set his/her vibration to it. Extinction is what is meant to be near equal to Heaven because the 8th Realm is in Resonance with the 8 Laws - with or without knowledge of them.

But it is the bodhisattva that exceeds Heaven in that Heaven cannot physically nourish or change the destiny of anyone against his/her will. It is the activities of beings, especially sentient ones that move chaos back to order and balance the books, so to speak. If Heaven could move without Life, as some like to philosophically speculate, then it would only move further and further towards chaos, and in the end the Universe would be full of nothing but dissipated heat. It is the organizational structure of life and increasingly so, sentience, that gives reign for the Chaos to spread.

So the bodhisattva, and likewise the mahasattvas and Buddhas who are foremost in using this 9th Realm vibration to surpass the Void, use the Laws both as a child to them (second bodhi) and yet also as a great king (third bodhi). They are a child in wonder, and then a wheel-turning sage-king in their manipulation of the Laws to further correct orientation all around them.

The practice of this is the second and third bodhis which enable them to be humble and yet powerful in the same swipe of the brush.

Not everyone wishes nor is destined to do this in a lifetime though all have the seeds of Buddhahood within them. Only one who follows the Mandate, adheres to the changes of the Dao, maintains rectitude and humility in wonder at the cosmic design, and promotes the Law fearlessly without fear of loss of life can become a "Sage Equaling Heaven." No Arhat nor learner-adept can do it... they haven't the humility nor knowledge, respectively, to do this great task. **It is the humble bodhisattva that makes a great sacrificial vow that will promote and live in the correct nirvana of the Lotus Law.**

The Lotus Law

The **Lotus Law is just another name for the Singularity (11th Realm)**, but in particular is an expression of the wonderful method for instant vibrational achievement of the mind which can cure the worst karmic diseases [like gangbusters!].

The Lotus Law (or Vehicle) says that one leaves the lower six paths (thus advances to Rotation/Thunder) through study under a teacher (choosing the Redeemers' dharma/scripture is salvation), practice in the Void (test of Faith), and healing, preaching, & teaching (the sacrifice of the bodhisattva). **This attainment is the true Nirvana also called anuttara-samyak-sambodhi** and it is a reality that can only be understood and shared between Buddhas.

That means you CAN/DID/WILL understand it IF/WHEN you engage(d) your Buddha nature latent within you.

The Lotus Law is the Mandate in its purest form as **both Void and Reality**, without the first division into yin/yang nor the second division into all things (Tian-Ren-Di). The Lotus Law is God, Truth, Nirvana, Karma itself.

Knowing this Lotus does not make one god-like, but rather tiny and insignificant. You are unique: just like everyone else.

Just knowing the Lotus is not enough, however, it says one must engage the Lotus Law through study, practice, and sharing it. In sharing there are of course good rules of thumb. One should consult the Lotus Sutra and the Daishonin's writings on this matter for clarification (see the Buddhism section).

Relativity and Quantum Theory (Basics)

Prior to the 20th century, mankind honestly thought they almost completely had everything figured out with the revolution in discovering a) electro-magnetic connection (only half of the forces were known), b) evolution (which has since changed much), c) the atomic model (which was not even half right), and d) germ theory (which has turned out to be a major paradigm problem in medicine).

Without going into each much, suffice it to say when Einstein came along and destroyed the Newtonian Universe as we know it... the shift was so powerful that people are still grasping its meaning in the west to this day. Newtonian ideas still plague mainstream society to this day (mostly because they are convenient in application)... and this includes seeing the body as a machine (thank you Descartes! oh honored fool of the age of 'enlightenment').

But as you're about to discover, the world is far more complex, and interesting than a table of billiard balls bouncing around. (Which, after all, did you know do not even touch each other when they do? That sound you hear is the shock wave caused by changes in the solid structure imposed by weak and strong repelling forces, which are much more powerful than electromagnetism holding the ball together).

(Special) Theory of Relativity - the physical aspect of the Law of Relativity

The paper that rocked the world of science, written by a 25 year old clerk and not some iconic genius of the academic world, laid out that the speed of light itself acted as though a cosmic speed barrier which tied the entire Universe into a space-time bundle, rather than them being separate.

$E = mc^2$ became a household phrase, this is true, and it is often the formula cited by non-atheist scientists as the evidence which proves God is basically a math equation.

But the equation you may not be familiar with is this one, which establishes the foundations of Relativity's paradigm changes to Newtonian Physics

$$\Delta t' = \gamma \Delta t = \frac{\Delta t}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}}$$

where

Δt is the time interval between *two co-local events* (i.e. happening at the same place) for an observer in some inertial frame (e.g. ticks on his clock) – this is known as the **proper time**,

$\Delta t'$ is the time interval between those same events, as measured by another observer, inertially moving with velocity v with respect to the former observer,

v is the relative velocity between the observer and the moving clock,

c is the **speed of light**, and

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2}}$$

is the **Lorentz factor**.

Which basically produces this graph about Kinetic Energy (related to speed by Newton's formulas)

This theory helped explain the reason we cannot see Black Holes

In other words, as you approach the speed of light the energy required to move goes to infinity meaning you cannot pass the barrier c thus the "cosmic speed limit" of 3×10^8 (three hundred million) meters per second or $\sim 586,000$ miles/s (that's about 4 moon distances in a second)

Well, as later revealed in Quantum Theory (Law of Vibration) this is not always true, just in cases involving mass.

Before talking about Quantum though, let's list the THREE GREAT changes to the Newtonian Universe

1. There is no constant observer; if an object has mass it is subject to relativity... Now at first this would seem to cause a problem for religion, but that of course is quite false:
 1. God is all the Universe, which is made of matter, anti-matter, dark matter, dark energy, and things we've not even discovered... and all is Void... so not matter. Clearly this does not apply to God.
 2. Thought and spirit are both massless. The body has mass, and when the mind is attached to the body, through the Shen and Po then our thoughts and viewpoints are relative... but whence inspiration and intuition come to the Hun... that has no mass and is pure quanta, the formula for it has not yet been discovered.
2. The faster you move the shorter the distance (in that direction). Thus though the Milky Way is 180,000 light years across in Earth-time... to Light, which travels at c even in its own "reference frame", it takes only 7 seconds.

1. This is important to understand why our Universe may be a cosmic sized brain (of God) and light acts as a neurotransmitter between stars... (another time =D)

2. This means that as your mind, and indeed to a small degree body, moves faster than others' your sense of time perception is altered, and their view of yours as well. This may help explain why a person could travel far away for a time, come back, and to them they feel the same but to all others, they seem as if greatly enhanced and wizened.
3. The speed of light is the same in all reference frames, even its own... meaning that you if you were going 99% the speed of light and turned on a flashlight the light wouldn't be $c+99%$ of c ... it'd still be c to you... just as fast as always, because though to OTHERS you are going 99% of c ... to light you are just going not... c .
 1. This means he who can access the 11th realm (Nirvana) by detaching the Hun from the body in trance... or can live this detached way as a Tathagata (10th realm)... they basically don't just see others POV correctly, **they know others POV as their own.**

That's really all a layperson needs to know about relativity to make some major adjustments in their perspective (in other words, be a 8th/9th realm person)... to have compassion, to cease judging others, to understand that very few people are evil and most of us would make the same mistakes if we had the same knowledge and experiences that other - less worthy person - has.

Do NOT forget the Law of Relativity applies beyond the physical dimension! It is the River trigram... and without it, you are in danger of cutting yourself off from the God-realm simply by imagining your POV is the only one... rendering yourself alone in a sea of sharks.

Quantum Theory (The Laws of Vibration and Rotation)

Einstein himself did not know the door he had opened. Indeed if he'd known the implications, he may never have shared his work with the government later expressing his regret having helped form the atomic bomb. But it was not Einstein who made the progresses needed to develop the hydrogen bomb or other discoveries, like electronmicrography, which helped us figure out DNA and begin genetic modification... our most blatant picking of the fruit of the Tree of Knowledge yet... It was the quantum theorists, which were thousands and now millions of scientists who all started with one goal: fix the atomic model.

You see the original problem with the atomic model as a solar system-like structure is that it should degrade and implode... within seconds. Well, they later discovered that not only were there forces at play within the atom which kept this from happening...

- Weak - the bonds between neutrons and protons
- Strong - the bonds between neutrons which keep electrons from collapsing into the protons
 - both of these are > 1000 times stronger than electromagnetism, already a million times stronger than gravity!

but indeed the fundamental particles do not move in ellipses, they move in waves.

Quantum Field Theory graphed out... beautiful!

The search for the atomic model led to the discoveries which basically form the foundations of quantum theory.

1. Everything is in vibration according to the equation: $E = \frac{hc}{\lambda}$, since $E=mc^2+(1/2)mv^2$, you can equate these and get an important relationship between massive objects and their wave... basically establishing the wave-like behavior of all phenomena... the Law of Vibration
 1. Because a wave is based on Euler's formula, $e^{ix} = \cos x + i \sin x$ we see also that the Law of Rotation also is formed here.
 2. There will be a separate article explaining these special universal constants and their spiritual/mental ramifications (next time!)
2. You cannot know the exact location of a particle AND know its momentum... thus you must choose the question so that you get either a probability density, or the speed you want to know... known as Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle
 1. This means that, due to relativity, you must understand that what you think of, what you ask, what you want to know itself (rather than the answer) can change your entire result,

thus your reaction mentally and emotionally, and therefore your paradigm. Thus one man's garbage is another man's treasure... or perhaps it may even explain why some people see loss and tragedy in one light, and some in another.

3. They discovered a plethora of new particles, by crashing them together, and other strange things which I will write of later.
 1. Indeed they are still discovering new ones... all different according to their "spin".

2. It seems limitless, and in fact String Theorists think these particles are just differing versions of the vibration strings acting according to dimension forces and highly elegant 11th dimensional calculus. Unfortunately no equipment can find these strings as of yet... but the math seems irrefutable. A separate String theory article will come later. **Please go to Wiki to learn more now.**
3. These new particles also led to the discovery of Entanglement, the subject of a **Did You Know, if you are interested in how this plays out in human affairs.**
4. Lastly, and perhaps most importantly of us, Quantum theory established that light (and later all particles) exist in a wave-particle duality (more Law of Polarity beyond Electromagnetism and

yin/yang)

1. This is not at separate times but at all times
2. light comes in quanta called photons, these photons are responsible for the movement of electrons up and down in valence shells of atoms
3. This has led to the discovery of semiconductors, lasers, and almost every aspect of modern computing.
4. These photons are massless and therefore were the first real tie between General theory of Relativity, which is usually used for cosmic sized objects, and micro-sized world of atoms and the electromagnetic spectrum (another article on this later).

In the best sense of this duality, which is profound and difficult to fathom for the mind (like relativity), perhaps we should keep in mind that though our spirit and minds move along upward and downward curves, which are in vibration... indeed it is by the quanta of intuition, experience, wisdom, and insight (from the Beyond) that we grow upward in our own lives like Valence shells. Indeed, if we do not keep moving up, we will expel these and move back towards our 'base state' which we were born with... and this is probably the very foundation to how paradigms and habits work. So today I highly recommend injecting quanta of love and compassion, and wisdom into your life so that your paradigm may shift and your 'base state' move up and even when you fail to act super-humanly... you can still retain a high level of understanding of your fellow Men and Women, and all the living and inert beings of this planet.

The Arc of Opportunity

This is a minor subject, but still very important if not just to keep oneself from unreasonable expectations, heartache and frustration, which will harm one's health of course. To understand this, you should briefly re-familiarize yourself with the 5/90/5 (95/5) rule which is derived from the Bell Curve:

The left 5% corresponds to the opening of opportunity, the right 5% to the close of opportunity, and the center to the peak of opportunity.

It often happens that opportunities come slightly unexpected, and it is nice to know that we do not have to react to opportunities with our gut. That may be the best time to act, depending on the situation, but it is not required. Now when the time of an arc of opportunity is coming to a close, just like a life will flicker like a candle at its wick's end, an opportunity will have a flurry-time of opportunity. But it will expire without warning.

The biggest flaw one can make is striking with inappropriate force at the wrong time. For example, acting too forcefully in the beginning (like calling many times after a first date!) or too weakly at the peak period, and looking foolishly unprepared.

The other big flaw is to use the "Law of Attraction" and give up too early before the arc of opportunity can arise from the fabric of reality. One may find that in giving up the arc still appears but appears quite weak or pitiful even... this is not the fault of the opportunity, it is the fault of the lack of energy we put into it.

A common flaw among the timid, unconfident, lazy, indecisive, or overly respectful is to wait too long and the arc of opportunity has already passed. The good news is that rare are the

opportunities that cannot come again or in similar form. It is very rare to meet with an opportunity that we cannot experience but once in a lifetime. However, one should be able to analyze these when they come and realize whether or not they are really so very important.

In Business

The influence of money, and also the sexual, tribal, and psychology energy that often becomes part of sales and business is a common cause of inability to correctly analyze one's particular place in the arc. Take it from a long time sucker: you can be left looking and feeling silly if you don't strike the iron while it's hot and when appropriate. That being said, it is often the fault of inexperience and youth.

I have also been the victim of my own greed and impatience, trying to move an opportunity to quickly, or acting as though it were a once in a lifetime opportunity when really it was quite commonplace.

In both those situations I lost thousands of dollars, not to mention the mental stress, anxiety, and emotional trauma it caused.

Everyone has struggles with flowing and timing the Dao. That, my friends, is normal.

Getting past that and being able to make headway... that is less common by far. The major thing is timing.

If there are three skills I would say to any young person to develop as quickly as possible, they would be, 1) speaking skills, 2) interpersonal skills and communication and 3) timing.

Part of these things are emotional control (or lack thereof)... and part of them are mental focus. Business is all about both of these habits among other things.

In Relationships

The largest source of frustration in human affairs by far is in relationships. Relationships are basically regulated by two things:

1. The arc of opportunity controls the likelihood of successful dating and mating
2. The Law of Harmony controls the likelihood of successful continuation of the relationship

So before you can have a successful relationship, you have to recognize the arc or timeline of opportunity for making something happen. This comes in three stages: 1) time to become a couple, 2) time to marry, and 3) time for having children.

Everyone's life is different, so it would be difficult to say an 'average' for each period, but in an ideal society built upon biology, it would probably look like 1) two to three weeks, 2) six months to three years, and 3) one year (if planning) to 30+ years depending on the age of the woman at marriage.

But more common are the little opportunities... either as a couple to act in the interest of their future or as an individual to continually prove oneself for the other - buying flowers, saying kind things at the right moment, taking care of one's responsibilities, making up after a fight, etc...

This is the importance of knowing timing in a relationship or marriage.

Avoiding Bad Timing

There are probably five major tips that will help one avoid the pitfalls of missing plainly good opportunities.

1. Do not ask God/Universe - do not Attract - that which you are not ready for or do not seriously want. This is the meaning of avoiding "fool's gold rush."
2. Beware: in any undertaking the obstacles will appear
 1. There will be new obligations unexpectedly appear
 2. There will be money shortages; this will often be not real but merely a convenient excuse.
 3. There will be lingering doubts and conflicting paradigms and beliefs
 4. There will be naysayers, doubters, cynics, and chicken littles - be careful who you share your dreams and thoughts with!
 5. There will be time issues; "Life is always full, the question is what is it full of?"
3. See through "Paper Walls" that you can just as easily walk through.
 1. Remember, not everyone exercising authority has an legitimate power or legal power to enforce it; clearly perceive these forces and push through them
 2. If you are fearful of repercussions, get legal backing; Pre-Paid Legal is a good cheap way to feel protected.
4. "See the Great Man" - this is the consistently good advice provided in the Yi Jing (Book of Changes) as what to do when you are stuck... seek advice from someone more knowledgeable than you.
 1. Often these people will be very busy, write your questions as logically and thoroughly as possible so you can cover the most ground... when they start to sense sociability usually they will say they are busy and have something else to do.
 2. If you do not have the "great man" in your circle, make the next opportunity you attract to be "find the Great Man" and see what sort of people God brings your way.
5. Learn the difference between advance and withdrawal, firmness and flexibility... all too often we are the victims of acting bullheadedly, stubborn for completion, and do not know how to retreat (and advanced together). Or we withdraw when we should advance. Or we may be firm outside and appear firm but really too flexible inside ourselves. Or we may be too flexible outside to others, pretending not to be obstinate inside. Or altogether be only flexible or only firm, not able to be both at the same time.

These are the main tips I have for not being smitten with unhappiness due to loss of good opportunity. Just remember, though, to let go of opportunities once lost. After all the Universe is full of opportunities, good or bad, and they can and will come again: so fear not!

Evil Qi

There are several causes of disease in TCM.

1. Emotions (extreme or prolonged)
2. Lifestyle (diet, habits, beliefs/thoughts, work, family)
3. Trauma (body, mind, or spirit)
4. Evil Qi
 1. Cold - winter
 2. Wind - spring
 3. Heat - summer
 4. Dampness - long summer
 5. Dryness - drought, fall
 6. Fire - drought, exposure
 7. Summer(damp)heat - late summer, humid-summer, storms
5. Epidemic Qi (TB, HIV, cholera, etc...)
6. Iatrogenesis (western or eastern sources)
 1. literally - treatment generated
7. Parasites & poisons

But it is most commonly assumed that the idea of the evil Qi is not applicable today now that we don't believe in ghosts and demons, etc...

I'm going to give you a couple examples, however, of evil Qi that is not spiritual, but is insidious nevertheless, and I want you to be aware that these exist in many forms. It is not necessarily a conspiracy of ghosts, but as you will see, it oft feels just as creepy when you experience it.

These are all anecdotal experiences, until you feel it for yourself, it is doubtful you will understand it rightly.

The Open Window incident

In San Diego, because the temperatures do not vary, it is not customary for people here to own air conditioning - which is in the end a very good thing. However, during the day where it might be 90 degrees, at night it might drop to 50 in the spring or fall.

Our previous apartment had a front view with the day-long sun and it heated up pretty well, so we'd gotten into the habit of sleeping with the window open. However a few nights of this and noticing I'm getting a dry throat, and I decided, "Let's just sleep with it cracked, to let in some air and out some heat."

Well, everything was fine until nearly midnight when, while in samadhi, I felt a cool, finger-like wisp of air creep down my forehead, pass the glabella (brow), roll like a ball down my nose and cheeks, and then, like a ghost creep around my nostril!

Now, odd as I thought this phenomenon was, I was not worried yet... until I felt my body respond with a shiver (in the wei Qi) and suddenly my emotional mind (Hun) cried out in terror (nonverbally of course).

You had better believed I closed the window.

It may be melodramatic to imagine a creepy cold air reaching through the window down your snoring mouth and pulling out Lung Qi... but when you think about how your chest needs to stay warm and moist, the vision of cold, dry air stealing this thermal cushion is nothing short of insidious.

Thus I recommend that if it is not absolutely necessary, never sleep with any type of insidious, slow wind (or A/C) blowing in your room at night. Better to sleep without covers and sweating than in exposure.

Sunset Evils

Of all the lifestyle tips to provide (with regards to exposure), such as not having sex after drinking, or not partying too late at night, or eating warm with cold foods, etc... None seems as bizarre as this: do not go out at sunset. If you must go out, go out an hour later, or an hour before, but not at sunset.

More than one day I've noted that an "evil" feeling wind picks up as soon as the last tip of the sun has set from view... again like in a ghost story like all the ghouls can rise from the earth and roam free.

I believe that **the official explanation has to do with changing pressures**, especially when near the sea as I am in San Diego, but I like to view it from Chinese philosophy.

When the ultimate Yang, the sun (indeed that is the source of the character and meaning of Yang) sets, the Earth is temporarily without yang, and the yin aspect of the Earth and the evils are replete, while your body which has been dependent on solar heat is weak.

Thus the energy shifts and a cool wind blows at a time when your wei Qi (immune system) is particularly vulnerable.

Whatever the reason... if you want to avoid waking up with the sniffles, avoid the winds of sunset time.

Water Evils

Now there are three types of evils that are present in water (which combines readily with Wind to create a real problem for the body)

1. Dampness (wetness) is the obvious one, but actually is least likely to overcome you unless you are completely exposed, usually for a long time, or in excess (like wading in dirty water or being in a monsoon). Or surfing.

2. Cold evil is the most dangerous. People do not realize that you can develop hypothermia in 85 degree water (say in the Gulf of Mexico) if you are in it long enough. Coldness is not to be trifled with.
3. Heat (toxic) evil, or Fire which is a stronger version can come from contaminations in the water. Surfers, pool goers, even people in bathtubs can be exposed to heat toxins usually microbial but sometimes as chemicals or minerals.

Once I went swimming in a pool and upon my second dive I unexpectedly had some water injected into the deep sinuses. This water must have been unclean (despite the chlorine, which is another heat toxin). The next day I developed pink eye, which I was able to eject with Qi Gong.

When the evil left, defeated, it felt like a cold drop of water coming from my eye in the place the redness had started. It went in a direction against gravity and there was no water droplet! ... very creepy indeed for our scientific world.

In this case cold, which can transform into heat in the body, had combined with a heat toxin to produce fire in a place beyond the Taiyang level where most of the wei Qi is (skin area). Strategy or simply weakness in my body's armor? You can choose to believe in the germ theory and that evil Qi does not exist, but I promise you you will be much safer knowing that germs are evils and that the environment is often evil, too.

Shen Evils

By the time the Shang Han Lun was written (Treatise on Cold Disease), the Chinese no longer (as doctors) believed much in ghosts either... though reputedly many Chinese commoners still do to this day.

But that doesn't change the facts of the medicine's original theory, which says that an evil Qi is any Qi that conquers the body's Zheng Qi or "righteous Qi" and subjugates you to illness.

Now normally this referred to invasion, but clearly in the case of mental illnesses (and spiritual ones I assure you) it is not usually a real pathogen but an event or thought/belief that is the genesis of an internal evil Qi.

Many forms of trauma, such as rape or car accidents, often end up with the person developing strange physical maladies, such as cysts or chronic nerve firings that are unexplained by structural damage. If a person is lucky, they can get an acupuncturist who sees the pattern in the right way and resets the body's view of these pathways, and these conditions can "spontaneously" resolve.

But in other cases these evil Qi from the outside can traumatize the body (or the mind) and progress all the way to the spiritual level, leading to cases of insanity, mania, OCD, depression, withdrawal, addiction/escapism, PTSD, schizophrenia, etc...

To make conditions worse, often along the ways as the person's armor is broken open by their experiences, other evils such as mentioned before or in the list just now will combine with the original trauma and strengthen the "enemy's encampment".

Such is the case of a person with repeated car accidents who is now addicted to drugs which are a taxation on the Qi, Jing-essence, and Shen-mind, as well as generating cold, damp, or dryness internally, which blocks Qi.

Sometimes these people "lose it" all at once, sometimes after years of trying everything... many end up homeless where phlegm can accumulate from exposure and then they have "misting" of the mind and cannot tell one thing from another, or that they are even in the same room with you.

But the most insidious Qi evils of the Shen are 1) bad ideas and 2) shock/exposure

Bad Ideas

Ideas that root themselves in the fertile soil of our subconscious often do not start malevolently. Usually, they start with admiration of another person, sometimes with education (willing, like from school or unwilling, like commercial jingles that get in your head and have a blatant message that makes you want to spend money), and sometimes as an emotional reaction to seeing something we do not like.

These ideas are not bad because of some external judgment (as from God) necessarily.

Sometimes they are good for other people, but not for us.

Veganism, for example, is a particularly virulent idea (like all diet fads) that often takes root in a well meaning mind and then next thing you know an individual is on a cold-raw diet that is tearing their guts apart and leading to chronic arthritis, aching, headaches, and emaciation. Usually one can tell that an idea has become a virus in the mind because the individual will seek to plant it in others and the recipients may actually be repulsed for an unknown reason... usually emotional reaction to the moral argument. This may actually be a Hun-Po (bodily intuition) reaction to the sight of the individual who is obviously ill.

Another example is nihilism, which on its own seems defensible except when you look at how Nietzsche died unhappy and alone and you know it must have been quite a foundless idea.³

I am not going to list all bad ideas - all the cults, or political beliefs, scientific propaganda, nationalism, etc... - in hopes you will see them. If you have strong Small Intestine and Gallbladder channel Qi, you will see them for yourself if you are aware.

But I will say that the key here is just knowing that when you look up to someone, they can implant all sorts of crazy ideas into your noggin which may take years or a lifetime to remove, especially the people we trust implicitly from childhood.

But just as the human body is a breeding ground for microbes and parasites... the human mind is a breeding ground for all sorts of unwholesome beliefs that can lead us to anywhere BUT where we wanted to go.

Shock/exposure

Usually shock causes an emotional response which we cognize as an idea, and then... see above.

But occasionally the shocks are to our body or spirit levels and transform themselves into Shen-evils. This can be particularly potent when in the presence of someone who is mentally unstable because of 1) entanglement and 2) our compassion.

Entanglement is a useful concept for masters, but the bane of woe for those who want success in anything and cannot seem to find their weakness or failures. Often it is who we

associate with and share energy/space with that is causing us to be muddled. Some call these people Qi-vampires... I like to call them well-meaning friends.

But more insidious even than the fact that you might entangle your Shen with a mentally sick person (unhappy or worse), is that you may actually befriend one or spend time with them and they show you something, while you are compassionate, from their twisted point of view and you TAKE IT FOR YOUR OWN.

Forgetting the window of your mind, you see instead what they see, or want others to see to get empathy, and now you've inherited sick Qi of their Shen.

And as Qi follows Shen, your diseased Shen will now infect the mind, the body, and your actions being led by the body's emotional responses (in most people of the lower realms who do not dominate their karma) will start to generate reactions and thus your karma reinforce this sick paradigm.

I can give you three examples, two from media you can get in almost any Best Buy or comic store.

1. In *Ghost in the Shell 2*, Batou (a cyborg) and his human partner visit a hacker, who causes the partner to enter a brain loop towards insanity. Batou is saved by Kusanagi, his 'guardian angel'. I highly recommend this movie it is very deep and this scene is a classic example of being "led about" by another's will.

2. In a book called "*Watchmen*" the narrator, a psychopath whom the reader comes to admire and understand (just as I said above), has a pivotal and important scene with a well-meaning psychiatrist who is treating him as sick. But as he asks what Rorschach sees in a blot diagram, the tail given is so gruesome that the psychiatrist begins to slowly doubt his work, and life's meaning... and much later we see him in the street waving a sign "the End is near" which happens to be Rorschach's old 'job' (when he wasn't killing criminals ruthlessly).
3. In real life, in my old dojo there is a strong - reverence we will say - for the particular eccentricities of its headmaster. This man, a man of intensity such that his high blood pressure caused both an aneurysm and 90% heart block due to hypertension/atherosclerosis, a man of lust for fighting, has an interesting passion. He does ironbone to the point where he actually enjoys the pain it causes... and ironically as he damages the Qi pathways of the channels, it aggravates his Yang Rising condition.

There is nothing wrong with this per se (as far as right/wrong), but the result has been a general desire to emulate him, despite many clear and large human faults/anti-social behavior, that has led to this particularly self-destructive behavior being repeated and taught. But this method of iron-bone training is not correct for the body. It does achieve its aim, but the question is, "Is the body/spirit supposed to be a weapon?"

My point is not that anyone/anything is bad... but that an idea, even if well meant (or good for the person who originated it), can turn from something of admiration to a disease-causing-behavior and this can be passed on for generations on end.

This, after all, is the cause of the spread of fundamentalist ideas, such as Jihad... all of these started with someone spreading an idea that later could be revealed as destructive... but by then it was too late. People have died (for thousands of years) because of this phenomena.¹

So I will warn thee, be overly careful about which ideas you take in... if you are apt to admire something or are shocked and reviled of something... better to examine it and make sure you are not stepping into a ravine (or away from an illusion and into a ravine in fear). In fact, many artists shock you on purpose to get this reaction... do not allow your mind to be controlled by these individuals or their hair-brained ideas.²

And I hope that as you leave this article you see that evil Qi has an explanation, but the important thing is that it's evil and can be thwarted with a righteous army (of the body or mind), if you are prepared.

Alchemy: Reversing the Flow

After months of wracking my brain for several months, working with the Qi, etc... I have been able to finally determine the internal method (Nei Dan) for actually achieving the "takeover" of the normal flow. This understanding comes to us, albeit still shrouded in mystery and allegory, from the Understanding Reality text by Tung Po Chien, commentary by Liu Yiming (transl. Thomas Cleary).

At first the tendency is to see this as a complete metaphor for reverting to youth. Normal flow being to follow biological urges and emotional reactions and age the body by over-using the Golden Flower. Hence the immediate reaction is "use the Light less." But this isn't a reversal, now is it? It is only the first step in the reversal process.

Let's take a look at the normal flow:

- **Wood->Fire and regulates Earth**
Literally, the liver produces enzymes which are both dumped into the duodenum for digestion, and into the venous return which circulates through the heart and lungs. Both of these situations create the potential for Liver Fire to "catch" stomach and heart on fire. Furthermore, the Liver-wood, burning, can raise Liver stagnant Qi to Yang Rising and the nervous system becomes inflamed, causing easy irritation, angry bursts, etc... which lead to rapid aging through over-use of the Golden Light.
- **Fire->Earth and regulates Metal**
The blood circulates through the body, nourishing flesh and brain, enabling the Earth energy to fill the body with Qi. However, as the heart gets inflamed so too does the digestive system. Meanwhile, the heart fire can enter the lungs, which are brittle and dry, and scorch them. This is a literal

flow of blood in the circulatory system. Also the heart fire can attack the colon causing IBS and colitis.

■ **Earth->Metal and regulates Water**

The flow of food is through the intestines to the colon. Thus any fire in the stomach can pour downward into the colon, burning it. Also, the Spleen sits underneath the lungs. So when Liver Fire spreads to Spleen, then both lungs get burned from below. The other fact is that the Spleen hates dampness, and when damp foods are ingested, excess insulin is kicked out via the channels to the taiyin partner, the Lung, which produces excess surfactant and causes coughing. Regulating water, this enables fiery enzymes to pass from the spleen and pancreas into the kidney and bladder, thus heart fire can pour down and burn the Source (Mother of all Qi).

■ **Metal->Water and regulates Wood**

The lungs are the father of all Qi, the "prime minister." Thus they require the aid of the Mother to have interaction. By now the mother is all taxed out, and the Metal is weak, brittle, scorched, and disused. Thus it is unable to properly regulate the Wood, and the General which should be held in check is unchecked and gains power by overtaking the granary/accounts (Earth). If the PM is unable to govern the country for the sovereign, then the individual loses control of their reality and health, and both spiral out of bounds and out of control. It could take months or years or decades, but the result is the same: non-fulfillment of destiny.

Worse yet, at the end of the day, when the country (body) is properly governed, excess profit is supposed to be stored back in the Kidney (Water). This not being done, instead the essence is sapped repeatedly, habitually, and the person thus ages both physically and spiritually. Aging here does not mean maturity but being "used up." To be used up spiritually means to become tired ere your task is fulfilled. Destiny belongs to the Water energy, after all via the will-power (zhi).

■ **Water->Wood and regulates Fire**

The Water controls two key ingredients which are the source of all health in the body:

- **Kidney Yin or Jing-essence:** semen, ovum, DNA, marrow, RBC's, CSF, and brain matter. Literally the deepest fluid materials in the body
- **Kidney Yang or Ming-Men "Minister's Fire":** the endocrine system which runs from the testes/ovaries up into the pituitary and hypothalamus, including the pancreas, thyroid, and thymus, as well as -shared with San Jiao - the lymph nodes.

When the control of these are lost, the result is devastation. It can even lead to the usurping of Sovereign Fire by the Ming-Men Fire if

there is too little "security" (Qi) to protect the sovereign. This means hormonal imbalances. The Ming Men Fire is the water-fire (yin and yang) balance of the body.

Take the balance between PTH (parathyroid hormone) and calcitonin. A brilliant design to regulate bone density and serum calcium.

However, in most cases people ruin this and the result is less and less calcitonin through waning Kidney Fire. (PTH does not tend to wane).

Thus the result is accelerated bone loss, osteomalacia, osteoporosis!

Furthermore, the water is supposed to regulate, meaning encourage the proper function of the Fire (or heart). Aldosterone, DHEA, and the Renin-Angiotensin system is meant to keep the blood pressure in regulation and the nervous system also regulated. It is the autonomic nervous system which regulates the beating of the heart. When the Water Qi is out of balance because the PM - Lung - is generating it, then the blood does not flow smoothly and the sovereign does not serve the people, nor is able to rest at night. This condition may worsen to fears by the Heart Shen, that the General (Liver), the now degenerate child of the Kidney, will conquer the capital and replace the sovereign with another.

This really means that the Mind of Tao is easily usurped by false ego - the Conditioned, Human Mind.

Bodily, it means palpitations, insomnia, nightmares, etc... all of which age the sovereign through stress.

This is the "normal" flow, which means that the person is out of control of their Empire - the body, and their Karma.

Reversing the Flow

The Steps to Achieving Middling Alchemy are as follows:

Alchemy

1. Superior - alteration of mind-body-spirit vibratory rhythms to create proper resonance, cease following the human mentality and follow instead the Mind of Tao. Over time, training the "child" to become like unto the "father" - or Heavenly Father. This psychological process requires humility, patience, and perseverance all of which fall under the Furtherance of the Great
2. Middling - alteration of the body's aging process to produce a flowering of mind-body-spirit that is readily evident in Karmic output fluctuation. The cessation of "bad" karma and the production of "good" karma, as well as magnetism, vitality, joy, productivity, and tireless effort seem utterly juxtaposed with the amount of energy spent, because the alchemist relies not upon personal

energy but the Qi.

This is the work of "internal herbalism."

3. Inferior - the production of chemicals through scientific processes, for ingestion; or the use of drugs such as psychedelics; or the use of herbs for the restoring of the harmonious processes - the goal of which for all three is to externally bypass the above processes to arrive at the same quintessential Truth. Shorter term, more instant gratification.

1. Cease wasted Qi by eliminating leaky habits and placing bans on related poor habits (such as watching TV, playing video games, etc...)
2. Use R&D processes to begin augmenting diet and lifestyle, meanwhile studying one's internal paradigms and thought-habits, to reprogram the ego, and allow it to recognize the Cycle of Mind, its logical folly, and entice it to step down and let the Mind of Tao reign life.
3. Use individual moments to test the ego's ability to "let go" control while simultaneously enjoying the mystical manifestations and hidden meanings which re-affirm choice #2
4. Begin repealing negative habits by lifting bans on habits that are not bad for health but allow the mind to de-stress; again being mindful of the fact that "one yin stirs all yins" meaning some habits make one revert to negative habits.
5. Through continued internal meditation arrive at Truth often, repeatedly, and come to enjoy it more than the "world" which means ever increasing inner revolution and research into the hidden processes within Oneself. The ability to bypass religion and dogma to directly perceive the Truth.

When one enters all five gates, not leaving any "behind" merely integrating them stages at a time, then one will be sufficiently inwardly aware to understand the following:

- **Fire->Wood and regulates Water**
The shen/Self is the True Self. The one who can choose between his inner tiger (ego) which is a survival program generated phenomonally by the complexity of the body, and his Mind of Tao, the true Prime Minister. This Mind works for the Shen, but transcends it. It has direct access to the General, and can replace the General. The false General (ego) wins the heart of the army by its ferocity. The Hun-soul wins the heart of the army by his magniloquence and wisdom. The Shen can choose the latter and cage the former. By not executing the former, one shows forbearance. It can be taught, but only by watching for a long, long time the successes of the true Prime Minister. This PM will enable the Lung energy (through breathing meditation to properly regulate the kingdom via the channels. Furthermore, the Wood is the Eldest Son, via the Water being the Prime Mother. Thus the Eldest Son in control of the Sovereign Fire can now control the Empress Dowager. By respecting her position, there is growing

confluence and love. She never abuses her natural strength, nor spoils the child. And in hearing the power of her grandson and chosen heir, she retains repose. Her husband's power then is freed from the need to "come back from the dead" and run the empire in his weak old age. Thus the Kidney Fire or Ministerial Fire, via the Ancestral Qi can intermingle and lead to sage-wisdom for the sovereign. This well pleases the Dowager (Essence) whose husband's altar (adrenals) are not neglected.

Internally this means the quelling of the liver fire and nerve plexus via the Vagus nerve (brain belongs to Fire), leads to direct control over the adrenals.

- **Wood->Water and regulates Metal**

The Eldest Son pleasing the Mother, the mother-son degenerative cycle is broken. Mother gains repose in her weakness and security in a strong son, rather than him sapping her daily. She has a grandson who gives her great joy. The eldest son moves on to conquer the whole kingdom in the name of Benevolence, rather than ferocity. The Shen of the general is in proper harmony with the regulation of the kingdom, as the liver is supposed to be and was in youth. It is therefore easily about to have concourse and "regulate" the Prime Minister who is the lungs and thereby govern the army which is the Wei Qi (Defense Qi). This relationship is like the Tai Kung receiving orders from Duke Zhou, the son of King Wu. In this way the empire receives the blessings of Heaven. Though the Tai Kung is wily and dangerous, the Duke has nothing to fear because the general is well regulated and happy in his conquering of barbarians and criminals. There is plenty of illness to fight in the body, without the immune system attacking the body itself. Thus the defense Qi has plenty to do. Also the General is allowed, after his long term imprisonment, (as King Wen, son of Wu was), to finally emerge from the cage perfected, and trusted by heaven to conquer the world and overthrow evil. This means that the person, after long years of struggling against habits, is able to forget them easily. Addiction to the 5 flavors, the 5 notes, the five elements (in color) are easily overcome.

As for colon, the metal energy is controlled properly and the IBS and colitis cease and bowels become regular and smooth through forgetting the constant battles of life.

- **Water->Metal and regulates Earth**

Through internal sensing of the endocrine glands and the adrenals, one is able to properly open the Chest and grasp the Lung Qi. Like a tiger with wings, like riding a dragon to Tushita Heaven, the individual meets the Qi of Water with Metal, calms the Fire (heart), and can thus operate the reverse. This leads naturally to the dispelling of desire, which although is born of the Fire (chest chakra) it befuddles the intellect with rationalizations (Yi) and stirs the stomach to desire ever more and more. This leads to being fat, lazy, and impeded because the diaphragm is blocked. But now the Water energy becomes like food, the essence like water, the conquering of inner chasms like leisure. One needs to go nowhere to have a good time. Thus the

desire is restrained, and the limbs are properly nourished and with lessened worry (as to having relied upon the Tao for power), one is able to protect the muscles.

- **Metal->Earth and regulates Fire**

The lungs take amply from ancestral Qi (Zong Qi) and fill the chest. This produces a "nectar" that comes from the pituitary and down the tongue. This jade fluid and essence "fills the belly" while one "empties the mind." In the end the person is able to pass lung Qi into the Zhong Qi and combine with food properly, which leads to pure essence in the Dan Tian. Normally the Lung channel passes from the Zhong down to dan tian, scooping it out like ice cream, then bringing it up to grasp the Lungs. But now one can pass energy (via Reverse breathing) from the chest back down to the Dan Tian. The physical wave motion creates a pumping, and combined with San Jiao breathing to create vacuums and break stagnation, the fresh fluids and blood from the Mansion of Blood nourish the Dan Tian. By controlling lungs properly, the person supports the heart. This is like the PM giving the Sovereign repose, like Shun aiding Yao in the running of the kingdom. This means the heart is regulated, strong, tireless, and the brain is crisp and sharp like a sword. The intellect is not abused into knowing un-necessaries. Vulgarities have no interest to the 5 Leaders and they rebuke them, and repulse the barbaric hordes and filth. Thus the wars bring repose to all the people, even the people involved in gangs and riots and terrorism (cancers and autoimmune disasters). The kingdom is settled by the merging of the 5 Leaders and the making of Just War (meditation) upon the kingdom within.

- **Earth->Fire and regulates Wood**

The Earth is humanity's great Mother. It should govern our thoughts, feelings, and we should live eternally off of her bounty. Our humanity's great ego form eating the fruit of the Tree of Knowledge has led to our nearing the brink of disaster. Eventually the Earth Mother will break us to restrain us.

Internally, if a person wishes to control the natural degradation process post Tian Gui flowing (puberty), then they must by all means use logic, which comes from the intellect (Yi). As a matter of course, the Water energy and Gu Qi (food) must produce glucose for the proper regulation of muscle and brain. The normal flow results in depletions of glucose, hence addiction to sugar grows daily. The Reverse Flow provides sugars even when there is no food, via the reaping of muscle. This is only a matter for survival of course.

When the General regulates the accountant of the granary, it is supposed to be necessary for war. When it is habit, then this is called embezzlement. Instead, the accountant should control the General most of the time through funding for the army.

This means one should reduce activities, especially unnecessary ones first, until one has unending Qi for all activities. The General having joy in things to conquer, does not mind a limited pension and a budget, knowing that war

devastates the state's resources and drains the people. Activities are fun, and entertainment enjoyable, but not to excess.

Internally the person can control the liver via the amount of food introduced and its type. The choice of fewer triglycerides means that the liver produces less cholesterol. The "conquering" of exercise means the liver will produce HDL and reduce dampness (LDL) and fat, which enables the pancreas (Earth) to properly regulate glucose without addiction to sugars.

Since sugar alters consciousness (via the frontal cortex), this is desirable because sugar (yin producing) excites the ego into a lustful stage and will lead to the desire of many other bad habits. Enjoyment of sugar is a luxury/pass-time. However as a main mode of nurturing the kingdom leads to health degeneration.

A government that loves money and power rather than Virtue and Benevolence will seek not the Tao of governance, but allow criminal mafias to invade. This means damp, phlegm, blood stagnation, etc...

When these 5 Shen/Leaders come together, it is like Yao and Shun governing the world; like King Wu finding the Tai Kung, like Duke Zhou protecting King Wen, like Zhuge Liang coming together with Liu Bei, Zhang Fei, Guan Yu, and Zhao Yun. How can things not be righted? They will be, because the system is balanced. forward flow is natural, unstoppable. But with Reverse flow, one can slow the system down, prevent the train from running off the tracks, etc...

~Shifu

On Gurus

Gurus, My Response to Them by [Shifu R. Careaga](#) on Friday, November 25, 2011 at 4:18pm ·

Followed by an updated article Gurus vs. Spiritual Guides; Shamans vs. Healers; Mysticism vs. Magick; Kumaré

There are a lot of "gurus" who practice

distilling and trying to eliminate or control the Mind. I ask you, with simple open inquiry: if they figured it out, why are they again in this incarnation and again thin and bony?

Who says the Mind is **bad**, and furthermore what qualifies them to make that statement? Do they know of all the 5 shen and the 3 minds that are the products thereof? Do they know the links of causation and the source of Karma? Do they know the 11 factors and 10 Worlds? [quite literally many "gurus" in the West have never read the source texts, and many in the East *cannot* read the texts... hence many false teachings are created by the egoistic mind.]

The Buddha himself practiced austerities and came to realize they led to nowhere. And he taught Hinayana to the People who were already looking for a door out of Samsara, until he knew they could handle this Truth: there is no doorway out, only sublimation back in.

If you were born you were born for a reason. Your karmic evolution is not yet complete. When you are ready to remain with God you will; all others: seek life in some form suited to your Soul's status.

So why try to destroy the Mind... the very thing that connects us to the Source? The fractal portion of Glory Almighty.

Does it makes us lonely? Yes.

Does it make us cling? Yes.

Does it desire? Yes.

Does it experience and cause its own turmoil? Yes.

But even the leaves die and stones wear away. A tree may seem sublime but it can also be besotted by termites or cut by beavers and cannot run only be tormented. In this Saha world there is no safe refuge, whether there is a Mind or no Mind. Zen may seem no Mind, but no Mind does not plan bridges and perform life-saving heart surgeries.

Zen is beyond no Mind. It is perception of the Mind, not extinguishment of it.

Seeking to destroy the Mind is fruitless. While you would trash the Intellect/Ego, the subconscious and unconconscious (together: Id) would reign supreme.

Would you meditate all day? Doing nothing is not the Dao. Even doing nothing there is Karma. And when you sleep the two minds would still reign supreme. They run 95%+ of your life, and you cannot destroy them, not without starving them and hating them and dying like some silly king of the Upanishads. They are the networks of the lower CNS and PNS/ENS and your connection to the Source itself... to destroy them is ludicrous.

Would a sage-king take advice from a man that has starved himself half to death? He would as soon starve the kingdom. The people would revolt and the king overthrown. The collective consciousness knows this is not the Way.

When Bodhidharma found the monks of Shaolin half-starved they fell asleep during Ch'an (Zen) practice. He did not say "the mind is nowhere therefore destroy it." He had them do Yoga and get strong. Strong body, well nourished, means less distractions for the Ego when in samadhi.

Those who think highly of the gurus, that is fine. Able to go without eating for years: ultimate discipline. But I tell you now that practice is just a practice, it is not the Way. Discipline that is painful is not discipline it is punishment. A prison built in the Mind and carried by a soul from existence to existence, barring the door to Heaven/Nirvana.

The Way is compassion and sharing the Experience we are here to receive with others, especially friends, and in remaining open and trusting and especially Zheng - righteous. Day by day after becoming adults in a corrupt society working to better ourselves and subconsciously follow the Will of Heaven/God. Benevolent, sublime, always moving forward: evolving. Leaving the processes of growth and destruction to work without controlling nary a thing but our own processes and what belongs in our spheres. Fathers showing up. Mothers guiding/nourishing the family, supporting the husbands. Grandparents interested. Friends supportive, inspiring, and happy. Pets well taken care of and taught - for that is why they have come to you. The whole

world - your world, perceived by your Mind - revolving around this benevolent principle. Destroy the Mind? ... Destroy the Family, destroy the People, destroy the Country, destroy the World. Atheism, existentialism, nihilism they nearly ended things in the 20th Century! Don't be fooled by elitist philosophical branches and economic and scientific skeptics... what do they know and can they show the results of an entire society succeeding with that principle?!?

Do not be taken in by shiny words, or the promise of "ancient wisdom." Just because it is old doesn't make it right. Shall we stone the adulterers? Should we chop the hands off of teens that steal from stores? These gurus, mystics, etc... they also have evolutionary paths, and all I say is how do they manage their own world? Is it fit to manage your own?

If you follow a guru whose world is reducing, hoping to become like a self-help expert promises: rich and successful those are two different vibrations. Either upon opposite ends of the spectrum, You cannot hope to have praxis or harmony of mind and soul. If a self-help "expert" promises reduction leads to fullness, careful they are not selling you a fashion. If a guru promises emptiness means completeness, be wary lest you be caught in a logical snare.

The Void is not empty and the Real is not True. If what you perceive did not exist anywhere then you would not perceive it. It is in the Mind and only the Mind that you can perceive. To move to the Void is to pretend this is the door to enlightenment. It is not. Enlightenment is the door to the Source/Heaven/Nirvana.

First understand, then retain, then upon death the realization comes to bear. If it is your time, worry not!

Compassion and leadership, and respect for ALL the forms of existence, big or small, rich or poor, alive or dead, enlightened or pitiful, these are the keys to the Dao. Ponder on it or grasp it singly in Zen -either way you need a Mind.

So do not destroy the mind, understand it (not the brain, the Mind!). Understand the processes, paradigms, and Laws. They will teach you what no person, Facebook snippet, website, or book can. The Truth Within.

Revisiting the Guru Within

Recently I reviewed a movie called Kumaré, to which I will give a brief list of problems at the end of this... but one thing it was successful at was helping me to look at this Guru question again. One thing I never want anyone to feel is 'bamboozled' or like they are trying to be 'led' into something (convinced? yes, but not dragged). I'm not here to build a following for myself, but point to the True Way, which exists and has many, many names.

Sufficed to say I enjoy the writings of certain gurus, and their knowledge can be extremely profound. But there are a lot of people 'stalking the lands like wolves at hunt' as Daishonin coined it talking about Zennists of his time; and these 'gurus' have two things in common.

1. They have very little real or formal training. By formal I don't mean college or pedigree lineage, I mean they do not read the source texts. They read A text, such as the Gita, and then pontificate endlessly upon myriad other doctrines relying upon their initial enlightenment, but not refining the Self away; indeed they have larger egos often than others or 'ordinary persons' (laypeople)
2. They usually try to swindle people in saying "you can have the Truth but only if you listen to me."

Well actually the deepest teachings of every book, including the Bible, are that the Truth is found through one's Self and that way ONLY. There is no other way. As the Lotus Sutra said, there is not a second vehicle, let alone a third vehicle, there is only the Great Vehicle. The Great Vehicle is the Golden Flower... the Christ itself. If one seeks it outside oneself, such as from a Pope or a guru, then one has left the basis and cannot find truth no matter how many rocks are turned over.

This is because though people get far away from it, Enlightenment is actually always present, right in front of the face in the mirror, and actually right in the heart (which in Chinese and Sanskrit the word for heart is the same as mind).

This is the difference between a guru and a spiritual guide (bodhisattva). The guru holds the teaching within and keeps it away; while the spiritual guide merely points the finger. When the student is ready the teacher appears. Then the student learns and the teacher isn't needed anymore. Eventually the text isn't needed. Eventually the Buddha/Christ isn't needed. Eventually even God isn't 'needed' but is desired above all else as the Source is that which ends all wants and fulfills all needs.

This is also the difference between people claiming to be doctors or special healers/shamans instead of True Healers. True Healers guide a process and then get out of the way and let the Qi/Holy Spirit/Prajna do the work.

The way of the Shaman requires much dedication and much self-restraint of the Ego. How many can say they have this legitimately?

It reminds me of the difference between mysticism and magick. People claiming to practice magick trick others but they also trick themselves. The only magic is the mystical. Things that manifest of themselves. Does a person 'initiate' a mystical experience? Yes, but only when they lose the Self. Losing the Self, the mystical produces myriad results, all mysterious and perfect. This is the secret of the Lotus Method, and the Taoist Alchemy. It is not that I do anything; it does it all by itself.

Kumaré; A Practical Paradox Proves Itself Wrong

And by Wrong I mean illogical and inconsistent with Tian-Ren-Di; aka "Incorrect" or "false"

Recently, a film caught my eye, available on Netflix. I highly recommend people to watch it so they can, above all else, learn how easy it is for the Open-Minded to be fooled and given a ride; for money or any other reason.

But there are probably about 5 problems with the film itself, and its method, ending with a paradox that will mislead the subconscious mind.

1. It was an experiment performed (by a non-scientist) unethically. No prior consent was given; no methodology set up nor tested. It was done, ultimately for a story that was to be sold; however genuine the intent originally was. In the end, Mr. Vikram Gandhi is making money from this enterprise. That isn't science - well, these days it is - but the main problem is the Ethics. After the experiments of the 20th century; I would have thought we'd moved beyond that. This is beyond Candid Camera... this is messing with people's Karma and livelihoods...
2. Because the experiment used real people, real people got hurt. Most notably people who had real livelihoods at stake, such as the yoga teacher, psychic, and Law of Attraction teacher. Is their ego in the way, or his? The irony is that Kumaré; Vikram's ideal Self; once he knew these people would never have done such a thing to these friends. Especially not for money and film. He revealed their intimate personal lives and details to an international audience, giving them embarrassment at having been duped (although the duping should not have changed their opinion about who he is, that's not the point, they still felt/sensed being duped.)

3. Ch14 Lotus Sutra

4. "... As for associations... [a true Bodhisattva] does not associate with actors and illusory entertainment..."
5. ~The Buddha
6. I would imagine this also means pretending to be something you aren't on film.
7. Because the "teaching" he "made up" is a REAL TEACHING, it gives the audience the impression that anyone can make up anything and it is Truth. But actually he just happened to know some real teaching from having listened to Grandma growing up; and his Kumaré Self can only provide real teaching; not a Lie. Which is irony; he came up with the idea using his Human Mentality, but the Mind of Tao was manifested and then he wanted to be it professionally and permanently. Thus PROVING the teaching of a real, bonafide Truth is Truth after all; and the human Ideal.
8. Yet, because he 'made it up' the audience is left to wonder if they should not question the Teachings of real gurus, such as Jesus Christ (for example). On top of this, there is the ostracizing of the Westerner audience from real Vedanta and Taoist and other teachings (like Jewish mysticism and Christian Gnosticism) because if studying those makes you a sucker like these people, who knows YOU might be embarrassed too, one day in a Candid Camera experiment.

9. Finally, and most paradoxically of all is the Unveiling. As a practice itself, that Teaching is Truth and perfect. However, the method here was not correct. Firstly, because nobody has followed a real process, they have used some self-help steps from a book or something 'made up' to practice unveiling and they do not even know what was unveiled. See Darkness hexagram #4 line 3.

Secondly, he did not participate in the original Unveiling, which I found to be fairly cowardly. That may be a judgment but it's important as we shall soon see.

Thirdly, the Ultimate Teaching of Kumaré is that you unveil the Guru-Within through the "Mirror" technique. Actually this is true but they didn't use a mirror, nor did they truly unveil the Guru Within that day but through the subsequent 40 days following. The Unveiling was just affirmation and revealing self to others; but true Unveiling happens as you live.

Finally, and this takes some thinking, but if the people had not been instructed by a Real Teaching, they would not have changed. They would not have headed down the road with such conviction. They would have actually remained in previous conditioning. Many of the interviews over the 40 days showed people continuing to use his teachings. They were focused on him, on his teachings, his methods, their hearts focused on Kumaré, not on Vikram, because he did not Unveil at the ceremony. So for 40 days these people continued to use the Guru!

So when he says that you do not need a guru, it is within you, he is right... but he then shows that people can use a fake guru - such as Yoda, for example - to achieve the same. This does not prove you should use the guru within (unconscious) to the subconscious mind. You see, the conscious mind sees the trick, but the heart still sees the "fake" Kumaré, which is a real guru using real teaching, and the heart sees it as 100% real. This lack of equality between conscious perception which says "Oh, he is Vikram" and their hearts which saw only Kumaré creates a lack of praxis.

So what happens when they do not continue the practices? Then they start to doubt both the teaching and realize they really need a Guru, and when they had a guru they were better off than when they had Vikram. I'm not trying to project, I'm providing the logical issue here. So far 10/14 people still talk to him; but I wonder if that will remain or not? Once the Big Lie becomes Truth; then revelation of the Truth is then a Lie to the mind and thus the natural mind - which is only truthful from birth to death - will reject a truth as a lie. It is not a lie, it is just bad process.

So this paradox will yes, challenge their egos, but also could theoretically harm them for years, decades, even lifetimes. Considering the unethical methods, the hurt feelings, the national embarrassment of a religion and movement... I feel this is clearly crossing a major line and so cannot say this teaching is as true as it could be. Because the Process was not true, and was based on a lie.

Although Kumaré is 100% real within him, he still duped people, and so one cannot say he found the Buddha within. That was clearly not the case. People must change the karma naturally, and not through deception. There is hard work AND there is instant enlightenment, but one needs both.

People will say, "Well that is the point of Art: to challenge.... to be a living paradox." Yes that is the point of art, but not of science. The study of Spirit is not an art of itself, it is a Science of Life. Literally Ayurveda (of which Yoga is a mere part) literally means Science of Life. Gnosis, too, means knowledge not art. I am for art, but not for art that actually hurts people. And I am certainly not for science that is used to hurt people and in the end, profit is made. When experiments are conducted such as this, they should be done only once if at all. But actually this has been done before... not just by Sasha Cohen, but others. See Marjoe for an example.

It's not that I have a problem with whistleblowers, either. But I do have a problem with somebody interfering in a negative way with someone else's path. If even one single person who is ready to study the Vedanta sees that documentary and is dissuaded, wow what a working of the "devil". If one person hears a preacher that spouts hatred, the detriment is enough, so why have it to where millions can be haphazardly affected? This is not something that a real teacher would do. I hope people go and check out my article on [Evil Teachers](#) so they can understand it isn't the person that is "evil" it is the deceit of the ego - the Human Mind being made into the Master, but really it should be the servant. Thanks for reading!

The Buddha Stream

If a person is not first familiar with streams, they need to review the articles prior to this and come to an understanding about the Spiritual Plane.

Now a Buddha is merely an individual that though they have attained liberation of

Mind, has been asked to clarify Reality for the whole world. They don't have enemies, they don't have self; but they take up an ego in order to answer the queries presented. Their thoughts, though are not their own, but come from beyond the Asymptote and they are guided to reveal the Truth.

The rest of us, when we reveal truth, we borrow from our Selves and create ego, and thereby produce self and other, and so conflict. But a Buddha can transform the meta-space and psychic ether around them and all who approach, even the evil-minded who mean to harm him, will be sublime and listen.

Therefore it is beneficial to learn this; for one it is a birthright... secondly, it is the final vibratory stream that oscillates not violently and haphazardly but lovingly around the central Source-stream that is Straight.

The Mind produces realities and realities are relative. Thus many vibrations exist.

One can enter the buddha-mind and never know it, but being weak in strength and inflexible in sincerity and intent, retain it ever so short compared to other things.

However, bit by bit, little by little, one can observe this Buddha Stream as not simple moments but a series.

"If I do this... then I am like this..."

Following THIS stream a little ways is equal to 10,000 medicines and endless doctrines. There is no comparison to this state of self that is non-self... or non-self that generates the Self. One's Self perceives the Beyond, just right 'there' and one

has no need for words or actions. Awareness, samadhis, dharanis, powers they are yours and yet pointless and unnecessary.

If one can run into this stream, try to grasp it without grasping. The longer this grasping but not controlling can take place, the stronger one gets each time.

If this can be done repeatedly, then anuttara-samyak-sambodhi is not far off; the Wisdom Embracing all Species that can only be understood and shared between Thus Come Ones.

It's all Good

Heard a quote yesterday I improved it only slightly, "He who knows that he knows, [and what he knows] is Wise, follow him. He who knows that he knows not is Aware, teach him. He who knows not that he knows is Asleep, wake him. He who knows not that he knows not, is a Fool, shun him." I really enjoyed that, and added it to the only three or four

quotes I ever bother to remember correctly. Most of the time my quotations are paraphrases of the idea, but this one is really very good.

It struck me that few people really fall into the first two categories, which are really the better of the four. If you know not that you know, you aren't much use to anybody, let alone even yourself. That was such as I was until only [recently]. I put that in brackets because it was not really recent, unless you consider the passage of Time overall, it's just that I did not allow myself to come forward, which is almost as bad - but does have a purpose. However, considering the Bodhicitta that I have received/taken it was really rather selfish of me to allow my insecurities about Knowing to stop me from teaching the Law. For that I apologize. It is as though there is a line, "He who knows that he knows, but pretends not, is Selfish, berate him."

There is a saying, "It's all good..." and though that is true, not all good is equal. It struck me all at once today and I wish to share it with you now.

- The Highest Good
 - Emotional knowledge of the 8 Laws; demonstrated in pairing || uniting || harmonizing Yin and Yang in our lives

- Global Conscious-Awareness
- Enlightenment/Salvation **types** and how to find them
- Knowing the Meaning of Life & how to teach finding it
- The Path of Reversal aka the path of the Sages (not asceticism)
- The Middling Good
 - Love
 - Inner Peace
 - Non-action and Correct Action
 - Non-form, non-clinging aka Letting Go
 - Correct Virtue, self-forging, aka ridding oneself of Sin/Vice
- The Mundane Good
 - Serenity
 - Passing Joys
 - Luck
 - Contentedness

These are not the same in terms of equality or goodness. A clever student should discern the difference immediately. A smart person with some effort. Mundane people with much effort and guidance. Inferior people will not be able to hear, much less see the truth in this, and will - at least in this lifetime - be forever searching for fulfillment via Mundane Good.

Using your meditation to heal

Meditation, whether it is quietude, qi gong, yoga, use of psychedelics, or simply chanting/praying, is one of our key methods of spiritual pursuit.

Tom Brown Jr.'s Grandfather (Lone Wolf) defined the path as anytime the mind is quieted.

In TCM theory, meditation is thought to be a matter of quieting the Yi, focusing the Zhi inwards, allowing the Hun to swim abroad, and then the Shen and Po can simply exist without being subject to the Yi's pensive nature. **Need to review the Shen?**

In this article we are going to explore the medical uses of meditation, especially Qi Gong, rather than the martial, which is vastly overemphasized in the martial arts community.

Though it is true the Qi can be transported into power, let me remind the reader that that amount of Qi generated is nothing compared to the inherent Qi of the body, which is all the bound up energy of the matter, all the chemical energy of the metabolic processes, all the electrical energy of the nervous system, and all the mental and spiritual energy for which there are no known equations, and for all matters may be much greater than the bound atomic energy. So, forgive me if I poo-poo the "powers" of martial arts masters who use some insubstantial Qi to move a fist a trifle amount faster than normal... that energy difference is only relatively substantial to a human... to a mountain it is nearly **zero**.

Using Qi gong to heal thyself

This, certainly more than the martial application, is the truest reason to take up Qi Gong.

More than once I've personally used this to detect (and later defeat) so far 16 successive colds within hours. You see the body has certain qualities and networks which enable you to know of a disease state prior to the symptoms' arrival... much as a forest is alerted by the tree on fire or under fungal attack (through chemical transmitters).

1. Nervous system
 1. Upper CNS - Yi/Shen - last to receive data, after it has been prior filtered... think about how nothing reaches the President (you) before passing through secretaries and desk workers (the lower CNS).
 2. Lower CNS (Limbic system) - Hun/Shen - receives data from the PNS about the body, and interprets commands from upper CNS on how the body should act. This is where telekenesis happens.
 3. PNS/ENS - Po/Shen - performs most activities on its own, but is monitored and modulated by the CNS and by endocrine (hormones)... the ANS portion is like a state or local government acting on its own. The immune system function is like the military which from the White House down to local

Using Qi to diagnose others' ailments

Before you can do this, you really ought to master the first column or at least become reliably proficient.

Now, there are as many different natural healing modalities as meditation types... I can only cover ones from TCM here. And the primary Chinese medical diagnoses are:

1. Radial Pulse
2. Tongue
3. Color
4. Odors
5. Sounds or noises
6. Emotional expression (Shen-Qi)
7. Palpation

Of these I will omit the tongue because it is primarily a diagnosis of the Yi, which is not meditational but intellectually driven.

Pulse

The pulse is normally an intellectual instrument predicated upon the patients' delivery force, flux of blood, and tensile nature of the smooth muscles surrounding the vessels. All these are structural forms of Qi. Now some doctors, not just western MD but even TCM think you can only get information from this, but this is not the case. Though **it is true** the force and quality denotes vital Qi and therefore prognosis as well as the type of disease present (cold or hot, internal or external)... **and it is true** that the tensile nature may denote substances in the blood or even emotional stress... **and it is true** the flow will indicate types of stagnation... that does not in any way indicate HOW to treat.

Most [read: nearly all] doctors using the pulse thusly will use the pulse to feed the Yi information which is fit into TCM theory, life

- militia is all under central command to some degree.
2. Hormonal system - a series of feedback loops and chemical transmissions of data in a quantitative format (rather than streaming)... typically works on a curve
 3. Proprioception - this unique ability of the PNS cells and sense organs (especially inner ear), is used to sense the body's location in space and time... but it also can sense other things.

experience (clinical), and hopefully at least some intuition that spits out a decent treatment.

HOWEVER... a better way to use this to diagnose is to ALSO (include the above method) "hear" the patient's body speak. In fact... this is the ONLY way to become a renowned mystical pulse taker.

Now, reader, please understand there are lots of false views within even the TCM field concerning Qi exchange. Some do not even think Qi can be exchanged... some only through P8/K1, etc...

All of these ideas are simply not based in physics.

You must understand that when you touch the radial pulse - or anywhere on the body for massage/palpation - you are NOT touching the patient... you are sensing their presence through fields... Since we are 99.999999% emptiness as it is, you must not see their body as separate from yours (and a good practitioner of any medicine would not do this anyways)... but that it is simply another object with its own "net" of EM energy and sensations. When you enter the effective range (ranges degrade by the square in fields) your body increasingly becomes aware of the Vibration this person is in on a Body, Mind, and Spirit level. When you consider that you never really touch them, you become aware how profound telekinesis and proprioception really are...

Anyhow, in touching the pulse... listen as you do in the last column and realize that you are doing the following:

1. Hearing their cells, tissues, and organs, and Qi "chatter" in their net
2. Hearing your own body respond to this chatter with concern, empathy, and defense

Limbic system + Cerebellum + spine = Lower CNS

See below for a full body slideshow!

These various aspects are what enable you to "sense" disease. Now, how do you do it?

Well, the answer is right above there.

When meditating, whether you use a Fire method (heavy breathing aka super-oxygenating the body to fill the blood and channels with extra Qi) or Water method (silence... using Qi already present) by quieting the mind you become silently aware that you are like a loud person in a vast open field.

By quieting the mind, you are now able to take note of the things immediately and far away surrounding you. You may, if you put your mind in the lower CNS (nape of head) or in the ENS (dan tian/navel) actually receive messages about the health state of the body.

As you become more advanced, and do it more often (daily is best), the CNS will start to translate images into words or even guttural sentences which essentially establish the problem. Think of it as though the President leaves the Oval office and goes to the site of emergency and talks directly to the people, rather than through normal filters.

It really is that simple.

Hints:

- *If you want to increase your efficacy, and decrease the time to proficiency, I HIGHLY recommend getting charts of the body, both western and eastern, and learning anatomy... you'd be surprised what knowing the exact location and shape, size, even nature of the organ or tissue can do to help you "talk" with it.*
- *In my opinion, water methods > fire methods simply because fire methods are loud... abrasive forms*

3. Projecting your own body's response onto your mind and theirs, causing a echo effect.

When you do this effectively, you will receive diagnosis and instructions such as lights, colors, images, words, point location, may even feel them, or rushing sensations, fatigue, emotional reactions etc...

NOTE - DO NOT buy into the idea that this is how you can catch their "disease"... the only way you can do that is if your vital/wei Qi is weak or Shen is weak and you are thrown off... in which case a doctor YOU SHOULD NOT BE!

Literally you will not catch a flu just in exchange.. and even if you did, you could easily defeat it.

COSE

Much as in touching the patient, you can, with practice, pick up these ambient qualities of their external messages... like the tree talking to the forest again ... and in gauging your reaction to these observations you may - if deft and honest, and able to separate pure and turbid - be able to formulate a diagnosis by using the 5 Element method. **There is a school which teaches this method**, here are my thoughts/responses to it

1. They should use the tongue; it is an invaluable tool.
2. The color shows up many places, not just the temples; in fact all over the skin color changes can tell many things.
3. I feel many CFs can change... just that most people do NOT change, and this can cause a problem if you do not adapt to this possibility that in different epochs of a life, different themes may denote different CFs;

and not receptive in nature.... now at first breathing audibly and to a count will help to quiet the mind and clear it of daily worries... but eventually it is important to breath according to heartbeats and to do that you need to be silent enough to "hear" them in your ear... when you do this, you're starting with the center of Shen-Qi and this is a good thing, too... because the Shen-Qi is the master... not the Yi (which is mostly located in the prefrontal cortex)

- *Try to see the body as a country, with rivers, valleys, deserts, mountains, lakes, etc... Qi moves along contours of the "land" of your body... ever look at a microscope of skin? Kind of looks like a rough desert, doesn't it?*
- *Learn some TCM theory... especially about the ying/wei and four levels of wen-bing disease.*
 - *The Ying Qi is the Qi of the Po, and guides reproduction and healing*
 - *The Wei Qi is the defensive aspect of the body including White Blood Cells, thermokinetics (fevers), etc...*
- *I highly recommend getting Tom Brown Jr.'s Grandfather and convince yourself of the value of creating a healing Sanctuary you can go to in meditation.*

Once you have done all this, then what? Realize that when you are assailed by external factors, or disharmonized by internal ones, the most important thing is to break the habits of denial and laziness. Once you do this, you will 'hear' the body tell you that the ying & wei are separated

though today's Dx is always most important.

4. Half of the Tx is the method of extracting (in people who can recognize themselves as it happens) and this is maybe more important than the CF (element)

Palpation/Massage

Using your "eyes of Qi" (fingertips), it is important to seek out knots in muscles, areas of dryness, scars, etc... in muscles and skin that may block channels, and hold emotional memory. Emotional memory is held within muscles, and unfortunately this includes smooth muscles, so as the ENS experiences emotional trauma, it may lodge very deeply... do use intuition and be willing to "touch" the patient in sometimes uncomfortable areas/ways if it will help to locate a Qi blockage... for example in the iliacus muscle beneath the abdomen (womb/LJ) or inner thighs (LV/KI) or rib-flank (HT/SP). If you are not overly self-conscious and not lascivious, this will not scare them... they will in fact relax as you unblock that locked up Qi.

Sensing it is simply a matter of paying the least attention to sharing the space with them... your body IS already reacting to their presence... are you aware of what it is saying?

Emotional Expression

In simply talking to the person... you will share 80% of your data with them bodily, only 20% verbally. Try your best to use the energy you normal expend in formulating clever/witty responses and questions to instead...

1. Really hear the message they send physically, mentally and spiritually (and if they are different)

[best way I can say this is you feel normal inside and cold in your skin] and get Qi sensations of fever&chills before a thermometer shows it... of body aches before anything really aches... of aversions to elements outside...

You'll even start to get preventative messages such as, "don't get in that water" or "don't eat that"

If you've been sick, say from food, you'll know exactly which food did it.

If you are traumatized, you'll know exactly which movement did it... and envisioning that move will cause the Qi to react with pain (your internal warning gauge of disease).

All these powers can be yours, except...

1. If you hold biases or doubts about this
2. If you have phlegm, damp, or other stasses blocking your channels (such as Parkinsons, MS, stroke, etc...)
3. You cannot understand it.

2. Search your body for an internal response... observe if it is compassionate or repulsed/negative... and act accordingly
3. Intuit a diagnosis in this talking period... then do all other diagnosis and see if they match. If they are far off, what does this say about you, your honesty or biases, and your rapport with them?

WARNING - It is very important to denote the difference between JUDGING the patient and EVALUATING them. judging is based on your sense of right or wrong, usually to do with your belief system... evaluation is about what is right for the patient's health, physically, mentally, and spiritually. For example, you may be vegan... and as soon as the patient mentions they don't eat much meat, you want to personally encourage them to give it up altogether. But really, this PT may be anorexic, atrophic, have an eating disorder, etc... and otherwise actually need more red meat to heal... and this is an evaluation of what their body needs, not what you think is RIGHT.

Using Qi to heal others

Qi diagnosis itself is so profound, you almost have half the work done for you on the spot.

BUT, naturally if you want to go to the next level, it's imperative that you take the aforementioned skills and the data you gather about diagnosis and prognosis and apply this to healing, an act of the 9th realm in complete purity.

Article I

To do this, you can use **any** modality... but the further the degree of separation from the ailed body/mind/spirit to your own then the less you use Shen-Qi and the more you use Universal Qi, which is often super fine.

For example, if a person has been raped, or has PTSD... surgery (like a labotomy) is wholly inappropriate (except to repair tissue). In certain cases, especially more in the past, they used electroshock therapy to induce the brain to release endorphins and other positive hormones. These are Universal Qi methods, but are more or less completely wrong for 90%+ of patients who need cognitive based therapy (Yi-Shen), massage (Po-Shen), acupuncture (can be Universal Qi or Shen Qi, dependent on practitioner's awareness and intention), and spiritual help (Hun-Shen).

But, say for example a person is in a bad accident, or is about to have a heart attack or stroke, or has had an aneurysm... then it is wholly inappropriate to use slower Shen-Qi methods and lifestyle modifications because the body is about to be grievously injured or die... and how can you heal the mind and spirit without a healthy body?

Article II

You must then understand that if you can project Qi/awareness of mind in diagnosing, and the body receives instructions on how to act from the mind, then you can in fact instruct their body as you would your own.

- This requires the patient to be at ease, not engaging their more powerful pre-built network of control
- This means rapport and a good environment
- This means you must be highly focused, with a clear goal in mind... this requires many years of practice.
- You are not responsible for "failing" to instruct their body how to heal. One thought or belief they have, one habit, anything in the slightest can undo hours of work in seconds... it is not your fault.

Article III

In deciding where to focus Qi, know that the following factors and axioms apply:

1. The patient must have enough Qi, be willing and able to heal, there must be no blockages, etc... so the body must be a ready field in spring to sow good crops of healing.
2. You must have enough Qi, mental and spiritual space, no personal emotional/ethical blockages, etc... so the farmer's backbone must be strong and upright.
3. The environment must be supportive and nourishing - color, odor, sound/music, magnetics, people in it, emotional expressions/body language, etc... so in other words do not sow crops in a storm or a blizzard.
4. The patient afterwards must have healing space - this usually means a support system. Be cognizant if they do not; if it cannot be helped, then you must double your efforts, if it can, be gentle in helping the person realize they must make inroads to changing how others treat them while they are healing (in the least).
5. Do not open awareness or new doors the patient is not ready to enter... whatever your modality from dentistry to palm reading... all are dangerous for the unprepared!
6. Never expend all of yourself... a weakened body can be harmed by already present enemies "at the gate"
7. Do not break typical ethical or patient-doctor boundaries... create professional environments that are conducive to healing, do not remove them from the other environment and insert them into your personal world to "rub off on them"... unless you are a spiritual teacher, then do as you see fit.

8. The Qi follows the Shen (Will)... you can guide their Shen and therefore their Qi or directly their Qi... but be aware that their emotions if exacerbated may harm the body or engender the disease process... Usually this involves fear or anger, but grief also comes to mind as something that a doctor can easily give a patient.

In conclusion, you should definitely explore all three worlds of using Qi to heal... but most important is to heal thyself first... and from that allow all other things to follow. Without a healthy doctor, who is the lighthouse, how can the patient know the way out of the fog to safety?

Whatever your method of cultivation, do it and do it with gusto and bravado, and do not let the Idols of the Cave dictate your beliefs about the limits or abilities you have to help yourself or others heal. There are thousands of cases out there of people healing miraculously - and I know of dozens of cases personally - where Qi and intent of mind were solely responsible for diagnosis and healing... and it was not the intervention of a drug, herb, or surgery at all that did it.

Take care, and good luck!

Where is my Subconscious?

Ever since Freud westerners have been familiar - though ignorant of - the existence and profound meaning of the subconscious. Some may even know that there is a difference between the subconscious and the unconscious, a subtlety that is significant as we shall see.

But unlike western psychology, Chinese psychology has known of the subconscious and unconscious for more than a millennium. Now western science itself is only just recently - in this century - starting to detect the presence and effects of the subconscious due to the use of **fMRI or functional MRI**, which can literally show you where activity is occurring in the brain.

Most scientists still perform their research in the cortex and especially the pre-frontal cortex, but already a lot has been uncovered showing that it is literally the substructures of the brain that control many of the things that we feel, think, and do.

I am going to skip the complications and using the verbiage of previous articles, tie directly together for you a mental image of the mind. It would be handy to also review the structures of the brain **and nervous system**, but it is not completely necessary.

Finally I will conclude this article with a brief introduction to methods to contact and 'ping' your subconscious and unconscious minds.

Your Key to the Mind

Western	TCM	Structure	Functions
consciousness	Yi-shen	neocortex	thought, memory, activation, sensation
subconsciousness	Hun-shen	hypothalamus, cerebellum, posterior gyrus, medulla, pons	mediate commands with sensations, determine safety and issue warning signals, control fine movement, *house mostly separate area of brain
unconsciousness	Po-shen	lower CNS, ENS (digestion), PNS (muscles), GTR (reflexes) substantia nigra, reticular formation, endocrine system, lymph system, immune system (and to some degree, nuclei of cells, especially reproductive cells)	regulate fight or flight, rest and digest, carry out commands, distribute information, filter sensory, control cycles of hormones, protect body from **houses a completely undetermined emotional self

note - memory technically belongs to the Zhi of the Kidney, but the Kidney controls Jing which is white substances, so this seems redundant with the Yi-shen's function - you may call it wrong, but remember they did not have microscopes or MRI when they assigned memory to white matter. Also gray (black and white) matter belongs to the Kidney

As we can see, the descriptions get larger the deeper we go... this makes sense, they are larger and larger parts of the body. It also makes sense because 99+% of nervous system activity occurs below the cortex. The reticular formation in particular is responsible for eliminating 99% of sensory that comes 'up the pipe' from the body in the form of:

- nociceptors/pain receptors
- chemoceptors
- proprioceptors - sense your position in space and time
- thermoceptors
- specialized receptors specific to the sensory organs (eyes, ears, etc...)

All of these are constantly firing, and this - along with cellular activity, digestion, and instinctive reflexes forms the heart of the unconscious. However, what science has not yet discovered that TCM has is that the unconsciousness, which is made up of connections between cell nuclei and muscle spindles and peripheral nerves, houses layers of emotions. These emotions can be created or unfortunately for us, locked away, in these tissues, which have absolutely no ability to understand or cognate them, let alone therapeutically flush them away. Thus people of anger resorting to alcoholism (Liver), grief making smokers smoke more (Lungs), rape leading to fibroids and infertility, trauma to phantom pain, etc... These emotions can only be cognitively identified by you through the mediation of the subconscious mind. Your body may often be the bearer of the brunt for your poor habits and emotions... but all day long you are the recipient of the unhappiness or happiness felt by your body. This is why bowel obstruction leads to irritability and also *an inability to let things go*.

So it is all the more important to understand how the subconscious works, and how to speak to it and through it to provide the much needed therapy to the body.

Some useful metaphors:

consciousness	emperor	president	'mind'
subconscious	ministers	white house staff	'soul'
unconsciousness	fiefs	the People	'body' and 'spirit'

Clearly the President is a busy person, concerned with important affairs of state (your life). He/she cannot be bothered by mundane issues. That is why the country has ministers, agencies, legislators, etc... to speak to the People and learn the will of the true rulers of the country who control the economy, man the military, and sustain its lands. A good President or emperor will from time to time go among the People and learn from them about real issues and concerns. This means you will from time to time directly perceive the **causes** of diseases that you see manifest externally in examination, palpation, lab tests, etc... from the doctor or during illness. The illness is not the cause, it is the little sensor in your car that tells you something is not correct. The cause has yet to be determined until you go among the People of the nation (your body and cells) to ask what it is.

However, unlike the President, this must be done through your subconscious. True, western medicine has devised ways of looking into the blood for invading pathogens, or to see if your chemical balance is out of balance, but that doesn't effectively give you the Harmony of communication through your subconscious. You know why the body is experiencing things, but the administrators are not going to go along with you that way.

Therefore the **ONLY method is through direct perception by your mind** - meditation.

There are many types of meditation. You should familiarize yourself with the **Eight Types** as well as the **use of Qi** and the **types of Evil Qi**.

But in the end, the types of meditation most effective, I've found, is either 1) Listening and receiving or 2) Sacred Sanctuary.

Listening and Receiving

The main emphasis in most Qi Gong is in pushing an agenda, namely building of Qi and breathing rhythmically. It is very good for healing. But suppose you are already heading down a bad road, how is acting without changing course going to do anything but either slow you down or speed you up - inexorably you will arrive at the [un]desired destination set by the karma you've chosen.

The first good method you have to harmonize your body is to simply lay quiet and listen. Slowly bring your mind away from the forehead, where images and thoughts assail you all day long, towards the back of your head where the subconscious is housed in the posterior gyrus and cerebellum - the 'little brain'.

But you cannot just move your mind backwards, you must also "receive" the information given, without arguing or analyzing it too much. Through this way you give a 'voice' to the advisors to correct your orientation towards your subconscious, which may not be in agreement with you.

- You think one way and feel another - Yi/Hun disharmony
- You feel one way and act another - Hun/Po disharmony
- You are unable to make a decision or...
- Your decisions always get thwarted (go astray)
 - Diets
 - Can't get past laziness
 - No motivation
 - Unknown origination of negative emotions

All of these things result from too much 'pushing' of the mind and too little listening to the soul and spirit of the body.

It is another way of saying too much me and too little spiritual connection to God. God is, after all, the ultimate Hun from whence your imagination, creativity, and deeper happiness derive. All carnal forms of these things are transient and never produce long lasting health and happiness. Listening and receiving is the number one method - the simple method - for correcting such imbalances.

The Sacred Sanctuary

A more complex, visual method (useful because the vision center is located in the posterior gyrus) is the SS meditation, which follows these steps:

1. In a quiet place and comfortable position - image you are going from your home to a magical place only for you
2. To get there you must pass through something ominous, like a forest or mist,
 1. Do not linger
 2. This represents your thoughts and cortex' mind.

3. Once clear you enter a beautiful landscape, and find a doorway of any design you want.
4. Entering the doorway you make your way to a sanctuary
 1. This represents the subconscious mind
 2. It should look the same every time
 3. Make it big enough to change/make additions to.
 4. Regulate your breath naturally, do not count breaths
5. Go and find your "Master" or "guru"
 1. This is the Hun, and can even be God, Jesus, Buddha, whoever...
 2. The 'voice' of this Master is fatherly, honest but not malicious.
 3. When you ask questions answers come true and bluntly.
6. Ask to be led to your 'healing room' and follow
7. Visualize laying down on a table
 1. You can also imagine separating into a spirit and body, body on the table and you with the Master looking at it.
8. The Master (and you) will perform healing ceremonies varying from herbs and acupuncture, massage, to fields of Qi, aromas, and even surgeries!
9. When you are done healing... go out the way you came, and thank the Master. An attitude of gratitude is primal to healing.
10. Do not share your inner sanctum with others... make it very private. This is how your mind and body really are.

This method uses visualization, even sound and smell to correctly orientate your mind and thoughts with your body and environment. It also, like before, gives voice to those parts of you that rarely get a chance to speak with you. Finally, you gain good insight into whether what you are doing is harmonious with God and your surroundings. Please read the **'Inadvisable Practices'** article as a supplement to this practice, especially if you intend to share it.

I hope you have found this article enlightening, it certainly is VERY important to be aware of yourself, and now that we have such deep knowledge about the human mind, why not also know thyself through the three levels as well?

Phasing In - Seeing the Soul or Spiritual level

The main goal here is to get past our physical attachment to the body, fully < .000001% of our true body of potential realities, and to see the soul as it is TODAY. The soul vibrates, too, and has its own anatomy and layers. These are very difficult to study, because there is no machine available for this process. You can only do it through meditation or through taking psychedelics which change the normal ways the brain interprets data (whether by speeding up or slowing down).

This method is the non-psychedelic way.

First, you must become familiar with theta wave state. Theta wave state is beyond the normal alpha and beta wave conscious and subconscious states your mind tunes to. To get

there, you can use music such as Indian or chanting, or Theta-wave music which sells on the web, or is free on YouTube, or you can simply do what the Natives did when hunting:

1. Flatten your gaze - expand your eyesight to the full lateral and azimuth of your eyes, 180 degrees in all directions
2. Pull your ears - gently - back, to open the LV/GB channel.
3. Form a light "Buddha" smile on your face to relax the muscles into Original Face.
4. Try to "tune in" to your original "true" frequency¹
5. See all things as impermanent and understand they are not "real" just one actualized potential of a practically infinite set of realities.
6. Eliminate your belief in time.
7. Subdue the ego, cease to see others or self (in mirror) as separate entities but instead part of one whole Mind - the Superego.
8. Be happy, filled with love, patience, and compassion.
9. Note the bright light parts of the face and the dark spots, and get impressions. Beauty? Hideousness? Sadness? Joy? Love? Respect? Death? Can you see all of them in tandem?
10. Allow these things to flow through the mind without attachment to one or the other.

When you stare at yourself or another person long in this state you will release the ego's emotional baggage and come into tune with your own True Self, which is part of the transcendental whole. At that point you are "in phase" to borrow an engineering term for a signal. After all everything vibrates, including the psyche (Hun-Po). The Yi can observe this but only passively. Any attempt to control the process or take over and then you will fall back out of phase, and go back to normal life. That is perfectly OK. It may seem turbulent BUT REALIZE that is only to you coming out of phase, the rest of society will not notice that the world is more turbulent until you point it out.

CAUTION - becoming obsessed with phasing in may actually be harmful to God's purpose for you. There is a reason for all these actualized potentials and also for free-will; so do not become obsessed (with anything) especially with being "perfect."

Measuring Success in Spiritual Alchemy

When you exercise you typically see a result good or bad. The muscle gets bigger or you get injured/inflexible etc...

But how are we to measure alchemical success? It is really about three measurements. #1 physical health signs and physical rewards, #2 mental health signs and awareness rewards (samadhis and dharanis), and #3 spiritual health signs esp. Happiness rewards.

#1 So typically what we look for are decreases in signs of depression and anxiety. Less leg or other twitches, less rashes acne and autoimmune breakout, regular stools no longer alternating loose hard/ribbony/pebbly nor constipated... we want 1-2 at most 3 bm's a day, light yellow urine not clear nor dark & odorous. We want less muscle tension esp neck shoulders and low thoracic and lumbar.

We want increased sensual acuity and decreases in signs of hardening and degradation such as nails, skin, teeth, hair...

We want to see your facial lines disappear and your face to gravitate towards the "buddha smile". If you get frownies you can expel them. You want symmetrical face and eyes. You want skin color to become not shaded nor pale in the aura. You want no fuzziness nor bad hair-days unless its just dry out.

You should have less pops unless you are a wood element in which case you need to pop-not popping is bad.

You want to cease biting nails lips and tongues.

Your nails should have no fungal infections

Your hands should remain clean mostly without washing... and not too oily a head or skin nor too dry.

Your mouth will have moisture but not soggy.

You want a long pulse but not wiry nor deep and slow.

These are some of the signs physically that you are. Tuned into your highest self on the physical plane.

#2 On the mental plane this gets trickier. Firstly you shall have naturally less need/want for yourself but you may depending on #3 and beliefs want more for others' positively speaking. You want to see your mind less racing nor stuck on an idea; ie mentally constipated.

Your happiness though fleeting or long will be less materially dependent and if an extrovert you now enjoy silence/stillness and if introverted you enjoy the banter of others and no longer loathe/despise humanity. Your interests in destructive forces of art, music, and entertainment while remaining may wane for interests in positive/creative endeavors. Your taste for crass or perhaps (be honest) mean things may wane for more uplifting messages. Though hopelessness may remain you find hope and Willpower more abundantly. Your lust and zeal for change and new tastes may increase though you are not beholden any longer to them for sustenance in a pointlessly materialistic society.

You will feel happiness with regard to the sudden manifestations of material wealth although you desire them less than before (irony). your prayers come true more often and in a positive light rather than self fulfilling doom. That thing you needed for your creative project/endeavor/gift... it appears whimsically. Your friends and others will suddenly call you without anything more than a thought or hope that they are well. You may start seeing in fact future events.

More importantly what started off as awareness of physical and material changes you will now begin to note the environmental strata around you is shifting in sync with your emotions or vice versa. You will know inherent dangers of weather. Bad driver days you will detect and avoid car wrecks for example. Or that mtg you wanted but is about to be canceled suddenly won't hurt your feelings. That betrayal you never saw coming you will feel enterically/viscerally and know of it before it harms you... and its harmful effects will upon examination actually be boons and protections to your karma and pain for enemies. You will see less conflict and literally others will become like to yourself. You'll see yourself in enemies. You'll see your mistakes in sick people. Their faces will become mirrors and shades of alternate streams of your own data.

Quite literally you'll gain the buddha mirror dharani and be able to co-habitate the 0-space with a person and see your own face in theirs and theirs in yours though they understand not why or how.

You'll be able to detect elemental types and mitigate your threatened ones with yang and restrain your threats with yin shen.

Your mind will in meditation become a pool and all sounds or thoughts ripple it. You'll master any meditation or lucid technique within hundredths the time of those that are not using alchemical methods.

Every doctrine will be as open to you and unthreatening as a phone book's various advertisements. All sciences will reinforce your understanding and religions will seem to agree though their proponents argue.

The asanine will be like great studies and you'll see little things reflected into greater things. Quite literally spontaneous wisdoms will appear from your subconscious and you'll accept these wisdoms without worry or argument and your mind will become God's garden. The devil may play but the light will be upon him and yet you will not feel ashamed because both enlightenment and salvation are already yours from birth and YOU KNOW THIS. You don't mind being told it though because after all everyone has become like you and you like they. They fear for salvation and strive for bodhi so you do. But you have these jewels and so do they. Your compassion and love will extend even to enemies, traitors, tyrants, sinners, and even God.

Your mind's lucidity will be its only threat. You'll cease worrying about achieving Perfect Enlightenment because you'll know EXACTLY what keeps you from it, why, and how long you need if you were or wanted to change those steps...

#3 In the spirit you will find many companions of differing paths. Although all can use 1 path none do but they approach the same Mountain nevertheless. Not all who wander are lost... and you will not have worry but just compassion for those in the Forest. Nor will you despise or begrudge those who sit on the observatory Cliff. And those that lend rope you'll anchor or replace. Those that lend not rope you'll help to mend their stinginess by opening eyes and hearts. Those that climb single-mindedly you'll help to touch the world of those in the Forest. You'll share a map of unbelievable breadth and detail and yet find no problem adding notes to it.

Potentials previously closed will open. Illnesses impossible to cure will become as just speed-bumps or paper walls.

The spirit realm will send animals and omens to warn you and you'll NOTICE them. You'll find that your spirit soars and is Indomitable even in cities of despair. The fear of death will end with knowledge of yourself and your path and destination/port of call and where you are right now.

The problems of the world will be understood in relation to spiritual changes of the collective consciousness... they will be matters of unfortunate times or perhaps normal ratios of difficulty in samsara or even perfection depending on your belief systems.

The mind will have a longer tranquil Cycle of Mind section while the lower 4 realms will deplete in length... even disappearing for some people who spend all their time in the upper 4 because they have left the World (mostly).

But even those within the world will be able to shift between worlds and understand all the spirits at play and how the people perceive their worlds whatever it is as an endeavor of uniting force... and you won't be affected negatively by these changes. And even if it is a negative/hateful world you are stuck in you'll detect its pathogenic invasion of your world and your Qi body and you'll be able to usurp the enemy Qi.

Your Qi will be sacrificed less or at least willfully and knowingly rather than habitually and without foreknowledge.

The Qi Movement will show you all ways and when it's stuck you'll KNOW you need treatment and you will receive treatment though you don't want it.

Frustrations will melt with breath while obsessions will either go away or become empowering.

All of these spirit benefits will be these spontaneously and without concentrated effort... but if you have to focus on it you'll be successful even though it may take days or longer. But mostly spontaneous results will happen but the irony is you won't own them anymore. How weird...

And when you wish to escape to the Void you won't need to sleep and dream you can use a silent wordless Samadhi and you will just Know the Truth and wish to share it but alas... words ruin its simplistic beauty. Many have tried but you know viscerally how vain it's been.

Namaste.

The Concept of Death

The concept and question of death has fascinated everyone since the beginning of consciousness. Animals such as elephants and dolphins have been shown to grieve already and it is surmisable that our ancestors first began creating myths concerning the afterlife as early as the invention of fire and language via body noises. Certainly the quest to understand what happens after we die has motivated theologians and philosophers, yogis and sages for at least 10,000 years. There are - to be simple -two basic spiritual views and one atheistic view. There is the one life or spontaneous birth theory which involves the belief that we are born as if from the seed of the Mind of God, and then when we die, our life's deeds determine the infinite future of our afterlife. Then there is the cyclic view that life is birth, death, and rebirth, and when combined with the concept of Karma, is used to explain the variety of stations in life, forms, and experiences we have, as well as good or bad things that happen to us.

The atheist view is simple: spontaneous/coincidental birth that leads to complexity due to somewhat chaotic and somewhat organized programming and leading to biological success (or not) and death. Death then is simply a dispersal and rotting away - cessation.

All of these views, according to their own perspective, tend to regard the other views as heretical, ignorant, or illogical. In western philosophy, cyclic perspective and intuition are not logical. In eastern mysticism and shamanism, the view that death is forever is seen as ignoring the evidence found within nature. In science, matters of the spirit are neither proven nor disproved. And aside from this many atheists see the afterlife as a capricious

system of imparting morals, and as being quite individual to interpretation. On top of this some spiritual systems do not believe in a soul that passes from life to life, and that such a view is a matter of 'clinging' to life and hoping for eternal life. Certainly the health and anti-aging industries are a testament to the fact that people prefer not to die or face their fears surrounding death.

So two fundamental questions arise: of course the first is... what is death and what happens when we die? The second is why are we afraid to die? This question will lead us into other interesting topics, all of which I hope to provide AN answer to... not THE answer. What follows is not meant to be insulting to any heritage. Point of fact it is my intention to prove that as with everything, the Bagua Dharma unifies all the data, as long as the parameters are set. So within the Bagua Dharma, **all three basic views have validity.**

What is Death?

It could be described many ways. The cessation of natural functions of the body. The separation of mind and body. The split of yin from yang. The end of a journey and beginning of a new one. But none of these particularly works well in all cases. For example there is a Tibetan meditation called the Death Trance where the body has died, but for days, weeks, and even months will not rot. The person is pronounced dead and does not return from death¹, but yet they are not like as to other dead people. And then there are cases like coma; does the mind remain or does it leave? Does the body die first or the mind?

This leads to the question... well how is the mind related to the body anyhow? There is the vague understanding that the mind is related to the brain. But also it is related to our emotions and our physical health and therefore that arises the question is it the nerves themselves or the neurons? Where is the soul contained, if it exists?

The only answers that seem to be arising in the field of science is that complexity of interaction and inter-relation leads to spontaneous and exponential increase of consciousness. So if a single bacterium has say a unit of consciousness of 1, then 3 of them should have at least 3 and perhaps as much as 6, being 3! (factorial). So a 10000 cell individual would be much more conscious than a 1000 cell individual.² Our brain has billions of neurons, and a large number more neurons are contained in the peripheral nervous system throughout the body... each of these connected to other types of cells which form organs.

Intelligence of Plants

Each cell having a nucleus and its own semi-conscious organelles within it that perform functions apparently of their own decisions. And all of these therefore connected to the whole individual, would constitute a consciousness many many times more aware than the bacterium described above. Research into the intelligence of plants has revealed that this

holds true with root systems, which seem to have form of consciousness, and of course we all know that plants will move or react with stimulus even without a brain.

So the typical scientific view of consciousness arising from a brain may not be entirely accurate. Therefore it is conceivable that consciousness can exist separate from this brain, or perhaps even arises solely from complexity itself... not necessarily nerves, but any form of complexity. Crystals, stones, shells, homes, anything with remarkable complexity that generates inter-relating fields where electronic and magnetic data (and perhaps more) can pass between delineated entities or objects may indicate life.

The change of this view of life from the typical organic model would certainly explain all shamanistic 'spirit world' points of view or the Mahayana belief that all things animate and inanimate have Buddha nature (atoms?). But how do we account for the two views in the same perspective? It is a Universe - one being the characteristic feature here - so we must reconcile these perspectives.

This is where the Triple-Plane comes most in handy. The understanding that the Universe is composed of three major 11 dimensional planes: Spiritual (undetectable with physical only instruments), the Physical (space-time), and the Mental connecting them. Consciousness therefore acts as the unifying force that unites the awareness of the yin-physical aspect of the Universe with the unseen, Spiritual aspect, which has currently been described in science as dark matter, dark energy, anti-matter, and other strange phenomena. In Chinese cosmology it is described as Qi, which cover not just this unknowable portion, but also the aspects called forces and flux fields.

Please review the article above to familiarize yourself with the design.

Now, with this Triple Plane we can explain that [via the Law of Evolution which contains chaotic, non-linear mathematics] we understand that the physical plane contains complex forms, **but it is the aspect of Mind or consciousness that give them "life" in the spiritual realm.** Conversely, if the object has a destiny (history, memory, and experiences

cause and effect) and is found in the Physical plane, it must therefore have life. Therefore death is easily explained. Is it the cessation of functions of the body? Yes, when that ending of function causes the **Instance** of crossing of the entity's mental plane to cease connecting the Physical Plane with the future (destiny) of that stream. [like going inactive in a game on a server]. Thus the normal body rots as the mind has left, but in an individual engaged in death trance (perceiving Limbo or Bardo as the Tibetans call it) would not be technically dead because their body is still anchored in the physical plane. Some cells die, sure, but overall they are continuing on just with less (no) activity. This proves that though the brain's activities are part of life they do not constitute life itself. The complexity and the "soul" for lack of a better word to define this Instance defines life and therefore death.

If one thinks on it, it explains also how sudden-impact ends life. There is no scientific explanation as to why traumatic impact would cause anything but extreme pain and eventual death. But some impacts are instantaneous. Why? Well the law of Conservation dictates that momentum is conserved. If an individual perceives they are falling, for instance, and are to strike the pavement... their perception will continue even past the striking point. Literally it will be as a dream is: happening without one knowing it. One will literally keep 'falling' in perception, and the Mental Plane's instance will instantly shift on the Physical Plane. In this "stream" we shall perceive the individual as having died but actually in other streams they will be perceived as continuing on, and until the individual loses the momentum (however that is accomplished when someone violates the law of gravity and therefore Karma).

Poor individual, right? Perhaps, perhaps not. In dreams, [where our Mental Plane all but leaves the present if not anchored by our bodies,] one dream easily rolls into another as soon as the dreamer is done experiencing the dream. My **description of lucid dreaming and such techniques may be poignant** or interesting at this point.³ But it is not central to the point which is that the Mental Plane (and its vibrations) are what are determining death or life in any given stream of reality - or what people say is "your world."

This has profound implications. First it explains that **both dual versions of life after death in spirituality are correct**. You have one life in any given stream, and then you have the eternity that follows as you pass into the infinite Spiritual Plane which is to say **a probability cloud of Destinies**. You get to keep trying and keep experiencing... and this goes on forever. Life and death, reincarnation, now also with the realization that most of our selves - our Self as One that is to say - are at any time not active (at least not in one Universe).⁴ This means that we are for the most part already in Heaven at all times. It is merely the single version of us which is not that is experiencing the 'fiction' of awareness.⁵

But if we can be said to be aware at all, the single version that is happening (including **all three minds**) is the dream, and all the other possibilities not happening are the fact. And when our awareness ceases to perceive one stream and perceives another, it is no different than basically infinitely being in the afterlife. Volumewise, our time is spent with the Beyond the 11th Realm. Timewise it is as though we barely existed.. and were a spontaneous blip. And yet, with the knowledge in physics now that time is a perception and not real, we also see the cyclical factor of life.

We've been in this Room forever now... and we always will be - because our perception keeps recycling upon this. Thus the major thing we must become aware of is that our knowledge of this does not empower us unless we can answer the next question: why are we afraid to die?

It could be blamed perhaps on the invention of dogmatic versions of explaining Karma, and the concept of sin. An external Hell, as it were. But as shown before elsewhere Hell is a mental vibration, and when in Hell it is by definition forever, there being no time outside of our Mind. But is it really forever? Not really, no. It is a passing vibration.⁶

But... there are many ways to die. The individual named before could pass a long period of time (relatively speaking) unaware they had died. And depending on their emotion at the time of death that period could be pleasant and go from a freefall into a swim in a Caribbean water and then after some time of relaxation a decision to be reborn.. or could be marked by screaming and running in fear from the very things the person feared when last alive... all of them now as manifest and possible as any other possibility. This in the Tibetan Book of the Dead is described as the reason why individuals choose to be reborn, is the fear or better put, self-denial of Nirvana. It is not that God keeps us from enjoying Heaven but that we ourselves do not experience that dream like state as pleasant, and therefore escape FROM it into what we illusory call "reality." This is life.

And perhaps, as the Tathagata Curve indicates, there is a precise ratio the God-Source uses or more likely requires for the Universe to function. After all, the Experience is not just individual, it is societal, species-related, and even Brahma/Krishna (the Physical form of I-Am) requires Experience and evolution. So perhaps a certain number of people are supposed to be born.⁷

Certainly in Mahayana the bodhisattva is not so much liberated - except from delusion - as burdened (willingly) to be a servant. What kind of servant? To the Thus Come Ones, the living fractal of the One Mind... the singularity manifest for the briefest moments in physical form, to teach the central Truth, and then return or perhaps travel elsewhere to share this message again and again and again, never ending.

Viewed this way it is unclear whether life's burdens can be called burdens. At least you and I do not have the responsibility of teaching people how to pay attention to their fractal aspect of God-Mind... and how to reunify. Some do, at any rate.

But still, I suppose the prospect of rebirth in a worse circumstance than we have now... clinging to the current status due to fear of the Unknown, and the moment's respite it gives our weary forms, and the pain that Samsara conditions us with is the main impetus; and not merely a ratio which seems impersonal and hopeless. At least if we perceive that it is our delusions - of self, of purpose, of meaning, of reality, of life, and of death - are something that are a matter of ignorance and actually simply a more error-riddled Mental stream (choice)... then there is the hope of at least tending towards the center and to abide therein forever.⁸

This "desire" may be forgiven amongst all our desires, because at least it gives us somewhere to steer our course.

But does the fear go away?

I think perhaps that is an individual question. How much pain has one [recently] endured and can [reasonably] withstand in between periods of forgetfulness that come with death and the choice of rebirth? In some cases trauma in Samsara can span lives... but most pains occur within this iteration/incarnation. That means the choice to fear death or not fear it usually arises from an individual incarnation's preparation for the act that one will die: yes... but it is not the end, nor anything to fear.

To be honest, it is probably a good thing to die. The amount of pains and burdens, ills, and losses that pile up within one life well spent is pretty amazing. Youth never lasts, and the ones we love are always torn from us... Even if one can let go of most it seems usually there is one person one cannot bear to part with. But if we are prepared, armed with information and mounting evidence, and have practiced some self-control... then actually death can give us a release; bankruptcy court for the soul.

The question is: are you ready? The samurai believed one must always be ready to die, and so do the Tibetans. I think maybe ALWAYS is a lot to ask. But some preparation might suffice. It would be a bit lamentable if one's family was already entering a stream that would be fun enjoyable, and you missed it and had to acquire new family somewhere completely different. Granted you wouldn't remember once there, but the pain upon entering that life could have some kind of detriment. The science of how souls enter the body is as of yet, completely inexorable. Maybe it always will be. Overall it seems more important to be certain of how one LEAVES than how one ENTERS.

So why does society fear death?

Other than the obvious "well because everyone does, summation of the whole" kind of thing... I think there is something to be said here about the Cycle of Mind and the Cosmic Scale. The CoM in everyone oscillates through many emotions daily and weekly. Some people it is highly pronounced. In others the oscillations are relatively flat and go from slightly happy to slightly unhappy. It is all individual. But the Process remains. This means on the Cosmic Scale, and most definitely Earthly Scale, and perhaps Regional Scale (nations, cultures), would certainly have these eras. Boom and bust in economy, war and peace in history, warlords and empires.... all aspects of the CoM applied larger.

At the moment our collective society fears the End of the World. It is perhaps because our subconscious is aware that our society's current behaviors cannot be sustained and this stream is spiralling out into nothing. In which case the individual must ask "why am I here?" Why did you choose this stream to join? Did you choose it because we are also enjoying god-like fruits of nature... is it because you are materialistic and prefer to be attached to material wealth? Are you here to see the flowering of God's Self-Knowledge through humanity at our crescendo? Is it perhaps that you are here to warn people the new way it is not The Way? Or all of the above?

Unknown... but for sure known is that fear is marketed and fear is palpable these days. If a person is to take care of their health and mental stamina as they enter dangerous times... times when one may be unaware they have died painfully or otherwise.... then the individual should be able to discern fear mongering from entertainment, and able to remove their fears. After all: there are a million billion things that can kill us, but we're alive and reading this.... there must be some reason that the world has not ended yet. Perhaps it will for people who fear it. Perhaps a Judgment will come. I say that judgment is every second, every moment, and carried within our Mind. And if that is so: as a society I ask that we all carry our hopes and go forward not fearing what may never arrive. How can one attain the Way with such fears killing his/her mind?

The Atheist View

As a former atheist I find it an amusing view... and a trifle bit simple. Besides, it seems also harmless when it comes to the subject of death. A soul can only pretend to be nonexistent for as long as it prefers... at some point the seed re-emerges and usually with vigor. The more disturbing aspect is the denial of Self that comes with it. To deny the Spiritual is to deny the Self because it is only the Spiritual Plane that enables Evolution to occur and time to be perceived. Thus it is not the rest of us I am saddened for but for the fool that buys into this self-denial. What's more disturbing is the arrogance with which it always comes with. The admitted ignorance but the unwilling to fix it. One is ignorant of the Self and "where" it is or its "evidence" and yet satisfied with that. Having been atheist I am but very sad for those who remain in such limited views.

And I can say there is a cure, but it must start with humility and asking "why am I wrong?" Not telling oneself "why I am right." I have done both in this incarnation, and I can say it was only due to past life good fortunes and some habits of my soul that saved me at all. I thank the Lord that there is no End, let alone to His love and compassion. The Thus Come Ones are here for us.... let us listen to them. This is my personal opinion I understand individuals have the right to choose as they will. But as the Daishonin writes, people will chase fame and fortune throughout their life, enduring the painful as though it were good, and not spend even a few minutes on their soul's future. Such a thing is lamentable. Ekiken added that people also will chase the impossible to get (wealth) and throw away the easy to keep (good health) [and love I would argue.] This problem is what I see amongst patients and souls passing through the Three-fold world (Saha) daily. Forgetting the real for the unreal (and still, still, still not recognizing Shunyata/Annuta right before them). If any of this ephemeral and ethereal life was meant to be taken literally, why we were born to live so short and so tiny as compared to the stars and galaxies... and mountains and Earth itself?

On Lifestyle Modification

Building on the last entry, the topic of "how TCM works" we must delve into the concepts that are the basis for the ideal lifestyle, as the medicine sees it.

More of this topic, as it concerns diet, is in my [5 Element Diet seminar](#) and [impending book](#).

However, some of the topics will be covered here as a general discussion of "how to modify your lifestyle."

First we must look at all the elements of a lifestyle:

1. Diet
2. Emotional and spiritual bearing
3. Habits
4. Beliefs or paradigms of thought
5. Exercise or activity routines
6. Social strata and relational abilities
7. Motivation, willpower, and discipline
8. Overall goals and dreams

There may be more things, but this just about covers all of the aspects we are interested in talking about. In The Shaolin Academy Archives I have another article on health, which contains various topics covered from the Health Class. In short this article says that there are 5 Pillars of health - Physical, Emotional, Spiritual, Social, and Financial - and that each of these has various parts that constitute their makeup. For every person what is healthy is generally different, however, there exists an ideal in Chinese medicine.

Now granted this idea of the Superior Man¹ is a bit sexist in that it was formulated at a time after the point when women held much political power in tribes and civilizations, so the ideal is dictated by and from men who developed it. However, most of the ideal aspects of the 'perfect' lifestyle according to Chinese culture, wisdom, and medicine are still applicable to anybody, regardless of various capricious beliefs or things such as allergies or genetic conditioning.

I

As it pertains to Diet the medicine mostly encourages moderation and a form of (in general) allopathic care. If you want to eat cold, eat something or drink something hot. If you want to eat dairy, eat something spicy to break it up, etc...

It also warns against overfilling or abstaining from eating, including vegetarianism (except by ascetics or other pious folks where it would nourish the soul), however in general one should eat mostly vegetables and fruits little meat or dairy or grains.

Finally the medicine warns against eating too much difficult to digest things, like raw or cold, eating too fast, or on the fly, or at irregular intervals and odd times.

Thus it follows that the lifestyle modification is to alter whatever one is doing to follow these guidelines. Practically speaking:

1. Avoid fad diets
2. Drop combo meals, drink clean water (and often), eat real food, and eat less
3. Mix up your diet
 1. 5 Colors - red, orange/yellow, green/brown, black/purple, white
 2. 5 Flavors - spicy, sweet, sour, bitter, salty

3. 5 Properties - bland, acrid, toxic, aromatic, basic
4. 5 Types - meats, veggies, fruits, grains, dairy
4. Avoid purging/cleansing except at utmost need (gallstones, toxic diseases, etc...)
5. Lightly exercise after eating, don't eat too late at night

Again more specifics are in the article as well as the 5 Element Diet manual, available for sale to the public (contact me for details).

II

As it pertains to emotional and spiritual bearing, I want to emphasize that it's not about what you believe, it's about what you do with that belief. Emotions are fine, however they tend to stagnate Qi and most people cannot control their emotions but instead are controlled by them. This fact has been verified by modern research into hormone released by the hypothalamus and pituitary which seem to be addictive to the body, especially the stronger emotions such as rage or lust.

Let me say this and this only about spirituality - Have a belief and do three things: study, practice, and teach. It's not about the answers you get, it's about the questions you ask. Later there may be a separate article on this, but I want to emphasize that the Laws of the Universe do not respond to answers which may be already placed in your head as assumptions and paradigms of belief... the Universe (God, Dao, Void, etc...) responds to the questions you ask and HOW you ask them. This is one of the most key points raised by Quantum and Relativity Theories: the observer is all important.

As for emotions, find a healthy outlet. Some people who have studied the 5 Elements, I would advise you to carefully study how each emotion of the elements guards and regulates other emotions. If you vent anger for instance, it may be better, but you may in fact make it worse. Instead one might try repentance (a form of regret or grief) to "cut the wood" and lower anger. It generally follows that after grief comes healing, thereby removing anger from the cycle. This is but one example of emotional control possible.

III

As it pertains to habits, the medicine is not explicit about all habits. It is very clear about substance abuse and sexual overactivity, that they are taxing to health. In general any habit over time is taxing to the Jing-essence² and therefore life-shortening. In fact, the only habits that seem to produce health are listed here:

- Spiritual practice
- Qi Gong
- Good diet
- Healthy emotional digestion (intake, absorption, growth, excretion)
- Daily light exercise - occasional moderate exercise - rare extreme exercise
- Stress elimination
- Plenty of rest and sleep, but not too much
- Continual learning - See Superior Man discussed below
- Family activities
- Continual health intervention and therapy

All habits should fall into one of those categories if they are to be considered healthy. Some things fall more closely to the "ideal" than others, depending on the habit, and one must see how one's body responds to said habit to discover the extent of its usefulness. Some bodies, for example, benefit from jogging, some get arthritic. The specific formula for your health and longevity habits will be profoundly different than others' It could be said, perhaps, that the tailoring of this formula, and discovering it, might be what life is about for all of us, and that those that discover the right balance for themselves overall achieve more gratification than the majority who do not take the time to do so.

IV

Your habits of course are created by your beliefs, many of which are not your own. The pattern of these beliefs and habits form your paradigms of thought about particular topics. Paradigms are natural, and as contrary as they seem to helping us find Truth, are absolutely necessary. Why?

Because it is paradigm modification which forms the foundations of solving the great mysteries of our existence and thus supporting our spiritual practice. The ability to observe and change one's paradigm when new information becomes available, better or more useful information, creates the wisdom we need to become fuller humans, and achieve the Superior Man status.

Paradigms themselves are like puzzle pieces, each seemingly gerrymandered and random, without context to anything specific. However, when placed together, for the person that has set their paradigms or rest them, or deleted them because they were unwanted gifts from childhood and Karma, it will be an empowering experience to look back upon this process and say, "I have done it. I have figured it out."

Figured what out? Oneself. Figuring out oneself is important not because we need others to know who we are, but because we measure ourselves by what we believe others see in us. Thus if we know ourselves, we will see this reflection in others' views of us as well, and therefore the random image without context will not look so much like a Picasso, but more as a Rembrandt or Michaelangelo. All have their beauty in context of when and why they appear the way they do. This is the profundity of Life.

V

Exercise and activity in general is one of the more misunderstood aspects of health. The medicine is not very big on calisthenics, though in external martial arts it is considered a cornerstone of health. True, it is far better to exercise and be active than not, but let us make a strong caution when it comes to exercise that overwork is another habit of taxation. Sweat is the viscous (fluid) of the heart. Thus it follows that too much sweat will deteriorate the heart. Many ex-athletes die of heart attacks, often with no direct connection to "heart disease forming diets." It is now known, in fact, that the primary agent of heart disease and atherosclerosis is not cholesterol, which is smooth and fundamental to health, but stress which raises blood pressure and injects histamines and oxidants into the blood which shred the arteriole walls leading to scar tissue.

Modern research from the National Geographic Blue Zone study has shown that it is not exercise specifically that gives health (except to the overweight)... it is activity. Few centenarians - if indeed ANY - when asked the formula to health have ever said, "I ran a

mile a day and was a body builder." In fact to the contrary mostly they talk about lifestyle. About the importance of being active in daily life and spending time with family and in spiritual practice. They also eat real foods and keep in general shape.

So let us be clear - be purposefully active, but do not stress out the body. Modify the lifestyle to include activity, and avoid chronic wear and tear leading to arthritic conditions, which block Qi. Muscles regulate themselves, building muscle is not all that important, and in fact could be taxing; do it only if you like the image, because a healthy confidence level is better than a low one.

VI

Social strata is a tough topic, and one of some contingency because few people these days wish to acknowledge the existence of a caste system in modern society. Rather than call it a caste, we call it a class. Well, where I am from class is something you have (or don't) not what you are. More accurately it is a caste, meaning a circle of people you are generally surrounded by and a level of social hierarchy you are subject to and understand.

The frustrating thing about this caste system is that because it is unspoken, there are few written manuals for moving up in the caste system, and only one generally known method: accumulating money. As they say though, "No matter how far a jackass travels he won't come back a horse." The only true method to move up in a caste is to increase one's value to society. The ancient Chinese way was to become a Superior Man and work in either the government, military, academia, or as a doctor.

This way does still generally work, however I can tell you from personal experience that the money issue is still a major part of the situation. Thus why I emphasize that you have to become valuable to society as well. You may be a true gentleman of the Arts and still be treated as lowly as a car mechanic simply because of the clothes you wear, and your manner of speech. See my [**Recommended Reading List**](#) for books on enhancing your value to society.

VII

Motivation, willpower, and discipline are something you either have or you don't. If you want to modify your lifestyle, you've got to have all three, as well as patience and fortitude because it is not easy, my friends.

However I will add this:

1. Sometimes all three are held abnormally low by health issues, including depression, physical blockages, or emotional stagnation at the mind/spirit level. Better to see a master doctor and help you to get the initial umph to "break the ice under the rudders"
2. If you don't have these and you don't even have enough to develop them, it's best to admit your faults and humble yourself and follow a teacher CLOSELY. You need to learn via [**entanglement**](#)³, where you harness their energy and learn their ways as a mentored student. If you can do this, as the Yi Jing says, you'll go from the dark to the light in no time. Just don't forget they, too, are human and remain with them for

the proper amount of time, and then go your own way onto the next teacher when you are ready.

3. Having Gung Fu⁴ is really a matter of these three things. But healthy lifestyles are about balance. Do not forget this: **discipline is that whereby you gain internal power. However, it harmful, is definitely not good.**

VIII

Some people profess to not having dreams and goals... such people are either nihilists, sages, or ignoramuses. Since you cannot know a sage by his/her outer appearances, I recommend having an open mind, but recalling always that "the only thing wrong with an open mind is that anyone can put anything in it."

As for nihilists, frankly they are not worth your time.

As for the ignorant, do not pity them or hate them, they are where they need to be - in the stormy ocean. When they are tired of the beatings from the winds and tides, then they will seek a teacher and "when the student is ready the teacher will appear."

----- Glossary

1. The Superior Man - a Confucian concept where a person becomes proficient, if not masterful in the 5 arts: music/poetry, martial arts, healing, writing, and culinary

arts.

2. Jing-essence - aka pre-heaven Qi, despite western confusion with Qi this is the most close concept in Chinese medicine to a "life force."
3. Entanglement - the concept where two entities, once in interaction, will share qualities or energies of each other once far apart. This is a vital component to the teacher-student relationship... from experience I will say it is difficult to get rid of entangled energy, even if you no longer want it in your life.
4. Gung Fu - excellence of skill

*Li Mu Bai - the modern conceptual image of the Superior Man or Sage
Crouching Tiger, Hidden Dragon (1999)*

The Middle Path

"The Sharp Edge of the Razor is difficult to pass over, thus the Gurus say, 'Salvation is nearly impossible.'" ~The Upanishads
A dismal start to the discussion, but not without useful merit. In essence, the quote means that it is easy to fall into extremes because of the discriminating and capricious (lit: easy-seeking) mind of the Yi.
First some definitions. Tian-Ren-Di = Heaven Man Earth

= Soul-Mind-Body= psyche+material universe=The Way/Dao= Heavenly Mandate. Yin=female,dark,dividing,nuturing,attaching,material; Yang=male,light,uniting,guiding,ethereal,and temporalYi=conscious mind=cortex; hun=subconscious=soul=CNS; po=unconscious mind=PNS/ANS, supra-conscious mind =God=our connection to the divine=Christ/Krishna/Buddha consciousness=nirvananouns are just nouns. blue has a million names but it's still blue.-----

Part of the below is based on some simple math related to the Law (dharma) of Relativity and logarithmic scales of energy conversion, where 1-10 represent the 10 worlds (Hell, Ghosts, Animals, Demons, Tranquility, Heaven, Salvation, Knowledge, Healing, All-Wisdom) and the Asymptote represents the divide between the material Universe and spirit, (ie: 11=God's Void/parinirvana/bardo) Technically there are subtle differences in the Beyond that are reached by per-determined mathematical functions of attraction between a mind as it enters death and the realm it should most belong to. But not the subject of this Article. 10 is easy, don't complicate it with "continuums" and "see the rainbow" speeches. Yeah yeah infinite spectrum.. 7 colors, it's Ok to be practical.And yes 11 is divine. 11 Dimensions, 11 worlds (10+1), and 8 laws+3 planes-----

The Middle Path, by Shifu Ramon Careaga

The major problem with most philosophical or theological studies is not that they differ. To differ is an evident property revealed by the dharma of Relativity which states that only that which has 0 Mass (ie: the Void and light) has a truly objective point of view. The problem is the tendency of the ego (psyche-body) to become increasingly detached from the Superego or supraconscious mind, by attempting to traverse discriminating views to their utmost discrimination, rather than to their unification (by looking for context). For example the entire philosophy of "atoms" has been from its outset, not only been illogical but has failed practical experimentation. YET the western culture's obsession with discriminating consciousness as a means to try and define a superstructure (as if studying the ingredients of a cake would yield the secret to why we love cake), has not abated but instead intensified. (This is directly related to our material culture and its inevitable crash forthcoming, btw - see Genesis for that prediction).What seems to elude the western scientist is the fact that the fractal design of the self-propagating superstructure (based on the laws), is not only infinite in both directions, but that size is - relative to consciousness - no different than distance. We're looking further afield upwards and downwards in an attempt to try to find the "end" of the structure, which is of course preposterous. There are at least six types of multiverse, which I have written about elsewhere. There are 11 dimensions, most of which we cannot imagine. 89% of the material Universe is unobservable by physical techniques and of course, according to the Triple Plane Theory we know why: you cannot measure the nonphysical with something whose mind and spirit variables amount to 0. Can machine have spirit? We don't know, complexity seems to be integral but not absolute. After all a mountain is complex (and short of accounts of mountain spirits) we've never received a direct radio transmission from the crystals of granite in Yosemite. BUT complexity notwithstanding, the human mind seems to have the perfect mix of all these things and is also the only known creature with the ability to observe itself 4th dimensionally. I can form an idea, write this, analyze it afterwards and analyze that memory and analysis, and recall it all temporally. That is a very special thing. HOWEVER it leads to some interesting problems for people in faith, philosophy, politics, and society. Because the tendency is to perform the analysis indefinitely without the wisdom of knowing how discrimination and analysis can lead down a rabbit hole of extremism. Technically speaking, all faiths have at their heart the Heavenly Mandate; that is the relationship between the Divine and Man, and his Environment. [hint: it's that darned ole' Triple

Plane again]. After that they diverge into a billion disagreements, which cannot be solved here. However, some interesting comparisons might illuminate to the intrepid reader a hint from the ancient days... something the Buddha said he heard a sitar guru say to a student, "The string, if too slack will not play, and if too tight, it will snap." So let's take a look at juxtapositioned views and the Ends to which they become consumed. Item #1 - Uniting polarities (yin/yang) dualism and the path of fixing Karma (cause & effect). These classic philosophies abound in all corners of the world. In fact they are actually just yin/yang, mother-father pairing of the same Unified Field. But the tendency of Man is as an individual or as a culture to become obsessed with one or the other and take them to the extreme of religious paths. And yes Science is a religion- it has dogmas/beliefs and repercussions for those who disobey the community; it is therefore a Church. Karma (and its cousin: the idea of Sin) has become the absolute focal point of probably greater than half the world's religions. Everywhere people worry about their moment to moment causes and effects; ironically unaware that the worry is itself a cause. The result: creation of entire schools that focused on non-action and non-attachment, which of course is practically impossible, antithetical to the Way, to the Meaning of Life, and of course... karmic in itself. The choice to be non-attached or to do nothing is itself a cause and an action. So any school that uses this as a basis or central scheme will have only this one dharma (of 8) as its focal point. Being the dharma most closely associated with the Godhead (personality of God) does not equate it being better or more Godlike. It may be very moral (as opposed to say, Tantrism which took the dharma of Polarity to the end of the Kama Sutra [sex!])... but such moral authority is not only BEYOND mankind - and everywhere we try to enforce this moral authority the world and mankind suffers - it is simply anathema. Lit: Satanic. To create manmade laws which try to forcefeed karma upon a person is sort of violating the commandment, "I am the Lord Thy God; thou shalt have no other gods before Me." On the other hand, people have focused on yin/yang to the point of ridiculousness, while missing the uttermost point of it. One need only read Zen or Daoist koans to see some examples of unuseful advice (albeit beautiful). By focusing on the dual, they have created separation whereas the polarities are not opposites, but complements. There is Evil, yes, and Good. Right and Wrong. But they exist together... there is no eliminating the other. Peace does not eliminate War, nor War eliminate Peace. Just shifts in energy from one phase of things to another (Rotation Dharma). Yet it has not stopped entire schools - and even medicines, from the vain attempt to forcefeed BALANCE of the polarities into systems. The irony here of course is that the Harmony Dharma (better said as Resonance) is a RESULT... of the unification of this dharma and Vibration dharma (or Quanta Dharma)... and this produces the Karma that one so desires. Karma belongs to the Godhead, and our polar attitude to us. If we desire positive karma, then we should adjust our attitude... not try to adjust the Karma beyond us. Meanwhile, polarity is simply too subtle to Grasp; it divides whenever we try... hint to scientists you can't find a finite particle they all divide into waves and more particles! Instead, we should focus on our Vibration and our FAITH in the Rotation Dharma and know that the 4 Heavenly Laws (God's Way) will manifest what "ought to be." It may not be what we want, but certainly will be what Is. (Conservation Dharma) Another issue has arisen between people obsessed with the existence or non-existence of God. Actually, both are correct. You see, the Polarity Dharma includes all that Is in the Conservation dharma... and Nothingness is its Polar complement. Our attitude determines our gravitation towards whichever. But That does not mean that one eliminates the other, that is illogical. Just because your consciousness has seen that 0 is the Truth (the unbreakable Toroid) does not mean that the 1 suddenly is without merit. That is not only simply CONTRARY to what your senses are perceiving, it defies the Polarity Dharma. God exists because the dharmas (and egos) exist. God's infiniteness is based in the unlimited fractal nature of the Evolution Dharma and its derivatives:

Relativity and Conservation. You can literally prove either one is true if you merely change the context of the math [in matrix algebra this would be the (inclusion terms) following the matrix itself]. So no wonder an atheist or scientist studying the Void (infinitely divisible matter) will find the Truth of it while a Theologian studying the Spirit (1) will find the Truth of it... they are both True according to the 8 Dharma! The 8 Dharma are not separate they are the result of one equation where the conscious 1 splits the Void into 2 polarities, and three planes, and $2^3=8$. But really it's all the same $1/0=\text{infinity}$ math function. [note - We can invent/discover a million forms of math, symbols, irrational or rational numbers (yes people even argue and split hairs over these)... but the original equations are most pertinent.] #3 Also there has been the division in thinking between enlightenment and salvation. Actually as it turns out you can have both. They are not exclusionary mathematically in the least. Enlightenment or bodhi, is just Awareness - NOT omnipotence (violation of Relativity dharma for a matter-based individual to have that; sorry Jesus didn't know everything that wasn't His job]. Awareness of self being limited and Self being unlimited. That there is no self save that which is created by our division (yin) from the Unity or One-Source (yang). Our free will (satanic self) generates this division and when we experience the lower 6 worlds; then our ego recognizes its fallacy and this creates need for salvation. This is not BAD. Atheists and hinayana buddhists all seem to have a problem with being a sinner or needing saved. This is a good thing. The Savior is a good thing. To have something + to think upon no matter what when entering the Void can ensure an attitude that avoids a) Limbo-Void (unless that be thy goal to be a ghost) or b) self-made Hell of incessant retribution and reincarnations (yikes! taxes forever???). The Christ Thus Come One is an avatar of salvation that belongs to all people. His function is not new, it is not unique (it happens on all planets to all conscious beings) but it is wonderful because if one can harmonize at death (and in life) with as close to God as any man can be than one can eliminate all sorts of sin and bad karma. And ending such things in any lifetime is like ending them now, for there is no Time except that which the mind perceives. The Buddha does not destroy salvation he incorporates it. The Thus Come One mind is Universal... it is the Son of Heaven (and in Buddhist and Christian canon that is what these men were called, was it not? I won't go into more of their similarities but they are MANY). This is the 10th world, and is to be celebrated. It is not an oppression except to the rebellious and self-glorifying. Rebellion is OK for awhile but it does not eliminate the Karma Dharma nor the accumulation of unwanted data. What is unwanted data but learning that we shouldn't have had. WWI and WWII was unwanted karma that maybe Man needed but should not have had. It stemmed from inept and fallible philosophies of nihilism of German minds in the 18th and 19th centuries. And from rebellious hearts.#4 Speaking of nihilism that is another one that people tend to take too far or contrast with hedonism... but actually both are extremes of the same "false yin" [lit: -1,0] polarity that has divided from the yang "purpose driven life." Now like all things,purpose driven lives can be taken too far... for example the sin of judgment 'pon one's fellow man. Jesus warned us about that. But clearly the false yin paths of nothing-belief and hedonism tend to destroy life. If not genocide and easy murder, then getting fat, lazy, stupid, and careless (esp. in modernity or any Empire) is the outcome of the other.So from just these 4 philosophical divisions among thousands we can see that the Ends can be extreme no matter the choice. That means there are only two logical conclusions to be made from a practical standpoint. Either a) it is all useless and nothing can be done except make up whatever one believes and carry on (probably not so useful if one flaunts the Laws) or b) all have their Use in proper time. Now Time doesn't exist outside of conscious-awareness of the Physical Plane and it's evolutionary ripples, (causes and effects) but still in practical terms, since everything follows a flow of seasonal changes, it would behoove most people to look to the propitious-ness of the Time they are looking at when making a decision about "how far to carry a doctrine." But no

matter what I promise you this: No matter how middling or extreme a doctrine is carried, if it is attempted to carry it outside or in denial of the 8 dharma, it will meet with disaster (lit: anti-creation or death). That is all it CAN DO mathematically. You cannot decide to FLY and just JUMP. Sub-laws of aerodynamics govern flight. Likewise, one cannot invent some semi-hedonistic purpose driven nihilism that is quasi Christian, quasi Buddhist and expect to get good Karma merely because of it. One must follow of course the sub-laws of Karma, which are not the discussion contained herein. Faith is important, yes, but reason can strengthen faith and illuminate subtle truths. But illumination also means greater responsibilities because it is more Yang to be aware, and the more Yang you are the stricter God's Laws are upon the knower. Thus you cannot become awakened and try to "abuse the system". One has to work within its boundaries and this is another form of faith based in "gratitude of Grace." Some things are not meant for us to Know. If someone discovers it and shares it, there is no sin in learning although some knowledge is sinful of its own nature. Buddha and Jesus both focused on paths that did not divide but unified. Their teachings and those of the mahasattvas (great teachers) that have followed all focus on practical use. Practical trumps philosophical because philosophy can, in all ways due to that Relativity Dharma, end up in a moral quandary or out of bounds with one's own Life Condition. When this happens, extreme or not, the Resonance Dharma is not forgiving. You can be highly at harmony and peace in a cult that has you commit suicide. That is NOT bodhi. Or you can be a very unhappy, raging Buddhist/Daoist/New Ager that judges people to the nth degree... both are useless if they do not bring that old Meaning of Life into play. If the Meaning of Life is not reached, Bodhi, salvation, and a Purpose Driven Life are in all practical terms, pointless. The Middle Path above all things is here to turn the Razor's Edge, which seems so dangerous and self-critical... into a wide traversible path where tiny mistakes are minor forgivable sins, and enjoying the things of the phenomenal world is not associated with guilt. Yes bad things happen, but so do good things. That cow that you ate that died miserably... well you may use the calories tomorrow to come up with a new invention, or save a life... and the bones may go to feed a starving dog in a kennel. You just never know. And not Knowing is blissful. Gratitude of Grace is therefore the most cherished gift of the Divine to all who seek the Middle Path.

Law of Evolution Explained

Rather than get into the crazy non-linear mathematics of fractals... I want to talk about the Law of Evolution and the implications of fractals and Chaos on it.

Firstly a fractal is an infinitely repeating geometrical shape (though nowadays the more interesting ones defy geometry and trigonometry) that no matter at which level you view it you see the whole. Now this is somewhat different in mandelbrot fractals where what you see depends on the zoom-level. But for simplicity just think of the mountain analogy where you take a tiny grain of the mountain and it's shaped like th mountain itself. Another good

example of a form of fractals is the golden ratio, a rather simple form used by nature to define ratios of shape and size in growth patterns.

This seems all rather Escher - interesting but useless - but in fact it is not.

As time has gone on, especially since the 1970s and 1980s with the advent of computers, scientists have found that fractals and in general non-linear mathematics (where $a+b$ is not $= c$) have huge applications in Biology, Engineering, Chemistry, Quantum Mechanics, and more.

Entropy

The concept of Chaos is very old, but prior to modern chemistry it more or less had to do with being the opposite of Order and with human society (since Heaven always kept things in order). But when physics and chemistry made the discovery that heat and sound are in fact forms of energy, and also that the Law of Conservation says nothing is created nor destroyed, only transformed - then the implication was clear. Every interaction, whether chemical, physical, or nuclear released this energy never to be recaptured again.

Thus was born the concept of Entropy - or Chaos - which was said to be continuously increasing in the Universe.

Now, of course the Law of Conservation is in effect and we are discovering that new matter can spring up out of dark energy and dark matter, and also we have not yet found the non-linear equations for the energy contained in mind and spirit... BUT the concept of Chaos is still there in a mathematical form.

Chaos, it seems is part of the Universe's existence.

Fractals

For millennia the ideas of fractals fascinated mathematicians because of the inherent concept of infinity. Calculus itself was born out of this concept of approaching limits at infinity, so you see the methods of defining a fractal were of great concern because they are not ordinary functions. Ordinary functions are plotted on a cartesian plan, like so:

A Parabola

Shell Method - Rotated Parabola

As you can see, this function has almost no correspondence with the world you see around you.

Even if spun around in a complete circle, which you can then use vector calculus to find the volume of... how often do you see perfectly geometrical shapes like this in real life?

Maybe man-made objects, but almost not at all in nature.

Fractals and Chaos in the DNA code

As it turns out this is because nature uses geometry very sparsely and relies on something called self-replicating structures. The best example, and most foundational is DNA. DNA itself consists of a double-helix spiral and four molecules, arranged in a seemingly Chaotic (non-repeating) fashion. Through the actions of cells, these DNA chains are split, copied, and then used by the cell to produce other molecules and even derives how to grow, how long to grow, and **when to die!**

A simple structure, yet already abound with un-predictable math.

1. Which sequence will exist after meiosis cannot be predicted.
2. Which codons or sequences will be selected for a function cannot be predicted... in fact it may be completely determined by ratios... or by God for all we know.
3. Which changes or mutations in the code are bound to happen during copying and replication (mitosis) cannot be predicted - nor what these changes will entail/produce.
4. Which segments of code will be activated to determine programmed cell death cannot be predicted (thank God).
5. Which segments will be expressed and which suppressed, cannot be determined; indeed we do not even know how the brain, another non-linear system, affects these choices; nor how far the mind expands beyond the brain and thus affects this system.
6. etc...

How is this possible? We have all sorts of complicated mathematical formulas, and yet we cannot even remotely predict with any reliability the behavior of a cell, let alone an organism, especially one with a soul and consciousness!

It's because simple equations (or even complex ones) only govern the foundational laws. They govern how fractal math works, but not the math itself. Non-linear math is Chaotic because it is supposed to be unpredictable.

Action Potentials - more unpredictable results within your brain

This unpredictability, as Biology has come to learn within the last 20 years, is exactly how Natural Selection works. At the edge of Chaos, somewhere where it is not too out of hand, but not overly predictable, is the forefront of growth and adaptability. Evolution, in other words, is not only guided by non-linear math... it IS non-linear math. The Law of Evolution itself, which corresponds to the wind trigram and says, "All things are in constant flux," is itself non-linear, unpredictable math.

You say, now wait a minute... what about:

- Solid structures?
- Law of Karma, if x then y!?
- Law of Conservation itself!?!?

Solid Structures and the Law of Vibration

As it turns out, your vision of solid structures is itself quite a delusion of consciousness. Not only are the solid structures you see **as empty as the air between your eyes and the objects**, and literally 99.999999% empty space and mostly mathematical fields, but they are also rotating in space and moving up and down along **wavelengths imperceptible to the eye! It is only because you share a relative time frame with them that they appear solid** at all.

If you were to live long enough, absolutely no solid object, not even a diamond, would remain solid forever. It would erode away because it is losing energy constantly (Entropy again) and therefore the stability of its structure weakens over time.

for that matter, nothing in the Universe ever stands still. Only things at **Absolute Zero** stand still, and there is nothing that is Absolute Zero except that which is "outside" God... in other words non-existent. If it is within the Universe, it vibrates, however slowly... and it rotates and it changes.

Law of Karma or Cause and Effect

You may feel now that non-linear math

defies common sense. "Well of course if I push a boulder, it will fall down the cliff." Wrong. There are in fact an unlimited number of possible outcomes of such an event. It so happens that the Probability Cloud (see left) suggests that the intended effect is most likely. Certain a force will resist you. You may push the boulder and instead it rocks one way then rolls back onto you! Or it may in some very chaotic dimension of the Universe float for lack of being tied down. Or you may even go right through the boulder. (< 0.0000000000000001% chance though)

Well then how are we supposed to use the Law of Karma to any effect? Firstly, if you understand the Bagua Dharma... you're not supposed to. **Let God take care of your Karma, you worry about the causes only.**

Secondly, I would tell you that Quantum Mechanics still shows that although the question determines the outcome and all outcomes are possible to some extent some are still more likely than others. If you commit murder MORE than likely you will be caught, tried, imprisoned, and maybe even executed. BUT it so happens that times exist when non-linearity proves itself... juries let killers off (OJ Simpson), judges throw out evidence or cases due to misconduct, asteroid crash on courthouses, hurricanes erase records, lightning strikes the defendant, etc...

This is all due the randomness of the Law of Evolution.

Law of Conservation

At first glance, this randomness and

perpetual change may seem at odds with Conservation. But in fact the two work hand in hand, just as wind sweeps fastest across a mountain. The more things change, the more we see all possibilities are themselves contained in the **M x N Matrix of It All**. The matrix itself is Conservation, allowing all possibilities, while it is the Law of Evolution and non-linear math that determines the outcomes themselves. Thus the Law of Karma plays the role of setting the marble upon the roulette table, Conservation is the table, and Evolution chooses the results. Relativity, the fourth Heaven-governed Law is that some people choose the winning marble, some the losing marble or number. Indeed the number may change depending on the point of view you have of the table. If you are the player who picks the winning number, great for you, bad for the losers, and most of all bad for the House!

The future of Non-linear mathematics

It seems that the age of non-linear math has come in Biology, design, neuroscience, and economics, but there are further areas beyond that where studies will be made, inquiries sought, and important Truths uncovered which will change Mankind forever. For example, the math behind the mind and soul appears to be non-linear itself, maybe even undefinable or irrational to the human mind (something only God can fathom). But if it were somewhat manageable, imagine the implications on spirituality and psychology.

As a matter of fact the entire field of medicine is coming to a point where it is plainly obvious that how the mind and body heal is itself unpredictable and non-linear, so great money is to be made from a pharmaceutical company that can institute a non-linear or intuitive method of teaching doctors to use its products to wild success. That is, if they ever stop just taking advantage of people by telling them one drug is a cure all for a disease! Space travel itself has also reached a head where we cannot go much further than our own back yard, so to speak, without unbinding space itself and perhaps using String Theory, etc... to shift dimensions. Maybe in fact this and the governance of the mind are connected (**Astralprojection** has been a power of meditators in the past, after all).

Economics is a field that is nearing the brink of its existence, like a deer that has eaten all its food it is proving itself too complex to be maintained and its wily nature makes it a destructive force on this planet. When the whole world is connected in one non-linear

system, in my opinion few dictators and banksters will allow something so unpredictable to continue to run the planet and cause world wars.

Finally, the Internet itself is a non-linear system that is still in its early inception and is moving along faster than most people could imagine, and getting more unmanageable as the days wear on. It may be that society has yet to understand the implications of social networking on the fabric of human life and whether or not it violates biological laws and societal laws. We simply cannot know as we are in the center of the fractal itself without the perspective of zoom. The company that tames this chaotic beast will have a very profitable future, indeed.

As for the Law of Evolution, it itself cannot be tamed, no matter how we try. The best advice I can give to any person is to instead try to enjoy it and live in tune with it. Rely on probability - you are built for that - but do not build a foundation of faith upon rock. Only build it upon your own mind and heart which are solely within your control (if they do not control you instead).

Uncivilized Civilization

There are two ways we look at the past (we should look at it as a lesson, but we never do, really).

Pining for it, imagining our current time is full of degeneracy.

Thinking of the people of the past as barbaric, ignorant, and somehow less than us.

Between the two, the former is conservative and traditionalist, and the latter is progressive and evolutionary. The latter accords with the Law of Evolution and the flow of the Tao which is always forwards, and the former seeks to remind us that changing for changing's sake is not necessarily the wisdom of flowing with the Tao.

This article is going to take the cautious side of the Traditionalists' perspective, with no romantic nostalgia or trapping of such a view. After all, there are many things that are, after all, better. No outward slavery, no child-forced marriages, no human sacrifice, no witch-hunts, no hanging people according to their skin color, etc...

However, it would be incredibly haughty and ludicrously narrow-minded to imagine that our society is in all ways better and less barbaric.

Humanities and Ethics

We love to pretend in the West, and not more in America than in Europe (the main difference being only ignorance and self-centeredness replaced instead by smug arrogance), that our Values (mores and taboos and beliefs) are much grander, loftier, more tolerant, and magnanimous than those previous to the Enlightenment.

This may be so in matters pertaining to Law, but in human behavior, it probably isn't so simple. We still have murders, rapes, aggravated assaults, gang-style/mob-style violence, kidnapping, extortion, blackmail, genocide, racism, etc... We also have a number of things that simply did not exist prior to the modern era: such as random un-premeditated violence (which we sometimes associate with poverty but is not necessarily so), mass-shootings with copycat repetition, gang-rapes, and a good deal of white-collar crimes that involve new monetary

technologies that simply didn't exist in antiquity (the corporation itself wasn't invented until the 18th century!)

So although many of our values are outwardly more lofty, in actual practice our society often falls flat. For example, we outwardly deplore sexism, objectification of women, glass ceilings, deadbeat dads, etc... however in reality we have a society of women encouraged to not just show more skin (even young tweens and teens are easy to be seen in "daisy dukes" or shorter!) but to use their sexuality to gain advantage over other women who may not be as sexually promiscuous, "beautiful" etc... In fact, many girls are encouraged to behave more male-like, aggressively seeking multiple sexual partners, engaging in behaviors that degrade male or female character, such as drinking to excess and sleeping with random partners. IS this not culturally encouraged? Fraternities and Sororities are such places our TV, movies, and culture acknowledges are where they happen and should happen.

Moreover, as women and girls are encouraged to be promiscuous, they are also encouraged to mate with less and less mature males (or females), with the likely outcome being early, immature creation of offspring. Nothing can be more devastating to a woman's future career, income, or life-destiny in this high-minded, idealistic "feminized" West than an unexpected child. Even more so, the media speaks out of both sides of their mouths, on the one hand propping up "Great Women" like Hillary Clinton or Sarah Palin and on the other, tearing her down, demeaning her, calling her names like "Bitch", etc... creating double standards for women all over. Be successful and be a "bitch" or well, why not simply be a dog in actuality for Snoop Dog and his entourage to lead around the MTV Music Awards with leashes around their necks?

For males, the situation is not much less bleak. An entire two or three generations of emasculated, drama-prone, immature, fatherless sissies, unable to hold jobs nor find quality girlfriends with whom they can successfully propagate. With words of shame heaped upon them for being too masculine, too powerful, too successful, too white (or black), too dumb to compete with women entering college and the workforce... a message that erodes the male psyche and confidence and self-image day in and day out, until you have an entire generation of 30 to 40 [year old virgins] working odd jobs with no career prospects, living at home with "mommy", often divorced, without giving guidance or learning from the children they procreate. Worse than this, they spend their waking hours seeking examples of masculinity - images of war, conquering, adventuring, and sports from the comfort of their own home TV or computer. Idly wasting away precious time and Testosterone in a foggy haze of self-neglect and wanton, ridiculous desire, hoping to achieve greatness while gaining blubber and character "points" for their online personas.

What humanity can there be, when a society not only degrades the self-image of both sexes, but also encourages the drama and vanity and pride that actively leads to divorce?! What solution is provided? Couple's Counseling? With all the negative imagery of the "blame game" and "shrinks" this is a oft-avoided salvation.

Meanwhile millions of teenage males enter college with less and less chances of success, and this is juxtaposed with millions and millions of females who enter college to chase ridiculous castle-in-the-sky expectations that they can build massive careers and have large families and take care of mom and dad, and somehow avoid autoimmune disease, bankruptcy, divorce, and failure. The cases are rare and usually distorted. Someone like Sarah Palin has not simply a stay-at-home husband... but entire teams of child-care and household providers. This is not a

luxury that the average, nay even 99% of women can afford to have, yet this is the new standard (unless it be porn-star/stripper!) that women are held to. The traditional, conservative, stay at home mom is likened to being a bare-footed, haggard old maid, who is too ignorant to know we live in the Golden Age of Opportunity. Yet onward and upward the rise of Qi Deficiency related syndromes and hysterectomies go for women too busy to not be "on the pill" or other estrogen related, feminine organ destroying medications.

However, when we really compare these outward ideals to the past, we find they really aren't terribly new. Aside from the Imperial nations (except Japan), most of the world remained a matriarchal society up until the arrival of Columbus in the New World. In fact, in many societies, including Japan, women were the active heads of household, and in some tribes, even of the entire clan. There was more respect and equality between the sexes in the form of "different roles, equal need." Sure, in many agrarian societies, the man was the head of household. In some he could kill or stone his wife or concubines at will. But in most traditional societies that were not Christian, divorce was always an allowable societal policy. Only in places of strong religious institutions, like the Roman Empire, or India where religious policies dictated that women were second class citizens, (and indeed widows the lowest, lower than whores, which at least had use to men of power), was there such disdain for women-kind. In fact, in ancient China, of all places known for its patriarchal attitude, more than 2000 years before Christ the emperor decreed that the widows and single-men be left alone so that they could propagate, and promulgate and be succored and not treated like second class citizens. Even in modern India there is no respect for widows. And in America, whores are outlawed, but not succored. We encourage abortions, not changes in lifestyle for more Virtuous kinds. Give access to drugs and birth-control, but do not also encourage self-growth and self-value.

Our society has much to learn from its own ideals. We have empty words such as "All Men are created Equal," yet everyone knows its speaker had slaves, and children by them. We have words such as "Power to the People," yet no real means for people to acquire wealth and power, except by borrowing from their time to work their way up a tedious, tipsy "ladder" which more oft than naught teeters and topples as a feeble old man (or woman) approaches the promised land of "retirement" ... something more of a dream than a reality with each passing year.

In ancient days if an emperor, such as Ghengis Khan or Ashoka or Alexander made it illegal to perform rape, let alone gang-rape... their words propagated even into the countryside and a commoner, even a woman could walk abroad at night without fear. But in these days we have a billion laws, local and state and federal, and a person cannot leave their very front door unlocked (whereas they could just fifty short years ago).

Indeed, our words and humanities.. can they even come close to the words of the Thus Come One's: Jesus and Buddha!? 2000+ years later, are we not still living far short? Water-boarding prisoners, extra-ordinary renditions, hijacking planes, gassing opera-houses to kill both terrorists and hostages, bombing our own Twin Towers to enable justified war.... these things indicate that the nature of power-driven Values have not escaped in fear or repulsion by righteous liberties. No, indeed. Only 60 short years ago we imprisoned all Japanese-Americans for being merely Japanese. We annexed Hawaii for her future plantations. We forced Polynessians out of Bikini to test a fusion hydrogen bomb and they are still unable to return home. For the sake of the rich, powerful, and ambitious, we have sacrificed every value, and given way on every Virtue. Traded

every principle for a promise that has been both empty and proven historically unrealistic. We listen to promises made by eager politicians, whilst in the end, we have a domineering police state, bent on running tanks and drones over our society for the sake of power. There is nothing different here than the Warring States, or the Dark Ages, or the fall of Alexandria. We have, in short, no more or less humanities than the past.

We can, therefore, go into our past, and the pasts of the world, to draw out virtues and ways of living, and conclusively replace the deficiencies of our present misguided values. We need not throw the baby out with the bath-water. We simply need to avoid believing that all that glitters is gold... not everything shiny and new is better. Laws may be new, but they may also be veiled trojan horses, masquerading as Civil Rights or Security, and being in actuality the seeds of new slaveries.

Evaluating our humanities, we cannot truly be humane until we accept the fact that we may have, as a species been equally, or in some ways, more humane in the past, and humbly learn from that. We need not make women wear dresses or hajabs in order to help them gain respect. But we should teach young girls about the realities of what men and especially other women will think of them if they behave in certain ways. We need not make boys into mindless killing machines and teach them to behead each other to teach them how to be strong, active, and upright, becoming pillars of society! Moreover we should not shrink nor fear to speak out against the antithetical teachings which espouse literal equality of the sexes. We are not literally equal, we are literally complementary. Each having its strengths and tendencies, needs and weaknesses. The appreciation of a good, honest, chaste woman, and a hard-working, upright man is not backwards or "Amish" or something heretical to modernity. It is a timeless value that each generation should learn to love and learn to become.

Justice

There are many things about ancient justice which are repulsive. From the flaying of Jesus, the guiltless man, to the tortures of the Jesuits and the burning of witches in Salem, Massachusetts. However, it cannot be "Justice" to put millions of victim-less offenders behind bars, in greater droves and numbers than anywhere in the world, merely because it is good business in a country where prisons are subsidized by the Welfare State. How odd and ironic it is... the Welfare State, which then terrorizes its poor and despotic with dashed dreams and brutal caging. The ideals of "reform" are not even at play. People these days simply want "criminals" to be locked up, and the keys to be thrown away. We want murderers killed or imprisoned for life. We desire that not simply one life be ruined but ten. And we wish to keep the psychopaths off death row despite their being a threat to every worker or doctor that has to serve and care for them in prisons and institutions. We do not give a merciful end to their life, and even try to restrain them - and anyone actually - should they decide they want to tend their life, a karmic right by God of anyone on the planet.

We put harmless criminals away with brutal criminals, making them into life-long criminals, rather than putting them to work to pay for their crimes.

By contrast, in antiquity although Justice was often hard, or brutal, at least it was two things: equally applied and religiously discussed. The very works such as the military classics of China, or the words of St. Thomas Aquinas explore the spiritual significance of the crime, the judgment, and the punishment. Rulers sought by all means to be ministered to on the merits of systems of Rewards and Punishments that regulated and equalized good and bad. Meanwhile philosophers

chastised them publicly among the powerful aristocracy, exhorting to either be more humane and just and seek Virtue, or return to the antiquity of humanity, and be as the aborigines who knew neither crime nor lie until the White Man (the agrarians) arrived to conquer and force this new world paradigm onto them. In either case, the philosophers believed that to be vastly superior to the then uncivilized and inhumane asylums and torture chambers and the current institutions of endless corporate punishment. A system which vilifies via media and propaganda the minorities, then impoverished, etc.. as less virtuous, but then makes a mockery of law and Justice by stealing money (or inventing new moneys to then steal from unawares buyers) right in the very public realm. We will publicly deplore the Bernie Madoffs of the world, but should Goldman Sachs receive one red cent in cheat, or should a wealthy rich yuppie steal an entire company, we'll not only not punish them with jail-time, we'll immortalize them in a movie!

I am not saying that we should instantly hang 'em high... God knows many a poor, desperate man was hung for horse thievery, and many a hapless aristocrat was unjustly revenged upon by guillotine in the French Revolution! However, should Justice of a very wise and sharp and widespread supported kind by administered, and swiftly, upon the daft, dangerous, and daring criminal, although we may not return to the simplism of the Native, we'll surely damned well do more to help the nation than by trampling upon the trodden! Naive? Nay, just historically proven. And if we cannot behead the pedophile or embezzler caught in the act of ruining lives, let us not feed them like kings and secure them from revenge, but make them work, using their bodies to build the nation instead of bleeding it dry as a hypocritical means to make ourselves feel more humane when in fact there is nothing less humane than to treat a human being less humanely than a stray dog!

Socio-economics

Our economics system, to put it mildly, is a farce. Even the farce is a farce in that those who buy into it do not even know it is a farce. In the past at least, should a wealthy merchant or greedy politician (such as Prince John) wish to make themselves fat and wealthier, they at least did so with the honor of a true thief. They did it by force and by guile and by effort.

These days not only are the poor robbed to pay the rich... the rich are robbed by each other in an effort to out-rob one another. And they do not even know it is highway robbery. Usury isn't simply overlooked - it's a forgotten word! Once upon a time, in the middle ages, usury could land a person in Hell let alone jail. When the sabbath was observed. Why even in the 1980s insider trading was punished. But now usury is the name of the game. The more people you can steal a house from, the more mortgages you can sell to house-flippers, and the more the profit works despite inflation. In fact, it keeps one's bank ahead of inflation. Never mind that the persons one is foreclosing upon are one's neighbors. Never mind that they are one's customers! Nay, never mind that there are any laws of any kind (since there are no real punishments of any kind!) After all, in a system where new money is invented and adopted, you will encourage not only the white collar criminal, but the blue collar one, who will find ways to create softwares that rob unsuspecting grannies or steal the IDs of innocent middle class people. Such unpunished criminals then teach their criminality and the fame of the wealth in criminality spreads ever faster and faster. Soon if a person isn't engaged in theft, they are the fool, not the upright model. If you don't steal from the hotel when you're there you're a sucker. If you pay for mp3s you're an idiot. Why not!? The software companies steal from the customer, providing inferior products that break purposefully.

Fifty years ago a train or refrigerator built will still run. Now a person is lucky if a product makes it one year past warranty. Computers get faster exponentially, while the operating systems that run them seem to get slower.

Companies steal from each other. China steals from the world's copyrights. Yet no one is punishing anyone else or at least avenging their losses. A man whose house is stolen by a bank illegally will simply pack it up... maybe trash a home for revenge. What weakness! In 1776 if our ancestors had merely packed it in and taken it all in stride by having peaceful march sit-ins and handing out leaflets, when they were economically bullied, the British would have hung the lot and had a laugh about it.

Now we have police body slamming pregnant women, and tasing and killing old, defenseless men, and no one avenges them. The [un]Justice System certainly is not going to. When an oil company wants to frack your land and run a pipeline, they simply have you removed from your family lands. When your home is invaded by the DEA/FBI whose sole job seems to be these days to maintain their budgets through the "War on Drugs" because this supports the contractors that are publicly traded, no one bats an eye. Or if they do they must be "sovereign citizens" or "right wing nut jobs" or "Constitutionalists" who are nothing but mere Chicken Littles who want to cause trouble and need to just "get over it" because "we don't all need M-16s and RPGs."

Meanwhile, in antiquity, Jesus kicked over the stands of the money-lenders, and Robin Hood punished Prince John. If a person tried to hurt you financially, this was viewed the same as a physical assault. I am not advocating duels and pillaging, or even blood-feuds ala Hatfields and McCoys. I am however, wondering when people will make the connection between their freedom and the divine right to wage a Just War. Upon the enemy, upon the aggressors - violent or passive - upon the system, upon the corporation, upon the state, upon the corporatized and ever increasingly brutal police, upon the lying media, upon anyone that receives not Justice from the System, and thus encouraging the politicians and bureaucrats to change policies and punish not just the Martha Stewarts of the world, but those who perpetrate major injustice. We made trial of the President for lying about sex. But didn't bat an eye when he admitted personal fault for the deaths of dozens of religious people within their rights to congregate, and 13 of them children. When the country makes no example of its leaders... even when they take personal responsibility, then what hope can there be that the People themselves will not become thieves and criminals?

It is no wonder that our faux-feudalism, aka "capitalism", has devolved from pro-family business and entrepreneur to nothing but mere fascism: the perfect blend of tyranny and corporate greed. Politics and War

Politics has always been dirty. As soon as there was a tribal leader who could touch the spirit world in ways no one else could, there were whores, warriors, and philanderers for him/her to take advantage of.

However, while in the past politics required a bit of willingness to "bite the bullet" - Alexander Hamilton, anyone? - these days, if a man slanders, lies, commits crimes upon the mantle of public office, he is merely "resigned". In this case I am, more because of the example it would set for everyone, but partially because those who wish to rule others can never in any age be trusted, advocating outright public, brutal punishments. Caning, flogging, hanging, etc... or perhaps for moral gaffes and scandals something more like holding a sign that says "adulterer"

or wearing a Scarlet Letter.... would absolutely be more appropriate than treating these lowest of the low better than we treat young college kids who get caught with an ounce of pot. How can we expect a government to behave, and righteously fear the People - nay, for the People to believe they should fear us - if we provide an environment that encourages ignoring the public outcries and sidling up like pasty-prostitutes to big money lobbyists, many of which pollute the environment, ruin general healthcare, or take advantage of the disadvantaged!?

It's no use the water-board a suspect, they will lie. But if you water-board a liar, you will get their truth. Everything a coward fears to share will be traded, and with gusto! They will name names, places, dates, give access to files, and provide ample evidence to end the reigns of mafiosos and machine-operators. At a very minimum, our leaders should be subjected to monthly or quarterly polygraph examinations; and barred from running for office more than twice.

We should be in the business of breaking monopolies, since after all diversity ensures the security of the nation. Not in the business of putting them on government regulatory boards!

In antiquity, especially in China, there is a rich history of able ministers ousting the corrupt and censuring the rulers with upbraiding and history lessons that gave ample political weaponry to the opposition, thereby balancing the elite with their always conniving opposition. Put the dogs upon each other. Put business in the business of ripping the throats out of government hypocrites. Give government the ambition to destroy corporate giants, and watch the markets thrive through competition.

Religion and Spirituality

Perhaps it was inevitable for true spiritual experiences, be they direct through rituals such as pagan dances to the sun God, or shamanic such as the taking of Peyote or Blue Lotus in order to have a discussion with a deity, should end as the mainstream course.

Agrarian lifestyles and systems were, after all, created for the purposes of control and predictability. There is nothing predictable about Heaven. After all, if it were, why employ oracles and diviners?

However, the difference between the early religions, be they Egyptian, Hebrew, Chinese, or Brahmic.... and those of the massive corporate, soul-less churches these days ... or terrorist-producing schools of backwards Muslim nations, cannot be good or healthy.

In ancient India, Ashoka encouraged a confluence of religions and ideas, adopting the pacifism of Buddhism and the pragmatism of monotheism's family structures, and the politics of Hindu caste system to create a society of morals so profound, even the animals were treated kindly.

In Alexandria, the mixture of manifold philosophies and religions led to the invention of the astrolabe. Astronomy made dramatic leaps forward and long before Galileo, heliocentricity was mathematically proven.

But the power-hungry (demons!?) ever seek to degenerate anything. Gone are the days of honest, humble small churches working to stay humble Sunday morning, then participating in a barn-raising in the afternoon, thereby encouraging the practice of that old Commandment, "Love They Neighbor." Now, instead, super-churches exempt from taxes take advantage of the growing number of bleeding-heart pacifists who wish to better the world, but without wit or wisdom to know the difference between lip-service and real service.

What would be truly wise is to continually seek out not what words say, but what they were meant to say. Not how they are interpreted by the societies and institutions of power, but how

they are interpreted by the wise-men themselves... and do they seek always to "row the boat backwards"?

Why go backwards? Because wisdom and spirituality always requires rowing backwards, reversing the flow. Abandoning the old to seek the new leads to Cultural Revolutions and the murder of thinkers, old people, priests, monks, nuns, and the burning of their books and knowledge. The ends of Epochs, not the beginnings of new ones. To begin a new Epoch, one must simply go far enough back in antiquity that the human race can repeat something. Don't care for old fashioned Christianity or Judaism? Become a gnostic or study the Kabbalah. Don't fancy Judeochristian worldviews? Study the Sino-vedic systems. Don't fancy the eastern mysticism? Study Norse, Wiccan, and Druid magicks. Don't fancy the west or east? Study Mayan, Inca, and Aztec mysticism. Don't fancy society? Study the Hopi, Apache, Cherokee, and Australian Aborigines. I am not opposed to Orthodoxy or Puritanism, I am opposed to ignorant judgment and narrow-mindedness. Considering the era we live in and the weapons we possess we can no longer afford them, especially to be mixed with Nationalist fervor.

There is no rhyme or reason to throw out these ancient wisdom systems to seek to create a proto-Christian, uber-elite version of modern Christianity. Christ's words, like Buddha, were well ahead of their time, and are ahead of the times now. We can row backwards, and in rowing backwards, we'll find that the landscape around us rows forwards ever more mystically, and beautifully. And this time, perhaps with wisdom if we're lucky, instead of mass hangings and book burnings and the slaughter of cultures like the Tibetans! There is nothing more sad than how in a mere 30 years, China threw away more of its cultural heritage and richness in the vain seeking to be Westernized than has ever been done anywhere by any people. 30 million dead in the name of modernization. What ideals!

Healthcare, Food, and Water Systems

Perhaps more than any other area of review here, we clearly need to "row backwards." Our views on food are nothing short of self-destructive. As has been said on Facebook, we have a healthcare system which ignores our food and a food system that disregards our health. Technology has enabled us to increase our productivity, and increase our nutrition, and increase our palate. Not only can we have foods from wherever, we can have them at any time of the year! But, considering the fact that the entire planet is designed in cycles, rhythms, and with the idea of "ripeness" to guide all activities... how can such wanton neglect and now indeed ignorance of our food supplies be healthy?

Beyond individual health, the entire West is failing to learn the basics of growing, the basics of food identification, and knowledge of what things are good for you and what are not as good and should be consumed less. If the ancients thought city-slickers were out of sync then, they would not know what to make of a society that has made pizza into a vegetable!?! On top of that, people do not even know how to cook anymore. Many people live from frozen entree to Ramen noodle packet to mac'n'cheeze. We surely cannot expect that hydrating with soda and filling up with complex carbohydrates and memorizing types of minerals and vitamins to take as round tablets into our digestion will suffice for health and longevity building nutrition!?

But wait... this is exactly what is purported. Meanwhile, all the research into longevity, arguably the most solid and important research conducted thus far this century has pointed to all the facts about real health coming from traditional cultures:

Eat real, organic, and whole foods
Mostly vegetarian
Male vs. female clearly distinguished
societal hierarchy, and an appreciation of older people
sabbath observed
some kind of religion
cultural support
large friend networks
family oriented
purpose-driven life

Note there is nothing about jogging, cardio, vitamins, statin drugs, baby aspirin, milk, using sunscreen, fat-free, no protein, no carb, no fish, only fish, no gluten, no soy, only soy, paleolithic, raw, juiced, smoothies, carb-cutting, calorie counting blah blah blah...

In other words. Tradition 1, Modernity 0.

The simple fact is that we didn't even lose these truths until the Industrialized age. It wasn't that ancients knew better than post Enlightenment. Post Enlightenment knew better than 20th century modernists and post-modernists and that's a simple fact.

At this point all we're trying to do is patch up the dam on Truth, and the holes are getting bigger, larger, and more difficult to ignore. The drugs being invented at this point are categorically types of poisons, the miracle being that any of them have the side-effect of anything positive at all.

Most of them kill the liver, kidneys, sense organs, nerves, hair, reproductivity, or worse: outright kill you. Deaths by drugs is 7 times higher than cars in the United States, and 700 times that of gun related murder.

If you need to suspect who will try to kill you in your life, look no further than your next HMO or doctor. That is a sad fact and not a joke, in the least. No hyperbole.

Surely the leech-craft doctors and snake oil salesmen of ancient and medieval Europe were not good for people, but we have plenty of holistic, safe systems that can round out the current healthcare genius knowledge we've acquired: TCM, Ayurveda, Persian, and Cherokee, Homeopathics, Naturopathics, and Western herbalism. We're not talking about using voodoo or tapeworms or drinking urine here. We're talking about real wise system that combines detailed anatomy with the wisdom of how to actually treat people to attain balance.

As for water systems. Nothing could more ingeniously and poignantly illustrate the simple fact of inferior-minded philosophy about health than our water. We use chlorinated (a poison), fluoridated (radioactive and harmful to the brain) water, which still is contaminated when it leaves the plant, to pump over vast distances through aging, sometimes toxic, leaky, or even leaded pipes to reach people at their homes and businesses, wasting billions of gallons a year doing what can literally be done locally, by plants, with rain water for practically free.

On top of that, we sell still impure water for more than we sell oil and gas. Water is a substance of which we are all made. It has to be not only inhumane and unconscionable, but unGodly and perhaps damning for us to charge what should be given for free.

Worse yet, our plastic bottles fill the world and the oceans themselves, our mother of life on the planet and perhaps future homes, with a toxic soup of decay that is harmful to wildlife, the soul, and the eye. There simply is not excuse for it, and no comparison of this atrocity with say the wars of the Shogunate period of Japan, or with the takeover of America by colonialists. This is

1000 times worse, or more, than anything humans did prior to 1900. More people have died in the 20th century's wars than any of those periods by far. And more animals and wildlife have been harmed by the oil and plastic (which decays so fast archaeologists in 1000 years will never know what we wanted with the substance) revolution than by any other thing man has done or perhaps will ever do if we survive our own catastrophe.

The simple fact is this planet can sustain 100 billion people - if we lived the right way - but as we currently do, no more than 20 billion, and anywhere over 10 billion not with any sort of quality of life without worldwide strife for water, food, and shelter. The wars that shall be fought for water resources may be more tragic than anything else, given that it rains for free in every place on the planet save the Chilean desert. Even in the Sahara there is rain.

Surely when Yao and Shun diverted the inundating waters, and the Egyptians worshiped and tilled the Nile, and the Romans built the Aqueduct mankind then understood and appreciated the power of the most magical substance that has ever and will ever be found.

Science, Math, and Technology

Surely in this area, a person may feel I must be jesting, or deluded to imagining the ancients knew more than we do. Nay, I do not feel they knew more, it was that they knew how important it was. The average commoner these days has literally no idea how these marvels we are surrounded by are made. They see them only as useful, natural, and never-ending. Never mind the level of waste, the man hours spent on frivolity, the toxicity of production and then disposal, and the sheer dollars lost through poor investments and subsidizing the addiction to technology. We have equations so complexly derived and researched that tell us how to make antennae out of people's arms. But no one knows the math equation that will solve world hunger, or clothes for all children, or water for all people.

They say the task is too complex to solve the world's energy crisis. Yet they can spend trillions on advanced, complex space programs and on particle accelerators which divine the inner workings of atoms. They build giant science machines that are used to study things that are invisible to the eye. They have powerful magnets that exist not for cleaning metal out of forests and oceans, but for putting grams of substances in and then discerning their magnetic wave patterns... all in a vain and useless attempt to get "to the bottom of Everything." A task we now know for certainty of trends and the mathematics of fractals to be impossible.

We actually know that we can advance technology and science faster than it can be integrated into the very institutions that teach them... let alone into government policy and into society.

People are blissfully unaware of the magic around them - of light, electricity, silicon chips, diodes, plasma screens - all of these things were black magic 200 years ago. Science fiction couldn't guess them 40 years ago. And this magic is simply un-understood, ignored. The nescience has become so commonplace that actually people are less interested in math and science. The assumption of an entire society that it must naturally continue and therefore we needn't try so hard or work so hard anymore.

Rather, our love of technology has given way (thankfully not to weapons as much anymore as) to entertainment. Entertainment technologies get more investment than foreign aid. And they're more profitable, so why not?

In the ancient days an equation was like a revelation from God. A new compounded substance became the fashion of an era, lasting perhaps centuries. Entire wars were fought for the secrets of silk and steel. The stones of Stonehenge were so carefully manipulated, worshiped, crafted,

and placed that they stand even today. Much less the Wall of China and the Pyramids. All of which were feats not just then, but apparently now, when addle-brained sissies cannot imagine anyone doing such hard labor or achieving anything so grand (because we take so many shortcuts now). Our buildings are made of plastic and plaster, then surrounded by fake stone. In Aceh, the only building left standing by the tsunami was the Mosque. In Athens the Parthenon has survived nearly 2500 years of earthquakes and war.

By contrast our dilapidated buildings, warehouses, and bridges collapse within 50 years. We cannot even build the Empire State Building again, it is too dangerous, we would never permit it. Instead, we build buildings of glass and wood to make glorified temples unto our own power and might. Yet they cannot last forever. True the leaning tower of Piza was not made right and tipped. Many things like that happened in antiquity. But once they fixed it, it held its shape the remainder of the time. How would yours or my home stand if it leaned at 5 degrees? I have seen barns tilted like that that do not make it 20 years!

Surely there are things about the way that ancients thought and built which can be re-incorporated and would not only enhance our design ideas but perhaps make them more humane as well. It cannot be with any conscience that we have Wal-marts which house none and yet will stand earthquakes, and yet hovels like in Haiti and Rio de Janeiro which house millions and cannot stand a five-pointer. How can this be?

It is the Hubris of the West, the ignorance of the masses and the callousness of the elite, wealthy powerful (whom the People let reign unjustly for so long) that results in the waste of a Golden Era.

Instead of a [Black] Golden Era we have inherited an era of lost hopes, wasted time, and an ever growing list of crises which cannot be easily solved, especially if everyone has blinders on to the lemming behaviors of modernity, whilst decrying "Chicken Little" for every person that attempts to break the mould and warn the public.

I believe, and not without some long term analysis, that a revisit to our antiquity and our history can make use a just, verdant, and peaceful society; with more humanity and not less than we currently have. I know that many will naturally disagree, or fear to return to less tolerant times. But tolerance notwithstanding, liberty without responsibility is a recipe for disaster and we cannot escape the judgement of Karma and of God/Nature's laws. Indeed, no society, from the Mayans and Babylonians, to the Caucasians and Egyptians ever has. What goes around, comes around. What we do to one another we do to ourselves. This ancient, biblical or Aesopian or Buddhist wisdom, whatever you want to call it... it is time we really start to pay attention to it. Or shall history find this society and epoch wanting as the only society with both the means and motive - indeed the capacity - to understand all the wisdoms and all the knowledge of the ancient world through our math, science, technology, and sheer luxury and not the wit to apply them!?

thank you,
Shifu Careaga

Dreams and other spaces of trans-consciousness

Let me start by saying I am no expert in this field... either from a neuroscience perspective, or a sagely, spiritual guru perspective. There are probably more gifted and advanced experts in this subject within your own life. I just wanted to share what I DO know from firsthand perspective, and if it helps you, reader, then so be it.

Firstly let me start by saying that lucid dreaming and dreaming within dreams (and again) is totally real. But they are also very difficult states to get into and control. I do not recommend any of these techniques I've personally used without a teacher. Why?

1. There are states where the Qi flows in unpredictable and intense manners... if you do not know how to fix a problem, you may cause long term issues. What kind of issues?
 1. Chronic Qi stuck in the brain (any of the three chakras) can cause headaches, migraines, vertigo (more on this later), confusion, delusion, and paranoia.
 1. The brain is the Sea of Marrow, but its functions more correspond to Heart-Shen (Yi, Hun, and Zhi) which makes it the primary place where Heart and Kidney communicate.
 2. Blood is the mother of Qi, but Qi is the commander of blood. It circulates it. Stuck Qi of course causes blood to stagnate. All stagnations eventually transform to heat. But Qi in dreams is so intense it may actually cause Fire to ascend and begin this process.
 1. Heat/Fire is the source of untoward consumption of yin... this may lead to autoimmune or neurologic diseases (such as demyelinating disorders like Fibromyalgia, SLE, Parkinson's, etc...)
 2. Heat/Fire also stirs wind, which can carry Phlegm upwards and block the orifices - either literally as in a thrombus/emboli or psychologically, such as a person prone to schizophrenia or Bipolar disorder might have happen if they taken LSD or other hallucinogens and cause their own "psychotic break")
 3. Qi also circulates fluids which correspond to yin. Other than decocting (lit. cooking) them into Phlegm with heat, the Qi can not carry them as they should, leading to...
 1. Bone/disc/skin dryness --> spinal, lymph, or eye issues
 2. Urination/defecation/digestion/salivation problems
 3. Joint lubrication issues & immobility
 4. Seminal or vaginal issues (in the fluids)
 5. Endocrine and therefore hormonal issues (not in production but in transportation)
 4. The Qi is the "fluid" of the Spirit. If it does not flow, then your mind and spirit cannot perform body-like functions with your thoughts and feelings
 1. Under or over Consumption of new ideas
 2. Weak separating of ideas - good vs. bad
 3. Mental constipation or loosely formed ideas getting out
 4. Obsession, pensiveness, worry, paranoia, compulsive behaviors, and possession (energy/thought type)
 5. Misappropriated or inappropriately expressed emotions.

2. There are realms of spiritual consciousness which you may or may not be trained for - and without a teacher you may not know. I personally have not met anyone (read: attracted anyone) in my life who is truly and knowably qualified to teach me. These techniques were devised and studied routinely in the upper halls and chambers of temples and by Shamans whom had done Vision-quests and Sun Dances and walked the forests on the other side of the Razor... how many common people living in today's plastic-money world have spent that kind of time? And can prove it!?
 1. The existence of demons is religiously agreed upon, and psychologically we all know we have our own demons. Liu I Ming would warn that these come from the mix of our Acquired Conditioning with Heavenly Primordial Qi during puberty. If you enter these states, you may encounter your own or other demons
 2. It is not known FOR A FACT if you have your own mental space in dreaming or share a collective space, or something of a mix where if you leave your "house" you enter "public space."
 1. I have personally found that in trying to tap my wife's consciousness during dreaming, she screamed in holy terror and it scared me away. But upon waking up she had no recollection
 2. I also found that she could not guarantee (on a separate account) to remember to tell me something when we woke up; my response, "Well then you're not Real."
 3. These two separate instances lead me to the conclusion that you can enter a more public space, perhaps even enter anothers' dreams, but by and large, our dreams are mostly inner projections.
 4. If this is true, it seems to me God designed it this way for a reason:
 1. To heal.
 2. To be safe and sane; "ignorance is bliss."
 5. There is plenty of inner space and freedom to enjoy without venturing out into the Unknown... especially without our own personal poet Virgil.
 3. Time travel or "astral projection" is dangerous.
 1. It's dangerous on LSD, "Sage" (Salvia), "shrooms", and peyote... because no one controls it, and the substance must work its way through you.
 2. It's dangerous to others if you cannot handle it mentally.
 3. You're tampering with the modus operandi of God, which is OK for Him but maybe not for you.
 4. You may have difficulty getting back.
 5. I once had an astral projection in my sleep... when I woke up I could see straight for several minutes nor wake up... so if you like feeling helpless, be my guest.
 4. I have personally found that the main sensation of extra Qi in your head while dreaming is not more power, but less and more heaviness. Lucid dreaming is enough, but when you add Qi - without knowing how - I found it to be very disorienting. Why?

1. My theory is that the Qi of the Du channel (CNS) which literally governs the extraordinary vessels (cranial nerves and PNS) tends to get stuck at the DU16 chakra, which is the Cerebellum and Medulla... these govern balance and coordination and not that far away is the occiput which has vision so even if you break through the next area is the eyes and that can cause that sensation of vertigo.
 2. The big question is do you know yourself enough - and know why you're doing it? I found that in my lucid dreaming I act childishly, that my ego is more present. I do not do evil, but I do not exactly do anything useful like take a lotus stance. I've flown around, I've driven the batmobile, I've flown on a magic carpet, I've pummeled mountains, but I rarely did anything useful... except perhaps solve some problems or learn a martial art technique or two. You may be better than I am and more mature - I hope you are... but you may also not like what you discover.
 3. I once discovered that I was capable of murderous, disgustingly sickening rage... and thankfully I also had a part of me to restrain that part. Maybe that's the paradoxical proof that we are all capable of evil or good at any moment. But you may not be mentally healthy or happy enough to discover this.
 4. I also have personally encountered demons - mine or otherwise difficult to know - and I've encountered wonderful others, usually angelic women. I once had a woman blow a breath on her fingers then sweep my arm. In real life my arm lit up. It was great. But then I became obsessed (mildly) with this experience. Eventually I discovered a truth: you have to seek without seeking to find these states.
3. Now if you've read this far and you're still determined to go through with it, then I will share what I know.
1. The best trick to lucid dreaming is being cognizant of reality.
 1. Now some people like to say "I want to lucid dream tonight"
 2. I've found it easier instead to notice absurd things and say to myself in the dream "that makes no sense... ergo I must be dreaming."
 3. From here, personally, I've discovered I have a finite time before I go back to uncontrolled dreaming.
 4. When you wake you will not be rested - so it's best to do it on a weekend when you can sleep in.
 5. When you're lucid dreaming, it's best to do something non-sexual, spend your time enjoying yourself
 1. If you're absolutely determined to do Qi Gong, remember this, "A little goes a long ways."
 2. In your dream state your access to the glands and subconscious structures of the brain that are non-cortex is as easy as turning over your hand. Do something like focus on an injury, or a periphery... you'll be surprised the level of euphoric feeling you get in your body.

3. Remember it's not something for nothing - you will be tired... you will need to eat more to replace lost hormones and ATP and sugar in your nervous system (all are Qi)
2. To dream within a dream, follow these steps.
 1. First, open your Small Circle of Heaven - takes dedication and time...
 1. You can "cheat" or shorten the time with magnetic mattresses and pillows, acupuncture, and lots of Qi Gong breathing
 2. Be sure to complete the cycle... do not become enamored with the chakras, especially the third eye
 3. If you have a partner of the opposite sex, they can pull or draw Qi towards them simply by being present... this will help complete the cycle.
 4. On the face the Qi will tend to diverge easily... don't let it... make sure it enters the tongue and throat and descends the Ren, or it will not go right to the Dan Tian (Sea of Qi).
 5. When you first awaken kundalini (DU1) do not lust for this again... focus on getting past Ming Men... then continue on. Continually drawing from Ming Men may (I don't know) lead to Jing deficiency in the form of CNS fluid loss. Masters and gurus can ignore this, they know how to lubricate properly.
 2. Second, repeatedly practice this at night as you fall to sleep, but go from heavy breathing to subtle breathing... think positive thoughts
 3. Thirdly, do not become enamored of the first dreams you have with Qi... these are not matured... your Qi is probably just in the back of your head.
 4. Now, begin practicing doing this in the morning when you wake up
 1. The time we are shooting for is the "in between" place of sleep and waking.
 2. Use these times to create your "sacred place" - this place you are safe in and only you know about.
 3. This time is usually best reached after you've woken up a little and then fall back asleep in the mid hours of the morning.
 4. What happens is you try to wake up, especially as you are hot and greasy, but you cannot because the Qi is going since you trained it to do this in the morning.
 5. You're used to lucid + Qi dreams at night because you practice at night
 5. When you go into the second layer it will happen without you're knowing of it.
 1. Some clues are: when you "wake" up you will likely hear noises/voices. This is your ears picking up things you cannot know
 2. You may think you see "ghosts".
 3. Often your mind will be on repeat

4. You may get certain phrases stuck in your head - when you really wake, write these down, they have profound meaning to your life and Life in general.
5. Make sure you have an alarm clock set... and be sure you are able to wake up if you should encounter demons.
 1. If you are a HEAVY sleeper - like can seep through tornado/thunder type - then always do this with a partner.
 2. When you are under attack - self or otherwise - your Wei Qi will light your whole body on fire... this will cycle the Wei Qi of your partner, much like a forest fire will set all trees on edge... they will wake and wake you up.
3. To dream lucidly within a dream means you simply must note that you are dreaming and you are aware you are dreaming already.
 1. Usually you will be using your Qi somehow.
 2. Usually the second layer is "playback mode" where you get a story.
 3. You may in fact discover you are lucid by "dying" in your dream... and noticing you have not really died. This is a clue. Just remind yourself that it is your dream and that you cannot be harmed, and the pain of the death will go away. You WILL remember that feeling when you wake up.
 1. I once had an alien attacking me - I have a lot of Alien dreams or body-snatcher dreams - and I realized I was dreaming, and changed the alien into an annoying woman. The dream then left and I lost lucidity. This saved me much terror which I never directly suffer but instead witness and live in fear of. You may have your own version.
 4. More often you lucidly dream in the first layer AFTER "waking" from a movie-like dream.
 5. If you are unsure after waking twice from a dream if it is real or not, try to do something complex, like type an email.
 1. This is not foolproof. Contrary to popular opinion you CAN read and even do math in your dreams
 2. Memories may or may not be helpful. Today, for instance I dreamed I do a D- on a test I took 2 weeks ago and know I got a 95% on... and it still did not tip me off.
 3. The reason an email is a better idea than writing is that computers and the internet are moving, electronic parts, unlike the brain, and it's more difficult to "project" that fake reality into your fake reality.
4. Astral projecting is not my specialty... and it doesn't seem easy to control. I cannot provide a method. And if I could, I probably still wouldn't.
5. The state you really ought to get to is replacing naps or augmenting sleep with Qi so that you feel more refreshed and healed rather than tired.
 1. Lucid dreaming is not all that useful for this - except to escape from our own demons and nightmares.

2. You want to go blank... not have desires or expectations
3. You will find that the best time for this is BEFORE the Wood time, say around 10pm-11pm rather than Wood time 11-3am when you will have more intense dreams.
4. Your 1-1.5 hour naps can be replaced with 15-25min power-meditations which are equally refreshing if not more, and alter your mood less... except in the right direction.
 1. Start by breathing lowly, close your eyes and lie flat
 2. Let all your thoughts start coming in and building and building, acknowledging each in turn and letting them turn into a vortex in your third eye.
 3. Flush them... like a toilet.
 4. Be ready to receive "affirmations" from the Divine. These are instructions.
 5. Now that you are refreshed and realigned, with fewer anchors in your frontal cortex and new blood in there... go out and follow the instructions. you will find you are "in the zone"
4. Finally I want to make a comment that the growth you get with the meditation should be used for healing... not for vanity or other things. Your subconscious and conscience cannot be tricked. You will punish yourself if you do not do good with your powers
5. I want you to know finally that it is possible to alter sleep cycles with this meditation work. In my experience, it is useful if you need it - say you are driving and Serotonin is getting dumped into your blood like crazy, you can use it to drain the RN and send the hormone to the Liver where it's destroyed. But you will find that this is not good if you are prone to insomnia, and regardless you may not be able to sleep on time or be tired the next day, etc... This is burning the candle at both ends. Be careful.

Happy dreaming and be careful whatever you do.

Reversing the Flow, Alchemy pt. 2

posted Jun 8, 2015, 5:00 PM by S RC [updated Jun 9, 2015, 10:32 PM]

In a [previous article \(click\)](#), I went over the PRIMARY "reversing the flow" alchemy, which was, as explained, not a literal reversing but slowing the Five Elements down to regular speed.

However, in this article I want to talk a little bit about Temporal RTF Alchemy. It's not a hard concept to understand, but rather difficult to achieve.

So, you have this season cycle of 5 seasons: Winter, Spring, Summer, Late Summer, Autumn; and that's an odd number in a fixed time period, and you have the yin and yang alternate years (well, some alternate, some are consecutive, please see Heavenly Branches theory). So you end up with seasons that sometimes start on time, sometimes don't, sometimes are cool when supposed to be hot, and sometimes extra hot or extra cold. Etc...

The effect this has upon the "6 Epidemic Qi" or the 8 types of exposure is to heighten, lengthen, shorten, or delay these effects. So whereas, for example, Wind-Heat season typically starts in March, it can be delayed (by a La Nina), until early April. The effect, if the body is normally used to the March time, might be negligent, or catastrophic, depending upon the strength of Wei (defensive) Qi of the individual, and their a) age, b) stress levels, and c) diet/lifestyle.

What does this do to the body? All the exposures cause closings, and even Qi rebellion, in the channels in various, and different places of the body. The most obvious effects, for example, might be say Autumn (Metal time) weakening the Lungs, or Allergies of spring, causing Wood Rebelling against Metal (Liver heat scorching lungs/throat/sinuses). Then again, the effect might be more in a secondary or tertiary tissue (again Wood in spring affecting tendons).

Turning Vinegar into Wine

All this really does, though is reveal a good secret to the cultivator. Two of them, really. To the casual person, or lay person, it means there are forces they cannot prevent and they simply have to suffer them. But to the cultivator, there is really some interesting alchemical experimentation possible - if you can properly sense the season and the pathogenic Qi!

For example, the first thing is that if a person senses the Hexagrams about to change into the new season, one can pre-meditate and change their mind into the new form-factor and begin the alchemical work (tilling the soil, so to speak) on projects. That way you can do pre-work in winter, before the Spring arrives.

OR, conversely, if one figures out one has been subjugated to these environmental effects, one can undo them quickly. This I call the Temporal RTF Alchemy. By ending quickly the effects of, say Summerdamp, one saves weeks to months of Qi, and avoids absorbing harmful disease energy, such as arthritis, vertigo, nausea, etc...

Better yet, if one knows the 5 Elements, one can take advantage of the time to add to their elixir (requires concentration for 10 days).

Example: Summerdamp belongs to Earth, but is the reversal of Earth back onto Fire (undesireably). Taking advantage, first one a) prevents disease by avoiding certain damp foods, and ingesting ginger; b) reverses the effect through Qi Gong and fixing the Qi Hua mechanism, and; c) As water constrains Fire, we use the Kidney Restoration method and various Kidney Yang Shen and Daoyin exercises to strengthen Kidney to control the amount of Stomach Fire attacking heart.

If this is done correctly, then Fire has been controlled correctly, and during the FIRE hexagram (#30) when Summerfire starts, one can contain and direct the True Fire and Ming Men fire to mix Water and Fire and form the alchemical fetus.

More information on this is available in the Nei Gong Zhen Chuan classic (click to go to Amazon).

Example 2: During wind-heat season there is a lot more fire toxin. For a person with too much Fire (pitta), this will be hard to use. But still, a little can go a long ways. A little bit of heat can produce a lot of activity, so wind-heat would produce great effects.

Conversely, the wind energy cannot be captured, not easily or safely. But, what can be captured is the Thunder energy of spring, or rather, used to undo the negative effects of latent Evil Qi within the body.

Example 3: During the winter the Kidneys are weak. It is cold. The cold cannot be used to build Kidney Qi directly... however, the wet season is the time of rest, and long nights. That means that one should follow the program, and rest more. Also, Earth contains Water, which means that one should eat well, and especially eat foods of the earth (gourds and roots) during the winter. And Metal generates Water, so that means the time to prepare is in Fall. As far as meditation goes, it also proves that breathing and breath work is all important during winter.

There are almost infinite examples of this.

The main thing that is to be remembered is the simple principle of the Temporal RTF Alchemy, as well as how to use the Elements based on not just the emotions and time of year, but the very energy in the air and climate. **[\(See the last Article on Yin/Yang days\).](#)**

Paradigms

Your reaction to this 'paradigm chart' **as well as the article** partially informs you of your particular paradigm. Though I do not agree with the conclusions of the author, he of course makes some strong arguments in his analysis.

As Galileo once said of God's laws in response to the individual opinions and dogmas of the Church, "**It moves anyways.**"

What is a Paradigm?

The textbook **definition** of a paradigm is:

-noun

1. Grammar .

a. a set of forms all of which contain a particular element, esp. the set of all inflected forms based on a single stem or theme.

b. a display in fixed arrangement of such a set, as boy, boy's, boys, boys'.

2. an example serving as a model; pattern.

However, for our benefit we will define it as **a pattern of belief, thought, and behavior.**

The reason for this is that it is the best usable, practical definition. As we saw in the **11 aspects of Karma**, which work together with the Buddha's 12-Linked Chain of Causation and the 8 Laws to generate our karmic experience, **the paradigm we have is the most important aspect on a practical level for guiding our destiny.**

Without changing our paradigm, we cannot grow, and certainly cannot understand and incorporate the 8 Laws, or even just the Law of Harmony, into our daily living.

Much of the 12 Linked Chain itself is based upon our patterns of behavior, as well as the Noble Eightfold Path.

Think of your paradigm as the 'operating system' (like Windows or Mac or Linux) upon which your mind works. We all get this computer we call the human body, and what Chinese Medicine calls the Qi Ji or energy machine, to have experiences. We trade Jing-essence for wisdom and knowledge and carry that back to the Void at death and there must be a purpose for this grand design (which **chaotically self-assembles through the Law of Evolution**).

One may choose an infinite number of different operating systems, but ultimately there are only two types: those that are powered by open-source, faith based software, and those based on controller-type belief systems 'proprietary software', which refuse to acknowledge the very laws that they operate upon.

Those who choose to obey Law and Order, if they follow certain steps and maintain their Qi Ji and all its parts in working order will attain **the Meaning of Life**. Those who follow the other are trading Jing for achievement of transient goods because ultimately they do not inwardly believe in the deeper order and Beyond (11th Realm or God-source).

The irony is that those who utilize the former paradigm **can also achieve material satisfaction, security, peace, and a more lasting happiness...** and that those using the latter can, if humble enough and willing switch to the other side. It is literally just like switching operating systems.

Of course the difficulty is we have all these experiences and images and long-held beliefs that form a sort of pride, attachment, and inertia to change. **I call this the sclerosing process of the Qi Ji. Both body and mind "harden" and become less flexible and adaptable.**

The irony of paradigms is that they are designed to keep us from doubting the paradigm and to become more like self-fulfilling prophecies as time goes on. This is because a) the momentum gathers and continues forward and b) the paradigm is like an endlessly producing seed that produces and produces beliefs, even new ones. **As we attract persons and beliefs and experiences into our life with our mind's imagery and body's vibrational output through the Law of Harmony, we often get exactly what we expect, and this reinforces the paradigm.**

This is a GOOD thing. BUT only if the paradigm is the correct type. If it is the incorrect type, which denies the Law and Order and Truth of your being... it will inevitably lead to unattainment.

In societies that routinely reach old age at a higher rate than other places, they have found that purpose and family, and being creative among other cultural behaviors (all of which form a paradigm or world-view) are key to the factors of longevity. Moreover the people live longer and stay active, healthy, mobile, and do not go senile. This is because dementia is karmic consequence where the spirit and body begin to separate early, because the spirit knows the mind is not correctly oriented.

I am not saying it is a punishment, I am saying it is the disease state of a lifetime of behavior and beliefs that do not accord with what one knows inwardly is true. This behavior leads to either chemical and bodily exposure or to other forms of dementia. It is relatively few people whose inborn genetics (genes) are set to acquire dementia, and even then it is modifiable in a large percentage because of epigenes which can turn off and on genes.

The level of influence our mental state has on our body and our spirit (via vibrations and habits of behavior, both set by your paradigm) is hitherto little understood, except in eastern mysticism, particularly mahayana Buddhism (like Vajrayana and Zen) and Daoism. Only recently in the last 10 years has scientifically accepted studies commenced studying the effects of thought and meditation on the brain's electro-chemical physiology... and to be sure they will never complete the research because there are many deep layers of meditation most of which cannot be studied with machinery.

At any rate, paradigms are important in setting our beliefs, acquiring new experiences and beliefs, forming or negating old habits, and **ultimately determining our Destiny.** So it would be important to know how to change a paradigm.

The Qi Ji

The human mind, and definitely other sentient minds including future ones in other species, is a marvel. It can:

1. Have an experience and record it
2. Analyze, evaluate, or judge the situation in past, present, or future.
3. And act by modifying, appending, increasing, decreasing, ceasing, or denying behaviors

Moreover it simultaneously unites various spiritual levels, communicates with the 11th Realm, and guides movement through telekinesis. At times, a person can read others' thoughts, or share thoughts (telepathy). For example, I will now think my son's name, and in a few minutes he will wake from dream-worlds and come in here.

This Qi Ji's special characteristics, and inherent Buddha nature, enable us to modify our paradigms, which are ultimately the source of 95% of health or disease, the remaining 5% being chemical or genetic in nature. Even cancer, strokes, and many infectious diseases are the results of our mismanagement of Qi in the body and actions that protect or expose us to danger. [The discussion as to whether these things are results of past karmic conditioning will be in the **Just Buddhism** section.]

To review: there are three aspects of the Qi Ji which correspond to the 3 Planes of Tian-Ren-Di or spiritual, mental, and physical plane:

1. Spirit (Shen)
2. Mind & Body (Qi-Xue)
3. Essence (Jing)

The Jing produces Qi and Xue, and Xue produces Qi and houses Shen, and Shen moves Qi and Qi moves Xue and transforms Jing, completing the Qi Ji cycle.

Now the Shen is divided into the following five elements:

1. Shen (fire) or spirit
2. Hun (wood) or ethereal soul
3. Po (metal) or corporeal soul
4. Yi (earth) or intellect
5. Zhi (water) or willpower/memory

The interaction of the Shen with the others form the various aspects of the Mind:

- Shen-Yi - conscious mind (UCNS)
- Shen-Hun - subconscious mind (LCNS)

- Shen-Po - unconscious mind (PNS)
 - Po-Hun - emotional/reactionary "Animal" mind (ENS, GTR)
- Shen-Zhi - memory/identity

From this we can start to see how the paradigm forms the seed at the base in the Shen-Zhi and creates habits, emotions, actions, and we finally see the results and our reactions are stored (at night through dreams and movement of the Liver-blood and Kidney-Qi) in the Jing... literally genetic code, marrow, and cortex.

Did you know a plant's "mind" is at the root tips?

For most people *there is absolutely no cognition of this process*. This is why we try to change something in the top layers of conscious (say try to quit smoking because it is 'bad for us'), but in the end it has little effect, **because the paradigm is stored in the deepest, fifth layer!** Quite a predicament.

Modifying Thought Behavior

Modern Psychology has a number of techniques they try to use, some more bizarre than others, but in the end all of these attempt to break through the 2nd layer to make an impact on the 3rd or 4th layer at an emotional level. This has a higher success rate than simply acquiring or being forced to acquire a new belief, **because the bruise it creates to the mental-spiritual psyche can of course move the paradigms and create a paradigm shift.**

But, ask yourself: is it better to slowly stretch or tear a muscle? Is it better to get tough over time or break bones and get tough quick? Is it better to build a building soundly and methodically or to bust out holes and insert steel I-beams in the gashes?

Medications, electroshock, hypnotherapy, and even toxic herbs and some strong acupuncture methods should be a therapy of last resort. The number one method for the vast majority of people should be to draw up long held beliefs, emotions (especially repressed ones) and enable the person to see them in the light of plain view, and hopefully this will make an emotional impact.

It is even better, therefore, if the person draws these things out themselves through centering the mind and penetrating the depths through critical analysis, internal dialogue, and experiencing the Qi Ji for themselves. This is the foremost type of healing of mind, body, and even spirit!

If you would like to acquire this ability, first read the article on Using Qi to Heal, then follow these steps:

1. If possible, learn Sacred Sanctuary meditation technique; this technique directly accesses the first three layers through imagery and mental movement.
 1. I teach this in the Bagua Dharma and Qi Gong I courses, so I will not teach it here.

2. During meditation (prayer, cognition, Qi Gong, or otherwise) pose questions to the 'ether'
 1. Most easily accessed at the back of the mind, the house of the Shen-Hun (the Master-healer)
3. The questions posed need not be dialogue, if the idea of talking to yourself frightens you, though this is a powerful method. It can be an image of typing into a computer if you wish.
 1. Answers you get should be honest but not malicious or childish. If they are, you know you are getting interference from the Shen-Po and though you will want analysis of why it is unhappy, it is not helpful to get it from this childish source... **get it solely from the Hun (intuition).**
 2. It may be helpful to use the image of God, or a sage/guru to have this internal dialogue if you do not want to treat it as a input-output machine.
4. Pose questions that inherently ask about your paradigm...
 1. Use specific thoughts, especially repeated thoughts or habits of thought
 2. Use specific incidences of emotional outburst
 3. Identify and analyze long-held beliefs
 1. Ask where and who they came from: **and if you trust this source**
 1. Requires evaluation - NOT JUDGMENT - of that person's outer and inner health, which are reflections of their own karma and paradigms having blossomed in front of you
 2. Many times it will come down to parents, teachers, or media.
 3. Sometimes you will not know where it came from... almost always you should erase sources you don't know of: how could you trust it?
 4. Try to play out situations differently, and see which version would have been best.
 1. Do not become attached. This process should allow you to let go of mistakes, not get caught up in them, which is what happens when you DON'T harmonize your Qi Ji and have a bad experience.
 5. Make an inner plan if necessary. Many times it will simply be a sense of peace that comes over you or an organ or body part may tingle/ignite with Qi and you know in your heart that you are healed. But if not, **make a plan and a way to enact that plan**
 1. This is because if emotional impact cannot be used, **the other method to changing a paradigm is through constant spaced repetition or forming new habits as it is called.**
5. It may help when you are done to write them up in a journal, poem, or story format, so you can read them later... many times the best analysis times for emotional impact are the least convenient for memory, such as peri-dream or in dream states, or in trance states, or at unrelated events where the mind is relaxed.
 1. Plus you can share them with therapists or your Chinese medical doctor,
6. Share your results with a **trusted** person, friend, spouse, or parent... to get reflective analysis. Use their body language and emotional reaction to learn from, not their words, which may or may not suit your needs and wants.

7. **Avoid the tendency to fight** the paradigm shift (embrace this as an issue with not having completed your process) or have negative emotional reactions. The hypothalamus is an emotional reactive center and tends to avoid change habitually.
 1. Also tend to **avoid, if you can, punishing yourself for not attaining either a shift or a new habit...** a habit of this can lead to a new paradigm that is very unhealthy.
 2. Try to **see struggle as growth**
 1. Form a habit of finding the positive aspect of things though you know there are both positive and negative
8. Be cognizant that **you are modifying your psychic vibrational state...** your cohort (or protective herd) may not like this and may not support new behavior, beliefs, speech pattern changes, etc... understand these things in a compassionate way.¹

This is more or less the process. The more you do it, like any exercise, the more effective you will be at it.

Nirvana Explained

Dear Reader, this paragraph has a threefold purpose:

- Apology - I am not, of course, able to explain everything in sufficient detail, nor can I teach you the best way to achieve the 2nd attainment of nirvana (Nirvana from now on). As for myself, and I'm not ashamed to admit it, I had to use psychedelics to experience **Suchness (tathata)** and though I will never forget it, how I lament that I've not yet done it properly. Realize, reader that as a good friend and Bagua master pointed out, *"We're supposed to see things like that using our meditation (Qi Gong)."* This means you should be able to increase synaptic processes and flow of blood sufficiently without using something that disturbs the Ming Men fire and causes it to surge upwards unnaturally through the Du Mai. Supposedly a monk once challenged a westerner to give him a cup of LSD and after taking it, reported no "hallucinogenic affects". This would indicate he was already quite capable of Suchness through his samadhi. That is the best way to see Nirvana.
- Promise - if you study this (and other articles before it, and the Lotus Sutra) I promise you will mentally understand the theory of nirvana, and then consequently the subsequent attainments, Nirvana and Parinirvana. But visceral knowledge - believe me I know personally - is far more powerful and important than mental awareness. Why? The viscera contain the 3 souls of the shen, hun, and po, which govern your higher self. Using the yi (intellect) and zhi (memory/will) to gather data is ultimately pointless because the shen, hun, and po are the parts connected to the body and therefore produce karmic action and dictate your results. This is KEY.
- Warning - if you are not ready to understand this... you will not. If you cannot - perhaps will not - and deny it, you are only harming yourself. Reader, do NOT go further if you have not thoroughly understood previous articles and studied. A seed of doubt can go a long ways towards self-denial, God-denial, and therefore ultimately lack of Attainment and completion. If you are not verse in math, that is not a problem... not only will I explain all diagrams in detail, but there will be a separate

article on Universal Constants. You should, however, review the **Multiple Dimensions** article prior to reading this...

Title: Moving toward The Consciousness. Simply amazing.

First, as mentioned in the **Reincarnation** article, and in **Chapter 6 of the Louts Sutra commentary**, nirvana, or extinction+emptiness must not be regarded as a goal in and of itself.

Why has it therefore been emphasized? If you understand human nature you will know three things:

1. People are born, in all cases, in the lower 6 realms, and live in varying degrees of them as far as their education and Karmic Jing (essence literally from one's parents) force them to. In varying cultures, escape from this is encouraged through religion and spirituality (study) because as the Yi Jing notes, when the **Tian Gui flows**, Yang is penetrated by Yin and through the degrading process of Wind (Law of Evolution) the person enters River trigram, signifying trouble due to lust and attachment to the 5 desires. As they age, the Yang is stripped away by this [false] yin until death comes, without attainment. However, with spiritual study, and the act of voice-hearing, one can enter back upon the Way and complete the Meaning of Life.¹
2. People being born this way, seek an escape because a) they are told it's bad to be like this or b) they actually realize their danger "in the River" and seek the other shore, rather than go down this river alone.
3. People then, having embarked upon the 7th realm seek an end goal... and give up easily because, after all, they are told the 8th realm is where it is at. Preachers do not tell people they have to become preachers... they tell them to come to church

weekly and do study. The good ones tell them to preach and share in their life - proselytize - but few sell that idea as good as Christ, the "fisher of men."

In the 8th realm, satisfaction is actually, relatively good - and we'll see why later - so few people wish to pursue it any further, figuring they've gone far enough. This is, of course, not the case, and in the case of nirvana, is definitely a mind-made trap.

Thus the goal is not nirvana, which is simply a state of mind one can choose whenever convenient, saying at unpleasant or down-time opportunities, "I am one with the Universe... there is no self... the grass is always greener on the other side... make lemonade out of lemons... etc..." and any other 'serenity now' statements.²

So before we go much further in explaining nirvana, let us define what it is, and what it is for...

1st nirvana is the state of mind of "letting go" and experiencing suchness, oneness, etc... all the aspects of the Life Aquatic. It is a time-dependent state, you experience it whenever you do the steps to attain it on the Body, Mind, and Spirit levels. The method almost rarely matters, because it is the free window view to the 11th realm... but it is not the door. Just as a jailed inmate looking out at the world experiences peace and escape from prison in the mind and spirit, but not the body, that is this particular situation EXACTLY.

2nd nirvana (Nirvana) is a bodily shift of vibration in order to harmonize with the 10th realm, the **only door to the 11th realm**. [see for Tathagata Curve, or see below]

It has all the characteristics of the 1st attainment, without any of the downsides... excepting perhaps that it is energy dependent (due to Law of Relativity and you having a massive body), and your strength with it depending wholly on your:

- Experience
- Understanding
- Vibration
- Destiny
- Capability

This Nirvana - I will warn you now - can be frightening... and not all psychedelics experiences lead here. For me, personally, I chanted into the state, and asked for it, and I was definitely not ready... but without it, reader, and perhaps this was my destiny, I could not write this article for you.

3rd nirvana or Parinirvana is entering death's door through the great gate of the Tathagata (suchness)... meaning either you mentally and spiritually have harmonized and know the laws thoroughly, or you are in physical rapture (trance) when death comes, and you enter what is known as True Nirvana. This is the end goal after attaining the Meaning of Life. There is no other worthier goal for you at death than this. At this point you mentally are at peace with being in the 11th Realm and you enter it physically and no longer attached to the body can sustain understanding of it - and yet you will cease to be you... but more on that later.

Now, as I illuminated in **Chapter 2**, **Chapter 3**, and **Chapter 4** of the **Lotus Sutra commentaries**, there are many pathways to the 9th realm, and as the next future article will show, I know of at least 2 culturally different versions of the one Buddha Vehicle (Jesus and Shakyamuni)... but Nirvana and later Parinirvana are the only ***living*** pathways to the 11th realm.³

Thus concludes the definitions. The final section, reader are a series of diagrams which explain the 11 realms, the 8 Laws, and the exact mathematical landscape of human life and why we experience these things:

- cyclical emotions
- highs and lows
- cycles of disease
- ability to like some people but not others
- ability to get along with some but not others
- ability to mate with others
- ability to accomplish life's tasks, goals, and dreams

The following diagrams I have constructed with 5 years of cogitation and development, 5 years of math and science background, 8 years of martial arts and 2 years (in this lifetime) of Chinese Medicine background. They are my masterpieces of sharing the Buddha Vehicle with you, and explaining Nirvana so that you, dear reader, hopefully can have the attainment you deserve.

First up is the "Tathagata Curve"

which explains the spiritual energy from the exponential perspective. This diagram, not ironically, is displaying Kinetic Energy of a mass approaching the speed of light, here set at "1", which acts as an asymptote and explains why only the Tathagatas, who are near to it, can open the door to the 11th Realm.

This means Jesus, Buddha, Ghandi, Mother Theresa, and whoever else you see evidence of being able to open the door for others and exhibiting living in Nirvana.

The AUC or Area under Curve represents the sum total of energy they contain... as you can see the Tathagata has as much energy allocated to him as all the other 9 realms combined... and this is a mathematical function (ratio) of the Universe... such that at any given time, someone somewhere is in the 10th realm, and together with the 5th-9th are offsetting the great amount of negativity and woe we see in our news and on our streets today.

Figure 1 - the Tathagata Curve

Now, of course the curve is not 'smooth' just as life isn't smooth. Firstly it is build of tiny plateaus, millions that no one can see and only the results can be analyzed. Also there are daily ups and downs, weekly ones, monthly, even yearly for the majority of people. The more you smooth these bumps out - called turbulence - the less energy lost in

your upward journey. The following is just an illustration, I have not altered it from the creator to suite my purposes, but it will do.

Figure 2 - turbulence creates different paths for different people.

Moving along, let us examine extensively the Vibratory curves of the 11 realms and then the aspects of the 10 humanly realms. The images are large, please click them to enlarge in another window. I apologize for the hand-drawn crudeness of these diagrams, I hope one day to be able (or to inspire another to) create a 3D, perfect mathematical version.

Figure 3 - the 11th Realm or Oneness (relative-less perfection)

This diagram, if studied and cognized (penetrated to the point of complete understanding) can open the way for someone to enter samadhi once (strong Qi Gong with the purpose of

achieving Nirvana) and come out the other end as a Mahasattva or Tathagata... literally breaking down the door to Nirvana.

Now for each of the vertical scales, or amplitudes, I used the 10 human realms (of Buddhism) plus the 11th of God. If you have not reviewed them in full, in brief they mean this: Hell is misery, Animals is senselessness (no wisdom in action and pure aggression), hungry ghosts is lust and greed and envy, Asuras is anger, rage, and hatred, calmness is meditative or occasional serenity, Heaven is joy, ecstasy, love, happiness, satisfaction, etc..., voice-hearers are students, arhats or pratyekabuddhas are the self-realized, bodhisattvas are teachers, mahasattvas are teachers of the Way to Buddhahood, and Buddhahood is true Tathagata enlightenment.

I have also taken the time to explain how each of the **8 Universal Laws (Bagua Dharma)** play into this picture [they are labelled 1-8]. As you can see, study of the Bagua Dharma is merely a lower vehicle (though very advanced, and cultivated from many religions and science) to explain the ultimate Law of the 11th Realm.

I have also listed some formulas which are the governors of the laws in question. I have also listed greatest yin, reverting yin, and greatest yang on the diagram...

Figure 4 - the 10 Humanly Realms (relative imperfection)

Whereas the last diagram is given to indicate the perfection of Parinirvana and death... figure 4 is shown to indicate a) Nirvana, b) how the various levels correspond to each other, and c) the problems of the lower realms.

Notice first that the realms are divided into 3 groups, Superior, Middling, and Inferior. The Superior realms (8-10) all indicate forms of consciousness most closely associated with oneness. The Middling realms (5-7) are realms that have a much better view than the Inferior realms, albeit with more "ups and downs" than the Superior realms. The Inferior

realms (1-4) are the worst in closeness to the 11th realm (God), and also they are more difficult life states.

I want to point out several characteristics that are important concepts here.

1. Note that the 7th realm actually has access to oneness, this represents the student who is constantly harmonized with their teacher, and whose vibration has become entangled with that frequency.
2. Note that the lower the vibration, the more rapid the frequency as a rule... this prevents the feeling of oneness while also acting as to give the person more opportunity to change their situation via the Law of Rotation.
3. Note that the lower four realms are none whatsoever good... but Hell in particular is the worst because circumstances, emotions, disease conditions, financial situations change so rapidly there that the individual often gives up out of frustration and tries to cheat at every turn to get ahead.
4. Note that higher highs mean lower lows... but in the case of the Superior realms, which are none whatsoever bad, more yin time means more cultivation, silence, reflection, and nourishment as it is True yin... while in the lower six realms, the lower Yin is a mix of this and also actual false yin (bad experiences).
5. Note that the natural separation of the realms denotes mutual affinities for other realms. Those born in higher realms will not see those born in lower realms as pleasingly, while the lower realms will find reasons to bash or "bring down" the upper realms, saying things like, "rich people are evil," or "money isn't everything," etc... Their language is typically fouler as their thoughts are more negative and conditioned by negative experience.
Meanwhile, movement into the upper realms is possible for anyone.
6. Note that though that is true, those in the lowest realms, especially Hell are usually satisfied (and unable) to move beyond the 7th Realm and are apt to seek "saviors" rather than save themselves, and will repeatedly be pulled back and forth through the door to the 7th realm (since the lower 6 are the human norm).
7. Note that the time spent in the 5th-7th realms is roughly half that of the lower realms, thus the importance of exiting those varied frequencies and entering the Superior realms, which still experience the others but are known as the states of non-regression.
8. Note that governance of exiting the lower realms for the higher is still governed by the Tathagata Curve.

Figure 5 - Phasing and frequency shifting (Relativity)

This diagram represents the remainder of human (and animal, spirit, plant, etc...) existence and why people are different. Note first that we are observing one single Vibration, not all 10. Secondly, note that the "phasing" of each vibration string represents one individual. This also means that the less "out of phase" people are, especially with each other as they communicate (and thus the importance of correct mating) the closer they are to exhibiting the nature of the 11th realm which has no out of phase nature. The further out of phase one is, the more destructive... to the point that if completely out of phase with the One, then death is imminent (usually violently so because of the **Law of Harmony's strict rules about co-existence**).

Also, please notice that some individuals within a vibration can exist on a higher frequency... and indeed we all do somewhat (mass X mind X spirit where X means "cross" and refers to matrix algebra multiplication to form a new subset). This is because of varying ages, life experiences, educations, accumulation of wisdom, views, paradigms, and especially psycho-somatic disease processes. (We are all mentally ill somewhat or we would have no ego and then be dead/part of 11th realm).

The more intense a frequency of an person in relation to their cohort of vibrations, the more out of touch or difficult to understand this person may be... that does not mean they are further from the Y -axis (Source)... the remainder of the cohort, through group-think (like cults or corporations, or whole governments like Nazi Germany) can be the ones out of phase... but it does typically mean they are in danger and should seek Harmony elsewhere. An individual can affect their frequency through many methods, but usually Qi gong and acupuncture are the best for strong shifts... herbs and lifestyle/habit changes are slower shifts.

But an individual can only change their Vibration by one of the two following methods:

1. Sudden (shock) enlightenment; like Satori or the bodhicitta or being "saved" and born-again

2. Constant spaced repetitious work; like meditation (samadhi), martial arts, helping heal others, religious studies, etc...
 1. this changes the current vibration, like **quanta moving an electron** up or down valence shells.

In general, the 1st method is better for movements in the Superior realms, and the 2nd for the Middling and Inferior realms, but there are no hard and fast rules there... In fact, moving up too fast can damage one's path by creating pride and that lower realm vibration will bring one back down. In general, however, externalizing one's path (asking for others to change) never works and almost always lowers one to the lowest realms.

Please note that though it may be possible to offset the same curves up or down away from the X-axis, I do not know what that would represent, so I have not put it here. My wife theorizes it would mean a strong mental illness like schizophrenia.

In conclusion, I want to point out that each person has their own vibration, they are mixed with others, and there groups are networked like a series of neurons or cells in a leaf... and all these vibrations do not remain 2D but in fact take up all eleven dimensions, which enables the world to have its various shapes, hues, sizes, and aspects that makes it interesting.

This "surface tension" that results is perhaps best visualized by the image of water droplets rippling the surface of a pond. The center representing the central 11th realm and the other little ripples the mixture of other lesser vibrations so that all in all it is all quite turbulent (either in the center where things are most curved or out at the side where the ripples are chaotic).

Figure 6 - what does the reflection represent to you?

But like in the image, there lets loose this one droplet, that is like a soul dying and going to God... or like a God giving birth to a new Universe... or a mother to a baby... or a writer to a new book... [etc...] Let this inform you as to your goals and dreams. And if this article

helped you to see the nature of Reality as-it-is in the [Life Aquatic](#), then my job is done. As always, comments or questions are greatly appreciated.

Now enjoy this psychedelic moment

Heart Fire Releasing Meditation

posted Dec 2, 2014, 12:54 PM by S RC

The purpose of this meditation is to remove Liver generating Fire in the heart and manifesting in the lips and tongue as canker sores and cold sores, sore gums, teeth pain, etc...

1. Enter a deep meditation, using whichever meditation you prefer; perform "breath tuning"
2. Perform the first leg of the [Reversing the Flow Alchemy](#), until you get to [LV14-Cycle Gate](#)
3. Picture a connection - such as an invisible blood vessel - between the Liver 14 area or what I call the "Qi heart" (on the right, obviously), and the right underside of the tongue, halfway from the back to the front.
4. Focus hard on it, such as using the [Sacred Sanctuary Meditation](#) to have your "sentry" or "guardian" shoot a laser at the point... a laser of cold, or pure light.
5. When it releases it will be a very sharp and sudden pain in the tongue that you feel recede in a direct line back towards the liver.
6. An alternate of this meditation would be performed for the left side in the event of sugar induced canker sores or cold sores.

TIP: To prevent Wood and Heart Fire Ascension, it would be helpful to do the [Kidney Restoration Meditation](#)

The body is basically a machine. But not a disconnected machine like a car, it is a bio-chemico-electromagnetic quantum shifting complex sensory apparatus with 8 yin senses, and 8 yang powers (extrasensory), and is highly active, mobile, and evolving.¹

It runs off of 0-point energy, which we call the soul or a soul-atom. This tiny spark, which for all we know could correspond to a star on a higher or lower dimension somewhere is very, very powerful. It exudes a toroidal energy field (called an aura), and runs best when all the chakras are aligned within the body. The yang aspect of the chakras are themselves swirling fields, and the

yin/physical aspects are glands and nerve bundles that connect them. The nerves and psychic connections of all of these form a complex network of vessels and channels we call jing-luo or simply mai.

The Meridians are used to pass complex information between the chakras and to bring data input to the main quantum computer (your brain) which makes millions of calculations every moment. At the top of all of this apparatus of complex input and output, there you sit, worried about whatever it is you do... following the intellect all over the place.

Now, basically this torus works best when you actively align the psychic chakras and physically unblock the body. When you don't it still runs, but it gets weaker. It is constantly rotating and sucking in energy from eyes, ears, crown, mouth and nose... these can be represented either positive (golden light) energy or negative (black-purple) energy, which then feeds into the top and is digested and expelled out the anus, urethra, palms, soles, and also mouth.²

The main parts of us tend to work well, but in our society toxicity has increased and increased and increased to the point where the typical flushing systems are overloaded a lot:

- Blocked lymphatics = blocked urination-excretion
- Blocked small intestine (usually emotional, but could be antibiotics or large amounts of food) = blood bowels
- Blocked cellular transfer = blocked sweat glands
- Blocked diaphragm = blocked lungs
- Blocked gallbladder = blocked liver and kidneys
- Blocked joints = blocked palms and soles

In particular, the last one is incredibly important, I have found clinically. The tendency to have no Qi circulation in feet and even in the hands has resulted in increasing amounts of toxicity in adults, children, mothers, and infants. It is no wonder that a little vaccine these days can overwhelm a child... everything else is full of poisons:

- Toxic food, air and water
- Toxic medications
- Toxic vibrations and sensory input
- Toxic culture

The ability to take in these energies at the top of the system and expel them at the bottom is critical to healing. But most people have no function at Kidney 1. This is important because if there is no Qi-field (aura) around the feet, it must be small in other ways, too.... perhaps weak endocrine, nerves, or lymphatics. Either way you can expect problems to multiply as the flesh that is exposed to the exterior radiation, impacts, and toxicity will rot and shrivel, and its ability to detox the body will decrease proportionately. Most of these people complain of "fasciitis" or "heel spurs" or they have nail fungi and deviated digits, or popped vessels distally especially medial ankle.

The Zhuangzi says the “True Person (ie- Complete) breathes through [their] heels.”
This is not a metaphor for breathing deeply. It is actually what happens after you restore the Kidney 1 “Bubbling Spring” and baptize yourself with Water/Source Qi. The Qi goes down the outside (Bladder channel) of the leg, at UB64 it crosses to KI1, and then bubbles outward. From there it goes over a waterfall and penetrates the ankle at 3, 4, 5 and then plunges into the heel and refills the aquifers of the heel. This can be a very painful process the first time, but is very necessary, because only when it is refilled will it then penetrate Kidney 6, enter the Ren/Conception vessel and rise up to recharge the ovaries/testes and adrenals, and continue UP the chakras (via Ren and Chong) to recharge all of the endocrine, finally culminating with the glands in the brain. By the way this makes the crown MORE able to be open. The less open it is, the less likely you are to be able to do this... so it makes this KRM technique all the more important.

1 - 8 senses are the normal 5 + proprioception, balance, and touch is divided into pressure and temperature

The 8 extrasensory powers: telekinesis, clairvoyance (and remote sensing), telepathy, time-dilation, levitation, prediction, spatial manipulation, and spirit communications (beyonding).

2 - the mouth is used to bring in and expel, and hence a great sign that someone is out of balance is by what words they choose to say and what ingestion decisions they make.

Pre-Work

The first thing you need to know is Breath Tuning basic information.

There are 8 major regions... but the Qi-breath can be sent to anywhere in and even out of the body. Most people live on 2 or even 1 alone. This is directly related to:

- Hypertension, hyper-everything but thyroid, which was hyper till it died.
- Neck and shoulder pain
- Migraines
- Infertility
- Colon and bladder issues
- Cancers

If you cannot breath to region 4, you need not even go further, you must must must regain control of your abdomen for breathing. Expect 2-3 months of this FIRST. If you cannot do this, you MUST AVOID:

- Kundalini
- Alchemy, sexual or breathing based, including Hermetics
- Transcendental/Tantric Meditations

You will generate heat and energy which will “bounce” off the blockages in the abdomen and cook your brain whilst draining your glands and because you haven’t restored the Kidney Channel, the Ren, Du, and Chong will shrivel and die.

I am not going to argue this... it’s a fact.

To practice, just lay flat and place a book on your abdomen below the navel and breathe in, pushing it up, and breathe out with either a sighing breath or a gurgling/low growl. Do NOT purse the lips or breathe through the teeth. That’s how you “puff yourself up” for a battle. You don’t do that to calm down you do it to get “amped”.

Do this until when you breathe in you can push on your perineum.

The Technique

1. Lay flat, cover your feet with a sheet or blanket. No crossed feet. If you are stressed, I recommend listening to soothing music, harmonic tones, gongs, or whatever else you have. You can also take a moment to watch a video on the chakras on youtube and it will use the mind’s direct access to open them up.
2. Clear your mind, regulate your breath (in for 6 count/beats, hold for 3, out for 6 is fine)
3. Imagine you are aligning the spine and chakras, opening the crown to receive golden light. Shut out negative interference.
4. Imagine when your abdomen breathes in (and you can use chest after it... just no Reverse Breathing) that you are expanding a balloon shaped like you are shaped, but is too shriveled.... it should be a few inches or even feet bigger than you but right now is like an old birthday balloon... blocked at the knees or hips, elbows or shoulders).
5. When you breath out, you push mentally, and with your mind as well the parts of the balloon that are for legs and arms, simultaneously expelling toxic gray air from the lungs. For hot days breathe out the mouth across the underside of the tongue, for muggy days

across the top of the tongue, and for cold days out the nose. If there is dryness breathe less aggressively, for mucus more aggressively. Do not strain.

6. You must repeat this every day, twice a day 20 min each or once a day an hour, until you feel the Kidney 1 point on your sole explode with bubbling Qi-energy. It will not be pleasant the first time. It may have electrical shocks, or itch, or stabbing pain.
7. After several days of this, gently guide the energy in towards the inner ankle area and “watch over it” like a hen watches an egg hatch. Do not push, pull, just protect. Feel the sheet gliding across your skin on your chest.
8. When the energy comes up the inside, let it go where it will, but ultimately try to get it to the perineum, and let it build there. From here you CAN do other advanced methods, safely.

Miscellaneous Suggestions for Improving Technique

- Use a colored sheet that matches the season or the weak Element in your body.
- Take the time to restore the joints themselves and “follow” the cables of the muscles back up from the knees to the Liver flank area and “shut off” the borrowing energy draining the knees.
- Move the arms into different positions to stretch the Fire channels... try placing “ballerina” hands over the Du20/crown so that the palms’ energy field helps the crown to blossom.
- Try placing the soles of the feet an inch apart to warm the soles; occasionally rub them to facilitate cellular transfer in the capillary beds. Remember, this point is expelling toxins your body misses, and also expelling bad juju that your P8/H8 (palm) points miss.
- Get foot-detox sessions occasionally to unblock the cells and lymph
- Avoid using the feet right after meditation, let them re-normalize so they are not too tender.
- Stretch the legs and use a foam-roller to help break up blockages “in the river” of the bladder and gallbladder channels
- Twist your feet with your hands and roll your ankles before, during, and after to make sure channels are aligned and getting more aligned.
- Move more often throughout the day and avoid caffeine to keep the capillary beds of the distal limbs open. Caffeine closes the distals to open those in the head. energy drinks are the worst for this, and it is very bad for the body.
- Get your spine aligned, one way or another... so that the toroid is not bent or kinked in any way.
- Self-massage neck, arms, legs, and abdomen.
- Learn the methods of cavity-massage. I can teach these in person. One word: vacuum.
- Practice yoga, Taiji, Qigong, Bagua, or Daoyin. Twist, bend, and move.
- Use cardiovascular exercise to “push” the pulse wave of the heartbeat upwards into the crown FIRST then down into the perineum second and clear out the Chong for the meditation ahead of time after weather fronts or emotional traumas.
- Use sounds to open specific chakras, tones, bells, or chanting all work fine.
- Circular rubbing and “pok-king” will also facilitate cellular release. Acupressure is great.

- Stones, gems, crystals, reiki, and all energy works can help “re-program” the body to allow for detoxing release, and are great to have the same day as KRM.
- Learn my 8 special techniques of enhancing meditation (shifucareaga.com blog)
- Practice daily, and especially after: running, martial arts, biking, hiking, swimming, or anything else that pounds the feet.

Supposing a person has had an ember that has been stored, either in incubation or in hibernation. How does one go about restoring this coal to an ember?

Suppose, moreover it could possibly be a toxic ember, radiating negativity outwards actively. This ember is most difficult to restore.

Restoring is a difficult subject, so briefly let's talk about these three circumstances:

Incubation

The incubated ember is the easiest to restore, since it is warm, and glowing, and 100% positive.

Incubated means that it was at one point more recently advancing with the Fire and the Bellows.

What does it mean to advance Fire? It means to advance Yang-energy and heat the substance one is working upon or transmuting. Advancing the Yang means towards purity and Life.

What is the Bellows? This means that which stokes the Fire; activity.

In meditation this is the Dan Tian and breathing, respectively, and the Spark of Life force and the Qi/prajna.

But in other matters it may mean more subtle things such as working hard at one's job/career. Or caring about your children so as to produce balanced and happy children.

To restore an incubated ember, there isn't much work to do (comparatively). There is a heating up to Fire process, a protecting the transfer

Hibernation

A hibernating ember is also known as a Coal. It is cold in nature, and is mostly yin. Why was it in hibernation? Probably neglect but sometimes one can put something into cold storage by recognizing a disaster immediately before it manifests.

If it is a worthy Coal it is pure Essence (true yin); if it is best left in stasis, it has too many alloys and needs refinement.

But even with it being nearly 100% yin, there is the spark of life, the seed of greatness. Like a seed.

So therefore the Sage person keeps every ember or Coal, big or small, in case of need, in a little glass jar.

What is this glass jar? It is merely a symbolic protective glass wherein a person can look but not touch. Beyond

Fission into Fusion

AKA turning Green Gold Violet

A Metal Man is a person who restores the Great Elixir of their Original Being in order to become rare in the world. However, there are different outcomes based solely upon correctness.

At the END, when liberation is arriving from whatever path is chosen, the elixir of Reality forms and one chooses ones path. In the vernacular, one chooses the Jedi way or the Sith way... for lack of an easier transmission.

The liberation arrives as crystallized Truth.

Those that see it and see a means to become greater than others and get 'free stuff' will turn toxic. They will put on their dragon armor and go to war with all people to subdue them and use up the yin in themselves in hoping to become immortal in the minds of, ultimately, temporary people.

Those that see the the liberation and think of helping and serving others will see a means to become low and gain greatness by them. If any fame is to be gained, it is through incredible effort and

process, and an adding of fuel process.

In heating up, this means hard work. Protecting, this means keeping the work a secret from usurpers, destroyers, and devilish forces. Devilish forces are thieves and distractors.

Transferring means to transplant like a sappling to a larger pot or the soil.

Adding fuel means to stoke the fire with the Bellows again as well as a material source. Physical fire requires wood or paper. Spiritual fire therefore requires insight or illumination.

An object to advance (such as rebuilding a car) requires parts; a relationship requires love and Accord.

The most important thing though is in the cultivation process, not to lose the ember, only to harness it.

the external, and only the internal can get at it.

One can be a success but appear a failure; it all is a matter of keeping this Coal buried in the ground away from prying eyes and doubting words.

In restoring it there must be incredible patience. The care can be a bit less because it isn't weak; though it may be brittle. This means that one's feelings or others... or the object of care itself is easily hurt by blunt trauma. But as for wind it will not matter much because the hibernation will cease in a spontaneous combustion and this cannot be ceased by wind if the work is hard enough.

The hardest part is the hard work; ceaseless effort must be applied. This means the time must be right, and the sincerity, and the correct application.

Knocking off old rust, one will quickly advance the Coal-fire to a blazing inferno, and then no one will be able to stop one's advance of this Unseen ember. Looked for by no one, expected by none least of all those who do not see.

Like a Phoenix rising from ashes; the restoration will be most impressive

self-transformation (that does not lose the Basis).

This is a Green-gold Metal man vs. a Violet-gold Metal man.

AKA Fission vs. Fusion. When metal radiates itself out it turns green and glows toxic. When metal crushes itself (the ego), then it turns hotter and hotter from silver to yellow to orange to white to blue and finally violet. At this point the metal fuses from one element into another. One crushes all 5 Elements into one flowing, endless energy, and it results in a warmth that scorches away all faults and warms everyone around one.

The main thing in transforming fission into fusion is to transform any ember of the green-gold man into the selfless violet-gold man. As long as selfishness remains, the radiation will harm life and essence.

In capturing the heat it is important to put it to work. The work that was in studying is nothing compared to the work applied. Endless effort, clarifying all Darkness, and then in the end, providing an equal glow upon all people, like the Sun. This is the purpose of the Violet Gold man.

The final statement to be said here is that cultivation is most important.

Easier means more protection is needed. Harder work means more care is involved in handling it. More heat means less destructible by yin forces... however, it is easier to do great damage by it.

So in cultivation one needs somewhere to go and something to do. When an ember first emerges one should not use it; but when it is restored one must use it IMMEDIATELY to stabilize it.

Liver Qi Depression Disorder

posted May 30, 2011, 8:20 PM by S RC [updated Jun 25, 2011, 10:28 PM]

This article is intended for students of martial arts and doctors of Chinese (and other oriental) medicine. You must be somewhat knowledgeable in the concepts of Qi and meditation to understand it.

The Liver in TCM comprises more than the organ itself. It also comprises the

foot-jueyin channel which begins in the foot and traverses the body, penetrates the groin, the viscera-organs, the diaphragm, and connects to the sense organs, especially the eyes, inner ears, and the cortex, where it finally connects with Bai-hui (Du20) at the apex of the head. This *jueyin* or reverting yin means that yin has reached its lowest point and now must ascend rapidly and emerge as yang in the topmost part of the body where Taiyang is said to be in abundance. The diagram at right demonstrates this phenomena in the Taiji Tu better known in the west as the "yin-yang diagram."

But physiologically we also know that the Liver has more functions. It is highly dependent on the kidneys for hormonal and filtration balance, hence the reliance of the Liver for its Qi on the Kidney Yang, and the especially strong connection of liver and kidney yin. In TCM the liver stores blood at night, which is used to nourish the Kidney (KI) Jing-essence, and house the Hun (soul). In the daytime the Jing is converted by Yang (adrenal energy) into Qi to move the blood out, make new blood (in the Heart and bones) and this balance keeps the Wood-Water relationship in balance.

The Liver (LV) is also the first protector of the Heart (HT) because after the food is digested in the Spleen¹ the material is first filtered and metabolized by the Wood organs of LV and Gallbladder (GB) before reaching the HT and Lungs (LU). This connection is via the portal venous return system and is the Middle Jiao

(MJ) of the San (3) Jiao (SJ). But we also know that the LV sends hormones of control to the SP (pancreas and spleen together) for the regulation of endocrine recycling of red blood cells. [If you're going to receive the waste of another's work, make sure the work is done properly!]

Hence the LV from time to time, if over-active can affect the Spleen/Stomach (Earth) and this Wood-Earth imbalance creates a general MJ stagnation.² If one can imagine a complex engine or clock where the gears run too fast on one side and too slow on the other, and then flip back and forth to compensate, it is easy to see this is a bad situation.

Now, we also know that after this blood storage and filtration, the MJ (portal veins) go to the pulmonary system which is the Upper Jiao (UJ). Since the blood, once oxygenated eventually goes into the brain (and extraordinary bowel in TCM), and the mind is known to be in the brain, and the HT governs the mind in this way... it can be said that if the LV is stagnant, hyperactive, or ascending (of its own accord), it will afflict the mind and particularly the emotions. This physiology strengthens the Hun-Shen (psyche) relationship between the autonomic (sympathetic/parasympathetic) nervous systems (ANS) and the Central nervous systems (CNS). This, as well as the jueyin-to-taiyang philosophy explained in the beginning, gives us the true relationship of the LV to Du-governing mai (channel), which is well known to be the CNS (spine and brainstem). This relationship also explains the aspect of the LV governing the eyes and ears... it is via the DU channel. It does not literally govern them, but the blood that it controls which comes from the SP and KI to nourish them with Ying-nutritive Qi (vitamins, minerals, oxygen) must pass through the LV (and pericardium/PC) to get to the Palace of Yang (heart and brain). If the LV (general) controls these things, it may easily affect the mind (emperor), causing much vexation. Thus the emotion of Wood (LV/GB) is righteous anger. When a person is in the throws of anger or rage, their eyes turn red, their ears ring, their thoughts are confused (clouded), their body trembles (d/t "LV wind"), and their voice becomes loud (Wood is the season of Spring or loud activity).

Finally the LV governs the genitals via its channel. This relationship is not understood as well as the Kidneys, and it may indeed be the relationship of the LV/KI that aids this. But, examples exist, such as erection (or priapism in extreme) where the penile organ turns to "wood."³ It is also true that the GB channel (shaoyang) controls the Dai-girdle mai (DM). The DM wraps around the waist, and holds the genitals in place, as well as plays a secondary role in the anatomy of women⁴. Also, in women, the buildup of menses in the uterus (Bao Gong) is a product not only of HT blood and KI essence and KI yang (hormones), but the needed blood to finish it and the energy to move it comes directly from the LV organ⁵.

Thus it is that the LV has many strong physiological functions. It is well known as an organ alone to filter more than 40,000 known contaminants, and it metabolizes nearly every drug or herb that we consume, and thus also controls healing. Without a LV one dies very fast and if a LV becomes very hyperactive one also will die quickly and painfully.

This is why-reader-those who wish to learn about longevity would do well not simply to nourish the KI essence (yin in women, yang in men), or the SP Qi (dietary energy)... as is popularly believed... but to soothe, course, and free the flow of the LV - the commander General of the armies of the body. The LV controls the middle by controlling the San Jiao. If it does this, it also controls the whole body.⁶ Thus it is my belief that "LV coursing" is the absolute essential of health and longevity⁷.

In the follow paragraphs I will discuss the causes of THREE distinct types of LV Qi depression, their known effects, some assumptions about what not correcting them could lead to, and then give specific methods for relief.

LV/DU Imbalance (Psyche stasis)

Because the LV is anger, and the SP is the organ of the intellect, and the LV tends to overact on the SP almost daily in modern life through the stress etiology (cause)... the mind tends to be assaulted by two seemingly inseparable pathologies: raciness and pensiveness.

Raciness is the quality of activity and movement. As the Taoist I Ching says, the mind is like Thunder over Thunder, rolling from one thought to the next without any awareness of the separation or ability to stop of its own accord. One can be thinking of ones errands one moment, and the eyes catch sight of something that reminds one of something, and that starts a huge chain of memories that more or less are played out on the mind as a projection, surreptitiously replacing the eyes' input, and eliciting all kinds of passions (emotions of pain) and regrets or other negative feelings, resulting in decisions that may be hasty or incorrectly come to... and by the time one returns from this fantasy voyage, often one cannot even remember the first errand on one's mind. This is the aspect of Thunder-activity, and thunder is the power of LV Yang in the body.

Pensiveness is, however, the aspect of the Spleen-earth, which tends to mull or ruminate, gnawing as the Stomach would, upon an old thought or memory which is acting as a gallstone in one's side. It is pensiveness which famously leads to ulcers, emaciation, and obsessive disorders. This aspect is what is engaged in the projector of the brain, which is in the front of the mind. It is the Yi-shen

(intellect) which writes or reads this article, while the Hun-shen of the Liver is what guides my fingers and your eyes.

So the tendency of the emotions (re: passions) to inflict damage upon the psyche is what causes this particular distress syndrome, and begins the downward spiral into the other two disorders. Being the gateway cause, it is also easiest to treat.

Results of this pathology are:
anger/short temper
confusion (aka lack of focus)
ear-ringing
PMS
excessive dreaming/disturbed sleep
Worry and anxiety disorders
ADHD
lack of appetite
HBP

The disorder is aggravated by:
stressful lifestyles
poor diet (usually eating on the run)
coffee/cigarette abuse
alcohol
excessive TV/video game/internet use
and karmically speaking-being of the lower vibratory states (continual anger particularly)

The treatments are:
Lifestyle - traveling, walking daily or along the beach, hiking, sports or other mobilities

Exercises - walking, digging, or cleaning - any repetitive task - that removes the activity from the Yi will separate the duo. The mind can mull without gnawing and the body can course the LV Qi. Jogging is OK, and a common tool, but it is a bit damaging to the joints and HT Qi.

Diet - a habitual use of mint or small amounts of low-grade alcohol (such as red wine everyday), as well as use of vinegar and oil (to activate the GB and cleanse the LV) will make the Wood element happy. The flavor of the Wood is sour, so it is pleasing. If one has sugar cravings, this is a sign of the Wood-Earth

disharmony. Consumption of both is essential. As one can see, our society clearly prefers more sweet to sour, but both are in excessive and incorrect use, indicated widespread LV-SP disharmony that is rooted in the psyche.

Herbs - Sheng Jiang and Chai Hu are essential to movement of MJ Qi. If there are other conditions present such as deficiency, then more herbs should be added, but daily or weekly ginger, mint, and bupleurum teas are good enough to prevent most cases of anxiety. Speak to your herbalist prior to this. If you have a tendency to migraines, avoid the use of Chai Hu (Bupleurum). A formula that may be used with prescription would be Si Ni San or Xiao Yao Wan.

Acupressure - LV3, GB41, SJ5, PC8 or PC6, Taiyang (temples), and ear massage of the center and the groove will drastically soothe the psyche and move Qi.

Qi Gong/Meditation - A simple quiet, water style meditation is recommended here. When one is feeling anxious, paranoid, insecure, overwhelmed, or generally stressed, proceed to a quiet place (or a quiet walk when one is proficient). Close the eyes and allow thoughts to race forward in the mind. Observe them dispassionately, patiently, allowing that they will not cease for approximately 15-20 minutes. As they come forward imagine moving backwards away from them (or down to Dan Tian if you are aware of this). This will separate the Yi from the Hun.

~15-20 min in you will arrive at a blank space. When you are suddenly calmed, and the ears open, the heart slows down, the chest breathes big and the belly feels more hollow (less heavy)... then you have successfully coursed the LV Qi and unbound the LV-DU Qi stasis.⁸

Diaphragm Lock (Qi Hua Disruption of the Zhong Jiao)

Diaphragm Lock ranges from a mild nuisance (such as post-Thanksgiving syndrome!) to a serious life-threatening situation, **such as overeating that causes major distention, COPD, and chronic disease like diabetes and CHF.**

It is quite simply where the Diaphragm Muscle becomes inhibited in movement. In the early stages, or daily, one may alleviate this with the mind alone. But when it lasts for years, it is difficult to undo because of the introduction of the internally generated pathogen: Dampness.⁹

Since ALL channels except the Dai Mai pass through the Diaphragm¹⁰, it is actually a disorder that, like Wind, leads to 10,000 more. The diaphragm can literally choke off the esophagus, aorta (CH-mai), or if the LV Qi is stagnant

enough, become a heating pad (inflammation) that cooks the Heart and Lungs. Since these are the two organs of respiration and circulation, they more or less control the mind. No good circulation: no happiness. No happiness: more compensational behaviors (such as eating). Eating like this, one tends to sugar and rich foods. This causes Dampness. The Dampness is NOT stored in the blood at first but in the flesh and channels, below the diaphragm (which blocks their rise).

So this condition is excess yin below, excess yang above (LV Yang rising or LV Fire flaring)... both are incorrect and this Qi-Hua (transformation) disruption of the natural rhythms of the body leads to all sorts of complications. Too many to try to name here. Some of them are merely complications of those in the last section. Such as atherosclerosis (dampness in the veins) coming from HBP¹¹. HBP - btw - causes more irritability, which causes more stasis.

The main etiology is stress but also an equal part of diet and habit. The best treatment is therefore lifestyle modification ranging from extended vacations to complete makeovers (career changes, diet changes, getting a life coach, joining a program for anger management, going to fat camps, etc...)

If this disorder continues, eventually it will be unable to be reversed by conventional methods, and there will be so much dampness that exercise may cause HT Qi collapse (heart attack), stroke, or death. It may be in fact that this person has a serious emotional trauma at the Shen level, meaning psychological, or even deeper, such as a karmic scar to the Hun (soul) which forces the person to respond to life anxiously. Counseling and the work of deep energy healers would be necessary.

BUT in most cases some standard therapies will work.

Massage - monthly is a must. Diaphragm release is a start, but also deep tissues of the back where emotions are trapped, and ovary massage are recommended. Cupping/Guasha on a regular basis to free the Luo-mai where emotions tend to become trapped and cause muscle lock.

Herbs - Chai Hu Shu Gan San, Dan Zhi Xiao Yao San, and Ping Wei San are important MJ freeing formulas. Use of mint is irrelevant except for daily soothing, one must dredge the channels using moving and cooling herbs. Mu Dan Pi, Dan Shen, Chuan Xiong, Chai Hu, Zhi Ke, Gua Lou, and more are needed to break up the stasis. This requires the supervision of an herbalist - DO NOT TRY TO DO IT YOURSELF.

Exercise - weekly or even daily Taijiquan (Tai Chi) or Yoga, and active cardio exercise will be a must.

Qi Gong - The San Jiao Qi Gong, which takes 5 minutes, is the best formula to unlock the diaphragm. Other Qi Gong exercises which require Dan Tian breathing

will be sufficient but may not give the raising of the Clear Yang to Bai Hui that this method does.

Acupressure-RN6,8,10,12,3,14; GB21/SJ15 (traps) release for the inevitable shoulder/neck pain, GB20, misc UB back "shu" points; SP6, LV8, ST40, ST36, GB34, SP10, SJ9, PC6¹²

Certain things will absolutely aggravate this condition (other than emotional disturbances and fatty/greasy foods). More alcohol than 1/2 shot of whiskey or 1 beer will do the opposite intension of moving LV Qi and cause not just stasis but LV Yang rising and even LV Fire. Similarly, acetaminophen or other "pain relievers" which may be taken to alleviate a headache will cause the liver to produce toxins that assault the UJ and stagnate blood in the MJ. The formula to treat this later must and should be Xue Fu Zhu Yu Tang jia Chai Hu to remove the toxicity.

Coffee will probably at this stage be a habitual amount and abused resulting in cold fingers/ toes or even hands and feet, meaning the emotional anxiety is at the Po level and very deep.¹³ These conditions will require Si Ni San in varying dosages... if the Qi has been taxed heavily and CHF is present they will also need Si Ni Tang. But the only true method to relieve such spasm is dual action of quitting the coffee/cigarette habit and deep meditation to express the emotions held at a distance in the furthest aspects of the channels.

The most common result from the lack of treatment here, emotionally speaking is Depression. At that point only meds and psychological counseling will be able to relieve and prevent the next stage.

LV Organ Imbalance

LV organ disorder ranges from moderate -such as increase LV enzyme output and BUN/creatinine in the blood or urine - to very severe even terminal diseases such as hepatitis or cirrhosis.

It is rare to see it come all the way from humble beginnings described above, and more likely to come from either a major shen-disturbed lifestyle (such as alcoholism or drug abuse) or a very powerful pathogenic strike (such as HIV, hepatitis, or drug overdose).

In the former condition the LV Qi becomes stagnant almost instantly and turns to LV Yang rising and LV Fire quickly. The LV Fire stagnates/cooks the blood. If there is a long history, such as alcoholism, dampness is cooked into phlegm, such as cirrhosis (fatty liver), and this phlegm can even be carried around by "Liver Wind" which is a fancy way to say the bloodstream, or high blood pressure.

Because the phlegm cannot be expelled, as it is not in the lungs, it will traverse the channels, mostly the blood luos (venules) and become entrapped in the extremities, most notably, the upper jiao. Phlegm conditions such as psychological distress, even breaks from reality. Or more CNS (DU) based symptoms, like stroke, lesions, aneurysms, emboli, TIA, and strange-incurable autoimmune diseases may set in.

The phlegm is very sticky, very turbid, and not reachable by surgical technique (whereas in the last section such things as clots can be surgically removed). This phlegm is systemic, and plagues the functions of the body, primarily the senses and mental affect.

The result is a generally poor prognosis.

However, powerful therapies, such as pharmaceuticals and inferior grade herbs that expel phlegm, and are toxic, will force the body to expel the phlegm with the body's own fluids. HOWEVER, once sclerosed, such expulsion will only dry the phlegm more, turning it into a permanent lesion. Pharmaceuticals may also be able to reduce the symptoms of the phlegm even if they cannot remove it from the CNS pathways.

That is why it is essential to remove the organ stasis early on with the above methods, and then, case by case, basis, with an established pattern, the use of a powerful dredging and harmonizing formula.

The one caveat to dredging is that if the patient is more than halfway deficient - as almost all patients will be somewhat to more than halfway so - then one MUST supplement the sources: KI yin, yang, SP Qi, LV Blood, HT Fire, etc...

Failure to do so will actually shorten the life span BECAUSE the qi required to metabolize the meds/herbs in the remaining functioning liver and kidneys will be consumed, and may become more stuck. It is a risky thing to try to force phlegm expulsion at this stage. It may require liver transplant.

NOTE - If there is ascites, that must be expelled to relieve the LV and HT from the excess of phlegm-damp in the MJ and UJ. Acupuncture, massage, etc... will not work, one must use either meds or cathartic herbs such as Gan Sui and Ba Dou.

Another cause of Liver Organ disharmony might very well be parasites - so one must always keep that in the mind and use the tongue. Parasitic tongues differ from general lifestyle damp-heat tongues because they have irregular or strange things like geographic coats and sharp, deep cracks in the MJ, etc... Spotting of the mucosa may also be seen. Conditions of LV Wind without phlegm (early stage autoimmune disorders, usually), conversely to the thick yellow coats of LV failure will be instead thin with deep valleys and scanty, dry yellow coats. The LV here is being cooked, instead of doing the cooking. This is a pathogen of the PC -

emotional or genetic or contagious or chemical (beware chemical poisonings, they are common).

Qi Gong - Even up to moderately-severe conditions such as HT Fire or LV Fire, one can use meditation to remove the organ imbalance. It would be wisest to do the first two meditations listed today before trying this... **and it may take some years to also acquire such a skill. (The skill of doing this FOR the patient is not discussed in this article).**

To start, one must calm the mind, and move from Yin Tang to Bai Hui (DU20) to DU16 (the cerebellum) where the Hun is truly housed. From here descend the Du mai to Du4/Ming Men, and enter the cavity. Find the Dan Tian (seminal vesicle) and skirt along the bladder up the ureters to the kidneys. (Or use the shu points if you know how) Here nourish the KI Yin with calm watery thoughts, and then activate the Ming Men (adrenals). One should at this point be activating GB25 and LV13. When the whole cavity is filled with Qi awareness one will notice the LV is like a hard, cold stone or even a Void. Using the cold-fire of the adrenals, move from LV13 towards LV14 towards RN17 (upper Dan Tian). From here the HT Fire (thymus gland) will quell, and also the Qi will cross the diaphragm bridge at RN15 (HT access point) to the spleen tip, and this will be the LV releasing the correcting LV yin-blood to the SP, instead of withholding it. When this happens the red tip of the tongue should disappear, the body may even feel to become cooler to the patient. The mind will relax and the face will smile. Deep seated hatreds and grudges will instantly be released, and compassion will soar in the Palace of Yang. The Yi will wish to sleep and the dreams will be pleasant but the sleep too deep to recall them easily. The patient will wake rested. Warning - if on the table do not wake earlier than 30 minutes as stupor may result from the depth of mind not returning immediately.

Can acupuncture, diet, and exercise moderate this condition? Not really but they will be definite aids in the constant battle. The biggest unknown here is how deep the etiology is, and it almost always seems to be in the hun (soul) level, which is karmic. The person may experience something in this life, or worse, past lives which they cannot recall nor without years of meditation even begin to express beyond the vascular muscle spasms, and the result is a very frustrating sense of "wrongness" or anxiety about their outer world. It may be that the *Ghost* points or *Window of the Sky* points are useful. I have even gotten powerful reactions just to "color identification" meditation, but **these can be dangerous if the patient is not ready to deal & heal.** Co-treatment or sole treatment by a therapist and probably best; a hypnotherapist is essential to unlocking these latent pathogenic states. But it is certainly not going to hurt them to try all the other modalities as well.¹⁴

Conclusion

LV Depression Syndromes are preventable diseases in most cases, but can also be serious traumas. It is up to the trained healer or person analyzing themselves through meditation to seek out the causes and best methods to relieve these conditions. The above are general guidelines, and not meant to cure all and every case. It is always what is appropriate to the situation. Some therapies are too intrusive for minor cases and yet too weak for stronger ones. A liver transplant would obviously be inappropriate for everyday stress (right?) likewise the use of mint is not appropriate in coursing the Qi of a chronic alcoholic! The pulse and tongue and a good intake are the keys and guides to successful treatment. But more so also the use of good observational meditation will likewise be essential to the patient and everyone else's health.

Polarity! Profound beyond words.

posted Aug 21, 2010, 1:45 PM by S RC [updated Feb 15, 2014, 4:13 AM]

The Law of Polarity is not simple dualism, as has been chastised by the great gurus of all the major eastern traditions, from the Gita to the Dao De Jing. It is in fact, a law of interconnectedness, as I intend to show.

Before I get into the particulars of this Law, which corresponds to the Fire trigram in the Bagua Dharma, I want to explain the above statement.

In the west, we tend to think of this law mostly as it applies to concepts of opposition:

- positive and negative
- up and down
- good and evil
- republican and democrat

These divisions are due to two major problems with the western mind - it is both young in terms of the culture does not embrace wisdom gathering, and it is also divisive by nature in its sciences, religions, and politics.

These of themselves are not wrong, they just are lower states of vibratory consciousness. When we are children we are supposed to mark things in black and white, it is part of moral rearing and security.

But as we mature we tend to notice how the lines blur and the spectrum of white becomes a rainbow of colors and prejudices.¹ This is only natural, as we shall see later on.

But this does not show the above statement to be true, only remarks on the opposite idea. However I want to make this clear: this Law is not separate from the other Laws, as say a statute is from another, but is rather a particular expression of it, and in each Law one will find the other seven as well, all simultaneously (Conservation).

For example, the Law of Cause (Yin) and Effect (Yang). Or the Law of Evolution (Yang) and Conservation (Yin). Or Relativity (Yin) and Quantum Vibration (Yang). Take more abstractly linear math (yang) and non-linear math (yin).

This Law is so pervasive that it literally shows up everywhere. People marry, and even gay couples only form if one partner is more yin and another more yang.

Even in males and females, you can have a yin (effeminate) man and a yang (masculine) woman.

This Law is literally everywhere. Thus the Chinese named it the Tai Ji Tu or Grand Ultimate [Truth].

It is this reason why the Law of Polarity or Tai Ji Tu is at the center of the Bagua Dharma, forms its trigrams through binary math, and guides evenly the heavenly dharma of Karma that it corresponds to Fire, for Fire is illumination and represents life and wisdom itself. Theoretically speaking one yin (mind) is surrounded on both sides by two yang principles (Karma and Polarity) which are like father and mother to us all, as they are father and mother to Vedic and Chinese philosophy respectively.

But it is absolutely vital to remember: they are not two, nor separate from the other seven... they are One.

Electromagnetism

The ancient study of magnetism (yang) and electricity (yin) itself has historically been an example of divisiveness. It took thousands of years for western science to realize that the two are actually one force that is related via mathematical equations and field theory. Indeed within the field of EM study it is vital also not to just deal with them as one force (in the lab, not empirically as in electrician's work), but to also apply yin/yang theory to each. That is, in electricity there are positive and negative charges, and in magnetism positive and negative poles.²

This aspect of how things can be divided is, as we shall later see, an important aspect of the Law of Polarity. For now we shall not go too deeply into the two sciences which study one force (of the four). Instead I just want to briefly point out the interesting aspect that the positive attracts the negative and the negative the positive.³

It is as though the Bible's instruction, "Be fruitful and multiply," is a edict that cannot be escaped even at the center of things.

How is it that atoms do not collapse? Momentum, fields, weak nuclear force, and covalent bonding keep these powerful concentrations of the Law from collapsing inward (normally) and it is the interesting interactions between electrons and nuclei (protons) which produce the wide variety of phenomena that our mental eyes perceive.

Finally, I want to point out that even the concept of an electromagnetic wave (Vibration) is itself a duality, for it takes an **imaginary number (yang) to describe waves** in real (yin) space-time [yin and yang].⁴

Spin

One thing that was discovered in 19th and early 20th century chemistry was the concept of valence levels and therefore orbital shells which ultimately have to do with the "spin" of the particles in interaction. Now spins and orbitals are not a simple matter to discuss, but for simplicity let us suppose that we are just looking at a ball in space. If it were rotating in one plane, it could have only two spins: clockwise or counterclockwise.

Then again if it spun in another plane of the three, it could only spin up or down. Etc...

It is the combination of these various spins which comprise the Laws of Rotation and of Vibration (waves), which are related mathematically and conceptually by the idea of spin.

Thus the nature of a particle is to rotate and vibrate (have spin) and thus be a wave, creating the famous wave-particle duality that has boggled the minds of young physicians since the early 20th century, but is absolutely vital to the use of everyday technologies like semiconductors.

Yin Yang Theory

As one can see the concept could be applied from all directions. Heaven and Earth, which are all yang and all yin respectively could be likened to spiritual planes and physical planes, and our difficulty in reconciling them is part of our pre-programmed nature and also indicative of the innate beauty of the superstructure itself.

So let us define the five [known] rules of Yin and Yang, as set down by the gods of ancient days:

1. Yin and Yang oppose each other.
2. Yin and Yang create/hold one another.
3. Yin and Yang control one another.
4. Yin and Yang cannot be destroyed.
5. Yin and Yang can be divided forever into each other.

In these five rules we see the aspects of the Tian-Ren-Di mandate, all known medicine and physics, the Law of Conservation, Karma, and finally the principle of the Creation of the Universe, which is to say non-existent.

Some of the deeper concepts thus revealed:

- The beginning of Time is the End of Time:: there is no Time, yet we perceive it.
- Without consciousness there is no unconsciousness, that is without us there is no Universe
- Eternity is a moment of now, infinitely repeated all at once and never.
- There is no Big Bang except that which we choose to see by applying our minds; It All is still just one Dot.
- Chaos is not increasing or decreasing, except in proportion to the existence of organized principle (Life).

- Good and Evil are in exact proportion - it takes less energy to be evil thus there appears to be more of it (Relativity) but it is all equal.
- The only lasting happiness is in harmonizing Yin and Yang within us, and around us, including our minds between Heaven which guides our Fate via our Karma and Earth which is our lives in essence.
- All existence (matter) is opposed by non-existence (anti-matter)
 - This is the meaning of Light combating Darkness in spirituality.

FURTHERMORE, and more importantly we must distinguish clearly in ourselves and our surroundings the major division of Yin and Yang, that is to say between True Yin and Yang which create and False Yin and Yang which destroy.

Each is a part of nature and of our lives. But it is the Sagely ones who advance the True Yang and nourish the True Yin which will find the most Harmony in their lives.

The nature of True and False is itself, of course male and female or yang and yin. One must be careful not to associate women with evil, because as said before all people are born coming from Heaven with pure Yang, then mixed with True Yin. All living beings are endowed with these laws and none of us better per say than another - except by our choices and karmic sowing.

But we all contain the innate nature to perceive this Law and live in Harmony. I've known nicer, happier, purer retarded folk and more evil but technically sane and sound regular folk. This itself just goes to show how powerful the mind is and how dangerous to itself and to others if unaware and uneducated. Ignorance is a false yin principle that equally afflicts us all at birth and the only cure (yang) is knowledge (true yang) and wisdom (true yin).

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Add files

Comments

S RC

S RC

Oct 15, 2010

4-One may wonder how does one associate yin for one thing and yang another? Yin is substantial and Yang insubstantial. Yin is dividing and Yang is unifying. Yin is following and Yang is leading/lawful. Yin sinks and Yang rises. Yin nourishes and Yang pulsates. Yin consumes and Yang produces.

Reply

S RC

Oct 15, 2010

3 - Here please fight the urge to attach the meaning good and evil to positive and negative. You'll do it anyhow, but just be aware that you are.

Reply

S RC

Oct 15, 2010

2 - Interestingly enough in electricity one can have standing charges by themselves (in fact one must have more negative charges or electrons than protons to have matter) whereas in magnetism there are no monopoles. So how is the Law of Conservation upheld in the former case? Well protons are much larger than electrons, and obviously their combined weight must be equal. Moreover the combined weight of charged particles must equal that of the more numerous (than protons) and heavier neutrons which have no charge. Moreover the combination of all particles must be equal to the combined non-weight of all anti-particles. As to why charges can exist "by themselves" and poles cannot... clearly you are not getting the point: they are not by themselves... they are attached via fields to some particle somewhere else and in fact all particles everywhere, thus they are all poles all at once. As a matter of fact the poles of a magnet are really caused by these particles in solid matter projecting these relational fields everywhere. But the appearance of the monopole vs. dipole 'difference' certainly satisfies logical duality and satisfies our empirical and practical minds.

Reply

S RC

Oct 15, 2010

1 - As a matter of fact the rainbow, as you may know is a small aspect of the Electromagnetic spectrum, which is to say an infinitely long spectrum of vibrations akin to having endless musical notes (as only God could).

Unadvised Practices...

posted Jul 8, 2010, 11:12 PM by S RC [**updated Aug 5, 2010, 1:15 AM**]

Many sources say many, many things on spiritual meditation and cultivation. I'm here to tell you you can believe anything you want to believe, however there are pathways that I - and Liu I Ming, the 19th century scholar who wrote the Taoist Yi Jing - think are inadvisable practices... not only from a meditation and spiritual point of view, but from a Chinese medical point of view.

Why? Because the process of disease can be acute or chronic, quick or long standing. Qi that does not flow correctly in one way or another can lead to strange illnesses, mental, spiritual maladies, autoimmune problems, and even psychological disorders.

Qi is meant to flow in certain patterns and on certain clocks, albeit slightly different for each person, they are not meant to be reversed or countered. So it will be worth consideration to learn these pathways *before* starting your Qi Gong or yogic practices.

Now, the specific practices that are, in my estimation, not advisable are the following:

- Focusing your Qi in any one portion of the body repeatedly...
 - Dan Tian
 - Yin Tang (3rd Eye)
 - Pai Hui (point of 100 meetings aka 10,000 revelations)
 - Ming Men (DU4)
 - various chakras

- Sexual - tantric - practices, not Taoist Jing preservation, though without a good guide that is also unadvisable
- Speaking in Tongues or seeking the aid of various spirits
 - You do not know if you can trust voices and spirits, only the Source can be trusted
 - You do not know if you are under mass hypnosis - this is how cults are formed.
 - Perhaps one exception is praying to ancestors, which invokes honor and respect within oneself and is definitely a good vibration to be in.
- Pagan practices - not including Native Animism (Natives had a less ethereal view of the spirit world than Europeans, more akin to Qi and Shen); more like rituals of dogmatic servitude and sacrificial nature; idolatry, etc...
- Clinging to forms or to non-forms
 - Clinging to action or clinging to non-action [lit. doing nothing to avoid karma]
 - Asceticism or materialism/hedonism
- Worshiping idols or mandalas - not praying/chanting to or through, but actually treating the items as dieties, hoping for gifts of economic worth.
- Apathy, kafaism, nihilism, atheism, anarchism, satanism, or other isms based on rebellion or denial of responsibility
 - To rebel means to accept the structure of heirarchy and Power, thus why rebel? Only people with self-destructive tendencies would subconsciously harm their own Shen.
 - To pretend not to care is to deny humanity in oneself... usually these people have a serious Metal-Fire imbalance.
- Enlightenment through psychedelics - again, unless you have a Native Shaman to lead you.

All of these practices forgo the Real to seek the Unreal. Clinging to extreme paths or not holding to the Real, forgoing the True to let go of the False, therefore falling into eventual ruin either way. Damned if they did, damned though they didn't. Life is meant to be lived. **The Meaning of Life is meant to be sought and understood by everyone - that is the gift of consciousness and its responsibility.**

Placing Qi in certain places, the Yi leaves the mansion of the mind and tries to do the work of the people. This is like the Prime Minister usurping the Emperor, then trying to be the palace gardener or cook. Better to make the Yi serve the Shen, and in being hollow it can be filled with purpose from the Divine. Then the mansion is set in order, the servants do the bidding of the ministers, both of the mind and body, and the Qi flows to all parts of the body correctly.

Many people think that Qi Gong is for extending life and creating longevity. This incorrect belief is often the root of the problem. Those are the Side Effects of good, correct, Qi cultivation. Longevity is about proper living and thinking.

Life is prolonged by living in accord with the Will of Heaven - the Dao. This, as mentioned before is done by tuning the Yi, Hun, and Po to the ultimate Shen [of Heaven] and advancing Yang (righteousness and Truth). It is by this method that the Jing is preserved, and non-action given meaning [lit: spontaneous action].

To not act is itself an act, thus in trying to attain non-action one makes the folly of failing to receive the will of Heaven and act on that will (aka take inspiration and opportunities provided at face value and use them).

Correct non-action means not stepping before seeking, not answering before asking, not going without withholding and waiting a bit to see if one's actions are correct.

By utilizing the Harmony of Heavenly Vibration, actions become spontaneous, effortless, and meaningful... thus the Jing is no longer harmed.

By extending the Zhi (Will of one's Kidney-water), one burns the fire of life (Ming Men water-fire) and Jing-essence is harmed.

Diseases set in as a matter of course because the Jing is weak and the Qi is weak.

All because one's philosophies and practices were not rational. Having irrational philosophies of passion leading to extreme ends, and having irrational practices that go on despite the warnings of the body - headaches, impotence, incontinence or constipation, pain, insomnia, nightmares, sweats, etc... - is a sign of ignorance.

Better to seek a teacher who can show you a mild way, where you can attune to vibrations of Heaven, slow at first, and then building as one's power grows and one's understanding match it.

A higher teacher is not easy to find, especially the higher level you current are. If you are low in understanding, then seek the FIRST teacher that comes to you naturally.

But do not cling to their path too readily, unless they can harmonize the five elements, balance Yin and Yang, and obey the 8 Laws without trying to battle them - or at least actively work towards that goal (might be okay).

In the end bad practices, poor philosophies (dictated by their leading to the Meaning of Life or not; one Christian path may lead to it but not another, for example, not because of the Bible but because of the preacher's paradigms) are all representative of False Yin (consult the diagram) and definitely degrade the yang of body, mind, and spirit, ending in separation of yin and yang - and death - without attainment, often alone and in grief.

Even if one is disinterested in enlightenment, salvation, or greatness, one should be rapt with intrigue about the Meaning of Life... or else why continue to breath and eat and feel? Attainment is just this interest, by definition.

Yin/Yang Practicality part 3: Family Alchemy

posted Mar 29, 2013, 2:51 PM by S RC [updated Mar 29, 2013, 2:51 PM]

I won't go into terribly deep detail about why, just post a brief diagram, but Family Alchemy is both one of the most challenging and the most rewarding processes that exists. In this, I can say I have lots of experience, with some palpable successes, but I don't pretend to have all the answers. Not even an old man on his deathbed can have all the answers in this topic.

So why is it important? From the following diagram, one can see that Family Alchemy is the tie between the Mundane and the Spiritual branches.

As you can see, relationships are the crossing between the mundane "in the world" and the spiritual "beyond the world." This has a double meaning. Firstly it means that one's future Family prospects depend upon the successes one has (and others perceive) in a relationship; secondly it means that one can transform either relationships through the Family, or the Family through their relationships.

The double meaning of this "tree graph" is also that the Source can be had by studying the branches and leaves, and also studying the Source leads to the ability to transform these other areas, bringing them all into one species, that is namely one of emancipation, salvation, liberation, and the eventual wisdom that frees all species.

Let's talk about the primary thing that people do NOT know that they NEED to know in order to make any progress. Success in transforming a family wholly depends - if one doesn't know the process of Advancing the Yang - on one's position in the Family.

In general, everyone belongs to two sets of Fu Xi diagrams. The one as they grew up, and the one in which they are the father or mother (unless this has not happened yet and then Family Alchemy is made harder).

Belonging to the Pre-heaven diagram, one must rely on one's position in the family and Advancing the Yang; belonging to a Post-heaven diagram, one can use one's own family successes to align the above and below diagrams; thereby turn dysfunction into function. Both processes take time, patience, and consistent energy and a consistent Basis.

卦名	自然	季节	性情	家族	方位	意義
Name	Nature	Season	Personality	Family	Direction	Meaning
乾 Qián	天 Sky (Heaven)	Summer	Creative	父 Father	南 South	Expansive energy, the sky. For further information, see <i>tiān</i> .
巽 Xùn	風 Wind	Summer	Gentle	長女 Eldest Daughter	西南 South west	Gentle penetration, flexibility.
坎 Kǎn	水 Water	Autumn	Abysmal	中男 Middle Son	西 West	Danger, rapid rivers, the abyss, the moon.
艮 Gèn	山 Mountain	Autumn	Still	少男 Youngest Son	西北 North west	Stillness, immovability.

坤 Kūn	地 Earth	Winter	Receptive	母 Mother	北 North	Receptive energy, that which yields. For further information, see di .
震 Zhèn	雷 Thunder	Winter	Arousing	長男 Eldest Son	東北 North east	Excitation, revolution, division.
離 Lí	火 Fire	Spring	Clinging	中女 Middle Daughter	東 East	Rapid movement, radiance, the sun.
兌 Duì	澤 Lake	Spring	Joyous	少女 Youngest Daughter	東南 South east	Joy, satisfaction, stagnation.

The Basis is a philosophical construction; a framework. It can be a Christian, Muslim, Jewish, Education/Science based... anything works... if one follows the rules of the framework. I have used and prefer the Confucian framework, but typically speaking whatever framework most aligns with the current Family Paradigm will produce the fastest results.

For myself, when I look across the culture of America I see a culture acting without a basis, and so I picked a basis that is difficult and far afield from what I perceive as corrupt and decaying to something which does not decay. After the tsunami in Japan I think the Confucian model showed considerable universal qualities. If one is interested, please read the Analects and the Book of Filial Piety.

Now using this Basis, one extends a mental pole from one's position as a father or mother back up through one's Pre-Heaven position. Where do the two align? The joining of the two hexagrams will give one their first clue to the Unseen.

You see these trigrams correspond to Laws. Your incarnation in one or another indicates the law in which you are weakest in and need the most work. Example: I am the eldest

son of eldest sons, and the family males in my family all have Unresolved Heart Chakras. As eldest son, I correspond to Thunder or Action - the Law of Rotation; which is also Faith. Faith as a failing was definitely the issue before my transformation and why I was sent here. I was sent so that people would believe a person can rise from mud and despair to Sagacity. So that my father could believe and my son could enact. The Heart Chakra is the Christ... so Faith is also another way of aligning the Christ and fixing the family problems. Eliminating despair and darkness with Faith, gaining great Strength of an eldest son, returning to a throne of sorts by leading the family in Faith, etc...

Now, each position has its rules and its places inside the family which will hinder or help it. If one tries, for example from the position of the middle daughter to do the work of the youngest daughter or son, they will be unable to enact that joy in the same way; instead the middle daughter should clarify her position, and clarify the family. If there are others acting out of sorts, she should then help clarify them. She must use her special relationship with the polar opposite - middle son or River - to correctly and sincerely clarify. If there is disunion between any two polar pairs, then the first action in Advancing the Yang is to align these, and when two poles align then the diagram is not freely rotating in space, to the disaster of the Family.

On Advancing the Yang.

There are in general, two methods in Family Alchemy.

The first is having children, and being successful at the aligning of the father/mother poles. This means True Yin and True Yang - see the Relationships article... and in so doing the children align and the Pre-heaven diagram will also align as the parents then look upon one with wonder and love.

The second is internal advancement which is to say striving for a long time in unseen successes and darkness; without the Family aware, until one emerges as a Spiritual dragon, surpassing mother and even father in understanding, emerging when they are on the wane and one is waxing strong to a Full Moon.

Of the two methods, the Family method is preferable, the other is less because the latter produces more Joy.

Easy Question to arise: what if the family has more or less than the Noah Setup?

Quite typically a small 4 or 5 person family will simply fill the gaps... either through marriage, or the friends of the children. In a single child, typically this is very true.

In the case of a very large family, it is often the case that a sibling will form a parent-like relationship with another sibling... which means that that second level is twice removed from a position of power to Alchemically adjust the family's Fate, and likely should just move from a new starting point and leave the Pre-Heaven setup to the Eldest Son and Eldest Daughters.

Of the two, who is stronger? Actually they are equally strong, but there is the question of the alignment. If the eldest son is blocked, he should focus on his wife's position and make it clear and let her align the families... if the eldest daughter is blocked by a mother, she should allow the power of a true yang son (or son-in-law) to transform the families... if they have opposite blockages, then they should switch and eldest son/husband affect mother in law and eldest daughter (or wife) affect father(in-law).

If one is a middle child one should focus on aiding and not worrying about the lack of recognition. If one is a youngest there is less responsibility and more enjoyment; and one should use this unique position to alter the family in a positive direction.

Dealing with Difficult Family or Selfish Individuals.

As is oft the case, and it isn't surprising, there are black sheeps or just plain difficult people who will judge, put values upon oneself, or refuse to cooperate in the simplest of things, such as Family gatherings, holidays, weddings, funerals, etc...

In such a case, it may behoove a WISE person to use the 5 Elements to deal with their Elemental type - but only if one is sincere AND correct. Sincerity means selfless, and that the correction is to benefit the whole family (such as quieting a Wood or Fire type to avoid family embarrassment)... rather than just make oneself feel better. Correct means not mistaking the elements and further inflaming.

First study the above diagrams, and then when ready, move to the 5 Elements. However, the 5 Elements are a sublaw, and the greater power is in the upper 8 laws.

Let's move through the above exercise and then talk about dealing with difficulties. My position is eldest son, and father, So Thunder over Heaven: 34. Power of the Great "The great lines, that is, the light, strong lines, are powerful. Four light lines have entered the hexagram from below and are about to ascend higher. The upper trigram is Chên, the Arousing; the lower is Ch'ien, the Creative. Ch'ien is strong, Chên produces movement. The union of movement and strength gives the meaning of THE POWER OF THE GREAT. The hexagram is linked with the second month (March-April). [My actual birthday is in May]

THE JUDGMENT

THE POWER OF THE GREAT. Perseverance furthers. [meaning patience to the extreme]

The hexagram points to a time when inner worth mounts with great force and comes to power. But its strength has already passed beyond the median line, **hence there is danger that one may rely entirely on one's own power and forget to ask what is right.** [Sincerity] There is danger too that, **being intent on movement, we may not wait for the right time.** [impatience and arrogance in correcting the degeneration of father and mother] Therefore the added statement that perseverance furthers. For that is truly great power which does not degenerate into mere force but **remains inwardly united with the fundamental principles of right and of justice.** When we

understand this point—namely, that greatness and justice must be indissolubly united—we understand the true meaning of all that happens in heaven and on earth.
THE IMAGE

Thunder in heaven above: The image of THE POWER OF THE GREAT.

**Thus the superior man does not tread upon paths
That do not accord with established order.**

[again... Faith in a Basis; and not ignoring the established Basis of the Family]

Thunder—electrical energy—mounts upward in the spring. The direction of this movement is in harmony with that of the movement of heaven. It is therefore a movement in accord with heaven, producing great power. However, true greatness depends on **being in harmony with what is right**. Therefore in times of great power the superior man **avoids doing anything that is not in harmony with the established order.**"

What this is saying is that I must - in using the Confucian Basis - accord with the relationship between Father and Son that comes from Time Immemorial. Not correcting the father by arrogance but by compliment... reminding the grandson of his grandfather's greatness, the grandson is aligned with what is proper and humbled.

So in solving the Heart Chakra issue, all I must do is align the family in Faith. Which means following a Basis and never forgetting it.

Now, looking at the Elements, Thunder is Winter or Metal-Water. Metal corresponds to Justice. It is controlled best by Joy and Love of Fire - so remembering to Love more than inflict Justice/Punishments... and controls Anger of Wood-Fire; so it is powerful in uniting family and controlling; except if it uses such energy in which case it will be ineffective.

THIS has definitely held true in my own life. I cannot say how many times this has been the case, and it was a long time before I was heard and listened to in the least though I spoke way too often my opinion. But as soon as I accorded with the 5 Elements and my place, and ascended to my 'throne' as a father and Eldest Son, I was able to begin changing the family but not by force. They are wily and everyone has opinions... but in being able to help the health of family is a great win, and also in them accepting my position and respecting it... that is a larger win.

Changing family attitudes is a matter of forgetting the Past and embracing the Now. When people hold onto the past this produces Pride which is stubborn and fixated. This is the problem of Relativity... how many children can be the Middle Son? Furthermore what does it teach the kids.

If a person cannot have Power of the Great, they should seek to clarify their position, Advance the Yang in secret, and when they are a True Yang father or True Yin mother,

the family will align, and all will be well in Heaven (one's childhood family) and Earth (one's own family).

False	True	True	False
 life's gifts never enough judgmental and critical feeling lack in mind pensive afraid short-tempered (loss of stillness)			
Excessive desires "fetch the moon" or "pie in the sky" high expectations sexually frustrated increased beyond normal ambitions unaware of cyclic changes in biology addictions (following Wu xing cycle to early death) *note rot starts in men from bottom up	Listens to "gut" - knows Right Active, spontaneous Virtuous deeds Regulating the inside and the outside Harmonizing force Controlling appetites	 Still within Listens well, and understands well Considerate of fragile male ego Not arguing point-by-point, which excites male ego to more false yang Attentive to male needs, husband before children, father before all	henpecking hesitant does not exert power does not dissuade false yin from external sources out of sync vibrationally with male/yang force assumptions made impatient for change
<p>"When either side absent, borrow from "other" to regulate children *Read as "do this->result" *#11 Tranquility forms a mirror with each other's feet meeting *can be applied hetero/homosexual, all vibrational information *Created by Sf. Ramon and Arwen Careaga co-mutually to describe the effects of polar Human Mentality activity -When both people are True, this is Home Mind-of-Tao-</p> <p style="text-align: right;">(c) 2014 Arcangelprojects.com</p>			

Yin/Yang practicality part 2: Relationships.

posted Mar 24, 2013, 12:15 PM by Ramon Careaga [updated Jan 4, 2014, 2:38 PM by S RC]

26 Then God said, "Let US make mankind in our image, in our likeness, so that they may rule over the fish in the sea and the birds in the sky, over the livestock and all the wild animals,[a] and over all the creatures that move along the ground."

27 So God created mankind in his own image,
in the image of God he created them;
male and female he created them.

Aside from being a commandment, and a biological advantage... and a way to avoid loneliness... there are alchemical reasons for marriage on a spiritual level.

Before proceeding, some definitions.

'female'=yin>yang, yin!=female

'male'=yang>yin, yang!=male

This will avoid the trappings of gender, sexual preference etc... Successful couples, homo or heterosexual always come from a pairing of yin and yang.

[The other week I had an infertility case come in, the woman was really a man inside and unable to get pregnant, and the man was really a woman with an overly masculine body and a female disposition, including voice. They loved each other but the spirit level was blocking their attempts to make a baby as her body was unable to understand the reception of yin. Disastrous!]

The 5 sublaws of the Law of Polarity: infinite divisibility, mutual opposition, mutual generation, mutual consumption, mutual control.

Law of Resonance: those which are in harmony with each other produce true yang (light, love, justice, respect, happiness, etc...); those not in harmony (and forced to remain together) produce false yin (danger, turbulence, conflict, hate, resentment, guilt, shame, destruction).

There are a great many couples that struggle because they do not understand the purpose of this; but naturally they get together with the best of intentions.

My purpose is not here to shame or force anything, but illuminate the best possible outcome. Obviously everyone's relationships are in different circumstances, and the wisdom of the I Ching should be sought in order to understand YOUR particular situation. But the bottom line is that if people want to follow these laws to produce the greatest Cause::Effect and arrive at the Golden Mean where yang reduces excess without losing purpose and yin rises above Earth towards yang/heaven thereby becoming strong within... then it's important to really understand these laws in a practical way.

So... why produce Resonance? Resonance if produced will help one to do as the last post I wrote talked about and put Earth above Heaven within the body and prolong life; meanwhile leading to Settled and uniting two people into a loving frame of mind.

It saddens me to see the Divorce Rate so high. This means people do not know how to have an End only a Beginning. The Tao cannot be achieved in this way.

Do you have to be married to reach Completeness? No... but you still have to couple Yin and Yang, so it still works, whether you're married to God, to Gaia, to money, etc... the Laws don't stop flowing for whimsy. Only Sages will understand the natural implication herein about reversal. Once you master Karma (Cause::Effect) via Resonance, you can master the Law of Polarity. But if you do not know, understand, or cannot apply... then in the end there is nothing but frustrating mistake after mistake.

So, let's look in depth at each of these 6 axioms and talk about relationships.

Infinite Divisibility

Infinite Divisibility is the primary issue that arises that divides a couple from communing and being able to understand each other. Chasing the dragon, chasing the tiger tail... around and around the arguments go. When the false yang prevails, it begins to criticize and divide, trying (vainly) to match the dividing, diverting, subverting power of yin... thereby producing false yin (so fellas yeah it's usually your fault) which of course strips away the true yang of the relationship.

Why does this happen? Generally speaking Pride. Someone's ego became >> the 1 and this made them 2. That violates trust.

So, some rules regarding pride.

#1 - Fellas or 'males' ... your pride cannot exceed your humility. You can have pride, but if it exceeds the relationship, one's status, one's Reach or Power (karmic/caste), or exceeds the limits of propriety, of ability of yin to provide to... this will lead to the engenderment of pride in the female.

#2 - Gals... two things. #1 never try to match the pride of a (vain) male... it is both pointless and impossible. Do not try to over shout, strike, threaten, or otherwise use false yang that incites a battle of bulls between double false yang. #2 never, never, never cut the pride of your male.

Why do I say this? Why must the female be stronger? Because she is stronger. Who can bear children? Who can raise them for an entire life without tiring? Who can bear the pain and sacrifice all? Only the yin counterpart. The yang is too strong, adamant, and unaware. Also, the female must understand the male has something to lose.

The male genitals are the rod and staff of power... they are the key to family success, and male ability to control this is the family's success. But it is something that can be lost. If a ruler can lose, they cannot be as powerful. Hence the Queen is stronger than the King. The Queen should therefore - in the interest of her offspring, and family - seek to vehemently and territorially protect the King from invading forces.

If the male is unable to control himself, though, this is his fault, and nothing to do with the female not performing her duties.

It takes two to tango, as the saying goes. Therefore in infinite divisibility any division is of equal wrong-doing. If either steps out, the query becomes who did wrong first. Usually the problem occurred 5 steps back, and though I blame false yang, both individuals can incite false yang. Vanity and prideful words are false yang. Bad leadership, shaky decisions by either party will harm the Resonance and lead to division. So both parties must seek to retain Unity. Never going to sleep angry, destroying the Unity... always thinking of the counterpart as one's salvation, not because they ARE, but because understanding them and why we are obsessed with them and yet battle them will help us understand our other Self.

Mutual Opposition

Mutual Opposition means that the male and female will see things differently almost always. This means that most relationships being ended over disagreements are a matter of the danger of the Law of Relativity.

The Law of Relativity opposes Polarity. It is Water and Polarity is Fire. Those that understand both have the Luminosity of fire, those that see nothing but opposition have the danger of the Abyss of River.

Thus in a healthy relationship, the twain should seek to unify the point of view. This again should be led by the male. Often females complain of not being heard... and males recede. This is due to excessive 'henpecking' by the female and the shedding of responsibility by the male leading to weakness within the male and haughtiness or sullenness in the female; both false states.

Therefore the male or more powerful should guide the conversation from debate towards dialogue... break fearlessly through the frightening gap that forms over myriad issues... if necessary due to false yang (bad leadership or example setting) humble oneself and listen to the other. But though the male must needs break himself, the female must seek never to break the male. A broken male is useless. Would one break a corvette so one has to push it to work? A broken male is useless to all; and a stubborn female is immovable and submerges with Earth.

The discussion must go from division to enlightenment, to unification... and all roots of evil should be rooted out before passing another cycle where the darkness of the Void fills one's head with fears about the plots of the Other.

Hint: the louder you are, the less the Other can hear you. Males must become strong enough internally to not fear the attack of the females... and females must become strong enough to control their ability to break the males. On this all depends.

Mutual Generation

Mutual Generation means that they support one another.

Yang cannot nourish; yin cannot create. Therefore the two must respect the others' strengths... when children are born, any weakness in this will become readily apparent in the behavior of the children. If the children are not right, seek the fault in the parents. BOTH parents.

Mutually generating also means mutually protecting. Yin craves security and material; hence males should seek to provide a home, and goods for kids, to fulfill biological drives which are often stronger than ideas or words in the female mind. Yang craves movement, newness and peace; hence females should seek to be adventurous, riskier than usual, and always strive to smooth relationships between prides of father vs. grandparents, father vs. sons, father vs. brothers... etc... Controlling and smoothing the male pride, using the following sublaw for good will not emasculate but instead engender the inner wisdom in the male... replacing Youthful Folly with wisdom and experience. A wise male provides for family better and better until the female has cultivated his goodness to the point where he ensures her security ad infinitum. Thus controlling him by not controlling him; not using the human mind but the wise intuition of the True Yin, the female will ascend like a basket carriage below a hot air balloon. She who manages her home with wisdom; yet allows the male to Govern and never harms the Governance of the male will gain ALL and lose nothing not worth losing.

As for the male, he must need to sometimes withdraw the Fire and sometimes to apply it with white-hot-lightening and Thunder to the relationship and family. This is because the relationship between Man and God is like the relationship between a father and family; so goes the family, so goes the Country.

If a Man is afraid, he should not blame the 'henpecking' of the Other, but seek it in his own inner weakness and suspect his Original Sin obscuring his Original Self... and meditate thereupon. If it is karmic - dad was weak, etc... - then he must needs to find the source of the weakness and reverse it first, then couple. But if already coupled, then he must be patient and await the time to change the female's opinion of him which means expulsion, humiliation, guilt, shame... they must be accepted to lower false ego and pride, and then accept oneself where one is AT even if it is the bottom of a barrel.

The female must - if she be receptive and true yin - perceive with wisdom this process and allow it... and if she wishes to rise herself, stop shaming and instead encourage. Encouraging and even following she will rise above.

Remember Bill Clinton? His way of handling it and Hillary didn't leave him - the PRESIDENT OF THE US!!! - she was foremost in shame. Not even Jackie or Eleanor were so publicly shamed. Yet she never left him and she indeed rose back up beyond him.

This is mutual engenderment [note the word gender is in the word], and it is accomplished via true yang or respect. If the male wishes to lead thoroughly, he should disavow the human mind of conniving and scheming and simply BE true yang. That's

why the female chose him to begin with.... Just BE yourself... and work on yourself. Yang energy spent will come back to her and she'll come back to you.

Mutual Consumption

Mutual Consumption means that the two crave each other so much they will sap the other in an effort to sample, understand, and become like the Other.

In a pathogenic sense this means false yin subverting and false yang receding, even to divorce or fleeing into the afterlife.

"Who is at fault" is ever the bane of solving the false state. BOTH are at fault, it is equal in all ways.

HOWEVER as the cycle starts with yang, it is the male which must seek the solution. Through mismanagement, weakness, laziness, insecurity, the male will engender distrust and false yin and thereby receive false yang and this will consume true yang leading to a state of confusion, fear, anger, and as such, the male will seek to leave, blame, complain and do everything but ACCEPT.

This is faulty. In the female as well, there should be sought to understand what it means to reach the Golden Mean. the yin has further to reach to become yang... therefore why does the female strive so hard in life? First obeying parents, then 'husband' then children... always striving. Obviously to overcome the spirit's propensity towards the Earth; the material. Not a problem, do not feel guilty (false yin) ... simply APPRECIATE that the male is the external salvation... what makes him special? What attracted you? Was it mere biology? Are you driven by procreation? If not, then it must be spiritual... the whole world loves a male hero, sage, guru, athlete, movie star, president, etc... This is because the male connects one to father and then the Father. Understanding the Father, understanding the Self, solving the riddle.

As for the male, why for do you aggrandize yourself when there is the more marvelous thing to behold? Can you produce the child, nourish it... have the strength to patiently protect it all its life? Every father I've met wishes to disavow the child upon adulthood of responsibility and seek freedom - as is natural. But the mother never lets go... never forgets her responsibility. Appreciate her strength and seek to cross nearly over; but never leaving the yang behind. Understanding the female = understanding the world... understanding the world = understanding Samsara... understanding samsara = understanding Nirvana and the Self. Therefore the female is your external salvation since the female's property's and characteristics will illuminate your own faults and reasons for Earthly existence.

Thus the twain engender each other with love and enlightenment.

In fixing the false yin and false yang states, both sides must Repent. If he is faulty and unfaithful; what about you made him so? OR if you prefer, why are you attracted to faulty yang? If she is faulty and unfaithful, what about you is weak and unable to hold her and guide her chastity? Are you as good as you can be?

Resolving this problem leads to 10,000 benefits and earns the admiration of family, society, and God.

Mutual Control

Mutual Control means mutually governing. He is the ruler, she is the master.

What do I mean by she is the master? Surely God is the Master? Verily, she is the master because she seeks God more fervently. I see more women on the table stabilizing Qi... and more men in bars and wars... who is more angelic in practice? The male is born stronger in yang, but usually by age 30, it is reversed.

So in marriage, it is good for a male to first find himself, seek bodhi or salvation or both and then seek marriage for then he will admire his master as well as care for her like a rare flower. She may never fathom his depth but she'll admire it. And he'll cherish her for her Earth-like flowering all her life.

But let's suppose that a male mistakenly seeks the Other as a means to claim himself first... no problem. Then he must simply pay 3x the attention to his mistakes and be patient and accept the false yin that is reflected on her as being from within him. She can still pull it from him - as easily as she does anything else. She is the master; and he should let her be master who wants to be happy. The male mind is feeble, blocked by desire for lusts, power, greed, and vanity. It is moreover prideful. Finally, the male brain is linear in a cyclical world (lit: ruled by Rotation)... and is unable to wisely see many things at once but needs time to pass to perceive it; unless he takes time to train and learn transcendent thought. Still the female brain is marvelous and can hold multiple conversations at once, never missing a syllable and memorizing many things. Sadly it is marred with one fault above all in that it is passionately in love with the human mind. It loves his human mind; if she can train her mind to love his enlightened mind, then she will be a great Queen above all other vixens and he'll never think twice about leaving her dominion.

So at any rate there is no time before death that a male cannot fix his issues. There is no time before divorce that a female cannot control him just 'so' that he uprights himself. Yet she should be wary of her own power and not seek to harm the male pride nor harm the relationship between male and God. If she wants her King to bring all the world to her; why harm that relationship?

And if a male wants to give - as is most commonly why men are so Romantic according to studies - and isn't just trying to TAKE as most false yang is... then he should seek the wise rules of Governance and observe nature and observe God.

See how the birds and mammals mate and court? The male must work hard... God gave the male excess yang to be used... not to be wasted in vanity. Let the male shine like a Cardinal or Peacock... but the male should hide that shining in the presence of the female and aggrandize her - especially before children, causing them to learn the rules of society and good behavior.

Meanwhile she should vaunt and applaud the male at every corner, allowing him to avoid the pride of aggrandizing himself... she can therefore spread his fame and help her sons achieve fame and daughters meet true yang males rather than the myriad, wasteful refuse found in bars and clubs wilely selling/peddling their sperm for a cheap one-night-stand instead of true communion! The female who sees this is a Sage already. The male who sees this will meet a White Lotus.

Law of Resonance

Thus we come to the Law of Resonance after delving into Polarity in depth. Where do we stand? Honestly? Can things be better? Always... is it a little or a LOT? It should be discussed.

In creating such discussion, the leader of it should be wary of philosophy in excess unless the Other be philosophically endowed.

AH here is a problem... growth. If one grows ... especially outgrows or grows in a different direction... how to achieve Resonance?

Then the wise one will return to Vibration (drawing upon the potentials of Conservation-Source)... proceed to turn the wheel of Rotation, and then enter Polarity (discussion) with wisdom and self-righted purpose.

It is possible to be in resonance at difference levels... but is it sincere? Hard to know. Sometimes males just need to be older as they aren't mature. Sometimes though it is purely about control and such a male can never understand.

So it is important if one grows alone to then come together and unite/commingle and therefore entangle yin and yang. EVERY-TIME. The longer one waits, the worse the disharmony gets.

Whose responsibility? Both. Naturally.

So back to where we stand... if there is more to do, then it should be done with Resonance, as that produces true yin and true yang. True yin is the nourishment of love (such as good sex) while true yang is the governance of true yin (such as respect). Producing these, the couple will appear special, and be placed in a special category, as those unable to be detained by bad luck and society. They will conquer all. The male will remember he wisdom. The female will remember his firm strength. The male will seek to be flexible. The female will seek to shield his Honor.

These properties mutually co-mingling will lead to prosperity, greatness of servitude -for children and friends and family will esteem virtues and seek to replicate them, and so goes society. Those who ignore the laws and sublaws will end up in a downward spiral, wasting years of good profit.

It doesn't have to be perfect. Just >50/50. 50/50 means no progress. Progress requires great forward struggle until nonstriving is reached... and then the difference between male and female will end and the marriage will be a true friendship. Throwing such a thing away... this is folly and sorrowful. One has to start all over again after getting strength renewed. And introspection is required. But as they say Who can ride the Dragon?

Mount the laws and YOU and they can both ride the dragon together,
~Shifu

The Creationists' Theory of Evolution

posted Aug 23, 2013, 1:03 PM by S RC [updated Feb 15, 2014, 4:15 AM]

From the study of Biology and Neuroscience...

When Darwin expounded his theory of evolution, centered around the ideas of natural selection and species dominance through niches, it rocked the world of science and of religion. Indeed, if he had written it 100 years earlier, he might have been flayed and crucified. But it came at the right time, during the culminating apex of the Enlightenment period.

Although much of what came from that period has been overturned, including many of Darwin's ideas, it was a historic time when we thought we just about knew everything worth knowing. It was then that the idea that there was no more room for religious points of view to obscure inquiry came into being. Religious ideas were pushed out of colleges of science and left to rot miserably in theology schools and in humanities courses, which of course only foolish sociologists and psychologist majors take. The **real** science was to be done in math, biology, physics, chemistry, and engineering.

Or so we thought.

Now, in the last 20 years, groundbreaking research into fractals, **self-replicating designs**, complexity and chaos, as well as the use of fMRI and unique, less-biased research models are proving that strange phenomena such as psychological transference and instantaneous information transfer across large distances are not only throwing all

that 20th century bias out the window... they are revealing startling aspects of the Universe we thought we'd laid to bed.

In this article, I will explore the middle-ground between the dual camps of creationism and evolutionary theory. A place that should have been thought of by scientists perhaps over 80 years ago, but the research of quantum mechanics had not yet tended towards the infinities that it does now, and back then the idea that man could know and see everything, was still widely believed. But when your **visible world shrinks to 4% or less** in a matter of two decades, the scientific mind begins to harbor new doubts about the promise of deduction and rationalism.

What is Evolution? What is Creationism?

The Science Delusion

Evolution is merely nothing more than the statement that the Universe is in constant flux and nothing remains the same, perhaps not even constants nor equations. There is startling physical evidence that even the speed of light may be relative, depending on the mass consciousness of the scientists reviewing it!

And really, we all know this is true. No matter how much a Creationist or preacher may want things to be the same, the facts are nothing stays the same. Preachers lament often the changing landscape of the business of churchgoing, and of the history of Christianity; its trials and tribulations.. Right there it dangles in front of them: the solitary fact that nothing remains constant, not even dogma or theology. It would be funny, perhaps, to imagine a modern preacher trying to explain salvation to Abraham or to Moses or Noah, if they could speak at all. Their worlds are as different from ours as a whale from a salmon. There is almost nothing the same except certain timeless values that make religion viable as a teaching tool: compassion, love, wisdom, patience, etc... So why anyone in an age of cell phones, internet, TV, and airplanes would want the scientific opinion of a people who were trying to explain creation to youngsters around a campfire over 6,000 years ago is quite astounding. It simply makes no sense. The insistence that it does indicates more of a failing of our modern education system to adequately and thoroughly explain evolution as God's natural method than it has any bearing upon the reality of Evolution itself. It must have been tremendously difficult for Darwin's views to get hold outside the academic world, and perhaps people even wanted to kill him for his pretense. The suggestion that we are derived from monkeys is still one of the most contested topics between the two camps.

I want to lay that story to bed for both parties. We are not derived from monkeys. Our species evolved from apes, but they were not human until some two hundred thousand years ago. But more on that later.

Remember

You are not a body with a mind and soul, you are an infinite soul with a mind and body.

Your humanity is not derived from DNA. It is a cosmological birthright.

Yes, our species originated even in the see as a kind of worm-like creature, but that is no more human than it is dog-like. Being human has nothing at all to do with our historical evolution. Creationists can lay aside all quarrel for the moment - I will in time prove here and argue that we are in fact unique forms of creationism at play. But it doesn't change the fact that our species has an evolutionary history on this planet. Before we came here to this planet, this species didn't exist, and its predecessor was more or less nothing different or special.

It was, like any prairie-dog, coyote, lion, or zebra just another animal trying to remain alive and in tune with its environment. Subjected to hidden laws and principles that one moment would provide love and embrace, and food, and the next death, dismemberment, and endless lifetimes of pain and struggle.

The mass consciousness of the tribes of homo-erectus that migrated out of Africa may have been semi-aware, we cannot tell, but for sure their consciousness was very different and not human at all.

What defines a human is three things:

- Instiable curiosity and inquiry
- Imagination
- Balance

I add balance here to point out that there is no other species or object on the planet, save water itself, with the balance of yin and yang properties that humans have. Mountains are too firm, and so erode away stubbornly and with much reluctance. Insects are too yang-like and so live short, trite, meaningless lives, and whose main purpose is the service and pro-generation of plants and predators... even each other.

Only the human species has the unique opportunity for outward reflection, inward reflection, and reflection upon the method of reflection. We can attain Zen, and solve complex problems like Calculus, or how far away planets are that surround stars, and even see invisible matter's silhouettes, and super black holes. What profound adaptability!

So it is a bit insulting, an evolutionary biologist must admit to say that our DNA is not so different or special, that we have no soul, and that we are just advanced species. We are not just advanced, we are spectacularly over-advanced, far more capable to survive anywhere than any other species (save maybe roaches). We are capable of going into space itself. To my knowledge something only accomplished by one other species and it certainly isn't building space shuttles!

So what gives; why the difference? Why would one species, alone out of the entirety of the world, not only adapt to become dominant, as homo-erectus did, but even become super-dominant? And how has it managed to survive and not be plunged entirely into self-destruction. What tools were made to handle the extreme power that was unleashed by full consciousness?

Consciousness is the Key to Evolution

There are species on this planet which do not change in design very quickly. Indeed, sharks have had the same basic design for over 500 million years. Snakes and birds have changed since the age of dinosaurs, but not by an amount that lends to super consciousness. Could you imagine an ostrich walking around giving lectures, or studying its ancestry/geneology back 20 million years, running DNA swabs? Surely birds, mammals, reptiles, fish and especially amphibians have evolved. Australia, Galapagos, and the African Rift Valley are notorious places for demonstrating the capacity for change. But you don't find any Einsteins there. The entire idea is preposterous. Dolphins and Gray Parrots may be on the verge, but they have a long ways to go to reach the place Cro-Magnon reached and begin flint-knapping. The dolphin may find fire a bit of a struggle, and the parrot has no thumbs... I hardly think we will be receiving any lectures on pan-species ethics from Flipper anytime soon. We're more likely to learn from ourselves in relation to our studies of intelligent species of dogs, elephants, apes, baboons, and whales, and to challenge ourselves to be better guardians and encouragers of evolution, than to receive direct instruction from nature.

So looking at it, I'd like to point out that perhaps it isn't the **push** of evolutionary need, or natural selection and mutations, etc... which have furthered us. But instead the **pull** of a vacuum. Perhaps it was the lack of a dominant, benevolent, balanced species on the planet. And perhaps it was merely the happenstance that homo-erectus was the most ready and available *husk* of species that provided it. Can you imagine, though, one day the ape tribe is walking around, silently pulling bits of grass and berries when little Johnny, barely out of his teens (in ape years), stops and grunts to the herd, "Hey, maybe we should try hunting," or "Fire sure is warm."

Such revolutionaries of the species are the Buddhas and Stephen Hawkings and Ghandis of their own time. It must have been pretty astounding when through play, a pair a competitive, but friendly adults discover that not only can we smash stones together, we can shape them... and then we can shape them into something **sharp**. That idea... where did it come from? Even the crow which utilizes the hardness of the ground and the power of gravity to crack snails and nuts has not thought of this idea. Sharpness, what an ingenious concept. The use of it perhaps is only exceeded by the power of fire, leverage, and roundness.

So if pulling from a vacuum encourages growth, does pushing take a back seat? Our intuitive, meditation based religions would say no. In fact, the voices of oracles, of God, and spirits can be heard all around us. They may be coming from Dark Matter we have no idea. **But we do know that they have solved a number of key ideas in our own evolution:**

1. Antibiotics and vaccines
2. String Theory
3. X-Rays
4. DNA shape
5. Synthetic Dye
6. Rubber
7. Plastic

All of the above were discovered through intuition, by dream, or by pure accidental play. And the list grows and grows. While our ability to think is clearly very important, or else we would not have evolved with both a frontal and a pre-frontal cortex, it is our capacity to remain in the Now that has enabled us to become masters of our own destiny and of other species' destinies.

So these voices of encouragement, do they come from God, the Tao, spirits, or our own internal primal nervous systems?

Turns out that perhaps all of the above are connected.

We can surmise that there must be encouraging outward forces of benevolence from the first three, because we are not the only species that has innovation, intuition, and in fact, there are even examples of different species co-evolving for mutual habituation. I do not mean that they actively are molded by a master, as we do with dogs and pigeons. I mean that the bee, or moth, or bird co-evolves with a specific flower or tree to use each other and form a symbiotic relationship that cannot be rivaled even by the closest relationship between man and man's best friend, the dog.

Where the relationships, for example, between fox and bear, or birds and water-buffalos, or different birds raising each others' young come from... or other complex ideas such as building nests that hang precariously from tree branches (as opposed to in the nooks of branches which are available), simply cannot be explained by the mere concept of niches and need. There is no need, per say, for these relationships to develop, though there is benefit derived. But how can two different, semi-conscious species come to a conclusion together, no one can explain without the idea of either a spirit world where totem animals convene in council together, or of the gentle insistent voice behind intuition. While the fox may find it a stellar idea to hang out with a bear, certainly the bear won't find the situation at all to his liking. Yet, together they remain. And as for less seemingly sentient species, such as flowers, how is it they come to decide to adapt to manipulate certain species of bee or moth? To the exclusion of others, in fact. Is there some sort of contract signed in the spirit-world?

The evolutionist laughs, but they come no closer to answering it except to make up wild theories which merely show the ingenious methods by which the Divine Creator activates the benevolent, patient work of true engineering and design.

While we must scrounge up rare metals and oils, dig beneath earth and harvest electricity to produce boxed, plastic, soulless equipment... the Creator is able to produce caves of wonder while simultaneously guiding the instincts of trillions of species, not including the cosmos itself and its species. All through self-replicating design, and self-replicating principle.

And He still finds time for us, our needs, and to instruct us daily. Renewing us when we seek Him out, but allowing us our free will (as willful children do need). What astounding Virtue is the benevolence of Heaven. A clock made to run forever (or is it?), without direct sign of its creator, merely for the purpose of testing our faith in the Creator's existence.

Every other species is either super attuned to the cosmic buzz so that when a volcano will erupt they all scatter long before it happens... or blissfully unaware of the vengeance of God. While we are meant to struggle and come to grips with what is happening around us, to us, and between us (and nature).

This uber-consciousness has enabled our species to adapt far faster, meet more stringent demands, and still remain able to rear offspring, love, dream, and have leisure. We are driven from within to model the Creator and to create boundlessly, perhaps for His amusement (is He dreaming us?), perhaps our own (are we dreaming each other?). Yet we don't understand the why of it, as a species, and participate in this strange new techno-evolution no more aware of its power over us (with ideas, ethics, laws, morality, and ambitions) than the gazelle is aware of why their herd goes this way or that, or why the lion eats them.

But the uber-consciousness is clearly the prime culprit. It gives us incredible imagination, curiosity, and logical skills to combine with inductive reasoning which gives us the answers when we cannot fathom the new, the dark, the unattainable.

Evolution: A Divine Purpose?

Could all the pull of the Mind be for a purpose beyond our own gratification. I think most scientists with little imagination would already be reluctant to acknowledge the above, and scoff completely at the idea here. But most Creationists would love to know more if they could let go of the human idea of staticness. Ergo, I know that this is a middle-ground.

Both sides will, blissfully ignorant (or not so blissfully as the case may be for the prideful) or wisely in tune or otherwise have to admit there does seem to be a trending direction. What that trend is for is not easy to guess.

It may pay dividends at this point to revisit the time when our species came into being, and that difference that came from us.

But first I want to say that while all of the above I unapologetically state as fact and Truth, all that follows is mere conjecture, albeit based on some research.

It turns out that it isn't just that complexity creates consciousness. As a matter of fact, we know that all around us the complexity we see is a delusion of data. A holograph. Which means that the space we're occupying either isn't space at all, or is a virtual simulator, or both.

If it is a virtual simulator, then this leads to the idea that the Physical Plane (brane) upon which all the information is being projected is kind of a video-game (perhaps the source of our fascination with video games?). In which our bodies become, once again these machine-like weaponry which we upload into our consciousness and our soul atom powers.

If this is the case, then the answer to the why of our evolution is easy. We have a more powerful consciousness than we have machinery, and our needs, to match our powerful minds which are sort of floating around in the Dark Matter or some other ether are waiting for advanced enough machinery to arise that we can use. The early pioneers must have merely discovered the species by accident - not through some UFO craft (as there is no real archaeological/physical evidence to support UFOs), but by floating by. The early pioneers entered within, and most of their powerful consciousness would be unable to be used, and hence the insistent, persistent voice of intuition (coming from ourselves).

Our DNA would be modified by need, driven by biological urges at the behest of natural law, but with the bonus of consciousness driven rather than randomized mutation. Rapid changes would allow for more and more pioneers to arrive. And now they are arriving, by droves. We are terra-forming the planet to suit our needs, or perhaps the needs of a technological society, ala Krypton. Or is it that the vision of a Krypton like planet the memory of these data beings are re-incarnating? And is the nightmare of the Apocalypse the terrors of beings that either came from the earth and evolved upwards by being in our midst or our own people that came to love the Earth itself?

What about the purpose, if it be purposed? Is this a benevolent changing we are inflicting upon the planet, to guide it to something magnificent as our leading scientists believe and money-driven merchants push for? Or is it merely us being like a mold or yeast that consumes all resources, having a grand party of technological conscious-driven exploration, using up everything and then floating off to find new planets? We are, after all, already trying to locate new earth-like planets!! Giving up are we on the party here, before the remainder of the horde arrives?

Or is it that we will spread our genius, and our purpose to another Earth, through the ethos, flying at the speed of light, fulfilling an angelic purpose of raising the consciousness of species there?

Whatever the answer may be, it has become clear that we can no longer ignore the fact that consciousness creates, binds, and guides the Universe. Gone is the cold, dead, mechanical world. Mind, body, and soul are inter-connected. As to what we do with this wisdom, whether we wake up to it as a species or continue to act like a half mad-with-ambition and half-drunk cocktail party group, is really something we'll have to see. For many of us old souls with highly evolved senses of ethics, it may all be a bit frustrating. But as always, we'll have to await things with patience, guiding the deer like minds and the lion like minds equally, reminding them of the beauty of the perfect Tao, the Mind of Tao, and how we are indeed a special creation of Yin and Yang balance with magical powers... of time travel (through memory and projection), of telekinesis (we can move mountains now by will and chemistry), of alchemical ability, of study of the cosmos, of art, and music, and many more things. This is the excitement of such a job: it seems there is never an end to the angels/bodhisattvas' work. No end, means no reason to suspect our niche is running out. And from an evolutionary perspective, that means plenty of stability and resources for us. :)

-Shifu Careaga

Law of Resonance

posted Nov 9, 2011, 8:13 PM by S RC [updated Feb 3, 2013, 12:58 PM]

I hope your ears are cocked and set to receive. This Law, this little understood law is the secret answer to the studies of Vedics/Buddhism, Daoism, Judeo-Christianity, and physics and what it reveals .

Here it is: resonance (harmony or rhythm if you prefer) creates Yang. Naturally that means that being out of resonance creates Yin.¹

To understand this, one **must understand Yin and Yang.**

Anything that is solid, divisive, and substantive corresponds to Earth, the Physical Plane and Yin itself. Yin is the Physical Plane. For in life, the ultimate of yin one can be is dead and return to the earth. In this way one loses the fire of life. The soul, which is Yang, returns to "Heaven" or the Spiritual Plane. The mind ceases to exist separately, and as for the individual's stream in the physical plane, there ceases to be an intersection of the triple plane. Only the soul remains, since the physical plane is ever changing, and the body rots and goes away.

Yin and yang are difficult - slippery - to discern. As soon as you catch one, it divides. For most things, you really only must separate true yin and yang from false yin and yang.

	true yang	false yang
true yin	health, harmony, and happiness (love)	a fool waster of energy

false yin	yang consumed, shortened life think dead poets and geniuses and musicians	criminality hatred Hell itself
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In the physical plane, this law appears to cause problems, ala destruction of bridges if resonance is too great, but actually destruction of the material is just yin transforming into yang (no form). But commonly we all know harmony, in the proper quantity to be quite pleasing. All of our electronics, music, and indeed every relationship are guided by this single seemingly unimportant Law.

Every conflict or agreement, is Resonance in action. If one wants to change a situation... any situation... just evaluate the frequency you are in, and adjust to the frequency (vibe) you want to be in.

Sure that may mean:

- swallowing pride
- forgiving painful past histories
- forgetting grudges
- paving the road for getting rid of all old debts
- admitting faults

But it's all about what **you** want. The central stream is of One Mind, and has infinite potentials at your disposal. Of course as you age, and your yang wears out you become "sclerotic" or harden in your opinions, points of view, and even physical body.

So let's break this down using a specific circumstance. An all too common circumstance and important one (given the Meaning of Life): relationships.

In the beginning a couple may be hot and heavy, super-in-love, and have nary a disagreement. This is the fire stage, and since love is yang, is a sign of resonance.

If this remains relatively strong, yin and yang of the relationship combine, and yin and yang of the egg and sperm unite and this melding produces a new life - the birth of new worlds and new possibilities. The endless flowering it is called.

Now, suppose though that for whatever reason yin and yang do not keep up with their duties to retain resonance. It could be that they get into different interests, work different schedules, or one goes rotten, or both, or one cannot flex to mold to the other. Or both do it. Whatever the case, the result is anti-harmony, and therefore yin. The subjective world begins to tremble, problems arise manifold, and one's own vision of the issue becomes more separate/divisive. This is a part of the evolutionary process, but in some cases may be the exact opposite of what we desire in our hearts and our minds.

So many people fight relationships ending hoping to recapture love... this ignores the Laws. Instead if one desires Love, then let him/her work with their partner to create Harmony. Love is a byproduct of Harmony. God loves us all the more when we are harmonious with Him (the Data Source). So all the more that we want something, all the more that we should seek Resonance with our surroundings.

That doesn't mean to harmonize with everything. Harmony with false yin and yang, as mentioned in the Law of Polarity article, will result in undesired effects based on attraction. But, so long as one remains "correct with Heaven," then one can use this Law to ASTOUNDING effects. Why?

Because this Law also precedes Karma in the cycle of Heaven. That means that our Resonance or lack of is directly responsible for our subjective feeling of punishment or reward. It is OUR choices and actions, not the Law of Cause:Effect that generates our future. This takes the fatalistic feeling out of Destiny, and puts it squarely where it belongs: in our hands. It is our responsibility to create and harmonize with our own world, and with what is "right" (according to your understanding and culture). When we choose not to be in Harmony, that is a decision we must make with full understanding.

In the last article I mentioned that my own choices in a matter produced ill effects. That was a choice made with full cognizance of the Law. The results were mystifying, but of course, useful towards the Divine Plan, whatever they felt like to me. But making the choice purposefully did not lessen the sense of pain in the results, instead it enhanced it. The Law of Relativity in action, of course.

But, with a sense of calm, timing, and with the protection and blessings of a benevolent One Mind, truly I was not harmed, and was given some test to fulfill. If one cannot follow these ramblings at all without context, let me sum it up:

Ignorance of the effects, or of the Law does not eliminate the Karma... but IF one knows this Law one has the ability to - during conscious actions at least - create beautiful music out of one's own life. So long as one tries earnestly to understand oneself, s/he has the opportunity to modify everything:

1. Paradigms
2. Thoughts
3. Emotions
4. Habits
5. Results (favorable or unfavorable, on average)
6. and ultimately the Experience itself.

The key is conscious modification and programming oneself to behave subconsciously ALSO as one wishes.

In short, the Law of Resonance is our key. It is the ONE LAW that should be thoroughly memorized, studied, and practiced. Harmony with everything we seek. If we wish for something, we should seek first to modify our vibration to match that which we seek, love, friendship, careers, dreams, etc... and THEN can we earnestly and humbly ask for it.

If one can believe and accept this with all one's heart, then all the Laws fall away and there remains only our ever higher evolving stream and enlightening vibration. This is why it is the Lake trigram... the path to ultimate Joy.

Ayurveda and Chinese Medicine

posted Nov 22, 2011, 1:22 PM by S RC [updated Nov 22, 2011, 2:13 PM]

Given the fact that after Africa, India is the largest colonizer of cultures in the entire world, with influences in everything from religion, Latin, to music, it is no surprise to learn that Chinese Medicine has been influenced, to a great part, by India's own indigenous Ayurveda, the "balance of life."

To be sure, both have ancient roots. One thing unique to Chinese Medicine is its use of dualistic yin/yang principles to a high degree and of the channels. But Ayurveda itself is almost assuredly the stronger, historically, of the folk and herbal medicine. While they did not have acupuncture, what they lacked in channel theory, they made up for in acupressure and a deep understanding of nerve pathways, bone setting and other interesting techniques like "mud scan" which can tell them what areas have problems beneath the skin in the musculoskeletal system, and interestingly enough refinement of poisons and sharp crystalline minerals to the point where they are ingestible.

Strictly speaking, such medicinals must, of course, bio-medically damage the body. But so do parasites, and they have been shown to be useful - as any draining technique is - in treating excess. Poisons and minerals have long been used in both medicines, to great success in treating mental disorders and parasites, and especially the idea of "latent" pathogen, whether they be spirochetes, herpes, hepatitis, cancers, parasites, or old hot and cold pathogens from exposure (heatstroke, hypothermia).

So let's make a tabular comparison of the two medicines of these two great, and heavily populated countries.

TCM	Ayurveda
China	India
5 elements/phases: Earth>Metal>Water>Wood>Fire	5 elements: Air>Fire>Water>Earth>Ether

Meridians	Srota
DU20, Yin Tang, 3 Dan Tians, DU4, RN1	7 chakras: crown, 3rd eye, throat, heart, solar plexus, sacral, and root (kundalini)
Use poisons, minerals, and animal parts*	Uses poisons, minerals, jewels, and emetics.
2600 years of documented texts	3500 years of palm leaf texts
12 animal lunar astrology	12 constellations stellar astrology
Constitutional Type	Doshas
Folk massage (tuina), bone setting, gua sha, cupping,	Folk massage, bone setting,
Shen (psyche), and scalp, and ear acupuncture	Surgery, cosmetics, and psychiatry
Moxibustion (for more than sexual stuff)	Aphrodisiacs and Tantra
Qi Gong & Taiji (Tai Chi)	Yoga

As anyone can see, both medicines have excellent diversity and modern applications, and a long track record. However, two things distinguish the practice as it is performed in America. Number one, because of its use of toxic minerals, Ayurvedic herbalism is less accepted in the west, and the license is less powerful than the Acupuncture/OM license, because our license does not allow the use of so called "unacceptable or outdated herbs." Chinese Herbs are screened when manufactured in America and are generally cleaner than Chinese and especially, Indian supplement herbal products which have been shown to be containing arsenic, lead, and mercury.

Number two: there is a larger, and more accessible medical library in English, and therefore case studies and reviewable adverse effects for both patient and modern, western practitioner is simply easier for the Acupuncturist than Ayurvedic Herbalist. As it is, none of the puncture, bone setting techniques are licensed by HHP for Ayurvedic practitioners. Nor is use of emetics or poisons, whether they happen or not.

Regardless there is no doubt, and it is proven in the 3000 herbal pharmacopea in China, that India is the "mother" medicine. It is powerful and useful, even if not given the same credence and respect that Chinese Medicine is earning today in the west.

Diamond Alchemy

posted Mar 29, 2013, 3:07 PM by S RC [updated Mar 29, 2013, 3:44 PM]

Diamond in this case means impenetrable or indestructible. The hidden meaning is 100% Alchemy. 100% doesn't mean 100% of the time... it means 100% of everything reflects some level of understanding and some level of alchemy progress.

Every situation has a hexagram, which means a work. Every relationship or concept... everything cognized has a place.

When this is understood there is nothing that can keep one from practice. 1000 Mundane matters become 1000 Spiritual Matters.

Everything crosses from one to the other. The Small is the Great, and the Great is the Small. One's attitude in spiritual matters becomes one's attitude in life.

The Judgment becomes the Image and the inner the outer. When the inner becomes the outer, then the Diamond is hardened from coal. Meaning that the mundane and sooty world is transformed into clarity.

What does this mean?

A diamond is hard, precious, and can cut all substances. Cutting is its property of getting to Truth. hardness is its 100% Truth affirming property. Preciousness means it is hard-earned and should not be given too freely.

It should be available to all persons and yet should not be thrown away.

A diamond is a rare material, as compared to coal or dirt. This means it is rarely done as compared to all other people; that is seeking and especially attaining Truth. Doing so makes one a precious treasure and one should appreciate oneself for this, and not give oneself too freely or else the gem can be stolen - especially if one has only entered the emerald, ruby, or sapphire state.

Lotus Sutra

Manjushri suppose there is a powerful wheel-turning sage king who wants to use his might to subdue other countries, but the petty rulers will not heed his commands. So if he sees any time his [military] have won battles he rewards them [heavily] giving out [precious objects]... Only the bright jewel in his topknot he does not give away. Why? Because this one jewel exists only on top of the King's Head, and if he were to give it away (freely), his followers would be certain to express consternation and alarm.

When he sees a truly great soldier among his men, the king is so delighted, he takes that unbelievably fine jewel that has been in his topknot for so long and has never been recklessly given away, and now gives it to him. The Thus Come One does this [for the mahasattvas].

All stones like these are rare and precious, but few are as precious as well as unbiased and clear as a diamond. Being unbiased, one has no greater love for one alchemical process than another; even if one has greater love for say one's family than one's job. One treats them all with unflinching honesty, progress, and applies the Fire as is appropriate.

What is the Fire?

There are two ways to make a diamond: gravity+pressure and light+pressure. Gravity and pressure creates heat, and this heat removes defilement (from dead corpses) and soot and alters the chemical shape (alchemy) into a clear and impenetrable object.

Light from a laser adding pressure pushes the heat into the substance and transforms it from within.

Both processes result in a Fusion-like process. What separates this from a fission-like process is that after the Ember is formed, fission leads to separation and irradiation and eventually darkness. While fusion leads to a self-sustaining ember that even after destruction forms an ultimate diamond.

A diamond in space is still hard and perfect, and if light is applied it will diffuse it and if thrown by a quasar it will not be destroyed no matter how far it goes.

The diamond process will transform one from a weekend warrior sort of Alchemist where one's spirituality is only had in church, or in reading, or in tantric sex or taking LSD... to the sort where the Mind of Tao is everywhere.

When this is true and every single little thing is a big deal; then one can transform any defilement within into a virtue. Then everywhere one goes whether encountering pain or pleasure, friend or enemy, teaching opportunities arise... and if one is taught by all things, one cannot be greater than anything. Being this humble... all things flow into one like gravity and lasers pressurizing one into a direction of great Being. God is like an anvil, and the Firing process is like a hammer. This process of the hammer and anvil will be your shaping into the Original Self.

Some claim one should whittle the ego away. This is one way to reveal the Self. But all woods reveal different sculptures. At the center of every individual is a carbon based life; carbon turns to coals and oils and all such have diamonds at their core. It is not required to eliminate one's individual culture in order to make oneself a Diamond. Be careful to distinguish between reducing to destroy and reducing to add to. Adding others' greatness to oneself, removing one's alloys until there is a uniform strength.... this leads to the true lead and the true mercury and the truest of Gold.

Is Disease Karmic Retribution?

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What follows is not something I consider to be **fact**... it is a mixture of religious scripture from Buddhism, and personal opinion (which includes science in my paradigm/world-view). Do not suppose that I am the ultimate authority, and if you do not agree, please remember nothing here is meant to insult or deny others' beliefs. It is simply that I have been asked enough that there was a need to write this article.

There are two columns, one for scriptural Buddhism, and one for a more modern perspective. It would be prudent to read the article on [**Reincarnation**](#) prior to reading this article.

What Does the Buddha Say?

Historically, Shakyamuni Buddha was a Brahman before he ceased his ascetic studies and founded the Middle Way. There were three periods of teaching in his life:

1. Hinayana ~10years
2. Provisional Mahayana ~30 years
3. Period of the Lotus Law ~8 years

In each stage, the Buddha taught according to the needs and readiness of the individuals in the Sangha. The first disciples he had were all Brahmans, and for them he taught the method of extinguishment of the cycle of birth and death because that was what they wanted. That Law was the first to spread, and it has continued on even to this day but the precepts one must follow to use it are universally not followed anywhere. **That Law is what we would call 'expired.'**

Foreseeing the eventual failing of Hinayana, the Buddha spent the next 20-30 years berating his own students for their lack of perception and satisfaction in nirvana through becoming attached to the Void.

He repeatedly told them that they, like the women and evil people they avoided in their judgmentalism would never attain buddhahood, calling the fruits of arhatship itself a "Great Pit."

Then it came to pass that he finally drove away the disbelievers, easily dissuaded, and those with insufficient faith, and taught the **Immeasurable Meanings Sutra wherein he said, "In these last 40 years I have not yet revealed the Truth."**

What does Science Say?

In the interest of skipping the 'conclusions' that science has not proven nor disproven anything, I'll get right to the brass tacks: science says your karma is derived from your parents.

All your Jing - genes, which epigenes are active, what diet and beliefs you will have, the time you were conceived and born, all of this is the result of the activity of your parents.

What diseases you will catch is partly do to your own actions, but still largely due to the exposure your parents allow you to have as a child.

Now in western medicine they do not yet recognize the correlation between having say... a foot injury and Parkinsons. Or having the flu and catching herpes. For them it's all a matter of 'can you tie it directly to it?' Even things like aluminum and mercury poisoning are never completely tied to diseases such as Alzheimers; and we would certainly NEVER say that a vaccine causes autism despite the known side effects being demyelinating disorders!

But in another more practical science of Chinese Medicine, causation is all important because it determines the treatment.

Now put yourself in the place of the Sangha, especially his most devoted followers: that would either drive you away or make you ask '*what does that mean?*'

After much prodding the Buddha, Shariputra - one who had repeatedly been berated for decades - convinced the Buddha to explain the matter.

What followed was the longest sutra of them all, which revealed several truths:

1. There are no other vehicles to Buddhahood but the Lotus; all Buddhas know this vehicle and share it with other Buddhas.
2. All beings through this vehicle will attain their inherent Buddhahood.
3. **There is no cycle of birth and death nor cessation of the cycle of birth and death.**
4. All beings in all the paths of existence from the worst to the best have the seeds of Buddhahood.
5. The Buddha is a being which is a continually existing phenomena, and Guatama did not first attain Buddhahood in this lifetime but in the incalculable past; as we all did.
6. Those who look upon this Truth with joy and wonder will encounter it over and over again and always regain their Original Face; those who do not will suffer the lower existences.

This in no way negates the Tibetan/Vajrayana view from the Book of the Dead, which makes it clear that arhats and voice-hearers choose not to be reborn for they extinguished the mind. Until they become bodhisattvas and finish their

But even in Chinese Medicine we do not say a person has schizophrenia, for example, because they are being punished for betraying their parents, for example.

However, let us revisit what science has 'proven' if that is anything and analyze it with Chinese Medicine.

You acquire your Jing through two methods. The first is from your parents at conception (and later when you are named technically completes the birth of a person) and when you eat food, drink water, and breathe air.

Pre-heaven Jing is largely controlled by karma, while post-heaven Jing is less so (according to the medicine; remember the doctors weren't necessarily sages).

Pre-heaven Jing is determined not by the parent, but instead by Heaven. Now we know from the Bagua Dharma that the Heaven trigram corresponds to Karma. BUT forget that for a moment.

Instead focus on the idea of a benevolent Heavenly deity - God perhaps - bestowing an embryo with properties. Is this not the equivalent of randomized selection caused by millions of sperm colliding with a randomly matured oocyte?

The entire process is guiding by the Law of Evolution and the random chaotic math of that Law's domain.

Moreover the changes that occur immediately following - to the woman, to the egg, etc... - are nothing short of miraculous, ingenious, and frankly so full of opportunities for

doctorate, so to speak, at which time they will be reborn again and again.

In other words no matter whether you study the non-Buddhist scriptures and live the cycles without the Middle Way, or even study the non-Lotus methods which are expedients you study to complete your University of Spirit degree, you are certain to attain Buddhahood one day. As long as you deny the Lotus Law, the truth of yourself, you are not finished nor can you improve your condition much from one life to the next.

Let us discuss the karmic situation of various paths.

Atheism and Icchantikas

Icchantikas are "arrogant people of incorrigible disbelief." This roughly fits the description of an unfortunate half or more of atheists; did you know in medicine the prefix a- means lack of, as in deficiency in God? Unfortunately for atheists, they often have the irritating habit of trying to force their non-belief on others through angry tirades.¹ [This is normal because of the resonance between the fourth and eighth realm.]

One can deny Law, Truth, God, anything one wants... as Galileo aptly put, "It moves anyways."

The point is that if one requires evidence, one should be agnostic, or at least curiously confused... but to say, "I do not understand, ergo there is nothing more to understand" is the arrogance of an icchantika. The karmic punishment for denying the Law(s) is the worst; scripturally in the next life (and possibly this one the way the world is going) this person will suffer unspeakable suffering until they correct their views.

mistakes that the fact that anyone is ever born at all is a miracle.

Moreover the splitting of the egg is guided by minute forms of consciousness which carefully manipulate molecules of fibrinogen and DNA into specific locations so that when they are in proximity of each other they will spontaneously create cell division.

Later the cells use this minute consciousness to 'just know' how to perform what is called apoptosis: programmed cell death. Some cells commit suicide to form structures and at some point the being forms organs and a brain. When the brain and CNS form and heart beats, the being has a higher form of consciousness.

Now in mysticism, Vajrayana, and Chinese Medicine this is where we would say the soul enters the body. Science notes it by the reactionary behaviors (which are so cute on an ultrasound) which were not present before but now are.

This process of self-awakening continues through to adulthood, with various stages of epiphanies caused by changes in the brain structure.

In Chinese Medicine the Heaven bestowed life on a being, and the Jing is transformed into Qi and blood because of the Five Shens. These Shens enter the body and 'possess' their relative positions... in other words this is the equivalent of the changes in awareness and behaviors in the child.

The last to enter is the Hun and Po which are the two souls, one from Heaven (karmically chosen) and the

Evil Paths; Living in Sin

Those who are attached to the lower paths, and repeatedly perform evil very typically suffer karmic retribution in their present life, to say nothing of their next lives. They go to jail, live off of drugs and the dregs of others' filth and pity, are diseased in body and mind, fall from grace, and even fall into despair... some of them relying on suicide, murder or terrorism as an outlet.

The sutras say, though, even though these people suffer from one life to the next, they eventually can encounter Buddha lands (good people/lives) and enjoy the spoils of Heaven if they work on their karma. Some will form a relationship with the Lotus Law and finish their degrees. I personally can attest to this truth... I cannot think of a crime I have not committed in my past life or in the mind in this present life. I have in this very life repeatedly filled my mind and punished my soul with graphic violence and incorrect sexual imagery not equal to the value of my soul. The unhappiness this has caused me, it akin to the unhappiness you feel, and is exactly the unhappiness that Christ Buddha came to the Earth to relieve and forgive. His Law is meant to live and endure as a formula for salvation for ~2000 years. We are nearing the time when Christ's Law ceases to be upheld by people because their karmic choices are not in step with it or the Buddhist precepts. At that time - now perhaps even - only the Lotus Law medicine will help one heal. It is described as the one sutra that can make a scorched seed grow. The Christ Buddha has promised Heaven for those who ask for his forgiveness, and they shall have it until the end of this Karmic Cycle, when mankind returns to lowly origins in the forests; if there are any forests left to house him. This is

other from the parents through identity.

Both of these souls represent parts of the mind which psychology denotes as being below normal consciousness. Which is another way of saying they don't understand them at all.

But in Chinese Medicine, a bit more research has been done over time to denote the various level they occupy and the effects they have on behavior and therefore HOW they cause disease. For example obsession is the mark of the intellect or conscious mind which is repeatedly stimulated by the hun (subconscious) and Liver's over-activity, meaning a person feels an incessant need to plan and think up plans.

This obsession consumes Qi, and what kind of symptoms do we see: wasting away (from atrophy and not eating when hungry), cravings for sweets, irritability, tremulous tongues with bite marks, vivid often sexual dreams, dark eyes, headaches, dizziness, vertigo, etc...

This is a hun or heavenly derived soul that has two karmic ties:

1. It inherently was a successful person in the past, and lost everything, or did not complete something, or has been assigned or made to feel assigned to do something in this life.
2. It chose parents and so was born to parents who would enable, educate, encourage, and nourish this obsessive behavior.

In the post-heaven Jing category we see that in utero the fetus has

known both in Revelations and in the sutras.

Agnostics, the Confused, the Curious

Those who repeatedly leave the lower six paths in disgust - of the workplace, of the consumerism, of the corruption in government, of the wars and violence - they will repeatedly make ties to others in hopes of groping about to find 'the one' who can accurately explain their present existence and their existence in the past and how to escape the door.

They will encounter gurus at every turn, read book after book, in search of the Truth of themselves. I myself passed that way briefly.²

But... eventually in this life they will form a karmic tie that will later enable them to encounter endless Buddhas.

Normal People [of the Lower Realms]

People of the lower six paths form the basis for normalcy. Right now they live in the era of the end of a karmic cycle in the middle of the kalpa of continuance, and the times are confusing, exciting, dramatic yet boring (because everyone thinks the world is discovered). But in the immediate future these people will explore new lands both in space and in the mind and continually find new excitement in the drama of their violent wars against everything from disease and drugs to Muslims and aliens. There's no helping an addict until he/she wants to cease, and right now the addiction to wealth is like an endless party. Of course it must come to an end. If it isn't running out of oil it will be climate change or if not that then the collapse of world ecosystems and if not that the fall of the debt economy.

experiences, whether dietary choices in the mom or environmental variables like exposure to trauma or sounds/heat that turn off or on certain epigenes.

The epigenes then decide (and no one knows exactly how) which genes to express. For example in a family with a history of autoimmune disorders some sibling have the gene and do not express, some partially express, and some fully express those genes of the autoimmune disorder; current thinking is that it may be a reaction to the mother's immune system itself.

At any rate these genes enabled cause a living person to have certain dietary needs and desires, behave in certain ways, and even be more at risk or less at risk for mental disorders as well as physical ones. This post-heaven Jing forms the basis for a lifetime of experience which of course influences not only karma directly but the very paradigms which will determine the karma generated moment to moment.

For life after life these people will drink in their uniqueness the intoxicating elixir of consciousness and will proclaim their love of love, joy, happiness, sex, and entertainment. Their land will grow in size until each of them is like a guppie or tadpole in a lake, and no one can make any impact on the whole, but the entire collective consciousness of the whole will sway and affect them profoundly and they will feel oppressed. Everyone is born in these lower realms and most die here as well only to be reborn here again.

Bodhisattvas, Teachers, and Healers

Those born into this world destined to help others will take it upon themselves to fix situations, save the world, and heal other people. They will use their time as students (see above) to search for the tools to aid others. In their studies, however long these may be, they will try to teach others and meet with repeated frustration, persecution, agony and torment by those around them, and yet will forgive them.

They will exorcise their karmic diseases through actual practice and study in motion. The suffering they endure will be as the Buddha did with his own Bodhisattvas who now reside in the Tushita Heaven awaiting the birth of Maitreya: like fire forging impurities from a sword.

They will be like normal people and study all the vain, narcissistic doctrines of man in hopes of fitting in and being able to converse with their fellows. They will dumb their minds with the same illusory entertainment, willing even to engage in daily work and tax-slavery and deny themselves the pleasures of past studies they once enjoyed in a time when mankind studied wisdom treasures. They

One soul vs. Many

Now one area of obvious weakness is any research into the possibility that, since we are made up of infinitely old particles, atoms which came from stars at the Big Bang, and molecules of dead and consumed animals and plants... all of which carry entangled data forward through conservation... whether then we are not more aptly said to be reincarnations of two, four, or infinite beings based on our Jing (discussed above) and what we consume.

Does consuming a hamburger mean you acquire different Jing than from consuming a plant? Science might scoff, but consider this: consuming meat from a diseased cow is definitely more unhealthy a choice (karma) than consuming meat

will suffer in body, mind, and spirit and yet never repudiate the beliefs of others or refuse to aid a person. When they encounter suffering they will open their minds and hearts and try to understand. Their mind will be attached to the punishments of suffering in order that they may truly understand the minds of students and normal persons. They will refuse allegiance to arrogant priests, religions, governments/nations, and may allow themselves to be led into cults in order to cure the diseased therein. They will leave these structures and strike out on their own to lead others. For existence after existence they will live this way without the Lotus Truth until they finally desire to drink the medicine again and fulfill the Buddha's work. At that time the bodhisattvas will hear of the brilliance of expedient means, the security of the 3,000 Realms which promise enlightenment and Nirvana at any chosen moment, They will be satisfied and at that time not enter repose, but instead go into the world and deftly spread the words of the Buddha and the Lotus Sutra, and using this medicine and the powers of the Teacher of the Law, they will heal others of their karmic diseases, starting first with themselves, and then others at an ever increasing range. Then they will enter repose, and when they go into Bardo, will forgo Parinirvana once again to re-enter a diseased land and begin again... denying themselves the Lotus Law for eons until that land changes from a desert into a garden of Eden and yields the Law for them to teach once more. Their success or failure will be that which pardons or dooms a world-system (Planet). Such is the karma of the bodhisattva. At some point they will choose either karmic reward of the Dharma Body of a

from a healthy one. It likewise follows that consumption from a grass fed, organic cow whose meat is cleaner, and fat without hormones and toxic chemicals contained in it would be healthier than that of a factory farm raised cow. Needless to say how the consumption of meat from diseased, ill treated, stressed out animals makes you feel (which can change your health) is just as important as the possibility that it changes your anatomy.

If all our cells change over every 7 years... then naturally it would take about 7 years to completely modify ourselves or as completely as we can without the genetic level.

This too is just another example of karma affecting our health and disease levels via the choices we make in this life alone.

Now consider the possibility that the cow's sentience and nervous system modifies the cellular behavior and when their ethereal cell leaves the body the corporeal soul leaves an imprint of it. If that is the case, is it any wonder that we can alter our moods by what we eat (to say nothing of the organic chemical cocktail that comes with it).

Now what about plants? Their 'minds' are in the roots mostly but even still the plants have some consciousness and can modify their behavior to complex stimuli. Is eating plants able to change the chemical composition of our body: yes. Is it able to modify our chemical balances and internal ecosystem: yes. Is this the same thing as modifying our ENS/CNS behavior (Po): yes. Do changes in teh

Buddha of Perfect Enlightenment from youth, where they will teach as the Buddha did; or they will choose the reward of being a god in the Brahma Heaven for many kalpas.

Gods and Heavenly Beings

Like persons born rich in life, gods and angels are born with the continual presence of the Lord and the option to go into Buddha Lands and hear the Law, if they wish. Unlike the bodhisattvas, they typically choose to enjoy their seemingly endless Jing-essence by resting or engaging in tantra.

All things that go up must come down. Just as the birth of a god in a land is marked by the blossoming and happy increase in that land's bounty, the death of a local god is marked by disasters, wars, famine, drought, earthquakes, and finally purging fires. The land lies empty for a time, godless and full of devilry until a bodhisattva arrives and heals the land and new gods come there like a rich couple shopping for a home. The bodhisattva spreads the seeds given him by the Buddha, they grow and things are good once more, and the cycle repeats until finally the seeds are too scorched to grow again. At that time a great bodhisattva arrives and wins the land through war with the devil, plants his Sword of Truth in the ground and mounts instead a flag. He spreads the Law in the scorched lands where misery is on every corner and the people are gladdened and God sends the highest gods there to listen to the Law. The blessings upon the land remain for many thousands of years, and the cycle continues as mentioned before.

The existence of sentience is not a pre-requisite in Buddhism for gods to arrive nor for Buddhahood because all things sentient or non-sentient, living or non-living have the seeds of Buddhahood.

ENS and CNS affect our choices (through hunger, comfort, pain, temperature, etc...): yes.

So therefore your karma via the causes and effects of choices made is affected via the consumption of things you eat.

That lends to the argument of infinite souls without one via atoms of other beings/places.

However, let us not forget there is a certain part of us that does not change over and even if it did does not quite ever forget that which came from our parents and our childhood. This is the meaning of the idea that we at minimum are not reincarnated from one being but two. And each of them had two parents, etc... and pretty soon, within a few generations we are talking about billions of connections.

At an average of 3 generations per 100 years, that is 1073741824 souls over 1000 years, and the number doubles every 33 years. When you take in the entirety of known human existence (not counting prior to homo sapiens when we were naught but little monkeys) that is such a large number that the computer overflows (2^{121212} or 4 million years). If you are a Christian, this is still $\sim 6.58201822e+63$ ancestors in only 7000 years time.³

So it seems that the existence of karma - soul based or atom based - is a fact and not something to discard or bother arguing about. It would be most useful to study it.

It is how this world in the far reaches of our galaxy came to have life and have sentience... a Buddha passed here on the way to another world-system and a following god looked on the land with lustful eyes and blessed it to awaken to life. But it was the passing Buddha that roused the sentience in the Buddha nature of the world-system, and all the different kalpas this process continued until the present day, where we now witness the use and misuse/abuse of human sentience, and the karmic diseases which spread everywhere from them.

Disease as Repayment

Since each path itself has a different karmic footprint and therefore a different karmic outcome, it is said that disease is really an affliction accorded to all living beings but most according to their karmic debt.

Every religion has its methods of enforcing morality and Hinduism and later Buddhism is no different.

Whether you agree with this idea or not, keep this in mind: we all have stations in life, circles of friends, social classes, and come from families that also have these things. Who we are surrounded by, and our social standing (which determines our education) very often, more than chance would dictate, affects our health. It is no secret that if you want to lose weight - and all the chronic diseases that come with obesity, it is better to have thin friends. If you tend to eat in restaurants where the patronage is fat and unhealthy, you are likely to become that way, too. This is everyday examples of karma in action, whether you see the \cosmic life to life picture or not, it is easy to understand. All the Buddha is trying to say is that your understanding of the Law affects your paths you walk and this affects your environmental exposure, and therefore

disease is the resulting cause: do you want white collar diseases or blue collar ones?

These are the truths according to Buddhism of how diseases of the mind, which create diseases of the body continue for eons in a person's life. The medicine is the Lotus Law, though other lesser medicines suffice in happier more prosperous times... the medicine that is adequate then is paltry now and only the Lotus can undo the poisons that spread after the passing of Gautama Buddha and Jesus Christ Buddha's 2000 year reigns have ended.

In Either Case...

Disease comes down to choice and the state of the mind, which is really all the Buddha and Quantum physics have been trying to say anyhow. Can karma cause disease: you bet. But does that mean you have to be a victim... of course not. That's why treating the karma is so important. For more information, I highly recommend the Goshō passage by Nichiren called, "[On Curing Karmic Disease](#)," page 631, [The Writings of Nichiren Daishonin](#)

True Zen

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Nhat Hanh: Suppose you are drinking a cup of tea. When you hold your cup, you may like to breathe in, to bring your mind back to your

body, and you become fully present. And when you are truly there, something else is also there—life, represented by the cup of tea. In that moment you are real, and the cup of tea is real. You are not lost in the past, in the future, in your projects, in your worries. You are free from all of these afflictions. And in that state of being free, you enjoy your tea. That is the moment of happiness, and of peace. When you brush your teeth, you may have just two minutes, but according to this practice, it is possible to produce freedom and joy during that time, because you are established in the here and now. If you are capable of brushing your teeth in mindfulness, then you will be able to enjoy the time when you take a shower, cook your breakfast, sip your tea.

Is it Life Is Suffering or Life As Suffering?

In the beginning of Buddhism, the Buddha talked about how to end the karmic cycle of birth and death and therefore escape suffering. This teaching, found in the Flower Garland Sutra and summarized in brief in the Lotus Sutra is the heart of Hinayana: the path to extinction.

At that time, when the Buddha made his advent, there were no Buddhists, there were only various sects of Brahmanists, each practicing different doctrines according to the vagaries and opinions of their lineage and teachers. It was said there were 100 different schools. When the Buddha found his first converts, they were ascetics who were engaging in the destruction of the body in order to try to extinguish karma. The karma they generated was therefore solely self-destructive. The Buddha wisely perceived that no soul was ever saved from the cycle of birth and death - let alone suffering - through this method. So he preached the Middle Way, and taught the elimination of suffering solely through extinguishment of the ego.

This enabled masses, throngs of people to take faith in his teachings, when they found they were able to extinguish the mind and observe 250 strict precepts (which was their wont [when People hate themselves]). The faith spread and his fame went far and wide, and at that time there was a lot of teaching by reduction while expanding.

However, the Buddha had not finished the teachings, and when he perceived that his disciples had become egoistic again, prideful and clinging to these lower doctrines, he knew nothing could be built by expanding alone, so he began to reduce his following by eliminating those of little faith.

By constantly berating the very voice-hearers and arhats he had trained, he created many rips and tears in his own Sangha for the purpose of testing each disciple individually. For twenty+ long years he attacked the Hinayana, and now taught that Buddhahood was possible for all people - except the Arhats.

Why?

Because deep down the Buddha believed that monks who are attached to their monk-hood, attached to opinions, and yet refusing to see beyond the Void would only continue to tear apart the confidence, and humanity of the People, and the People would suffer under the thumb of dogma.

He had already ceased teaching that life is suffering and began sowing the seeds for the Mahayana understanding that **we see life AS suffering because of our karmic attachment**. He wanted all to have access to not just the simple nirvana of meditating on the Void... but to the true deep Nirvana of anuttara-samyak-sambodhi which he had yet to explain how it would be obtained.

Zen Without Dogma

During this period of reduction by reduction, the Buddha spent his time teaching how to live, because he perceived that it was the People who would carry on his teachings generation to generation. For one thing monks and nuns existed before and they destroyed their teachers' teachings through opinion and the filth of frivolous debate and even war (like Crusades). Monks always become embroiled in politics and that would be the end of purity in the Sangha. Secondly monks and nuns do not have children. Even if they did, it was all too easy for one surreptitious monk to politically and violently destroy another Sage or his family.

So the Buddha perceived it was not the arhats that would transform Samsara but the lay people. For their sake he wanted them to have a faith that could be practiced without forever-reduction ... eliminating desire to try for enlightenment which takes many kalpas of lifetimes to achieve.

So the Buddha continued to revile his own students and **in secret he began to train one or two disciples on the concept of true, deep Mindfulness**.

True Zen is without particular attachment to any doctrine and yet it embraces all doctrines, because as the Buddha later made clear in the Lotus Sutra, **samadhi upon the Lotus Law (all 8 Laws together) is the ultimate of Zen**.

In teaching this Zen he did not intend however that we should abandon the teachings.

Zen Without Doctrine

Ch'an Buddhism arguably was a rediscovery of the teachings that died out in India within the first 500 year period. But supposing it survived and came to China, it was certainly much destroyed when it entered Japan and the sutras that taught true deep mindfulness were abandoned in favor of the chic, cliquish culture of Japanese Zen. It was a tradition that lived off of the desire by the aristocracy to remain aloof, in the willow world of fantasy and war, unable to take blame for their own karma and the destruction they saw around them.

What Pure Land (supplication to Amida) did for the masses, Zen did for the intellectuals.

To make it worse, when Zen came to the West, where popularism is cherished and individuality adhered to as a doctrine of life - as opposed to individuality through

self-committment to higher ideals - the marketability of this chic religion caused it to spread like wildfire.

And yet, it is no more useful to obtaining enlightenment in this form than through being a warrior in the military where they teach one to be a cog in a wheel and eliminate the individual.

The true Zen has long been replaced with the convenience of intellectualism, and is the atheist's choice for alternatively acceptable practice in a world of doubt, cynicism, and reductionistic (rational) science.

A person who cannot see that which cannot be easily, physically explained, it is easy to embrace a philosophy (no longer a religion even) where doctrine is abandoned and God as well, where all there is to perceive is your mind.

Though it is true the Mind is central to enlightenment, it is but one-third of the Heavenly Mandate, just as physical science is one-third of Reality.

Perceiving the Mind directly - or with science - alone cannot solely give anyone enlightenment. Anyone can experience nirvana, it does not require any doctrine... and yet it is not complete in the least.

This is nothing more than people continuing their past karmic attachment to non-Buddhist or Hinayana doctrines which categorically hate life, the self, and seek to reduce by reduction.

There is a time for reduction by reduction when one is refining. But that time for mankind has long passed... now we need **a wisdom embracing all species - literally in this environmental climate.**

Everything Zen?

Can it be said that following complete Mindfulness we can achieve this wisdom embracing all species? Suppose that one would cease self-thought and instead act complete as a Pinnocchio, in total tune with the Dao. Supposing even only one person did this, and not all of society, let us examine what it would be like. Would in fact people be kind, loving, embracing, gentle, etc...?

In nature the ultimate of this Zen-like benevolence is the tree. But we observe that only a small percentage of the plant and fungal kingdoms is trees, all else are smaller bushes which compete violently for sunlight. And among trees there is difference. Some are violent towards other species, some solitary in nature, and some support each other at the expense of others. The Redwood, arguably the most evolved and enlightened of tree species because it is immortal and sharing by nature, still requires fire and destruction in order to seed. It will not seed, and thus give abundance to the forest floor until there is a fire. **This tree is no more than a glorified plant version of a guru meditating alone in a cave.**

By contrast, animals and other animated kingdoms of life are very violent, requiring daily, sometimes hourly consumption of plants, animals, and in some cases their own kind (as snakes with others snakes).

A people once existed who lived in accordance with this world in perfect harmony with it - and their resulting karma was **complete annihilation.**

This isn't to say they earned it, or it was right and Just. Far from it. But their culture lauded harmony with a consumptive world, and in the end they were consumed.

No one can exist - especially humans - without consumption. **But if your enlightenment requires destruction of the self, then you must logically resent consumption of others to sustain the self.**

Zen without doctrine - the zen known as Yoga of Action - leads solely to one place: the lower realms. There is nothing altruistic or any sort of wisdom embracing all species therein. By ignoring one's powers of deduction, reasoning, and creation, one leaves it to chance that all others will behave as one does. Though you may act responsibly, can it be reasonably assumed your neighbor will? You may love your neighbor as you love your child... but would a wise man trust his neighbor to act in the interest of the global community? Would you trust a child to not eat all the food in the interest of survival? It is necessary to have some discipline.

Thus the Yi Jing said long ago the **Sage loves all people and is the same with them, and yet he prepares defenses** for wars in the future because he knows the vices and devilry that exists in complement (as a product of) the potential to Buddhahood within all species.

It is clear that Zen is appropriate most of the time, but not at all times, and certainly it needs guidance or it will devolve into animalistic and instinctual behaviors that are so common and apparent in our mass-consumption society (that is supposedly enlightened by science).

Zen and the Heavenly Mandate (God's Purpose)

One could then argue that if one follows pure Zen from the knowledge of the Heavenly Mandate, which is a major growth in understanding from Mind-only existence, that this must be the wisdom embracing all species. If one knows the divine, knows the earthly, and knows one is a product of the two and should act according to some moral code (precepts or virtues, etc...) then isn't this following the Dao?

Nay I say for one reason only: **sticking within this paradigm will never allow one to change one's karma or position in the caste.** If you believe you should just "go with the flow" you live under the once again selfish presumption that you are the only being in your life. By being a puppet what man or woman could discern rightly whether they are doing the bidding of God or of the evilly driven ones around them, seeking to further their existence by using others?

The Buddhas were like fathers to us all, and good fathers know when to allow children to play along and when to admonish them to improve.

We likewise have Buddha nature, and even without seeking Buddhahood should at least seek to set the wrongs right as best we can (despite our Relative standpoint) because to not do so would be to watch and allow our fellow brethren to control, manipulate, and consume our fellow, weaker brethren.

When one is enlightened, Zen or not, one has a clearer point of view. If one has Zen one should also recall that though all morals are human constructs that change according to

cultural mores, **there is ultimately one morality which remains Universal: the 8 Laws and the Lotus Law itself.**

If a person is not blameworthy of breaking a human law or cultural more, or being unfilial, defying God, etc... but merely tries to coerce their and others' lives despite the Bagua Dharma, one is obligated to help them stop. This is called being a good friend and your brothers' keeper.

Now the various methods of correction are of course manifold, and cannot be listed here, but ultimately there is shoju - a friend in the orchid room method - and shakubuku which is battling evil to advance good. All of these methods' appropriateness is determined according to the Universal Qi, and *seeking the council of the Yi Jing is advisable.*

Is this Zen anymore? One should not forget that God gave us the power of time travel to change psychic vibrations and alter courses and ports of call for a reason.

For all intents and purposes if you are alive you are making the right choice, and within certain errors in space-time effects exist within the valence shell that doesn't involve either Armageddon nor anti-existence itself. So kudos, you have done well regardless.

But within that self-same shell there are infinite streams of possibilities (in the Law of Conservation) from which to choose. Thus one should stop, examine the situation, evaluate the situation and act forthrightly as often as possible, like a rock climber who does not wish to fall to his doom.

This is the Zen of higher consciousness, and it is not against enlightenment to say one can be Zen here too because that is precisely what the Buddha did.

Consciousness driven Purpose

What was the event a Deer Park underneath the Bodhi tree if anything but a moment of profound Zen that continued on? **The Zen of self-realization that also was later revealed in the Lotus Sutra to not be a singular event but a continuation of consciousness and a choice made.**

Remember Samsara is Life AS suffering... not suffering itself. The world of Samsara is distinguished from Nirvana only by one's mental perception of it.

One can see pain as torment, or as a chance to overcome suffering and either grow or die enlightened.

Granted, this is hard. It is hard to reconcile God's Purpose with the rape of women and children, or the bombing from afar of a people by imperialists. But indeed these can be reconciled within the mind by understanding that if one were in the others' shoes, one might act the same way. That is until you had that thought.

Once you can see the evil in the self, you can automatically know the pure good as well. Just as one is the sum of two parents, one is not pure evil only, but also pure good, and this combination allows us to be born with innate capacity for good or evil.

Our relative view of more good or more evil in the world reflects the inner battle within us that sees more good or evil in our souls.

There are two ways to properly repulse evil that are without struggle: when it just comes into life (as in a child first lying), or via pushing yin so far that it flips to yang. Often the best counselors of alcoholics are alcoholics themselves. The most peaceful within are the ones who have battled the most.

These two methods reflect Shakubuku and Shoju, respectively. At this time the existence of more manifest evil in the world than manifest good is indicative not of the End, but of the greater potential for good than evil - however infinite the potential of the latter may seem. This means that the time to go with the flow of destroying the doctrines of all world religions is only going to increase, and makes the Shakubuku of the Lotus Law all the more valuable in the future however impossible it may seem.

The karmic benefit of a society that nears the brink only to save itself through observation is much greater than if we tried to save it now.

This is the Zen of observing the various levels of dualities in the environment around one, not keeping solely to the Mind *but not becoming lost among the manifestations of yin and yang around one*. One must unite the two and see shoju and shakubuku as one, see them as a see-saw of sharing by listening and teaching the Law.

This is purpose driven not only by the Heavenly Mandate, which is what any plant or animal does, but by one's own self-acknowledged responsibility of one's consciousness (God's Gift)

Zen as an arm of Anuttara-Samyak-Sambodhi

The result of this is the realization that Zen must flow not only from Samsara to Nirvana (until death), but also backwards again to return the Order into Chaos itself. People are born in the lower six realms equally, and only achieve their caste (station) through parents and community. Thus the Sage who sees Zen now as a responsibility - NOT AN ESCAPE - **immediately can see the Return of this consciousness-vibration as the all important task of the Sage.** This is the explanation for *the purpose of the bodhisattva*.

Now the Three Bodhis, 1) name and form of Reality, 2) blending vibration and Harmony with the exterior, and 3) perfection of this in each moment until it is a lifetime is ultimately nothing but the practice of this Zen continuously.

Some would argue one can say this is not much different than Yoga of Action... except that Yoga of Action does not require knowledge of Reality in depth.

Here the True Zen is what we shall call samadhi or trance like perception, where one can perceive the every aspects of one's "room" that is to say one's foreseeable environment.

It is not a requirement that one be omnipotent to have Near perfect or Perfect

Enlightenment... the Law of Relativity precludes that possibility anyhow. **It simply requires one 1) know the Dharma, 2) see the Buddha, and 3) Live in Nirvana.**

To see the Dharma is to see the little laws, the big laws and the One Law (or God). To see the Buddha does not mean one has to be Buddhist - though enough of #1 and in some lifetime that will happen - it only requires believing in the deep potential present in every atom, particle, beam of light, etc... everywhere. To live the Nirvana only require that one rotate one's perception from Samsara, and see both simultaneously.

The Truth of Birthlessness

"How can that happen?" one may ask. Though it is true *the intellectual mind Yi-Shen is machine like in its orientation, perceiving on thought only at a time*, the **Hun-Shen is not**, and in samadhi (and the lower meditations) one will know. Furthermore, even your heart (hun-po) knows the good from the bad when one does not think about it at all. If one saw a child being beaten indiscriminately, or a woman being raped, or an animal tortured, or a car stolen, one does not have to ponder at all to know both the evil of the crime and the good, which is to say your compassionate desire to effectively change this outcome.

In fact your mind is likely only to get in the way with rationalizations, and selfish excuses that keep one from action.

In the popular form of Zen, one would either leave society in disgust and seek isolationism, thereby destroying the Meaning of Life, or one would act as an animal and co-engage in the act of crime, much as a mob riots and an individual walking by the riot thinks "well if they can steal and loot, then I can!"

They both seem implausible now, but they happen and often. In New York we hear of people over-stepping dying victims, and look at the jaded, cynical, self-driven, dog-eat-dog world-view that pervades NYC today. And during Katrina and afterwards we saw exactly that sort of animal like behavior instead of people lending helping hands.

Do not think it is impossible or one will be the victim of "going with the flow" and **that is not the internal power of a "wisdom embracing all species"**

Instead see one's ability to know and perceive the good and the bad simultaneously as a manifestation of one central truth, which became a central theme in the Mahayana leading to the eventual propagation of the True Zen, anuttara-samyak-sambodhi: the Truth of Birthlessness.

We are not in a cycle of karmic suffering... **we are in a cycle of no beginning and no end**... a continual potential to see our own internal perfection, forgive ourselves and our brethren and not be attached to outcomes which benefit us or our group at the expense of others.

We do not all have to sit in samadhi all the time, but if we can embrace the wisdom embracing all species, then we will not only restore Zen as it was when the Buddha taught it out, but advance our spirituality from being an intellectualist or celebrity oriented (and therefore very limited in scope) activity to being an activity that defines the very core of our society. At one time the Law of the Christ Thus Come One had people praying daily. Muslims still pray five times daily... but for what I often wonder? If we can harness these past and current activities, and centralize them on the theme of Oneness - God... then this act will foster samadhi as surely as a mighty Redwood springs from a tiny, rice-sized seed. If we respect God and His Laws, then samadhi/true Zen will return and our world benefit.

But so long as people cling to chic beliefs and popularism, the true Zen will be destroyed and the Buddha's marvelous method for perceiving the mind will remain an oddity of news specials and fringe aspects of society: and many people will be unable to gain access to the direct perception of their Buddha Nature. Thank you , and I leave you with this other quote from the Mahasattva Master Thay,

Nhat Hanh: The question can be answered when you can answer this: What happens in the present moment? In the present moment, you are producing thought, speech, and action. And they continue in the world. Every thought you produce, anything you

say, any action you do, it bears your signature. Action is called karma. And that's your continuation. When this body disintegrates, you continue on with your actions. It's like the cloud in the sky. When the cloud is no longer in the sky, it hasn't died. The cloud is continued in other forms like rain or snow or ice. Our nature is the nature of no birth and no death. It is impossible for a cloud to pass from being into nonbeing. And that is true with a beloved person. They have not died. They have continued in many new forms and you can look deeply and recognize them in you and around you.

The Multiverse

posted May 25, 2012, 10:33 AM by S RC [**updated May 29, 2012, 1:12 PM**]

Yes, fact: there are more than one **Universe, just as there are more than one Dimensions.** A Universe is defined as a single data stream occurring in observed sequence from inception to present; in other words though time does not pass, a Universe records events or changes in state so that Consciousness can review them in order to create and complete an incarnation story. The incarnation here is the life-span of **God** as it happens within THIS STREAM.

There are at least six main kinds of Multiverses, therefore (not one as is commonly understood... that version is merely the Spatial Multiverse). Five are simultaneous, but all hold true positions in the Conservation Dharma. They are all therefore also false because they represent illogical sets as a whole; this supports their Polarity Dharma.

The 8 Dharma holds for all multiverses, despite their differing realities.

The idea of a painting will be used here as a metaphor to explain all of them.

Triple-Plane Multiverse

This is a multiverse only in the concept that there are three layers to every single stream of reality: a (1) Spiritual, (2) Physical, and (3) Mental. The intersection of the Mental Plane (or universe) with the Spiritual Plane forms what is called the "psyche" and the Physical Plane is the observed Universe that is measurable with objects that occupy only the physical universe. This intersection of psychic field and Physical Plane is known as **"De Qi."**

If you have a painting, you see it only as one painting, however it has three layers. The physical lines and structure; the coloring and shading, and the physical texture. These are the Physical, Spiritual, and Mental planes respectively. The lines provide structure, the color and shading (yang (5 elements) and yin (shade)) provide potentials, and the texture informs our mind about the nature of the image or painting.

NOTE - One could argue that each plane is also a multiverse because they have (1) infinite potentials (Conservation Dharma), (2) 11 dimensions of perspective (Relativity Dharma), and (3) 11 main, and infinite sub divisions of potential vibrations (Quantum Dharma).

Spatial Multiverse

Essentially, this is the idea that if our Universe is like an object, that there are more than one objects floating in free space. This would be like having not one painting but an entire art gallery of paintings. This is the most commonly thought of multiverse when people talk about multiverses. They usually discuss shape, size, and distance, all indicators of Spatial thought.

Temporal Multiverse

The temporal multiverse is all about change. It ranges from the individual forward pictures formed by our collective Sentient experience, all the way to individual incarnations and reincarnations (Rotational Dharma) of entire Universes, from when the Branes collide, the Big Bang, all the way till expansion dissipates everything back to the Void (when God realizes FINALLY the full truth AGAIN) and everything recomacts and happens again. Basically the cycle of Ragnarok or Brahmic cycle. So every moment/second is a new Universe by Evolutionary Dharma, but also there is the Karmic Dharma of Universes.

There is nothing to say that all of them are in synchronicity, like trees in the fall and spring, it seems more likely that the great Spatial Multiverse experiences different incarnation Times for each child Universe. We don't know because of the fact that we cannot record data past our own incarnated Universe, and thus cannot physically SEE the other child Universes, only infer them from fractal (recursive multiverse) experiences.

Case in point, art comes in and out of popularity, season, and mood. It isn't like all potential art pieces are made at once and hung in the gallery. This is true too: not all thoughts reach fruition, they have to work hard until one or two do, and eventually one main theme arises at a time. The main reason we have defined limits on our daily consciousness is because we would be useless and extremely confused by infinite thought-awareness. Thus the need for temporal and spatial arrangements.

Lateral Multiverse

Overlapping upon every Stream are infinite right and left potentials to the Mental Stream to which we are upon. These potentials can be viewed as though one is standing between two mirrors. Now the image appears to stand still as one looks, but of course is different from side to side... but as we experience time moving forward (because of change) these lateral Multiverses ALSO simultaneously update their potentials and their feelings/responses to the stimuli they experience.

Let me be clear, these are all REAL, but only the ONE STREAM is actualized (aka "you"). You are the actualized Universe.

In another Spatial Universe, the situation may be different completely. But in this Universe, your "reality" is the only reality that "matters" because you cannot jump immediately to the right or left.

This is the downfall of the teaching the so-called Law of Attraction. It is not how the Universe works. Instead one can visualize a stream to the right or left out on front and MOVE TOWARDS that Universe, but one cannot instantly jump over. One can, through samadhi VISUALIZE them but the physical body's inertia does not enable instant switchover.

HOWEVER, repeated attempts to jump over will yield fast alterations. I have eliminated allergies within minutes merely by changing mental streams to the lateral universe. I highly recommend reading about Phasing In if you wish to see this firsthand.

In terms of paintings this is the clearer painting versus the fuzzier painting of the same image.

Vertical Multiverse

Also known as the "I could have been doing this" or "what if" stream. If you have a branching split in options, the road not taken usually bothers people if it's important, but reality is we're doing this all the time. I could die right now or get up to go to the bathroom but I am typing instead.

The vertical universe is the painting that IS; while the multiverse are the paintings that could have been, if only the artist had been of different mind, mood, or awareness when it was created.

Recursive Multiverse

Last one, and most difficult to understand.

Recursion is a thing within a thing. The best example is a painting of a person looking at a painting of a person looking at a painting, etc... What's it do? It gets smaller.

By proxy, one can imagine if you are looking at this painting, then someone is looking at you from a higher subest looking at the painting, etc...

This is the god isn't god because there's a bigger God multiverse. While true, let us for mathematical simplicity say that the God Source is the "container" of this infinite recursion.

The way the Recursive Universe works is this. Things spring up from the Void through a process of evolutionary self-complication and organization. They evolve into higher forms by being eaten, being reborn, being digested into higher beings, and their Spiritual Energy (shen-Qi) being resorbed into the Void and then recycled into new incarnations within the active Universe until they reach a sentient state. At this sentient state is the "middle-verse" which is to say where humans are.

When the sentient being arises from samsaric pain and realizes the upper recursions, they leave the middle-verse for the Heaven-Universe (for lack of a better term); which is to say a series of Spatial-Temporal-Universes that are higher up in the Vertical Multiverse. What the rules are for this evolutionary process isn't exactly clear or written anywhere. So as beings are doing it, such as Jesus, Ghandi, Dalai Lama, Buddha, etc... and as Tathagatas appear for their last incarnation in the Middle-verse, they leave road maps and clues for us and any other species that are arising out of the "Infinite Flower" to follow after.

Our species, our cultures, our language, everything is expendable, short lived, subject to extinction, etc...

But suppose we did survive to teach dolphins and chimpanzees how to do this upward vertical evolution... suppose Redwoods survive to teach Poison Ivy how to do this, then this would be the equivalent of the "gods" having taught us. Prometheus gave us Fire. Though Prometheus was a socially constructed metaphor for the rebellion from Zeus' natural authority over our human destiny, he also represents a real physical being a-la

the imagery conjured (art, stories) as well as the mental FACT that it touched millions of people as a real story. The spiritual plane (and therefore Triple-Plane Universe by completion) comes from his divinity and having passed into a higher consciousness of metaphor and legend.

So the question is, will parrots and dogs one day speak of humankind as their Prometheus, or Zeus (but in words strange to our ears)? Very likely according to the Recursive Multiverse. Very likely we are but like ants or fish in a tank, absorbed in our little reality, with little ability to detect what happens at the level beyond our Universe's stream.

The Five Devil Kings, the Four Demons, and the Death Devil

posted Apr 15, 2011, 2:21 PM by S RC [updated Mar 19, 2013, 1:45 PM]

In Mahayana you'll find reference to countless numbers:

- Thirty-two features
- 12 linked chain
- 80 characteristics
- Six paramitas
- 8 fold path
- Four Noble Truths, etc...

One of the more curious set are the four skandhas and the five devil kings. In Buddhism, since everything is a projection of the mind, this seems to be a strange superstitious belief. But the reason this is alien to our western minds is that we take so much literally rather than realizing that the Dharma is inherited from the Vedic system, in which the gods may not only reflect beings but even simple objects. There is a god in every household (or a devil), a god of a mountain, or a river, of marriage, of careers, etc... They are more akin to the Native American view of the spirit world which is used to explain movement of the Universe much as science uses today energy and fields and particles to describe things. They are not generally to be taken literally, although people who are incapable of understanding things on a deeper level (in this incarnation) will tend to. The Tathagata curve, based on $e=mc^2$ shows us that fully 80% of people at any given time will tend to see the Universe in this literal manner, occupying the first to seventh realms of Vibration.

But - remember - these things are projections of the mind, not anymore substantial than the chair one sits in, which is as thick as empty space (literally). It is merely in relationship that things take form, which requires consciousness. No consciousness, no form, no form, and no existence.

But what **are** these Devils and Demons? Quite simply: they are emotional states - vibrations - of the mind. Typically the subconscious and unconscious but sadly sometimes the conscious mind.

The Four Skhandas or Demons

These four are actually the sources of the description for the lowest four worlds in Buddhism (Realms in Bagua Dharma):

1. Garudas - those in absolute Hell or misery
 1. This is the realm of promise for those that are icchantikas/atheists, and those that continue the path of self-destruction (denial of the One Law)
2. Kimnaras - those that are in an animal only consciousness

1. For these, there is no good or bad, there just IS. That is why cannibalism is not evil, nor usury, or anything to these people, they are in a state of sociopathology.
3. Yakshas - or hungry ghosts; more on this in the Devil Kings
4. Asuras - or those full of hatred and unending rage

I feel certain that these are self explanatory. What I'd like to do however is talk briefly about the 11 Realms altogether and the Law of Resonance, which works with the Law of Vibration (the Realms) to determine Karmic output.

The Thing about numbers is that they have resonance in and of themselves. Each of the lower realms has a resonance (or two) with the upper realms. This describes the conundrum found within persons that, because of the presence of the triple-mind, they are actually experience a severance of intention and reception. It is confusing and downright cruel, but the Laws are unsurmountable and incontrovertible, so buyer beware!

Resonant Worlds

2,4,6,8 - the resonance of the apathethist. Apathy leads to kafka-like indifference, leads to whimsical judgment and amorality, leads to either tranquil-joy OR in the likely event of a miserable experience, revenge, a hallmark of the fourth realm. This self-satisfied prescience that "nothing really matters" becomes the justification for all things, and the self-knowing has only one reward: self-destruction.

8,4 - the problem of being an arhat in one life is that it leads easily, almost inexorably into the next life, and many to follow, as an ichantika. Moreover, the arhats when born into this Era of the Counterfeit Law experience only frustration and bitter resentment that people do not listen, do not understand. They are often well-educated atheists (I know from personal experience) whom practice either sophistry or are diligent debaters and believe fully in the Dharma of Doubt that so pervades the world since the rise of the Religion of Science (not that scientific methods are dogmatic, but the belief that they can know and solve all problems and all other religions are lies/false is clearly a dogma of reborn icchantikas).

3,6,9 - Fortunately for the the Yakshas, they have the pity and compassion of the Bodhisattvas or teacher/healers for it is often that the Yakshas envy or lust after the sixth Realm, and attach themselves to those in the ninth for fear of never acquiring enough to suit them. Moreover, when a person born as born into the sixth realm if by some mischance or karmic output they should lose that, they tend to occupy that third realm and wish after that which was once had and is now lost (barring of course they fall into a life of Hell because of some great misdeed!)

7,11 whereas the seventh realm is the gateway out of the lower six realms, the eleventh is the desired destination of billions worldwide. Let them that practice this harmony in

this life know that they shall have the doorway; but as to enjoyment of this world, it is better to know that $7+8+9=10 \rightarrow 11$. That is, study, practice, teach, and SERVE to get close. Do not merely ask, act and take advantage rather than be the victim of the Law of Karma.

5,8,11 Those that enjoy, and indeed are attached only to tranquility find the door through the seventh to the eighth EASY to pass through. One or two sutras or vedas, the Bible... and you're there. Remain humble as an Arhat and one will enjoy continual relaxed lifetimes if one continually observes the eleventh realm of God or Parinirvana in one's heart. The ONLY problem is...

1,3,5 This is the resonance of the demonic theft of tranquility and it likewise desires the same goal. It lusteth indefatigably after the same, but yet in denial of (and thus the source of the misery of self-born Hell). And as envy and revenge go hand in hand, it is not hard to be misled or finagled out of one's status as an arhat in this or any other lifetime. It's a game of russian roulette to practice the above resonance, and this is why

9,10,11 The upper three realms correspond to the upper great laws: Polarity, Resonance, and Karma, Karma being in fact the trigram of true Heaven whereas the sixth realm is merely the expression of Joy. The Law of Polarity is the trigram of fire or illumination, and the Law of Resonance which gives one access to the "good karma" or "evil karma" formed by the Polarity is represented by the Lake trigram (true Water). Water and Fire each have two Yang and one Yin, meaning that more of the mind is in the spirit and in the flesh. These three realms are the realms of the teachers & healers, saviors and gurus, Tathagatas or more pointedly the same Buddha Mind Everywhere, and the Source/Void/God, etc... They all have this in common: infinite love, compassion, and patience. Those that want the closest relationship to the 11th Realm or God should therefore abandon the seventh and eight realms as a destination and practice the ways of a bodhisattva and serve the Tathagatas. For them the prophecy of enlightenment is absolutely assured. For those that understand this paragraph, deep down, viscerally, they are enlightened already and need only begin to practice the service of their vow.

The Five Devil Kings

They are quite simple, really:

1. Attachment, Desire
2. Doubt and detachment
3. Greed, envy
4. Hatred
5. Fear

Fear is the only new one to add here, and it is fear itself which the devils delight in. For fear is what enables one to stray from the Light - the Source - and engage in creation of

these things which are not true or real, but are made real through misuse of the Minds. But rest assured, though these devil kings occupy the mind as surely as you can change your view of a cloudy, rainy day to a happy one, you can wipe out the armies of the devil kings at a whim. They will come back, because your momentum is not yet fully realized, but when they do: merely employ your bodhisattva powers and banish them again with the Light of the Christ or Shakyamuni or any other good Dharma. If you seek to understand them realize that their uses are confined to God's purposes, and do not overmuch use them for they will snare thee in a web of malice and evil in the end if you trust them one bit.

The Death Devil

He/she is based merely on this one thing: fear. To fear death, the afterlife, or the cycle of birth and death is to give power to something which had not formerly had power. What is death? It is merely the extinction of one's physical body and return to bliss-parinirvana - what is so frightful about that? Only that one fears to lose loved ones, one fears to lose one's work, and one's children. But my good man or woman I say to you this: the Tathagata hath said you have already indeed lost those except that you accept Him and believe unto Him and have Eternal Life. What does this mean? Simple enough - that when you exit those resonances that are lowest and move to the ones that are highest you will come to realize the Truth of Birthlessness, and realize that you are, through Knowing, as but one already dead. Chiefly your soul does not belong to you but to the Source (God) that your mind is not yours it is a fractal, a containment of the One in physical form, imprisoned merely by your Relativistic presence (or lack of presence)..That your spirit is one with mine and everyone's. What you do to me, or me to you, we do to ourselves. The illusion of separation is the product of the Law of Resonance in that the i-resonant becomes Yin (division) and the resonant becomes yang or Universal.

What have you then to fear from the Death Devil, the playchild of your mind, the inhabitant of your po-shen which craves form and experience. Your craving is a design, a device used to form new Universes, new realms, new galaxies... it is nothing which does you any good for it is in service to another, and that other is either the Devil King or the God... yet they are all the One Source. The free will is a gift, but it is as easily taken as anything else... there are billions of ways to die and only but four or five ways to live. As for Ways there really are only a handful which have any path out of the Forest and not all up the mountain of their own power, only for those with Strength and Volition to climb.

But enough of the Death Devil. I say to you this and this only: make him your puppet, not your king. The Tathagata is the only King worthy in this Physical Plane; and he has said time and again, fear not! Excepting of course you have something to fear, or rather rightfully respect, which is countless age after countless age of suffering for no other reason than one's service to the aforementioned Devil Kings.

~Shifu

The Ever-blooming Lotus

posted Mar 29, 2013, 4:07 PM by S RC [**updated Mar 29, 2013, 4:07 PM**]

What does it mean to say that a Lotus Flower "ever-blooms"? This means when the flower opens the stamens inside immediately open to another flower. If one were to zoom in upon the flower petals, one would also see ever-blooming Lotuses, and also their petals would be thus. Zooming out would see the first flower is merely upon the petals of previous lotuses.

The entirety of the system we refer to here reflects the Fractal nature of Reality. But the blooming, what does it reflect? The meaning of it is merely that wisdom comes to one of itself; and this wisdom is as expansive and varied as the reductionists' answers revealing more queries in their microscopic (ie: Socratic) approach to the world. However, whilst the reductionist world leads to a thousand myriad problems; the reverse process leads to cessation of karma and transcendence.

What does this mean for the practical, everyday user/individual? This means that no situation or blockage is permanent, no trap without an escape, no negative experience without a lesson that repays one threefold. Every single event, relationship, or experience unfolds to the betterment of the person towards the Self. Everything aids the Alchemical process and advances the Fire. Even recklessness and wasteful loss leads to INSTANT progress because of the mentality that is required to see the Ever-blooming Lotus in one's Dharma Eye.

How does this work? It works by eliminating the self/ego, and in doing thus and occupying the Buddha-mind or even the Buddha-stream, one progresses along a flawless path; even if for a short time. In doing so, one's emptiness becomes heavy. The heaviness draws in the light. Great drawing in draws great light and power. This leads, as previously mentioned, to the formation of the Diamond. The Diamond leads to clarity. The clarity leads to Vision. The Vision leads to the mindset which produces the Ever-blooming Lotus.

When the Lotus ever-blooms, no wisdom escapes oneself, no wisdom is impenetrable, it merely requires one to turn one's Eye towards it and focus with a laser-like intensity. In focusing, the full flow of a doctrine is revealed: where it came from, what it consists of, where it fits in a hierarchy of doctrine, where it leads; and ultimately is it healthy or unhealthy?

One can grasp a doctrine without being grasped by it. One can believe without it coming to encompass the entirety of one's self, diluting and deluding one from the central focus. For example one can appreciate a diet system's values without being trapped by the dogmatic cults of various obscure diets. Or for another example one can observe a political belief without becoming divisive to the point of nationalist fervor or hatred of others of different views.

In spiritual matters, an example would be that one can pursue the various practices that interest one without losing the point of a religion; or a religion without losing true spirituality. In thus being an 'ism' one is not contained by the 'ism' and instead contains and demonstrates the beauty of the 'ism' and can clarify its dark portions for those that are estranged from it.

This final wisdom or samadhi, is the ultimate point. The ever-blossoming Lotus is a tool to aid one in aiding others. It is not for aggrandizement of the self or putting a hierarchy between oneself at top and others at the bottom. If uses this way the lotus, like any fountain will dry up. But it only needs to be emptied again to flow once more.

The 11 Factors, 8 Awarenesses, and 3 Bodhi

posted Oct 20, 2010, 1:27 PM by S RC [updated Nov 1, 2010, 2:27 AM]

Once again, more information on how 11 and 8 keep showing up. The information from this article comes from either the Lotus Sutra - if you want more direct reading - or from the study of martial arts and mysticism in general. I would say it is superfluous, but once again, those who know of these have an enormous advantage in knowing about them personally rather than living without the knowledge at all and bouncing around life like a buoy in a stormy sea.

The 11 Factors

Originally the Lotus Sutra and the sagely inheritors: T'ien Tai, Dengyo, and Nichiren Daishonin called it the Ten Factors. We know from the Law of Relativity that this is because of the 10 humanly worlds are actually the first 10 vibratory realms of the Universe, the 11th being the Beyond or God or whatever you wish to call this singularity that contains and manifests all things.

It is through the 11 factors that it manifests all things, and science has forever been concerned with identifying these things, naming them, etc... but only in the Lotus Sutra and the commentaries of the above Buddhas do we see them listed skillfully and succinctly.

Here they are in verse form: Sho ho jisso, sho i shoho, nyo ze so, nyo ze sho, nyo ze tai, nyo ze riki, nyo ze sa, nyo ze in, nyo ze en, nyo ze ka, nyo ze ho, nyo ze honmak kuykyo to.

It means "this reality consists of:

1. Appearance
2. Nature
3. Entity
4. Power
5. Influence
6. Inherent Cause
7. Relation
8. Latent Effect
9. Manifest Effect
10. Consistency
11. From beginning to end

The last "Factor" has been split into its two yin-yang parts.

Science, as a rule is concerned with the study of the first four and, politics with the power and influence, religion with causes and effects, sociology and medicine with relation and latent effects, and physics with the sixth through tenth. But only sages seem to be concerned with all of them.

Lets look at each specifically.

Appearance is easy enough: it's what you see. But also it's what you can't see with your naked eye but only with your mind's eye, such as ideas, dreams, visions, imagination, and theories such as atomic, string, evolution, etc... which one cannot observe in real time but only with instrumentation and special methods. People often forget the things we've taken faith in and take for granted are really still just as fictional as magic or ghosts, because you do not perceive them directly but through your mental faculties which are as deluded as a drunk sailor mistaking a manatee for a mermaid.

Nature is the matter of those things which are found to act upon their own accord. It also manifests the 8 Laws. Entity is the divisible aspect of phenomena such as table, chair, tree, cat, person, whale, planet, etc...

Power is the factor that is the manifestation of Qi, energy, work, forces, fields, or anything that exerts influence.

Influence is based upon relation in that one cannot influence another without the other, so there is also the need for power and entity.

Inherent cause is both blatantly obvious causes such as crimes or activities, but also the causes made by thinking, imagining etc.. from Appearance. The nature factor is that which makes the 8 Laws move to manifest your mind into causes. Even without acting things go in a certain direction based upon the polarity of your mind towards unity or division: criminality vs completeness and wholesomeness.

Relation is that whereby the Law of Relativity perpetuates the relative causes to their relative effects, and is a central aspect to the Law of Karma or Cause and Effect.

Latent effect is what you cannot see, manifest effect is what you can. This is both temporal (now versus too long in the future to remember) and also the divine vs the humanly knowable, which is again the Law of Relativity in action.

Consistency is a reference to the connected nature. It is also a double or triple meaning for the 10th realm or the world of Buddhahood which enables an enlightened mind to perceive the interconnectedness of all things with the mind's eye which is now called the Buddha Eye.

The second part of that statement is "from beginning to end" and obviously is speaking of the 11th realm or the Beyond. The beginning to end shows the Law of Conservation's manifestation in containing all things and there being no end: no genesis nor Big Bang nor Armageddon, except for mankind as a species¹. The method by which the first ten factors are then manifest is through the Law of Evolution, the yang aspect of this pair, and it is only through these 4 Heavenly Laws above mentioned² that the 11 factors manifest It All.

The 8 Awarenesses

In my martial arts sessions I only generally speak on the lower six, which of course are most pertinent to people in a self-defense situation. But technically speaking there are 8 whole awarenesses that make up the one thing people call Awareness. There are plenty of sub-awarenesses just as there are sublaws and human laws. But here I will list them all, and the Law/trigram that they most relate to

1. Nature - Karma because this law is the king just as our natures and Mother Nature rule us
2. Environment - Evolution because our environment is constantly changing and adapting, so must we.
3. Situation - Relativity because the situation is relative to the POV of the person experiencing it and the objective witness
4. Reality - Conservation because this Law governs all containment of the 3 planes, 8 dharma, 11 factors, realms, aspects, and dimensions and the three ratios (golden, fibonacci, and 5/90/5 aka bell curve)
5. Choice of perception - Vibration because we set our own vibration by what we perceive
6. Karmic - Rotation - our vibration and choice of perception is what guides the rotation of the 11 aspects and 12 linked chain to weave our karmic tapestry.
7. Self - Polarity because this Law represents illumination of Fire and the act of attaining bodhi (situationally or further) through perception of the choice one makes and the directions it leads.

8. Dharmic (law) - Harmony because the awareness of the 8 laws themselves enables one to exist in harmony.

The reason that none of them directly match with themselves is because there is a need to relate all laws to each other through the 11 factors and 11 realms, thus enabling us to perceive the 8 awarenesses.

Being Aware is basically another term for anuttara-samyak-sambodhi.

The Three Bodhi

The first bodhi consists of eliminating ignorance and is called extinguishment. This means knowing in no particular order:

1. **Four Noble Truths**
2. **Noble Eightfold Path**
3. **12 Linked Chain of Karma**
4. 3 Planes [of heaven, man, and earth]
5. 3 bodhi [aka anuttara samyak sambodhi or nirvana, Nirvana, and Parinirvana]
6. **8 Laws**
7. 8 Awarenesses
8. **8 Meditation levels**
9. **11 Realms of vibration**
10. 11 Factors
11. **11 Aspects of Karma**

The second bodhi consists of eliminating the divisiveness of the first bodhi and is known as near perfect enlightenment. The requirement of Nirvana is to exist at the same vibration with own's environment. This is of course impossible at all time perse, because of the Law of Relativity. BUT however since each world contains the other 10 worlds and 10 factors and 3 planes² then one can be empty or ordinary and also have bodhi accessible at any time via the 8 Awarenesses and the use of the Buddha Eye.

Thus the third bodhi is known as perfect enlightenment and is the act of Nirvana and Parinirvana (death in this state aka the Return). It is a matter of wisely applying bodhi, concealing it at times and revealing it other times, always expediently, and always with kindness, compassion and without aggression or retribution, which divide. This bodhi is a lifetime of practice. By not sitting in the seat unless one should, it opens the door for others to as well.

Upon death the right frame of mind is thought to carry over with one's soul (or souls) into the heavens and the next life (lives) and thus one perpetuates the precise ratio of the Tathagata Curve with one's own life and actions. After all 5% of the people are

enlightened at any one time and carry 95% of the energy, whilst 90% of people in the Universe carry 4% and the last 5% only 1%.

This is because the fundamental nature of God is love and goodness, so only 5% of his body culls, the other 95% creates and evolves new things. But that is a discussion for another time.

Depth of the Daishonin

posted Nov 4, 2010, 10:53 PM by S RC [updated Feb 8, 2011, 2:50 PM]

I have read a lot of the writings of Nichiren Daishonin, but the depth displayed in the following Goshō, which is not one of his major treatises or commentaries or even a lengthy letter, just goes to show how one can be like a student swallowed whole by the deep wisdom of past masters.

There are probably no writers more well versed and at the same time so encompassing of their knowledge of Buddhist canon and non-Buddhist doctrines as well. I've learned more about Chinese and Indian culture reading his Goshos than through direct study.

The collection this comes from is called "The Writings of Nichiren Daishonin" and is a lengthy text of more than 1200 pages. They are generally arranged both by year and also by content matter. This single Goshō can be said to be the essential and theoretical teaching of the Buddha of the Latter Day of the Law¹ condensed into a very short prose piece found on page 486. It would be important - without much Buddhist study - to also read, "On Establishing the Correct Teaching," "Opening of the Eyes," and "The Sage and an Unenlightened Man". The Goshō "Letter to Horen" would also be a good confirmation of this teaching.

Reply to Lay Priest Soya

I have written out the prose section of the "[Expedient Means](#)" chapter for you. You should recite it together with the verse portion of the "[Life Span](#)" chapter, which I sent you earlier.

The characters of this sutra are all without exception living Buddhas of **perfect enlightenment**.² But because we have the eyes of ordinary people, we see them as characters. For instance, hungry spirits (3rd Realm) perceive the Ganges River as fire, human beings perceive it as water, and heavenly beings as amrita³. **Though the water is the same, it appears differently according to one's karmic reward from the past.**

The blind cannot see the characters of this sutra. To the eyes of the ordinary people [of the lower six paths]⁴ they look like characters. Persons of the two vehicles [of 7th and 8th Realms] perceive them as the Void. Bodhisattvas look on them as **innumerable doctrines**. Buddhas recognize each character as a golden Shakyamuni [Buddha]. This is what is meant by the passage that says, "If one can uphold this sutra, one will be upholding the Buddha's body." Those who practice with distorted views⁵ however are destroying this most precious sutra. You should simply be careful that, without differing thought [on the matter], you single-mindedly aspire to [anuttara-samyak-sambodhi]. A passage in the Six Paramita Sutra says to **become the master of your mind rather than let your mind master you...**

Third month (in 1275)

~Nichiren , reply to Lay Priest Soya

Speaking of Immeasurable Meanings, in the Gosho on page 493 shortly after this one, the Daishonin explains the meaning of time... I highly recommend his explanation of the principles of kalpas... and put it in context with the Law of Conservation. It's right there for you. Right in front of you!

Alkalizing and Acidifying the Self

posted Mar 29, 2013, 5:19 PM by S RC [updated Mar 29, 2013, 5:19 PM]

This is none other than what is meant by Reduction and Advancement. In acidifying, one leeches out the negative and removes the excess. In alkalizing one adds to the Basis; but one cannot do this without changing the elements.

What is this for? What is this about? Sometimes one has learned of something and it is not to be trusted as 100% accurate, not 100% pure. Perhaps the teacher wasn't pure in intent. Perhaps one was not sincere, not correct; or both. Perhaps one wanted originally to get to one thing but in manifestation one was unable to get what one wanted.

It is precisely at this time to first apply the acid process or "leeching" out of alloys to remove their negative darkness; then one can alkalize the remainder, transforming it from its unfortunate mundanity into a pure spiritual matter and then it can be added back to the Basis and help form the elixir.

What kind of examples can I provide?

I have heard people ingesting foreign drugs from untrustworthy people at large societal gatherings, wishing to see Reality... and have heard of people attending mystical gatherings or Native/Shaman proceedings that are held by incomplete leaders and teachers... both of

these allow small amounts of darkness to enter. I do not mean yin; there is always yin, but the yin is not true yin. It is dangerous here. And the open are sucked into the moment through sincerity but it isn't correct. Or they are correct but trust in the insincere. In the end the result is that there is an alloying effect to the new paradigm being revealed.

It is most unfortunate if people, because of this, throw it away in hopes of purifying themselves. This is like acquiring a kidney stone and ripping out the kidney. Or an ulcer and so removing the stomach.

People do not need to throw the baby out with the bath-water. They merely need to remove the negative subtly with acid and then take the remainder and apply a base to transmute it; then leave it and cool it.

What is this 'acid'? It is hard, honest truth that cannot be hidden from.

What is this base? It is a new Truth that transcends, changes, and illumines the entire flow of the previous alloy/defilement.

This is a thing I have personally done to remove and restore a harmed Ember that was and IS an essential part of my elixir. It has protected the other portions of the Elixir, as well as transformed the remainder back into its pristine state.

Applying the acid means using a dropper to carefully remove only what's needed and burn away the evil. Applying the base means SOAKING the small elixir in a base to get rid of the acid, transmute the free endings into smooth and pure surfaces. Then the piece has a protective incubating shell and can be stored indefinitely, without much loss day by day, awaiting the right time to attach back to the great Elixir and fire up again. Those who wish to hear the story of my example should ask in person for the hidden meanings behind this technique.

Basic Chinese Cosmology

posted Feb 21, 2012, 12:31 AM by S RC [**updated Feb 21, 2012, 12:33 AM**]

Here follows how I

-hitherto - understand Chinese cosmology. My growth in understanding reflects self-guided study. I do not belong to any particular school. If I can illuminate some understanding of the classics I will.

right: Norse Cosmology, not related but very cool.

The Basics

Chinese Cosmology is based on the Heavenly Branches and Earthly Stems, which in turn come from the animal zodiac and the basic yin and yang theory.

Yin is division and Earth, Yang is spirit and Heaven. So right from the name you know that everything has to do with Yin and Yang. Similar to the Mayan concept of three wheels of time each within the larger wheels comprising rotating epochs, the heavenly branches and earthly stems rotate.

Each day belongs to an element, yin or yang, and of course falls in an animal month, and all twelve **lunar** months happen in an animal year. There are 12 animals because there are 12 Earthly Branches.

When the calendar reaches the end of the solar year and time needs accounting for, the Chinese add a month that has no zodiac called "Ren Yue;" but other than this the months follow 30 day lengths (moon cycle is ~28-29 days).

See table:

E a r t h l y B r a n c h	M a n d a r i n n a m e	Japanese name		K o r e a n n a m e	Vie t n a m e s e n a m e	C h i n e s e z o d i a c	Dir e c t i o n	S e a s o n	Lu n a r M o n t h	Double Hour
		On	Kun							
1 子	zǐ	し (shi)	ね (ne)	자 (ja)	tý (Ti)	R at	0° (no rth)	w i n t e r	Mo n t h 11	11pm to 1am (midnigh t)
2 丑	ch ǒu	ち ϕ う (ch ū)	う し (ush i)	축 (c h u	sủ u	Q x	30°		Mo n t h 12	1am to 3am

				k)							
3寅	yí n	い ん (in)	と ら (tor a)	인 (in)	dà n	Ti g e r	60°	s p r i n g	Mo nth 1	3am to 5am	
4卯	m ǎo	ぼ う (bō)	う (u)	묘 (m y o)	mǎ o (m eō)	R a b b i t	90° (ea st)		Mo nth 2	5am to 7am	
5辰	ch én	し ん (shi n)	た つ (tats u)	진 (ji n)	thi n	D r a g o n	12 0°		Mo nth 3	7am to 9 am	
6巳	sì	し (shi)	み (mi)	사 (s a)	ty	S n a k e	15 0°	s u m m e r	Mo nth 4	9am to 11am	
7午	w ǔ	ご (go)	う ま (um a)	오 (o)	ng o	H o r s e	18 0° (so uth)		Mo nth 5	11am to 1pm (noon)	

8未	w èi	び (bi)	ひ つ じ (hits uji)	미 (m i)	mùi	G o at	21 0°		Mo nth 6	1pm to 3pm
9申	sh ēn	し ん (shi n)	さ る (sar u)	신 (si n)	thâ n	M o n k e y	24 0°	a u t u m n	Mo nth 7	3pm to 5pm
1酉 0	yǒ u	ゆ う (yū)	と り (tori)	유 (y u)	dâ u	R o o st e r	27 0° (w est)		Mo nth 8	5pm to 7pm
1戌 1	xū	じ ゆ つ (jut su)	い ぬ (inu)	술 (s ul)	tuá t	D o g	30 0°		Mo nth 9	7pm to 9pm
1亥 2	hà i	が い (ga i)	い(i)	해 (h a e)	họi	P ig	33 0°	w i n t e r	Mo nth 10	9pm to 11pm

As this indicates the cycle starts with Rat and goes to Pig. 2012 is Dragon, so chen is its earthly branch. Today being 2/20 that means that this is the month of the Rat because Chinese New Year only recently occurred. Remember it is a lunar calendar.

Now, there are ten Heavenly Stems, an ancient Shang era system for creating days of the week. When these are multiplied together they produce a 60 day cycle because the 5 elements are multiplied across the 12 branches on the yang side before switching to the yin side. $12 \times 5 = 60$.

C e l e s t i a l S t e m	C h i n e s e P i n y i n	J a p a n e s e k u n y o m i	J a p a n e s e o n' y o m i	K o r e a n (R R)	V i e t n a m e s e	<u>Yin</u> <u>and</u> <u>Yan</u> <u>g</u> (陰 陽)	<u>W</u> <u>u</u> <u>Xi</u> <u>n</u> <u>g</u> (五 行)	<u>W</u> <u>u</u> <u>x</u> <u>i</u> <u>n</u> <u>g</u> c o r r e l a t i o n s
1 甲	ji ǎ	ki n o e	k ō	갑 (g ap)	giá p	陽 (ya ng)	木 (w o o d)	東 Ea st
2 乙	y ǐ	ki n o t o	ot s u	을 (e ul)	át	陰 (yin)		

3	丙	b ĩ n g	hi n o e	h ei	병 (b ye on g)	bí nh	陽 (ya ng)	火 (fi re)	南 So uth
4	丁	d ĩ n g	hi n ot o	te i	정 (je on g)	đin h	陰 (yin)		
5	戊	w ù	ts u c hi n o e	b o	무 (m u)	m ậu	陽 (ya ng)	土 (e ar th)	中 Mi ddl e
6	己	jĩ	ts u c hi n	ki	기 (gi)	kỹ	陰 (yin)		

			ot o						
7	庚	g ē n g	k a n o e	k ō	경 (g ye on g)	ca nh	陽 (ya ng)	金 (m et al)	西 W est
8	辛	x ī n	k a n o t o	s hi n	신 (si n)	tâ n	陰 (yin)		
9	壬	r é n	m iz u n o e	ji n	임 (i m)	nh â m	陽 (ya ng)	水 (w at er)	北 No rth
10	癸	g u ǐ	m iz u n o t o	ki	계 (g ye)	qu ý	陰 (yin)		

To find out a year's number, you can use the steps in the Wiki article reproduced on the right.

Now, more important than the year or month is the energetic aspect of the day and even the hour.

The hours of a day are also divided into the Earthly Branches using again the animal zodiac, but more importantly have been correlated to the flow of the internal organs and channels' Qi. This means that one can know what the general energetic influences upon

and in benefit to any particular aspect of the individual by recognizing the time, day-type, and overall then the date; as well as looking at the alignment of far off celestial bodies.

Text Box

Thus, to find out the **Gregorian** year's equivalent in the Sexagenary cycle use the appropriate method below.

1. For any year number greater than 4 AD, the equivalent Sexagenary year can be found by subtracting 3 from the Gregorian year, dividing by 60 and taking the **remainder**. See example below.
2. For any year before 1 AD, the equivalent Sexagenary year can be found by adding 2 to the Gregorian year number (in BC), dividing it by 60, and subtracting the remainder from 60. See example below.
3. 1 AD, 2 AD and 3 AD correspond respectively to the 58th, 59th and 60th years of the Sexagenary cycle then.

The result will produce a number between 0 and 60, corresponding to the year order in the cycle; if the remainder is 0, it corresponds to the 60th year of a cycle. Thus, using the first method, the equivalent Sexagenary year for 2012 AD is the 29th year (壬辰; *rén-chén*), as $(2012-3) \bmod 60 = 29$ (i.e. the remainder of (2012-3) divided by 60 is 29). Using the second, the equivalent Sexagenary year for 221 BC is the 17th year (庚辰; *gēng-chén*), as $60 - [(221+2) \bmod 60] = 17$ (i.e. 60 minus the remainder of (221+2) divided by 60 is 17).

Examples

Step by step example to determine the sign for 1967:

1. $1967 - 3 = 1964$ ("subtracting 3 from the Gregorian year")
2. $1964 \div 60 = 32$ ("divide by 60 and discard any fraction")
3. $1964 - (60 \times 32) = 44$ ("taking the **remainder**")
4. $44 =$ Fire Sheep (丁未; *dīng-wèi*), see table.

Step by step example to determine the cyclic year of first year of the reign of **Qin Shi Huang** (246 BC)

1. $246 + 2 = 248$ ("adding 2 to the Gregorian year number (in BC)")

2. $248 \div 60 = 4$ ("divide by 60 and discard any fraction")
3. $248 - (60 \times 4) = 8$ ("taking the **remainder**")
4. $60 - 8 = 52$ ("subtract the remainder from 60")
5. $52 =$ Wood Rabbit (乙卯; *yǐ-mǎo*), see table.

That is the order of importance because the larger celestial objects have weak pull as compared to the moon, sun, and nearby planets. Mercury, for example, is very small and also very close to the sun and its effect is quite weak as compared to the effect of Jupiter which is massive. Yet Mars and Venus have more effect, but not as much as our nearest neighbor and controller of tides and human emotional and physiological cycles: the moon. The Moon is yin and the Sun is yang. These two constitute the largest extra-terrestrial forces *by far*.

However on earth the effect of yin and yang polar forces are also present.

The key to understanding things though is that everything works in "cohorts." Depending on the effect you are curious about, one must consider the level of cohort.

A society may have a yang day while another society has a yin day. Indeed some cultures are rising for the day while others are going to bed. This too, within the country some parts may have yang days and others yin days. And this is true too some friends may be having yang days and others yin days. And of course then it is up to each individual to determine where their energy falls in relation - vibrationally and spatially - to the larger energetic forces surrounding them: of friends, of society, or the world at large. For instance a person with fast-cycle type bipolarism will find they have a difficult time remaining on the same track energetically with the larger part of society. This means that their yin/yang cycles are different than the typical 1 per day as described above.

Now after this there is also the hexagram of the day to consider. This hexagram is based primarily on the prevailing energy of the day, and yet also upon the season and the date. But since the only way to acquire the hexagram (legitimately, not through an internet portal) is through one's own tossing, and each person has an individual toss for themselves, then there is no repeated, predictable form to this. Some hexagrams may last only a few hours as pertaining to a date, while the hexagram it flows into through the change may last days.

What is a hexagram?

A hexagram is a yin yang combination of two trigrams. A trigram is a three line representation of relative yin and yang properties in each of the 8 prime laws as correlating to Heaven, Man, and Earth. This triple plane system, when doubled as a yin (inner) and yang (outer) form a hexagram, and by math there are 64 of these. A hexagram also has changing lines as represented by minimal yin and maximal yang. When this happens they can invert themselves and the energy of the Universe flows (Dao in motion) into a new hexagram that is both informed by and yet distinct from the previous. On top of this there is a way of deriving the CORE energy from said hexagram and forming a new hexagram.

How to toss the Yi Jing is not the subject of this article, and one should attend a class to understand it.

The point is to understand what all these energies really mean.

Our body is surrounded by matter, electromagnetic energy, gravity, and inundated by radiation as well as many unknown effects from Dark Energy, Dark Matter, and even the Vacuum's energy. On top of this the psyche has a hitherto unexplored field of energy and should be understood to be a force upon us. Yet all of these things have something in common: the Law of Polarity or Yin and Yang.

If this is true then we may begin to see that how we approach and are approached by the world daily can reflect not necessarily a "fated" interaction (after all there is still the Chaotic principle of the Law of Evolution), but at least some form of "providence." That some actions will meet with more success because of favorable circumstances than other actions will that meet with unfavorable circumstances.

By using the Yi Jing, and paying attention to these forces, the Sage - or at least an adept individual - will discern and be able to guard against negative impacts to the psyche by knowing when to avoid an action or when to engage in it. This is basically the thinking and the reason for use.

The Chaos Effect

Unfortunately it appears that things may not - even in rotation - follow a linear path. A hexagram may progress out to another and then flow back in upon itself... or be carried

for for an extreme portion of time, or be so short as to be considered skipped altogether. Also yang days can follow yang days and vice versa. Or wood can, instead of flowing into fire, flow into water, its mother.

These effects are what provide "ripple" to the data stream and make "pulse reading" the Dao very difficult, and yet also very fun. Of course it isn't fun if we misread the day and feel it is a good day to go out and do something energetic and instead it turns sour on us. I recently, for example, started off very excited to go out and play basketball and not only had a ankle sprain but also received **terrible** news that day. Luckily my humor remained. But the point is that even in paying attention to one's inner rhythms one can misread the Dao. It is worth noting I had not consulted to oracle about playing basketball, so we will never know if the event was technically preventable, but I like to believe it was and hopefully I was not "fated."

The Main Point

The thing to take away from Chinese Cosmology (Astrology and Numerology) is that it has wisdom, fun, and utility in our daily lives. It is, of course, nothing to become obsessed about. At one time in Chinese history the people would do nothing from going on trips to even burying the dead without calculating a good day. This was very interesting because they also had no precise way to measure the minutes or seconds of the clock, so there was a dichotomy that may reflect some level of superstition. As a scientific society we want to respect the fact of cosmological forces without being tied down to a dogmatic ritual. Rituals and rites are the backbone of a good traditional society, but can also keep a society backwards in its thinking, and unable to obey the changes required in adaptation by the Law of Evolution. In observing any ritual - from tossing the Yi Jing to reading a fortune cookie, one should take the omens and oracles with some measure of truth and seriousness, and yet also light-heartedly. After all, quantum physics has taught us that just because something appears one way or likely to be one way doesn't mean it is a certainty, it may in fact be the **uncertainty** that is most true and most probable. In this way, perhaps, Godhead hopes to play us all for fools to teach us humility.

Nirvana Explained

posted Aug 18, 2010, 3:33 PM by S RC [updated Aug 26, 2010, 11:32 PM]

Dear Reader, this paragraph has a threefold purpose:

- Apology - I am not, of course, able to explain everything in sufficient detail, nor can I teach you the best way to achieve the 2nd attainment of nirvana (Nirvana from now on). As for myself, and I'm not ashamed to admit it, I had to use psychedelics to experience **Suchness (tathata)** and though I will never forget it, how I lament that I've not yet done it properly. Realize, reader that as a good friend and Bagua master pointed out, *"We're supposed to see things like that using our meditation (Qi Gong)."* This means you should be able to increase synaptic processes and flow of blood

sufficiently without using something that disturbs the Ming Men fire and causes it to surge upwards unnaturally through the Du Mai. Supposedly a monk once challenged a westerner to give him a cup of LSD and after taking it, reported no "hallucinogenic affects". This would indicate he was already quite capable of Suchness through his samadhi. That is the best way to see Nirvana.

- Promise - if you study this (and other articles before it, and the Lotus Sutra) I promise you will mentally understand the theory of nirvana, and then consequently the subsequent attainments, Nirvana and Parinirvana. But visceral knowledge - believe me I know personally - is far more powerful and important than mental awareness. Why? The viscera contain the 3 souls of the shen, hun, and po, which govern your higher self. Using the yi (intellect) and zhi (memory/will) to gather data is ultimately pointless because the shen, hun, and po are the parts connected to the body and therefore produce karmic action and dictate your results. This is KEY.
- Warning - if you are not ready to understand this... you will not. If you cannot - perhaps will not - and deny it, you are only harming yourself. Reader, do NOT go further if you have not thoroughly understood previous articles and studied. A seed of doubt can go a long ways towards self-denial, God-denial, and therefore ultimately lack of Attainment and completion. If you are not verse in math, that is not a problem... not only will I explain all diagrams in detail, but there will be a separate article on Universal Constants. You should, however, review the **Multiple Dimensions** article prior to reading this...

Title: Moving toward The Consciousness. Simply amazing.

First, as mentioned in the **Reincarnation** article, and in **Chapter 6 of the Louts Sutra commentary**, nirvana, or extinction+emptiness must not be regarded as a goal in and of itself.

Why has it therefore been emphasized? If you understand human nature you will know three things:

1. People are born, in all cases, in the lower 6 realms, and live in varying degrees of them as far as their education and Karmic Jing (essence literally from one's parents) force them to. In varying cultures, escape from this is encouraged through religion and spirituality (study) because as the Yi Jing notes, when the **Tian Gui flows**, Yang is penetrated by Yin and through the degrading process of Wind (Law of Evolution) the person enters River trigram, signifying trouble due to lust and attachment to the 5 desires. As they age, the Yang is stripped away by this [false] yin until death comes, without attainment.
However, with spiritual study, and the act of voice-hearing, one can enter back upon the Way and complete the Meaning of Life.¹
2. People being born this way, seek an escape because a) they are told it's bad to be like this or b) they actually realize their danger "in the River" and seek the other shore, rather than go down this river alone.
3. People then, having embarked upon the 7th realm seek an end goal... and give up easily because, after all, they are told the 8th realm is where it is at. Preachers do not tell people they have to become preachers... they tell them to come to church weekly and do study. The good ones tell them to preach and share in their life - proselytize - but few sell that idea as good as Christ, the "fisher of men."
In the 8th realm, satisfaction is actually, relatively good - and we'll see why later - so few people wish to pursue it any further, figuring they've gone far enough. This is, of course, not the case, and in the case of nirvana, is definitely a mind-made trap.

Thus the goal is not nirvana, which is simply a state of mind one can choose whenever convenient, saying at unpleasant or down-time opportunities, "I am one with the Universe... there is no self... the grass is always greener on the other side... make lemonade out of lemons... etc..." and any other 'serenity now' statements.²

So before we go much further in explaining nirvana, let us define what it is, and what it is for...

1st nirvana is the state of mind of "letting go" and experiencing suchness, nowness, oneness, etc... all the aspects of the Life Aquatic. It is a time-dependent state, you experience it whenever you do the steps to attain it on the Body, Mind, and Spirit levels. The method almost rarely matters, because it is the free window view to the 11th realm... but it is not the door. Just as a jailed inmate looking out at the world experiences peace and escape from prison in the mind and spirit, but not the body, that is this particular situation EXACTLY.

2nd nirvana (Nirvana) is a bodily shift of vibration in order to harmonize with the 10th realm, the **only door to the 11th realm**. [see for Tathagata Curve, or see below]

It has all the characteristics of the 1st attainment, without any of the downsides... excepting perhaps that it is energy dependent (due to Law of Relativity and you having a massive body), and your strength with it depending wholly on your:

- Experience
- Understanding
- Vibration
- Destiny
- Capability

This Nirvana - I will warn you now - can be frightening... and not all psychedelics experiences lead here. For me, personally, I chanted into the state, and asked for it, and I was definitely not ready... but without it, reader, and perhaps this was my destiny, I could not write this article for you.

3rd nirvana or Parinirvana is entering death's door through the great gate of the Tathagata (suchness)... meaning either you mentally and spiritually have harmonized and know the laws thoroughly, or you are in physical rapture (trance) when death comes, and you enter what is known as True Nirvana. This is the end goal after attaining the Meaning of Life. There is no other worthier goal for you at death than this. At this point you mentally are at peace with being in the 11th Realm and you enter it physically and no longer attached to the body can sustain understanding of it - and yet you will cease to be you... but more on that later.

Now, as I illuminated in [Chapter 2](#), [Chapter 3](#), and [Chapter 4](#) of the [Lotus Sutra commentaries](#), there are many pathways to the 9th realm, and as the next future article will show, I know of at least 2 culturally different versions of the one Buddha Vehicle (Jesus and Shakyamuni)... but Nirvana and later Parinirvana are the only *living* pathways to the 11th realm.³

Thus concludes the definitions. The final section, reader are a series of diagrams which explain the 11 realms, the 8 Laws, and the exact mathematical landscape of human life and why we experience these things:

- cyclical emotions
- highs and lows
- cycles of disease
- ability to like some people but not others
- ability to get along with some but not others
- ability to mate with others
- ability to accomplish life's tasks, goals, and dreams

 The following diagrams I have constructed with 5 years of cogitation and development, 5 years of math and science background, 8 years of martial arts and 2 years (in this lifetime) of Chinese Medicine background. They are my masterpieces of sharing the Buddha Vehicle with you, and explaining Nirvana so that you, dear reader, hopefully can have the attainment you deserve.

First up is the "Tathagata Curve"

which explains the spiritual energy from the exponential perspective. This diagram, not ironically, is displaying Kinetic Energy of a mass approaching the speed of light, here set at "1", which acts as an asymptote and explains why only the Tathagatas, who are near to it, can open the door to the 11th Realm.

This means Jesus, Buddha, Ghandi, Mother Theresa, and whoever else you see evidence of being able to open the door for others and exhibiting living in Nirvana.

The AUC or Area under Curve represents the sum total of energy they contain... as you can see the Tathagata has as much energy allocated to him as all the other 9 realms combined... and this is a mathematical function (ratio) of the Universe... such that at any given time, someone somewhere is in the 10th realm, and together with the 5th-9th are offsetting the great amount of negativity and woe we see in our news and on our streets today.

Figure 1 - the Tathagata Curve

Now, of course the curve is not 'smooth' just as life isn't smooth. Firstly it is build of tiny plateaus, millions that no one can see and only the results can be analyzed. Also there are daily ups and downs, weekly ones, monthly, even yearly for the majority of people. The more you smooth these bumps out - called turbulence - the less energy lost in

your upward journey. The following is just an illustration, I have not altered it from the creator to suite my purposes, but it will do.

Figure 2 - turbulence creates different paths for different people.

Moving along, let us examine extensively the Vibratory curves of the 11 realms and then the aspects of the 10 humanly realms. The images are large, please click them to enlarge in another window. I apologize for the hand-drawn crudeness of these diagrams, I hope one day to be able (or to inspire another to) create a 3D, perfect mathematical version.

Figure 3 - the 11th Realm or Oneness (relative-less perfection)

This diagram, if studied and cognized (penetrated to the point of complete understanding) can open the way for someone to enter samadhi once (strong Qi Gong with the purpose of

achieving Nirvana) and come out the other end as a Mahasattva or Tathagata... literally breaking down the door to Nirvana.

Now for each of the vertical scales, or amplitudes, I used the 10 human realms (of Buddhism) plus the 11th of God. If you have not reviewed them in full, in brief they mean this: Hell is misery, Animals is senselessness (no wisdom in action and pure aggression), hungry ghosts is lust and greed and envy, Asuras is anger, rage, and hatred, calmness is meditative or occasional serenity, Heaven is joy, ecstasy, love, happiness, satisfaction, etc..., voice-hearers are students, arhats or pratyekabuddhas are the self-realized, bodhisattvas are teachers, mahasattvas are teachers of the Way to Buddhahood, and Buddhahood is true Tathagata enlightenment.

I have also taken the time to explain how each of the **8 Universal Laws (Bagua Dharma)** play into this picture [they are labelled 1-8]. As you can see, study of the Bagua Dharma is merely a lower vehicle (though very advanced, and cultivated from many religions and science) to explain the ultimate Law of the 11th Realm.

I have also listed some formulas which are the governors of the laws in question. I have also listed greatest yin, reverting yin, and greatest yang on the diagram...

Figure 4 - the 10 Humanly Realms (relative imperfection)

Whereas the last diagram is given to indicate the perfection of Parinirvana and death... figure 4 is shown to indicate a) Nirvana, b) how the various levels correspond to each other, and c) the problems of the lower realms.

Notice first that the realms are divided into 3 groups, Superior, Middling, and Inferior. The Superior realms (8-10) all indicate forms of consciousness most closely associated with oneness. The Middling realms (5-7) are realms that have a much better view than the Inferior realms, albeit with more "ups and downs" than the Superior realms. The Inferior

realms (1-4) are the worst in closeness to the 11th realm (God), and also they are more difficult life states.

I want to point out several characteristics that are important concepts here.

1. Note that the 7th realm actually has access to oneness, this represents the student who is constantly harmonized with their teacher, and whose vibration has become entangled with that frequency.
2. Note that the lower the vibration, the more rapid the frequency as a rule... this prevents the feeling of oneness while also acting as to give the person more opportunity to change their situation via the Law of Rotation.
3. Note that the lower four realms are none whatsoever good... but Hell in particular is the worst because circumstances, emotions, disease conditions, financial situations change so rapidly there that the individual often gives up out of frustration and tries to cheat at every turn to get ahead.
4. Note that higher highs mean lower lows... but in the case of the Superior realms, which are none whatsoever bad, more yin time means more cultivation, silence, reflection, and nourishment as it is True yin... while in the lower six realms, the lower Yin is a mix of this and also actual false yin (bad experiences).
5. Note that the natural separation of the realms denotes mutual affinities for other realms. Those born in higher realms will not see those born in lower realms as pleasingly, while the lower realms will find reasons to bash or "bring down" the upper realms, saying things like, "rich people are evil," or "money isn't everything," etc... Their language is typically fouler as their thoughts are more negative and conditioned by negative experience.
Meanwhile, movement into the upper realms is possible for anyone.
6. Note that though that is true, those in the lowest realms, especially Hell are usually satisfied (and unable) to move beyond the 7th Realm and are apt to seek "saviors" rather than save themselves, and will repeatedly be pulled back and forth through the door to the 7th realm (since the lower 6 are the human norm).
7. Note that the time spent in the 5th-7th realms is roughly half that of the lower realms, thus the importance of exiting those varied frequencies and entering the Superior realms, which still experience the others but are known as the states of non-regression.
8. Note that governance of exiting the lower realms for the higher is still governed by the Tathagata Curve.

Figure 5 - Phasing and frequency shifting (Relativity)

This diagram represents the remainder of human (and animal, spirit, plant, etc...) existence and why people are different. Note first that we are observing one single Vibration, not all 10. Secondly, note that the "phasing" of each vibration string represents one individual. This also means that the less "out of phase" people are, especially with each other as they communicate (and thus the importance of correct mating) the closer they are to exhibiting the nature of the 11th realm which has no out of phase nature. The further out of phase one is, the more destructive... to the point that if completely out of phase with the One, then death is imminent (usually violently so because of the **Law of Harmony's strict rules about co-existence**).

Also, please notice that some individuals within a vibration can exist on a higher frequency... and indeed we all do somewhat (mass X mind X spirit where X means "cross" and refers to matrix algebra multiplication to form a new subset). This is because of varying ages, life experiences, educations, accumulation of wisdom, views, paradigms, and especially psycho-somatic disease processes. (We are all mentally ill somewhat or we would have no ego and then be dead/part of 11th realm).

The more intense a frequency of an person in relation to their cohort of vibrations, the more out of touch or difficult to understand this person may be... that does not mean they are further from the Y -axis (Source)... the remainder of the cohort, through group-think (like cults or corporations, or whole governments like Nazi Germany) can be the ones out of phase... but it does typically mean they are in danger and should seek Harmony elsewhere. An individual can affect their frequency through many methods, but usually Qi gong and acupuncture are the best for strong shifts... herbs and lifestyle/habit changes are slower shifts.

But an individual can only change their Vibration by one of the two following methods:

1. Sudden (shock) enlightenment; like Satori or the bodhicitta or being "saved" and born-again

2. Constant spaced repetitious work; like meditation (samadhi), martial arts, helping heal others, religious studies, etc...
 1. this changes the current vibration, like **quanta moving an electron** up or down valence shells.

In general, the 1st method is better for movements in the Superior realms, and the 2nd for the Middling and Inferior realms, but there are no hard and fast rules there... In fact, moving up too fast can damage one's path by creating pride and that lower realm vibration will bring one back down. In general, however, externalizing one's path (asking for others to change) never works and almost always lowers one to the lowest realms.

Please note that though it may be possible to offset the same curves up or down away from the X-axis, I do not know what that would represent, so I have not put it here. My wife theorizes it would mean a strong mental illness like schizophrenia.

In conclusion, I want to point out that each person has their own vibration, they are mixed with others, and there groups are networked like a series of neurons or cells in a leaf... and all these vibrations do not remain 2D but in fact take up all eleven dimensions, which enables the world to have its various shapes, hues, sizes, and aspects that makes it interesting.

This "surface tension" that results is perhaps best visualized by the image of water droplets rippling the surface of a pond. The center representing the central 11th realm and the other little ripples the mixture of other lesser vibrations so that all in all it is all quite turbulent (either in the center where things are most curved or out at the side where the ripples are chaotic).

Figure 6 - what does the reflection represent to you?

But like in the image, there lets loose this one droplet, that is like a soul dying and going to God... or like a God giving birth to a new Universe... or a mother to a baby... or a writer to a new book... [etc...] Let this inform you as to your goals and dreams. And if this article

helped you to see the nature of Reality as-it-is in the **Life Aquatic**, then my job is done. As always, comments or questions are greatly appreciated.

Moreover, even within the same Vibratory level, of course people are more often than not out-of-phase meaning they cannot understand one another's speech thoughts, and actions. See A-E

Phasing is not eliminated until the 11th Realm (death of ego/body - all 5 Shen) but the 10th & some 9th/8th realm can change phase at will/need hence the ability to get along with more people & see Sameness (Hexagram

Also, within this same vibratory level (Realm) or Amplitude in mathematics, some individuals operate at higher or lower frequencies relative to others in their Realm. This may be due to age, experience, culture/language, religion, or even psycho-somatic disease. Excepting the 10th Realm, we all have some form/degree of mental illness, so this explains why we can sense when others in our realm or lower realms are 'a bit off/crazy'.

As you can see, it takes little energy to remain in lower 6 realms (here the .6 and below). But each of the upper 4 gets more difficult. Only at a true Tathagata can pass the 10th barrier of no remainder in life... all others must await death.

Shen Disturbance

posted Feb 14, 2013, 10:07 AM by S RC [updated Feb 14, 2013, 10:41 AM]

Shen is one of the "three treasures" of the body in TCM. Jing, Qi, and Shen. There are 5 elements of the Shen: shen-spirit, hun-soul, po-body's soul, yi-mind/intellect, and zhi-Will. It's not specified if it is Free Will. Just Will. I'm not covering the five elements here.

Now the combo of yi-shen, hun-shen, and po-shen are the conscious, subconscious, and unconscious mind or super-ego, ego, and id for Freudian terms.

It's said that the blood follows the Qi, but qi follows Shen, and Jing is the mother of them all and is from the Water-Kidney system. (Kidney incl. kidneys and most of endocrine and reproductive system)

So shen disturbance is not necessarily mental illness, although mental illness is an extreme of untreated shen disturbance. Sometimes discerning if the body or the mind causes the shen disturbance is impossible, or at least unimportant for treatment because both are heavily out of balance.

There are 4 main causes of Shen Disturbance (and subtypes may be included):
Of the type that WANT to be treated:

1. Elemental Imbalance; usually congenital, either genetic, birth defect, or inherited from parents/homelife, prolonged exposure to the atmosphere - a condition of societal neglect that reflects family neglect - will lead to shen disturbance in most people.
2. Soul UnAnchored (aka "fuzzy soul"); usually caused by shock, trauma, PTSD, possibly rape/betrayal, sometimes drugs or poor meditation technique, etc... occasionally people are pre-disposed to this. In a few cases I've seen mothers with this PPM because of the loss of blood drained the kidneys and they have not enough Qi. The nature of the fuzziness will reflect the cause. Lack of anchor usually means a rising aura/mind that seems unrooted. They cannot really relate to people. Whereas trauma usually makes the person appear fuzzy and on the verge of tears.

Of the type that REFUSE to be treated:

3. Phlegm Induced; Phlegm is created by either the prolonged influx of dampness that is cooked over time by the Qi, OR by the cooking of normal body jade fluids (jin-ye) because of disease or lifestyle. This phlegm can only be removed by cough or bowels... dampness can be urinated away, but the kidneys do not do phlegm well. However, when there is ascendant Liver Yang, wind, or Heart/Stomach Fire, the heat in the blood and lymph carries the phlegm upwards into the head, such as stroke, MS, Parkinson's, Alzheimer's, schizophrenia, certain epilepsy conditions, etc... In some cases there are cognition and personality changes, and in other cases there aren't because the yi may not be involved.

4. Toxic-Soul; This person has an infected aura, usually because of abuse or repeated trauma, sometimes prolonged exposure to incorrect doctrines. Their programming may be turned towards the negative and always the only thing they can think of is the negative, because that is their experience. This doesn't mean if anyone isn't 100% positive they are shen-disturbed. Here we're talking about a very intense level where they have difficulty relating to others without anger or feelings of paranoia and persecution. Toxic souls may appear red or green in aura to the intuitive. But in their faces you will see more definite signs in the form of eye shape, color changes, etc...

All shen disturbance makes evidence in the face or personality. Obviously the most difficult to spot is the ever-chameleon sociopath. Often they appear charming and helpful, with a smile. Seeing through the mask to signs of disease may involve pushing their buttons when they least expect it, or perhaps recognizing that their smile never makes crinkly eyes. Also if the person feels betrayed if they flip into retribution/vengeance mode before feelings sadness, grief, or trying to communicate, these are signs that the shen is not in balance.

A person can have multiple types of shen disturbance, and also different people have different thresholds. A person can acquire fuzzy shen from a single unrelated news report that strikes them at their childish heart; whereas a homeless man can be inundated with phlegm from drugs, booze, and exposure and never wish harm or ill will on anyone, even if they cannot deal with their own life. Rich, handsome young men can become shen-disturbed into homicidal monsters for nothing other than perceived neglect, while neglected and abused orphans can become popular and gifted singers who simply cannot relate to their emotions and so sing them out from deep within.

MY final point being (since this isn't about treating shen disturbance): be careful about judging someone's insanity because we're all projecting mild forms of

shen disturbance if not worse. They thought Jesus was a nutter and in their own disease flailed and crucified him; and Devadatta went insane with jealousy of his cousin the Buddha, and so tried to murder him and drove a prince to murder his father and become besotted with leprosy... A person may appear CRAZY, but maybe they know something we do not.

If anything I've learned is have compassion for shen disturbed people they just want to be loved. Love may be the ONLY cure for a sociopath.

The San Jiao - Triple Burner

posted Jun 25, 2011, 10:28 PM by S RC [updated Jun 26, 2011, 12:05 AM]

Please first read the [Liver \(LV\) Depression Article](#). The LV controls the GB, which is tied to the San Jiao via the Shaoyang aspect. Also the LV and Kidney (KI) are closely related and this reinforces the effect of the LV on the SJ. So many things explained in that article will be implied in this article.

The Triple Burner

The San Jiao is not an extraordinary organ in Chinese Medicine. As a matter of fact, it is not really an organ at all, but two important systems (and of course the meridian that controls them). But in this case the meridian access is totally eclipsed by the size/magnitude of the internal meridian which is very poorly understood.

The San Jiao literally is divided into three parts: Upper, Middle, and Lower.

When we look at the functions, however, of the SJ "bowel" we find three very important aspects:

1. It regulates and connects all the parts of the body, uniting the upper, middle, and lower organs and extra tissues.
2. It regulates fluid movement using the Qi provided by the Lung and Kidney complex.¹
3. It regulates the interstices and pores.

In the olden times the concept was that in each "burner" there was a kind of oven or boiler that would use the Ming Men or Ministerial Fire² to heat the fluids and move them about the body. Clinically speaking we also know that disease also tends to be generally limited to regions in the body - head/arm and upper chest, abdominal, and lower abdominal/legs.

So what structures, biomedically speaking, fit the bill:

Clearly the regulation of fluid movement and metabolism is related to the lymphatic system. Indeed when we see the so-called shaoyang syndromes, most of them are a case of pathogens lodged in or around lymph nodes or between tissues where the body has a difficult time to expel them for one reason or another, hence the concept of "in between" pathogens.

But also looking at the body's anatomy, and why disease itself seems to be self-regulated to certain levels such as upper, middle, or lower, we notice that the body has also a unique venous return system. The bottom part of the body connects to the Inferior Vena Cava along with the lymph of 3/4 of the body. The head and arms, along with the upper lymph system dump into the Superior Vena Cava.

Portal Venous System

Meanwhile the abdomen has the Portal and Mesenteric Veins which literally are used to move blood with digested nutrients through the liver before dumping back into the Vena Cava and into the heart. This is the "Middle Jiao"

Mesenteric Venous System

SJ microcosm

So there are literally "three jiaos" in the body and the totality of lymph, lymph nodes, and venous return, a sizable portion of the body's fluids, are at any one time governed and maintained in the SJ "bowel."³

San Jiao Channel

The SJ mai or meridian however absolutely dwarfs the SJ bowel by comparison. How do we know this?

The San Jiao is said to control and regulate the pores and interstices (lumen), meaning the in-between layers of the body, right down to the cellular level and every fluid pathway in between cells and within the cells themselves.

This may seem impossible that a bowel without a central nervous system would do this, but please remember that while the Du Mai or CNS has ultimate authority in the body, for the most part the body regulates and runs itself. Every cell has its own programming and its own nucleus. Literally each cell is its own microcosm of a government, with its own sovereign in the center (nucleus), its own factories (mitochondria), its own SP/ST transport centers and organelles. Each of the 12 bowels is represented within each cell, along with the aspects of Yin, Yang, and the complex relationship of Qi and Fluids. [I will write a separate article on this at another time.]

That means that *something* must move those fluids about and that is the Qi of the SJ channel.

Moreover it is not just the body that has pores and holes for disbursing fluids and hormones through the blood or out of it as sweat... the cells themselves have pores in their **bilayer phospholipid membranes**. Though the receptors are governed by Yin and Yang, mostly of the KI, LV, and DU, the gateways are controlled by the SJ.

How is this possible? In TCM we understand that the Shen has the Po aspect or corporeal soul. This is basically speaking, the body's "mind", and we know that the body does many things of its own accord without any central nervous input. Cell reproduction, DNA scripting, immunity, storage of certain nutrients are guided by an unknown intelligence or some sort of mathematical complexity that has not been fully understood. This is what the Chinese call the Po.

In society the Po is the consciousness that causes us all to wake up in the morning, clean ourselves, go to work, pay our bills, raise our kids, and behave. If all these things were literally driven by a central government, we'd need 1000 people to govern a single person. Luckily we teach each other how to live and act and this social conscious connection is the Po in macrocosm. In the body the Po pretty much governs >99% of activity while the CNS, PNS, and ENS or Shen-Hun (psyche) govern only a bit. It is far less the CNS that performs many duties but the glands and other parts that work with them that do. (Much like the agencies of vast central governments).

It may seem to you that **you** are doing quite a bit, but relatively speaking, *you are moving in slow motion compared to these structures* which are not only tiny, but many move very quickly. ATP-synthase produces hundreds of millions of ATP molecules from ADP every second in order to keep you alive, and neurotransmitters are being manufactured, used, and reabsorbed at the speed of light in many cases.

Thus the San Jiao channel is not simply these in between spaces, but the small nervous system connections and synapses between nerves that connects all this together, and enables the Du (CNS) to govern at all.

Let me make that clear: the SJ mai itself is the tiniest nerve endings and connections and even electromagnetic fields from bonds that guide the cells of the body to act in accordance with the central control system.

For every venuol, capillary, gland, muscle fiber, or tissue there is either a nerve bundle or some other self-guided connection system of membranes. This super connection is the Po, and definitely regulated via the SJ/LU fluid metabolism system.

Thus the SJ mai is not only the 23 points on the body but in fact the largest channel in the body by surface area and scope of use.

The Alveolar Complex and Glomerulus-Nephrons are of the LU and KI organ respectively, but rely on the SJ "organ" or tissues and the SJ channel to govern fluid transport.

And yet, sadly, it is the least understood and utilized "organ-channel" system in TCM.

Fortunately the Shaoyang and Liver are better understood, and in many cases, dredging the Shaoyang and the Liver (cleansing) either emotionally or physically (through herbs, sweat-lodges, etc...) can clear out the SJ.

But the fact remains that fluid and blood stasis are some of the most common secondary signs in the middle aged and even now

young adults. Varicosities show up usually starting in the KI3/7 areas and work their way back up the legs. Often this clinical sign goes unnoticed or unappreciated for its devastating long lasting effect.

If the channel cannot flow, the organ becomes stagnant. If the organ is stagnant the emotions of the Po will become stagnant, and lead to seemingly unknown emotional affects that adversely effect the health and happiness of the patient. And of course could possibly lead to complications of phlegm and HT Blood stasis (clots) and heart disease.

Caused by KI Yang (and SJ) deficiency

So it is important to constantly "dredge" the shaoyang. Be active, receive massage, cupping, and gua sha. Get rid of varicosities, tonify the KI Yang (Ming Men fire), and eat warm foods to enforce the movement of fluids in the veins.

This is absolutely vital to the continued health of the individual once they have LV depression syndrome under management.

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Add files

Comments

S RC

S RC

Jun 25, 2011

3 - Zang=viscera and are supposed to be hollow. Fu=bowels and are supposed to be empty.

One is yin, the other yang. One stores, the other moves. However, in the case of the

Pericardium and San Jiao, the relationship is not quite the same. While the Pericardium is a tissue of very specific function: protection of the Heart, and does not store anything, the San Jiao is a very large, dynamic structure with an even vaster channel, and stores/moves a great deal of fluid and blood. The San Jiao is absolutely NEVER empty, though it is made up of many tubes and lumen.

One other area the San Jiao has some influence over is also the CSF or cerebro-spinal fluid. It likewise is never empty, and has many similarities in function to the Pericardium in terms of protection. So the relationship of zang-fu here has little to do with the internal structures and more to do with the fact that the channels are located on the dorsum of the hand, which is yang (SJ) and the palmar side, which is yin (PC). Any other relationship is quite superficial. PC is definitely Sovereign Fire, but as we have seen the SJ is most closely related to Ming Men Fire which is more related to the Water Element.

[Reply](#)

S RC

Jun 25, 2011

2- Ministerial Fire is the active/mobile "fire" of the body's natural Yang. The sovereign fire of the Heart is not supposed to move or be affected, thus the body has ministers which move about. In reality this is the difference drawn between the complex body maintenance of metabolism and temperature performed by the endocrine system, liver, kidneys, and CNS... and the simple "fire" of the heart pumping warm, oxygenated blood around. One is very active, dynamic, and complex. The other is a very static, regular relationship called the Pulmonary System. The Ming Men or life gate refers to the more dynamic aspect.

[Reply](#)

S RC

Jun 25, 2011

1 - It is said that the Lungs regulate the water of the body by dispersing Qi like a cloud would disperse rain. Meanwhile the Kidneys of course actually filter the fluids at a high rate. The two also form a complex relationship where certain adrenal hormones (KI Yang Qi) "grasp" the Lung Qi and enable breathing. This is the complex.

Mahayana Alchemy

posted Mar 16, 2013, 11:48 AM by S RC [updated Mar 16, 2013, 11:48 AM]

Taken from the Sacred Circle Alchemy Group

Okay, so before I write on Alchemy let's start with the basics and terms and chronology/history.

People should know that NOTHING was officially written for several hundred years when the Pali Canon also called the tipitaka was created in Sri Lanka.

So EVERYTHING is a subjective echo.

Secondly - and this is a phenomenon we've seen later in things like judo and aikido - the early teachings and his end of life teachings differ fairly heavily.

How to account for this? The Buddha's enlightenment at the bodhi tree was not the end of learning. It was simply the 'final' bodhicitta in a series of lifetimes. His journey back to parinirvana was a culmination but not starting at 0 and ending at 1... that was just his samsaric self. When he attained bodhi he also realized (we gather from sutras) that the buddha vehicle is a mental state that is like a jeweled net wherein all the buddhas throughout the universe preach the same central truths.

So why would he begin with the "hinayana" or lesser vehicle and arrive later at the mahayana or "greater vehicle(s)"?

The concept is called Expedient Means.

At that time there were 108 schools of Brahmanism and most were extremely strict. He had to enlighten brahmans who were stuck in the path of destruction of ego and strict nonaction and nonattachment. Thus the 4 noble truths which was the first sermon. 1) life is suffering (old age, sickness, death/rebirth, and loss) 2) suffering arises from the mind being not right, 3) correct thinking would lead to Nirvana and end suffering and 4) the 8-fold Noble Path prescribed the Way of the Arhat. Now Dr. Thurman claims noble here meant for the studied like monks and aristocrats. But that the prescription for commoners was quite different. This is expressed in the idea of Expedient Means.

E.M. is talking/teaching at the level of the listener. One's skill determines this ability aka the Dharma Tongue. Because the Buddha knew he had to convert people from extremism to a middle path he worked hard to travel and set up monasticism and lots of rules etc... which led to the formation of early sects. He converted nobility with his promise of Arhatship while commoners were gifted by his presence.

Now... of course eventually after 20 years he didn't walk as much as people came to him.

This meant now the hinayana which was all philosophies and dissertations of nonexistence based on the original revelation could give way to higher, more equanimous truths. Yet his first messages were what propagated and even still... look above that's what people hear and know.

In the mahayana period he began to really work on clearing the insincere and egotistical from the Order. Including betrayers. It was a difficult time and buddhists were everywhere and brahmans warred with them. At this time though all the sutras claimed that arhats and Nirvana was false and the path of the bodhisattva was itself enlightenment! Suffering and samsara became bodhi and enlightenment as in its roots and opportunities. Desire became a source and destroying it through arhatship actually a curse.

This is where people still wrangle!

To make matters more interesting in the post 500Ad era during the end of the former days of the law sects of the vajra or tantrayana arose which were blendings of mahayana and local traditions such as tibetan deism and hinduism. They were always reputedly schools propagated by his closest disciples who had received special transmissions. Zen or Ch'an as it was called then was just such a school. Bodhidharma brought 4 new sutras to China as the age of Buddhism was increasing in China and the far east.

Now as the Daishonin states all of the sutras are correct, each character being like a golden buddha yielding bodhi but one must remember that the Buddha taught millions of people and at least 10,000 expedient means were used.

So in this context I'd like to start in the next article. With an understanding that he spent his final 8 years on his most prized teachings clarifying the Theoretical or esoteric studies of the hinayana, refining ideas in the mahayana over 20 years of repudiating selfish desires to escape samsara alone through one's own efforts, and expounding on heavier concepts such as vajra/tantra, the lotus method, parinirvana, the school of non-non-being-nor-being, and Zen.

Some basic terms. An arhat or pratyekabuddha is roughly equivalent... it means a self-attainer. . A voice hearer or shramanera is roughly the same it means an aspirant to true discipleship. A mahasattva is a powerful bodhisattva. There are foreign or mythical bodhisattvas and there are literal people who are reborn to aid others. In the tibetan tradition a Renpoche is a lama who reincarnates to fulfill the bodhisattva way.

Theravadism is NOT hinayana although it retains the strictness of those sutras from early years. It does however in most southeast asian countries place heavy emphasis on monasticism ... and while tibetan is like buddhist catholicism, theravada is like buddhist orthodoxy.

There is also a wide range of mahayana. Pure land or nembutsuism is the worship of Amitabha while Zen is derived of the original Ch'an but de-emphasizes sutras. However most people do not know there are 3 zens.

Satori is a momentary enlightenment ... an aha! moment. While attaining Liberation or Perfect Enlightenment or becoming an arhat without any "outflows" takes time.

The 3 buddhist treasures are the Buddha, the dharma, and the samgha/community. To slander anyone of them is technically worse than murder. Oh... dharma here includes Vedic Dharma but more specifically means the New Testament of the Buddha (or Jainism or Sikhism... same thing happens).

From now on, unless I specify otherwise, because the tipitaka and upanishads and Chinese sutras are vast in size and number I will be utilizing what's called the Essential Teachings which differ from the Theoretical or esoteric in that a) the Buddha "seriously discarded expedients" (not really still a lot of simile and parable) and b) they were codified as "higher" by rigorous debate of serious Buddhist Scholars in China and Japan. By imperial edict it was laid out exactly the order and by the 1000s Ad this was probably reliable and anything new like the vajra prajna paramita sutra or any vajrayana buddhas which never physically existed were likely sutras of the Latter Day of the Law which is highly important to understand. This means the true teachings were in disuse and mistrusted widely while people looked for shortcuts and used koans to fake enlightenment. Some even wrote new teachings and assigned them to greats like Nagasena or Nagarjuna. But for our porpoises the debates of Tien Tai and 9 schools (and later Dengyo in japan vs 6 schools) resulting in the above paradigm will serve as a backbone for our Buddhist Alchemy.

Any other terms please ask or forward for clarification. Buddhist speak is like Kabbalah speak you get used to it. Fortunately other than mudras most of this is easy and quite logic dependent.

Q: did the Buddha refute God? A: no... the Buddha, like Jesus, never felt the need to clarify what was already known about reincarnation or God(s). Being a prince he had the best education in books, medicine, and martial arts as a young man.

Q: did he deny being the messiah? A: no he refused to answer. Why? Because he knew people would worship him anyhow and he wanted people to transcend that. He later mentioned the "buddha of the western continent" whom one could pray to and get sent to a pure land and become clean again. I believe this was a reference to the coming of Jesus. His goal was to lay the foundations of enlightenment.

Salvation and enlightenment are like pie and cake, have both if you want they are great... don't choose 1 forever. Buddha always said "worship the Law/Dharma not the man." And he included himself. He did not say not to worship the messiah he just refused to take on that himself. He was destined to die old. Jesus was destined to die and be reborn young. They are not opposites. One can be a christian and

buddhist through understanding the Thus Come One vehicle=mahasattvas (Tathagatas).

This is my main point today... this Alchemy is able to augment the Kabbalah and gnosticism and Taoism and Hinduism/yoga... it is merely very fervent psychology. All the faith is natural in dogma and religions but at its heart is the same 8 dharmas that run the Universe. It is simply true that under the above paradigm a Tathagata is also known as a World-Honored-One, unexcelled worthy/sage, far gone and understanding the world etc... and is this not truly what is said about the Christ and Buddha throughout the whole world?! Faith in that by recognition is personal but regardless the psychology is just philosophy of mind still. These paradigms form the basis of the Mahayana Alchemy.

Master Raz Says...

March 6 at 10:43pm via **mobile** · **Like** · **9**

Raz Iyahu Vajrayana contains the secrets of the sexual force and its highest form of utilization, the Buddhist concepts that contains the very advanced lighting path and were taught from teacher to pupil only.

This method consists of very high level application because in order to obtain the teachings, the pupil must already have mastered several aspects of himself prior.

This is likened to the Kabbalist obtaining the level of incomplete Tzaddik as described in the Tanya, etc. There can be no more chance for Rasha to occur in him although he is still very much aware of it. The pupil must be able to understand the instructions not just from the level of intellectual acceptance but from the level of Knowledge (Da'at) which is the attainment of some form of Knowing through direct experience - a higher form of understanding.

This is due to the relationship with the pure Light of Wisdom and not just the illumination of the intellectual faculty.

Vajra is indivisible and indestructible; it is wisdom-emptiness. As for the expression "emptiness" it is meant the pure light nature is called emptiness, because the pure light nature has an aspect of just emptiness, since for one in its factor of non-conceptuality it is empty of both elaborative conceptuality and inherent existence, and secondly yogins who have quintessential instructions achieve equipoise on emptiness through setting in equipoise on that pure light.

This is a knowing from some level of adhesion rather than a knowing from a level of intellectual understanding. This is the reason Vajraya could even be explained openly without fear of misunderstanding because the pupil who had not attained this level of adhesion has no properties by which to understanding the instruction.

When it is said that the teaching is 'secret' it does not necessarily mean the teaching is 'hidden', but moreso hidden from the pupil who is not yet capable of seeing the teaching even though it is presented to them clearly.

We can see this in the teachings of the Holy Arizal in Kabbalah and the subsequent commentary by the Baal HaSulam because the Language of S'firot (branches) is easily accessible by the pupil but utterly incomprehensible to the initiate nevertheless. Only the Adept has the skills to penetrate the text and uncover its true meanings and applications.

Correct. This is the 2nd reason I'm not specifically talking about vajra, and thirdly there are good schools if one wants the diamond pounder methods. So to sum up vajra: 1)there are few legit schools many were invented too late to be considered reliable, and 2)a student must needs find a legit vajra master. I have met not 1 but 2 people who have ruined their prajna self-studying vajrayana, and 3)I am not a vajrayana master or adept although I have experienced the tantra.

So... although I KNOW people want to learn vajra I do not think they should do so willy nilly without guidance. Mahayana Alchemy though, this I think we shall remain safe bc it is mental and the other Alchemy can provide the prajna/Qi work. Also there is a codified systematology in Buddhism already... and vajra and mudras are sub studies.

To be fair I also feel this way about zen since most people's problem is they cannot get out of their head. Originally zen was also transmitted secretly but not all sorts of people "master" zen without knowing it has 3 forms... nor reading Bodhidharma's sutras! As the Taoist I Ching says, "engaging in arbitrary guesswork."

If people are near to Raz or can find a Dzogchen master AND they become adept at the Mahayana then I can sanction vajra study.

1 of the cases I met the man was convinced God/Brahma was = Mara/Satan and everywhere he went he was fighting Mara. He was obsessed with escaping samsara. Very sad shen disturbed case. So just like kundalini people should pay attention and inquire, discern, listen, perceive, and then practice.

Ok, so what then is the "goal" of M.A.? It's 2 fold and simple really.

#1 to transmute one's samsaric experience and therefore samsara itself -individual by individual- into nirvana. So that each person sees and lives in an active/real rather than paper Dharma.

#2 in doing this one must transmute "negative" karma into "positive" karma* and advance oneself [lit: evolve] in awareness towards Perfect Enlightenment. Daily satori, daily increase in length of time blended with Anutta (void) leading to nullification of self and Sameness with Others > Yoga of Mind > Yoga of Action. Thus it is directly connected to Kabbalah, Gita, and I Ching/Taoism.

*in Buddhism the dualities or polarities are a matter of delusion. Suffering is not opposite enlightenment they are the same. However since we have a discriminatory mind and have not as of yet finished coalescing the black pearl we still live in the world (hence using facebook!) And must observe our Orientation. Positive karma would generally be considered 'desirable' and the more True North obviously the less self involved while negative karma would be 'bad' and southward is free will/egotism. Hence hell is below and heaven above.

Now nothing is truly only bad this is the Polarity Dharma but we call it so because every moment spent going this 'wrong' direction one is NOT doing goal #1.

#3 convert as many others as possible to this overall paradigm hence why I say every sincere member of this group is a bodhisattva of the earth regardless of faith or background. Even a sincere science buff who lands upon Truth such as a Quantum Activist is a bodhisattva. That will be because of the 10 Worlds/Realms I am to speak of next time.

Now the curious thing about #3 is it has a lot of sub-rules and self checks BECAUSE of 2 very good reasons.

1 is obviously religious fervor is rooted deeply in the egoic mind. So forceful conversion and predation upon the weak minded is taboo in succeeding at #2 and #1

Secondly is the fact that as the I Ching says one cannot simply transmute oneself without changing and one must be sincere in this consistently.

You notice I asked first for permission and interest in this topic? This is because if people are NOT READY nor interested, then forceful study would be the equivalent of theological rape. It would actually turn the person from the topic. And this is most grievous because after all, the central Truth in this process is shared throughout all the accurate schools. It would be the equivalent of trying to force a person onto the slope of the Mountain and yet they get scared and so turn and run back into the Forest (lower 6 realms or Samsara). It is also taboo because this violates #3

So #1-transmute samsara into living nirvana (pratyekabuddhahood=check!)

#2 transmute Karma into Yoga and end up as a Bhagavan
(bodhisattvahood=check)

#3 share willingly/openly/without force this Alchemy in such a way that others willingly save themselves. Or as Jesus said, "ye must become fishers of men"
You'll note the above matches the study, practice, and teach > Buddhahood paradigm. Or $7+8+9=10$

Now each level has its axioms, rules, etc... but as the Life Aquatic is an Active system if one makes mistakes the corrections come both harsh and gentle depending on one's error of ego.

If one can genuinely share this with ANY person no matter the background, one is practicing most earnestly. Stumbling blocks such as a negative past with Christianity or Catholicism for example... or despising Islam... these will become evident in one's Life Condition (caste, karma, health, happiness).
We'll cross raising L.C. later.

This is the foundation of the Mahayana Alchemy. A very early on MLM of spirituality. No doubt the same/similar to Kabbalah as Truth converges at the 0 space.

The end of second chapter, designated The Way of Knowledge.

"39. The wisdom of Self-realisation has been declared unto thee. Hearken thou now to the wisdom of Yoga, endued with which, O son of Prithâ, thou shalt break through the bonds of Karma.

48. Being steadfast in Yoga, Dhananjaya, perform actions, abandoning attachment, remaining unconcerned as regards success and failure. This evenness. of mind (in regard to success and failure) is known as Yoga.

49. Work (with desire) is verily far inferior to that performed with the mind undisturbed by thoughts of results. O Dhananjaya, seek refuge in this evenness of mind. Wretched are they who act for results.

50. Endued with this evenness of mind, one frees oneself in this life, alike from vice and virtue. Devote thyself, therefore, to this Yoga. Yoga is the very dexterity of work.

Shifu R. Careaga another translation for the Way of Knowledge is Yoga of Mind, and perhaps this is more accurate too to the concept.

THIRD CHAPTER - YOGA OF ACTION

Arjuna said:

1. If, O Janârdana, according to Thee, knowledge is superior to action, why then, O Keshava, dost Thou engage me in this terrible action?
2. With these seemingly conflicting words, Thou art, as it were, bewildering my understanding;—tell me that one thing for certain, by which I can attain to the highest.

The Blessed Lord said:

3. In the beginning (of creation), O sinless one, the twofold path of devotion was given by Me to this world;—the path of knowledge for the meditative, the path of work for the active.
4. By non-performance of work none reaches worklessness; by merely giving up action no one attains to perfection.
5. Verily none can ever rest for even an instant, without performing action; for all are made to act, helplessly indeed, by the Gunas, born of Prakriti.
6. He, who restraining the organs of action, sits revolving in the mind, thoughts regarding objects of senses, he, of deluded understanding, is called a hypocrite.
7. But, who, controlling the senses by the mind, unattached, directs his organs of action to the path of work, he, O Arjuna, excels.
8. Do thou perform obligatory * action; for action is superior to inaction, and even the bare maintenance of thy body would not be possible if thou art inactive.
9. The world is bound by actions other than those performed for the sake of Yajna; do thou therefore, O son of Kunti, perform action for Yajna alone, devoid of attachment.
10. The Prajâpati, having in the beginning created mankind together with Yajna, said,—"By this shall ye multiply: this shall be the milch cow of your desires.
11. "Cherish the Devas with this, and may those Devas cherish you: thus cherishing one another, ye shall gain the highest good.
12. "The Devas, cherished by Yajna, will give you desired-for objects." So, he who enjoys objects given by the Devas without offering (in return) to them, is verily a thief.
13. The good, eating the remnants of Yajna, are freed from all sins: but who cook food (only) for themselves, those sinful ones eat sin.
14. From food come forth beings: from rain food is produced: from Yajna arises rain and Yajna is born of Karma.
15. Know Karma to have risen from the Veda, and the Veda from the Imperishable. Therefore the all-pervading Veda is ever centred in Yajna.
16. He, who here follows not the wheel thus set revolving, living in sin, and satisfied in the senses, O son of Prithâ,—he lives in vain.
17. But the man who is devoted to the Self, and is satisfied with the Self, and content in the Self alone, he has no obligatory duty.

18. He has no object in this world (to gain) by doing (an action), nor (does he incur any loss) by non-performance of action,—nor has he (need of) depending on any being for any object.
19. Therefore, do thou always perform actions which are obligatory, without attachment;—by performing action without attachment, one attains to the highest.
20. Verily by action alone, Janaka and others attained perfection;—also, simply with the view for the guidance of men, thou shouldst perform action.
21. Whatsoever the superior person does, that is followed by others. What he demonstrates by action, that, people follow.
22. I have, O son of Prithâ, no duty, nothing that I have not gained, and nothing that I have to gain, in the three worlds; yet, I continue in action.
23. If ever I did not continue in work, without relaxation, men, O son of Prithâ, would in every way, follow in My wake.
24. If I did not do work, these worlds would perish. I should be the cause of the admixture of races, and I should ruin these beings.
25. As do the unwise, attached to work, act, so should the wise act, O descendant of Bharata, (but) without attachment, desirous of the guidance of the world.
26. One should not unsettle the understanding of the ignorant, attached to action; the wise, (himself) steadily acting, should engage (the ignorant) in all work.
27. The Gunas of Prakriti perform all action. With the understanding deluded by egoism, man thinks, "I am the doer."
28. But, one, with true insight into the domains of Guna and Karma, knowing that Gunas as senses merely rest on Gunas as objects, does not become attached.
29. Men of perfect knowledge should not unsettle (the understanding of) people of dull wit and imperfect knowledge, who deluded by the Gunas of Prakriti attach (themselves) to the functions of the Gunas.
30. Renouncing all actions to Me, with mind centred on the Self, getting rid of hope and selfishness, fight,—free from (mental) fever.
31. Those men who constantly practise this teaching of Mine, full of Shraddhâ and without cavilling, they too, are freed from work.
32. But those who decrying this teaching of Mine do not practise (it), deluded in all knowledge, and devoid of discrimination, know them to be ruined.
33. Even a wise man acts in accordance with his own nature: beings follow nature: what can restraint do?
34. Attachment and aversion of the senses for their respective objects are natural: let none come under their sway: they are his foes.
35. Better is one's own Dharma, (though) imperfect, than the Dharma of another well-performed. Better is death in one's own Dharma: the Dharma of another is fraught with fear."

March 7 at 7:03pm · Like · 5

Geraldine O'Donovan thanks, Shifu. --- so, karma is consequence of action and yoga is connection with "all" so ... transforming karma to yoga is done by letting go of the desire for a certain type of consequence to occur? how do you become desireless?

March 7 at 8:14pm · Unlike · 5

Shifu R. Careaga precisely. well you dont... BUT your desires become the desires of the All by ending selfishness and developing the Yoga of Mind. even when you "phase out" into egoic forms... if 100 desires arise they all serve the 1 desire to obey willingly and sacrifice Action to the One. an example would be one's hunger fueling a chef career and part of that career is charity work in places of hunger, for example. rather than just merely consuming food. just an example. again desire is the root of enlightenment, it isnt and "end" it's a transformation. one cannot end action one can let go of the consequence though. etc... karma will be dealt with later. so stay tuned.

March 7 at 8:21pm via mobile · Like · 5

Geraldine O'Donovan thanks again. that makes much sense. this is in kabbalah too. reception (using desire/the will to receive) for the sake of others (sharing/bestowing.)

March 7 at 8:28pm · Edited · Unlike · 5

Shifu R. Careaga ^ exactly; echoes of Truth in all corners of Jambudvipa! This is the secret meaning of "the Saha world will become level and pure." We can blast mountains and clear cut and force the ground level as a species but then it cannot be pure. Only through inner revolution can it become pure.

So now let's talk about Samsaric Experience. Samsara or the Threefold World is actually this idea that the inner is the outer. I believe Raz is on this topic somewhere. ~_^

The three planes of reality are the physical, mental, and spiritual (untagible or ethereal). In the human and as we learn later allllll things this is the body, mind, and soul and again the mind is broken into corporeal soul (unconscious), intellect, and ethereal soul (subconscious).

The first level is the Yahweh/jehovah/Krishna-universe (Godhead or Heavenly Ghost). The 2nd is the Brahmic (or other personality diety) God-mind. And the third is the [insert your name here] Universe which is the God-body. Between these 3 fractal multiverses lies the inner and the outer, Yin and Yang or Heaven and Earth.

But thiss is all illusion because it is One which is hollow (Anutta). However, because the mind has gunas and senses skandhas, it knows of the 8 dharma which are consummated by the mind-duality's perception of the Samsara. $2^3=8$.

So what happens is the mind stratifies experience into 11 realms, only 10 of which are "real" but of course most of the All resides in the unused Source (11th) which is Parinirvana or simple Beyond the Asymptote.

Now Gautama Buddha became popular for teaching a formula called the 8 fold path for ending the delusion and also used the 12 link chain (1 and 12 are the same 11th link) to show how karma was generated.

But Shakyamuni Buddha (same guy, here Mahayana names him for his clan, probably after his family was destroyed in a war and he was essentially the last Shakya king) became famous for his idea of the 3000 realms in a single moment of life.

10 worlds within all the other 10 worlds * 10 factors (linked by the 11th:consistency)*samsara (3)=3,000.

So.... what are these 10 worlds?

Actually in Yoga the idea had prexisted but 6-10 were all different heavens for different brahman gods. In Buddhism however the idea became an evolution of self. In the lower 4, people who react or try to control the 4 heavenly laws, we have in order: hell(misery), animality (no humanity), hungry ghosts (lust and greed and envy), anger demons (hate, rage, inscrutibility, etc...). Those who knew yoga could transcend gunas and skandhas and achieve the 5th world of tranquility and ride the middle path without falling for the enjoyments of the 6th Joy which was human heaven. Now though we can consider the 6th any form of joy, but the more extreme, the quicker ended and it wraps around to #1.

This rat race is collectively called the 6 human worlds of suffering... it's also known as living "in the world".

The 7th realm is that of the saved. The "voice hearers" who conceive a desire of salvation and leaving the rat race of mind and suffering. It doesn't matter what

method heard or sought it's the same Vibration. The sad thing is that the 7th realm is so close to the others... hence people can leave church and go out now loving their neighbors! Woe to mankind who is at misery in church and cannot wait to head right back into the meatgrinder, the burning house, Samsara... without first arming themselves with either enlightenment or the Love of their Tathagatas. Yet hope always remains BECAUSE in each world is contained all 10. He/she who knows this is empowered to do samsaraic alchemy. They know and this is the 8th realm of the arhat or pratyekabuddha. If rage rises up, they can transmute it INSTANTLY to compassion, forgiveness, and bodhi, end the ego/pride and escape the world without moving an inch. This is first bodhi or living nirvana. Goal #1. Now eventually such people who still have desires conceive a desire to teach others about how they help themselves by ridding the mind of delusional poisons and then over time change karma. If you stop watching drama Tv your world WILL improve! Well samsara is nothing more than "real" TV. Tv is just simulated samsara. Outer and inner being forced to be the same... hence news that is miserable.

Such people who are attained and also compassionate have a bodhicitta and are "born again" in the world moment to moment, life to life, destined to endure the world to share the Path. Bodhisattvas these are called. When satori comes and various samshis and wisdoms achieved all of this brings us nearer the Asymptote and this is the mahasattva turning into a Tathagata day by day. Until they are needed in some hell so bad (such as Israel 2000 years ago) they come willingly out of God's mind like glistening diamonds to dwell in the world. They feel the gunas, they sense the skandhas, they eat the food and taste the waters and smell the air, and instantly recognize the illusion throughout Jambudvipa. And they love us so much they cannot help but suffer immense hatred to share it with the addicts. Addicts hate being called addicts and they hate losing substances. Well... so we're addicts! All of us. Substance abusers. What we really abuse is our selves. What we really must transmute is first the Inner samsara and stop hoping/wishing the outer would change first. As the mahasattva Jim Rohn said, "stop wishing things were better and wish YOU were better." God rest his soul.

So that's the first 100 worlds in a single moment of life. In any of the 10 able to become any other one so that our Vibration VIOLENTLY oscillates and produces... say car accidents where before we were having an ice cream outing. Or forgiveness in a mother after having a child carelessly murdered. The Vibration Dharma allows us to slip into any realm and in between... it is US that has to be receptive to the inner, outer, and the Benevolent Principle, "I am that I am: Love". Next time I'll discuss more techniques to this alchemy including the 10 factors... to complete the 3000 realms.

Dwell on the illusion of the TV and how really it is 3 Tvs and then how all these are transitory without pure seque and therefore just fictions of the Mind.

Tien Tai

March 8 at 10:39am via **mobile** · **Like** · **4**

Shifu R. Careaga Sunday asked about 5 elements. You can use the 5 elements to transmute/control the process a bit. Metal controls wood so justice and meditation and patience control anger. Water controls fire so solitarity, introvertedness and fear of disobeying the divine power controls excessive passionate joy. Wood controls earth so anger can be transformed into compassion. Earth controls water so music and gentleness and forbearance can restrain fear and shelter the frightened. Fire controls metal and thus joy, mirth, and laughter can control grief and sorrow and consternation. For you Sunday

March 8 at 10:43am via **mobile** · **Like** · **6**

Shifu R. Careaga btw there is a reason Tien Tai won the debate about the hierarchy of Sutra doctrine. The Lotus Sutra is a) the first sutra to predict enlightenment in all beings and non-being, heavenly, humanly, male/female, adult/child, good or evil and b) it is the only sutra at the time of around 1100 AD that quoted the Buddha as saying this is the greatest sutra I have ever taught, am teaching currently, or ever will teach. The Nirvana Sutra which followed this sutra referred back to it, calling the Lotus Method the Great Vehicle itself. Thus the Daishonin quoted the Lotus Sutra calling it a great ocean into which all sutras flow like rivers and get their source as Buddhist doctrine. It is a sutra for everyone, initiated or uninitiated, however it is most difficult to accept, believe, and put into practice. The Daishonin wrote on this in the treatise "The Universal Salty Taste."

The Buddha said,

"The wisdom of the Buddhas is infinitely profound and immeasurable. The door to this wisdom is difficult to understand and difficult to enter. Not one of the voice-hearers or pratyekabuddhas is able to comprehend it."

"The Buddha preaches it in accordance with what is appropriate, yet his intention is difficult to understand."

"Because the Thus Come One is fully possess of both expedient means and the paramita of wisdom."

"But now I will seriously discard expedient means and speak only the Truth."

"The Buddha's understanding can only be shared between Buddhas, and this reality consists of:

1. Appearance
2. Nature
3. Entity
4. Power
5. Influence
6. Inherent Cause
7. Relation
8. Latent Effect
9. Manifest Effect
10. Consistency
11. From beginning to end

"Stop, stop!... if I speak of [the Lotus Sutra] the heavenly and human beings through the worlds will be astonished and doubtful. The monks who are overbearingly arrogant will fall into a great pit."

"The words that the Buddhas preach are not empty or false... This law is not something that can be understood by pondering or analysis. Only those who are Buddhas can understand it. Why?... Because the Buddhas... appear in the world for one great reason alone... to open the door of buddha wisdom to all living beings, to allow them to attain purity (re: extinction)... The Thus Come Ones simply teach and convert the bodhisattvas... they have only a single Buddha vehicle which they employ... they do not have any other, a second one, or a third one. The Law... preached in all ten directions is the same as this.

Let's examine this closely today. The first paragraph means that unless you use your buddha world inherent within you, you'll be estranged from this understanding. One must cease all ego and egolessness and find the "I am" or Bhagavan within and then observe reality as-it-is.

At this point, and only then will one understand. The bodhisattvas will believe but not understand. But those in the 7th and 8th world will have great difficulty. Why? Because their intent is not accurate. It is oriented "out of samsara" but still selfish. The 7th world Mind wants to be saved -it worries of itself. The 8th World Mind does not worry for anyone else, and only collects for self and not others.

The Buddha World combines the compassion of the 9th World with the humility of the 7th and the Wisdom of the 8th. Thus is able to comprehend this. So to understand the rest, right now you must engage your Buddha self. Do it right now, please.

The next part speaks on the paramita (skill) of wisdom - specifically the Diamond Perfection of Wisdom, and of Expedient Means. Which I've already covered in the Intro, but is the name of THIS chapter.

But the Buddha swears after having been asked 4 times and after 3 the egotistical crowd having left - summarizing the experience of the previous 20 years of teaching career - to "seriously discard Expedient Means. He still uses simile and parable, but this means he vows to answer honestly, even if it may cause doubts in the minds of the 4 types of believers - lay people, shramaneras, pratyekabuddhas, and bodhisattvas.

Then he says it can only be shared between Buddhas. This means now you must understand this using your Dharma Eye. This is the third eye but also a spiritual eye. It is a paramita that comes through attaining understanding. As Liu Yi Ming says "at first vague but then becoming clearer."

Then he lists the 10 factors, with 10 & 11 being considered one, but I divided into 2 because I'm gangster like that. No really the reason is it has 2 parts.

Appearance - self explanatory except what he means is that things seem one way when actually they are another or Not at all.

Nature - the factor of reality which describes its substance and behavior.

Entity - objectification created by the gunas of the mind sensing skandhas

Power - the ability to influence, move, or transmute; or sometimes to be controlled by an event or person

Influence - leverage

Inherent Cause - meaning the paradigm, belief, thought, habit, action chain that creates a cause

Relation - entanglement, synchronicity, and of course karmic binding such as family, relationship, etc... that binds a person to an outcome whereas not another. Diseases are a common example.

Latent Effect - meaning that there is an unseen force which moves to a conclusion

Manifest Effect - immediate appearance of karma

Consistency - unbroken chain or as is commonly known as Dependent Origination

-<http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Prat%C4%ABtyasamutp%C4%81da>

From Beginning to End meaning the unbroken Dharma Wheel (dharmacakra)

http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dharma_wheel

[Pratītyasamutpāda - Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia](http://en.wikipedia.org)en.wikipedia.org

Pratītyasamutpāda (Sanskrit; Pali:paticcasamuppāda) is commonly translated as de...See More

So... how to use this information??

If you understand that whatever world you are currently in contains ALL other 10 worlds.

AND you understand the above thoroughly, and investigate it thoroughly... THEN you can transmute from say... Hell... into Buddhahood instantly, understand the 10 factors that are causing the karma you have now, producing the Samsara you are in and you can then turn the Dharma Wheel and produce different, improved outcomes for ALL concerned.

I say ALL because this is important. Only a self-less turning is possible. In many sutras it says "no other being was capable of this turning." This means a person who is not in their 0-phase and tries to turn the wheel to give them good effect and other bad effect will instead not understand the 10 factors and the Latent Effect will be hidden from them.

One must understand that for the Alchemy to be Sincere YOU have to be sincere. You have to alter yourself. You have to change... You don't have to know the 10 factors and the 3000 realms in every moment... yet. But "subconsciously following the laws of God" will become your inner MO. Your will (zhi) will transform into the Will of the Divine Principle - Tian Ren Di. Samsara will transmute of its own suffering and issues into a living Nirvana. It is living Kabbalah, being a real Taoist, not just knowing some quotes from the Dao De Jing... it is Zen in motion... Yoga of Action.... THIS is how Mahayana Alchemy works. You know the worlds are there for you, and the 10 factors become your instrument panel... and the transformation happens all by Itself - the Golden Elixir crystallizes and the Black Pearl forms from the Wu-Anatta-Void.

And this completes the lesson on 10 factors for today. Questions? Comments?

Q&A

March 9 at 11:41am · Like · 4

Shifu R. Careaga "The Thus Come Ones simply teach and convert the bodhisattvas... The Law... preached in all ten directions is the same as this."

compare to "ye [apostles] must become fishers of men."

7+8+9=10

March 9 at 11:47am · Like · 3

Geraldine O'Donovan so, i have to have a desire to change not for myself but for the happiness of others because i am the universe that made them unhappy? do i have that right?

March 11 at 2:28pm · Like · 2

Shifu R. Careaga Not quite. But let's observe the radio body... if you are out of tune how can others entangled with you be in tune? After all, they share your cohort vibration. Thus aligning yourself encourages others to align via synchronicity. This is changing samsara into nirvana through careful observation leading to powerful advance. Take away yourself completely as the cause and solution.... be an instrument of good. The others that have their own karma are ultimately responsible for themselves.... so get out of the way. We think sheltering them from Truth helps but really it hurts. No matter what in my clinic i give honest answers... the healing is on them and i can't carry this burden on myself.... but i am glad to be an instrument of healing wherever possible.

OK. So the first goal is complete. Transmuting samsara into nirvana in daily life by recognizing vibration and shifting it.

Next goal was to transmute Karma.

Now there is the 10 factors, and the 12-link chain:

"At that time [the Buddha] silently agreed to do so... [after a lot more praising, three times in fact repeated as before and each time for the Brahma kings of each of the ten directions and] receiving entreaties from the Brahma kings of the ten directions and the sixteen princes, immediately gave three turnings to the twelve-spoked wheel of the law. [No one else] was capable of such a turning.

"Then he broadly expounded the [chain]:

1. ignorance-->action
2. action-->consciousness
3. consciousness-->name and form
4. name and form-->six sense organs (includes intellect)
5. six senses-->contact
6. contact-->sensation
7. sensation-->desire
8. desire-->attachment
9. attachment-->existence
10. existence-->birth
11. birth-->old age and death
12. death-->worry and grief, suffering and anguish (before to oneself and afterwards to family)

"If [these] are wiped out... then suffering and anguish are wiped out. When the Buddha expounded this Law... millions attained liberation. When he expounded the second, third, and fourth Laws, they were able to liberate their minds of all outflows."

This is the weft, the unbroken string.

BUT, also there is the warp, that is individual streams of your LATERAL SELVES. These selves both exist and do not exist.

To understand your lateral selves which are unactuated potentials, I like to use the mirror analogy. You are standing between two mirrors... to your left are your unhealthier selves unto obscurity and death, and to your right are your ever increasing godly selves unto your very Shiva-self. As you shift between them they all experience the same reality YOU do because they ARE you except they perceive it differently. To the point where you cease to be and every thing said externally to you is a message from God and a bodhi itself and you must resist the temptation to speak as long as possible... as soon as you say "you" or "I" you will tune out of that phase.

If you have any signs - see my Measurement of Alchemy article - of being out of tune, it would do well to tune in as close as you can to where you are only 2-5 mirrors away from your Shiva self.

btw sugars, alcohol, caffeine, TV... all these things will rapidly lower your vibration.

NOW. When you are in your best lateral-warp-stream; you will see Karma broken down in the chain and understand the origination of Karma and its outflows=outcomes. This is what it means to cease outflows. You don't really cease them, you trim them, like culling a bonzai. Obviously if you were drastically out of tune you'd need a hedge-trimmer. But now that you are up in the 8th, 9th, and 10th worlds for a majority of your conscious day, the trimming is less drastic.

At this point it becomes useful to understand the forward flow to Karma that produces moment to moment evolution and therefore perception of Time.

Paradigms (programming) -> beliefs -> thoughts & habits -> feelings -> actions -> results -> experience -> paradigms & ultimately birth and death.

Also one may stop and observe - since stopping is merely a matter of pausing evolution of self - if an outcome is desired, then will one's current Resonance or Dis-resonance (lack of harmony) produce the outcome desired.

Example: I am at odds with my boss, I argue with them all the time... I am considering sending a nasty email... first though I pause and observe: is it kind, necessary, and truthful AND do I mind being fired? Do I stand to lose much or gain much? Will it further the goals of humanity? Will it elevate my consciousness or cause me to get more mixed up with Acquired Conditioning... wait... why am I at odds with my boss... is it because we are very different or so similar there are aspects about this person I don't like because they are like me? What is the ultimate outcome?

So obviously there is more to Changing Karma than simply saying "OK I'll just change my vibe, change my beliefs, and change my habits and bam."

It is highly dangerous to rip a negative plant out. Without understanding the root indeed the SEED of a paradigm, it is destined to repeat itself. This is like ending one relationship hoping to meet Mr. Right and ending up with teh same Mr. or Ms. Wrong. What didn't change was the SEED.

Even more dangerous is ripping out paradigms such as "I grew up Catholic" without carefully selecting what to replace it WITH. Something will fill it. So many people find Evil teachers-meaning teachers who either mean harm or do not know they are harming-and take this for good. As the saying goes... out of the frying pan into the fire. One bad decision informing the next, this is the meaning of impetuous action

leading to playing in the den of a tiger. If you don't know how to play with tigers, how can you insistently play in a tiger's lair?

So the important thing is to observe, perceive, deduce, decide, gather the Will, act, be consistent, and firm though flexible to the Teacher/ing, and gather energy and then comes the understanding.

BUT in gathering in Alchemy, there is stripping away. This is where the anuttā comes from. This is where the sublimating and changing vibe comes from. Trusting in the teachings is fine, but without a teacher to elucidate the meaning, it may take some mistakes first to get them straight. Thus the importance of a good samgha.

As for Mahayana, the approach is quite simple. Study, Practice, and most importantly teach. The teaching is the third and most important. Your sharing and teaching helps you memorize and learn faster. It goes from theory to practice. So this type of teaching is not simple professorial lecture... it is getting in there. Debate and more importantly, learning to dialogue.

Through the PRACTICE - chanting, reciting, writing, poetry, martial arts, study.... GUIDING the way for others, the impurities of the alloyed Human Mind - the paradigms themselves root themselves out.

It is not that I force myself to quit horror films and shoot-em-up games it is that I become repulsed by them. It is not that I DEMAND others cease it is that they come to be like me and us together we are repulsed by the samsaric experience. Going together, hand in hand, the leader is propelled by their emptiness, like a sleigh rider. This person transmutes samsara and illuminates evil, causing demons to flee through Thunder that is gentle to gentle ears, and like Hell to those who insist on egoic evils. Arguers become entrapped but are surprised to find one is ready to dialogue on any subject. At first separation, but then likeness is found.

This practice yields RESULTS, and those results are the burning out of old negative karma, and the rising of a new Life Condition that is lofty and lovely. I have a patient now, but next time I will post some of the predictions of the good results.

There are three things informing thoughts and for each a different technique. One is thoughts leading to thoughts, one is feeling/emotion leading to thoughts, and of course patterned-habit (coming from paradigms) lead to thought.

These thoughts are not always thieves sometimes they are quite useful, so the question is how to engage those and rid ourselves only of unwanted thoughts which are thieves of time, energy, and focus.

Thoughts arising from thoughts... random and unceasing arise from the egoic self projecting forward unable to catch itself. Soon idle imaginings or daydreams... often harmless but usually tending to result in brash, ridiculous decisions or fancies as they are called... this is no way to proceed in Alchemy the Universe cannot keep up with one's intentions and nothing ever gets started let's alone finishes! It is best in these cases to first try meditation but in most cases unsuccessful it is best to try acting upon something that requires true focus - such as gardening - and by borrowing the goodness of oneself during a sincere task one can repulse the unfocused ego for greater and greater periods of time.

Thoughts arising from emotions disturb essence. Fear and grief and anger steal essence and anger, lust, and intellect stagnate Qi, abuse willpower and waste essence. The best way to deal with these is reverse thinking. Stopping emotions by draining the Metal element through breathing to cut passions, one can then engage the po or corporeal soul to activate the hun or ethereal soul and thus turn intellect of earth to intuition. This intuition is the Buddhamind itself and in particular is the Dharma Eye. With this eye one can espy one's internal demons and enemies, find their supply routes and sources and in one fell swoop turn them into shunyata-inexistence. The Dharma Eye can pierce the veil of darkness where normal eyes cannot. Knowing the causes and origins of things and their existence and thus their end results one knows their Story. The drama is completed and the attachment to the drama can be ended.

In some cases the emotions are more trauma than passion... and in those cases knowing they arise from pride and sense of self, both of the ego, one can repel the darkness of this pain by finding the 0 space again or using a mantra or mudra which harmonize one to the moment-same thing.

As for thoughts arising from patterns and habits of thought again the Dharma Eye that comes through practice and observation and compassion for the suffering of others will illuminate repeated behaviors and thoughts. This doesn't mean they end, now comes the need of use of a far-reaching Will.

When one's will is weak one may borrow on the level above one. Within one's world-level or below it there are always people in the next gate and then there are always people (or books or sages or Yoda) above one in the next world-level. If one knows one is in the 1st gate of bodhisattvahood as one has newly entered the path one can learn from any higher gate of the 7th, 8th, or 9th world. Even a wisened grandmother who is not on the path will know more about love and compassion by virtue of experience. But also one should return to source texts and tathagatas for the purpose of borrowing 10th world energy.

If one has progressed to the 5th gate of Arhatship, outflows at an end... strong as the Mountain one stands on... what now? Better to learn from a fool who tries to help heal the world than seek a 6th gate Shaman in a forest and end up without attainment of anything for all one's work. Sure you've ended liberation but who benefits? Ego only.

So in changing patterned thoughts it doesn't do to attack them vociferously... but through gradual penetration of the Zen-mind, centered, focused, empty, seeing all vibrations and strands of connection with a clear and lucid Dharma Eye... then one can know the habit, know its cause, know its cure, and when the time has approached advance lucidity which is spiritual Fire to "burn" away karma with a blue flame rather than red.

Thus concluding the attainment of goal #2.

As for benefits, here I'll let the Buddha talk,
"Medicine King, do you see [this great assembly] who seek to become voice-hearers, pratyekabuddhas, or seek the Buddha way? Upon these various kinds of beings who in the presence of the Buddha listen to one verse or one phrase of the Lotus of the Wonderful Law and for a moment think of it with joy I will bestow on all of them a prophecy that they will attain anuttara-samyak-sambodhi. "In addition, if after [I am gone] there should be someone who listens to the Lotus Sutra ... and even for a moment thinks of it with joy, I will bestow on him a prophecy... Again if there are persons who embrace, read, recite, expound, and copy the Lotus Sutra, even only one verse, and look upon this sutra with the same reverence as they would the Buddha... then, Medicine King, you should understand that these persons have already offered alms to a hundred thousand million Buddhas... have fulfilled their great vow, and because they take pity on living beings they have been born again in this Saha world.
"Medicine King, if someone should ask what living beings will be able to attain Buddhahood in a latter-day existence, then you should show him that all these people in a latter-day existence are certain to attain Buddhahood.
"Medicine King, you should understand that these persons voluntarily relinquish the reward due them for their pure deeds and, in the time after I have passed into extinction, because they pity living beings, they are born into this evil world so they may broadly expound this sutra. If one of these good people ... is able to secretly expound the Lotus Sutra to one person, even one phrase of it, then you should know he/she is an envoy of the Buddha.
"Medicine King, if there should be an evil person who, his mind destitute of goodness, should for the space of a kalpa appear in the presence of the Buddha and constantly curse [him], his offense would still be rather light. But if there were a person who spoke only one evil word to curse or defame the laypeople, monks, and nuns who read and recite this sutra, then his offense would be very grave.
"The finest alms should be offered to [the expounders of this sutra]... Why? Because these persons delight in expounding the Law, and if one listens to them for even a moment, he will immediately attain the ultimate anuttara-samyak-sambodhi."

"The sutras I have preached number immeasurable ... millions. Among the sutras I have preached, no preach, and will preach, this Lotus Sutra is the most difficult to believe and understand. 1

"Medicine King, this sutra is the storehouse of the secret crux of the Buddhas. It must not be recklessly transmitted to others.² It has been guarded by the Buddhas... and from times past until now has never been openly expounded [in this world]. Since hatred and jealousy toward this sutra abound even when the Thus Come One is in the world, how much more so after his passing?"³

The Buddha then repeats much of the info above, before he moves on.

"Medicine King, in any place whatsoever where this sutra is preached, where it is read, where it is recited, where it is copied, or where a roll of it exists [or on the internet in this case], in all such places there should be erected towers made of the seven gems... There is no need to enshrine the relics of the Buddha there... because in such places the entire body of the Thus Come One is already present... If when people see these towers they bow in obeisance and offer alms, they you should know that such person persons have already drawn near to anuttara-samyak-sambodhi."

"Medicine King, suppose there is a man who is parched with thirst and in need of water. On an upland plateau he begins digging a hole in search of water but he sees the soil is dry and knows that water is still far away. He does not cease his efforts, however, and bit by bit he sees the soil becoming damper, until gradually he has worked his way into mud. No he is determined in his mind to go on, for he knows that he is bound to be nearing water.

"The way of the bodhisattva is the same as this. As long as a person has not yet heard, not yet understood, and not yet been able to practice this Lotus Sutra, then you should know that they are still far away from [enlightenment]. But if the person is able to hear, understand, ponder and practice this sutra [the opposite is true]... because all bodhisattvas who attain the Way do so through this sutra [meaning they preach and convert the bodhisattvas to the Buddha vehicle]. This sutra opens the gate of expedient means and shows them the form of true reality. This storehouse of the Lotus Sutra is hidden deep and far away where no person can reach it."

"Medicine King, if there are bodhisattvas who, on hearing this sutra, respond with surprise, doubt, and fear, then you should know that they are only newly embarked on their course. If there are voice-hearers [and arhats] who, on hearing this sutra respond likewise, then you should know they are persons of overbearing arrogance...

"The Thus Come One's room [that the believers enter to pray] is the state of mind that shows great pity and compassion toward all living beings. The ... robe is the mind that is gentle and forbearing. The ... seat is the emptiness of all phenomena. One should seat oneself comfortably therein and after that, with a mind never lazy or remiss, should for the sake of the bodhisattvas and the four kinds of believers

broadly expound this Lotus Sutra... If they should forget a phrase of this sutra I will appear and prompt them so that they are able to recite the text correct and in full."

~Chapter 10 Teachers of the Law

At that time, when the assembly... heard how long the Life Span of the Thus Come One was... boundless asamkya of living beings gained a great many benefits.

"Ajita," said the Buddha, "When I described [my] life span, millions ... attained the truth of birthlessness."

...

"And bodhisattvas ... gained the dharani that allows them to retain all that they hear... and the ability to speak pleasingly and without hindrance... and the ability to retain [endless] amounts of teachings (so long as they have this self same source, all the expedients of math, science, religion, etc... are at your fingertips with this understanding1)... and are able to turn the unregressing wheel of the law... and the pure wheel of the law... and assurance that they would attain anuttara-samyak-sambodhi [or set out upon that road]."

At that time Maitreya arose and explained the last chapter again and these blessings and benefits in verse form.

Then the Buddha said, "Ajita, if on hearing [the life span] of the Buddha are able to believe it and understand it even for a moment, the blessings they gain thereby are innumerable. Suppose a person practices the paramitas (prajna or Qi gong omitted) for immeasurable lifespans... their benefits would not compare to that of the person that understands [the Life Span chapter].

"Furthermore, Ajita, if there is someone who on hearing of this long life span can understand the import of such words, the benefit is very great, and also [will] awaken in him the unsurpassed wisdom of the Thus Come One. How much more so if he causes others to read, recite, etc...

"Ajita, if living beings are able to in the depths of their minds understand and believe this sutra [life span], they will constantly see [and meet] the Buddha and see this saha world leveled and jeweled with the seven treasures. You should understand these persons have deep and penetrating faith.

"Again if they hear it and do not think ill of it, but respond with joy [their benefits will be great, etc...] Ajita these men need not for my sake build temples and towers... because they already carry [their alms] with them as they read, recite, etc...

"Ajita if after I have entered extinction there are those who can read, recite, copy, etc... this sutra then it may be considered they have already constructed monk quarters, offered alms, etc... [in their hearts]

"So I say, if after I have entered extinction [this stuff happens, the benefits are very great, like offering me alms personally]

"... and if for the sake of others he employs various [expedient means] to teach and accords with the principles in explaining and preaching this sutra, and if he can

observe the precepts of purity, keep company with those who are peaceful and gentle, forbearing without anger, firm in intent and thought, constantly prizing samadhi, attaining various states of profound meditation, courageous and diligent, mastering all good doctrines, keen in wisdom, good at answering difficult questions... Ajita these [people] have already proceeded to the place of practice and are drawing near to bodhi. Wherever these good people sand about or exercise, there one should erect a tower for others to offer alms to it [as they would to the Buddha]."

~ Ch 17 Distinctions in Benefits

**1 - Reader, you should understand that I do not know all of these things in the common sense. It is in having one central source that all my answers and abilities to tie all the world of data and varying ideas together... to know whence an idea came, whom it benefited, why it benefited them, whom it did not, what was it's inherent value, what was its resultant value, and finally what is its projected future based on its inherent Truth. This is the power spoken of here. I got it from this source, not just from living and collecting information! I asked questions, and these questions, asked accordingly well gave me the answers.*

At that time Maitreya asked the World-Honored-One, "If there are living beings who upon hearing this sutra respond with joy, what blessings will they receive?"

"Ajita, after the Buddha has entered extinction, if there are monks, nuns, laypeople, etc.. young or old, male or female, who upon hearing this sutra respond with joy, and leaving the Dharma assembly [sangha] go some other place [anywhere] and for the sake of their parents, friends, and family expound this sutra, and these persons after hearing this sutra respond with joy and set about spreading these teachings. One person, having heard responds with joy and spreads the teachings, and the teachings in this way continue to be handed from one to another until they reach a fiftieth person,

"Ajita, the benefits received by this fiftieth person I will now describe to you - listen carefully.

"Imagine all the beings in the six paths of existence, of all the worlds, whether they are life-born, egg-born, born of nothingness or from dampness, or from transformation, with form or without form, with thought or without thought, with legs or without legs... imagine that among all this numerous beings, a person should come who is seeking blessings and responding to various desires [of others] dispenses objects of great worth, enough to fill a whole Jambudvipa (a large area). This dispenser of charity, having handed out these gifts for 80 years then thinks to himself, 'I have already doled out objects to these many beings responding to their various desires... but they are now all old and decrepit, over 80 years, face wrinkled, hair white, and before long they will die. Now I should employ the Law of the Buddha to instruct and guide them.'

"Immediately he gathers [them all] together and propagates the Dharma among them, teaching, benefiting and delighting them. In one moment they are all able to attain the way of the srota-apanna, of the sakridagamin, of the anagamin and of the arhat.. to exhaust all outflows and enter deeply into meditation. All attain freedom and become endowed with the eight emancipations. Now what is your opinion, are the benefits gained by this great dispenser of charity man or not?"

"World-Honored-One, this man's benefits are [very great]... even with [just the charity] his benefits would still be immeasurable, how much more so when he has enabled them to attain the fruits of arhatship!"

"I will now state the matter clearly to you, Ajita, this man gave all these object of amusement to living beings in the six paths of existence... and also made it possible for them to attain the fruits of arhatship. But the benefits that he gains do not match the benefits of the fiftieth person who hears just one verse of this Lotus Sutra and responds with joy. They are not equal to one hundredth... to a part in a million. Indeed it is beyond the power of calculation, simile or parable, to express the comparison."

"... How much greater are the benefits of the very first person in the assembly who, on hearing this sutra responds with joy!

"Moreover, Ajita, suppose a person for the sake of this sutra visits a monk's quarters (or a home) and sitting or standing and listening for even a moment accepts it. As a results of the benefits so obtained, when his is reborn in his next existence he will enjoy the finest [playthings and life]. Or suppose there is a person sitting in the place where the Law is expounded, and when another person appears, the first urges him to sit down and listen or offers to share his seat (or table) and so persuades him to sit down. The benefits gained by this person will be such that when he is reborn he will be in a place where the lords Shakra, Brahma is seated or where a wheel-turning sage king is seated."

"Ajita, suppose there is another person who speaks to another, 'There is a vehicle called the Lotus Sutra, let's go together and listen to it,' and having been urged, the person goes and listens to it for even an instant. The benefits of the first (who is a good friend) will be such that when reborn they will be in the presence of dharani bodhisattvas. He/she will have keen faculties and wisdom, he will never be struck dumb, his mouth will not emit a foul odor, his tongue nor mouth will ever be afflicted, teeth not stained nor black or crooked or widely spaced, nor missing or fall out at an angle. His lips will not droop down or curl back or etc... [also with nose, face and ears, etc...] and he will be endowed with all the features proper to a human being, and will see the Buddha, hear the Law, and have faith in the teachings."

~Ch 18 Benefits of Responding with Joy

At that time the Buddha said to Constant Exertion, "If good men or women accept and uphold this sutra, read and recite it, etc... such person will obtain 800 eye benefits, 1200 ear benefits, 800 nose benefits, 1200 tongue benefits, 800 body benefits, and 1200 mind benefits. With these they will be able to adorn their six sense organs, making all of them pure."

"These good men and women, with their pure physical eyes they received at birth will view all that exists in the inner and outer parts of the thousand-millionfold world, its mountains, forests, rivers and seas, down as far as the Avichi hell and up to the Summit of Being. And in the midst they will see all the living beings, and will also be able to see and understand the causes and conditions created by their deeds [ie: understand Karma] and the births that await them [good or bad, etc...] as a result and recompense for their deeds.

"Moreover, Constant Exertion, if good men or women do these things they will gain the 1200 ear benefits to purify their ears so they can hear all the different varieties of words and sounds, etc... all sounds and voices including the voice of the Law and the voice that is not the Law, bitter or merry, of common mortal or sages, happy or unhappy, supernatural voices, [more sounds], voices of the voice-hearers, arhats, bodhisattvas, and of Buddhas. In a word, although they have not yet gained heavenly ears, with pure and ordinary ears [he/she will hear all that], and despite this it will not impair his hearing faculty."

This repeats with odors, saying finally, "If he should wish to distinguish one scent from another and describe it for someone else, he will be able to recall without error."

Next, of course is the tongue benefits, which include flavors and also producing a good voice, "If with these tongue faculties he undertakes to expound the Law, he will produce a deep, wonderful voice capable of penetrating the mind and causing all who hear it to rejoice and delight. When people hear this voice expounding and preaching, advancing argument point by point, they will all gather to listen. [All will come to hear it].

"Because this bodhisattva is so skilled at preaching the Law, the Brahmans and others will for the remainder of their lives follow and wait on him and offer alms. Wherever this person is, the Buddhas will all face in that direction when they preach the Law, and he will be able to accept and uphold all the doctrines of the Buddha. In addition he will be able to emit the deep and wonderful sound of the Law."

"... Because of the purity of their mental faculties, when they hear no more than one verse or phrase of the sutra, they will master immeasurable and boundless numbers of principles. Once having understood these principles, they will be able to expound and preach on a single phrase or verse for a month or more, and all that they preach at that time will conform to the gist of the principles and will never be contrary to true reality.

"If they should expound some secular [or scientific] text, or speak on matters of government, wealth, or livelihood, they will in all cases conform to the correct Law. With regard to the living beings in the six realms, they will understand how the minds of those living beings work, how they move, what idle theories they entertain.

"Thus although they have not yet acquired bodhi, the purity of their mind will be such that the thoughts of these persons, their calculations and surmises and the words they speak, will in all cases represent the Law of the Buddha, never departing from the Truth, and will also conform with what was preached in the sutras of former Buddhas."

~Ch 19 Benefits of the Teachers of the Law.

The Razor's Edge

The sharp edge of the Razor
is difficult to pass over
thus the Sages say
enlightenment is nearly impossible

Enter Within

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Lions

You should be warm as spring dew
towards others

Be sharp as an autumn frost
toward oneself

Strict and undaunted as a Lion's
roar toward Evil

Fire in the Hair

You must concentrate upon and
consecrate yourself wholly to each
day, as though a fire were raging in
your hair!

Home

11 Dimensions :: 11 Realms :: 8 Laws & 3 Planes of Existence

Why the Order of the E11EVEN?

1. Because it provides the foundational formula which combines scientific knowledge with religious knowledge
 1. Through the 3 Planes
 1. Science and math:: Physical Plane
 2. Psychology:: Mental Plane
 3. Spirituality :: Spiritual Plane
 2. Through teaching/explaining the 8 Universal Laws
 1. Cause and Effect/Karma
 2. Evolution
 3. Relativity
 4. Conservation
 5. Vibration
 6. Rotation/Cycles
 7. Polarity/Yin & Yang
 8. Resonance/Harmony/Rhythm
 3. Through support of the 11 Sects
 1. Mahayana Buddhism
 1. Nichiren/Tendai
 2. Ch'an/Zen
 3. Pure Land
 4. Vajrayana (Tibetan/Nepalese)
 2. Theravada Buddhism
 1. Thai
 2. Vietnamese
 3. Korean
 3. Hinduism
 4. Other Vedics
 1. Sikhism
 2. Jainism
 3. Hare Krishna
 5. Animism
 1. Aboriginal mysticism

- 2. Shamanism
- 3. Shintoism/ancestor worship
- 6. Judaism
- 7. Catholicism/Orthodoxy
- 8. Protestantism
 - 1. Baptists
 - 2. Methodists
 - 3. Lutherans
 - 4. Episcopalians
 - 5. Church of England
- 9. Modern Protestantism
 - 1. Mormon
 - 2. Seventh Day Adventists
 - 3. Witnesses
 - 4. Pentecostal
- 10. Islam
- 11. Other Philosophies
 - 1. Daoist
 - 2. Zoroastrianism
 - 3. Confucianism
- 2. Because it is not proper¹ for governments to interfere in the traditional realms of spirituality's influence on morality by legislating changes in...
 - 1. Social structure and taboos
 - 2. Cultural and linguistic regard
 - 3. Education
- 3. Because it is necessary to provide unity ala a form of a "United Nations" between religious movements and powers to provide a consensus to deal with the situation and with each other.

To see a world in a grain of sand
 And heaven in a wild flower
 Hold infinity in the palm of your hand
 And eternity in an hour.

What is 11-11-11

What is the Order of E11EVEN?

A Temple is any gathering place of members of the Order.
The Order is the collective vision of E11EVENists.

E11EVEN is not a religion, it is a philosophy of Inclusion which embraces the commonness/oneness of all phenomena and humanity/sentience.

As for 11:11...

The 11 Dimensions are found in String Theory, which mathematically binds Quantum Mechanics (Law of Vibration primarily) with Quantum Relativity (Law of Relativity primarily).

The 11 Realms are states of Vibration of mental-spiritual psyche. They are hierarchical, and the first 10 are for humans/sentients:

1. Hell or misery
2. Animals or malicious people
3. Hungry demons or the greedy/usurious
4. Angry demons or rage/hatred/spite/discrimination
 1. These are the Lower Four Realms
5. Tranquility and peace
6. Heaven or love and joy
 1. These are the Middle Two, and the Lower Six are aka normal human conditions
7. Voice-hearers or students who 'receive' a calling to enter spiritual life
8. Self-realized or ascetics, gurus, various wisemen/women
9. Bodhisattvas or teachers of the Way; whatever doctrine
 1. Mahasattvas or great-teachers of many many people; they teach the doctrine of the Bodhi Way (teaching to reach 10th Realm)
10. Buddhahood or enlightened state
 1. Temporary (accessible anytime)
 2. Permanent (through striving and acquiring wisdom and knowledge)
 1. Shakyamuni Buddha
 2. Jesus Christ Buddha
 3. Ghandi Buddha
 4. Nichiren Buddha
 5. Mother Theresa Buddha
 6. Luther King Buddha
11. Law itself:: Truth:: the One
 1. God/Jehovah/Yahweh "I am"/Allah/Krishna/etc...
 2. [Pari]Nirvana
 3. the Universe
 4. It All

5. Suchness
6. the Sound
7. Great Spirit
8. Qi
9. Dao
10. Wu/Void

The Order is the Yin aspect of the yin/yang pair E11EVEN::SHARP

E11EVEN regulates SHARP through regulating its leaders and reinforcing its directives/Constitution and keeping it from becoming a Monster or terminating it if it does.

E11EVEN provides a means for individuals of high-aptitude and moral awareness who wish to foster Peace in the world - by teaching the principles of Oneness to learn the methods of the Tathagatas (10th Realm) and Mahasattvas (9th Realm) - to gain great internal (and therefore external) power and become leaders in their communities and abroad.

E11EVEN is not for profit and not a church. We want no donations nor need any. What we do we do for the good of fostering dialogue between mankind. You need not believe this or trust it, we're not here to sell a product or convert you from a religion... we support you in your religious beliefs'!

Members of the Order of E11EVEN are those who have entered the fifth gate of Awareness:

1. That we are One.
 1. All knowledges and doctrines are parts of the same M x N matrix of It All
2. That those who know this are few; still fewer are those that seek to understand and penetrate its depths
3. That those who act on this knowledge are fewer still for unawareness of How to Act
4. That those who act must do so with spontaneity and humility, developing powers of the enlightened ones and great sages in order to win over doubters and those still under the intoxicating effects of the drug of the discriminatory mind (Yi)
5. That to act is The Act that enables the crossing of the Razor's Edge itself, fulfilling the prophecy of all the past enlightened ones.

C

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Add files

Comments

SRC

R

Ramon Careaga

Sep 18, 2010

1 - We support the RIGHT of atheists and satanists to practice/exist, though we do not condone it.

Just as we support the RIGHT of extremists in any religion. But we do not condone behavior that is dividing and vilifies/discriminates against a group simply on the basis of creed, race, color, language, etc...

Consequently, these kinds groups (KKK, Taliban, PLO, etc...) cannot become members nor receive representation within the Order as they do not believe in the brotherhood of Man. If we communicate it will not be a dialogue but a fierce debate that roots out Evil forthwith!

Tolerance is one thing, enabling is another!

Explanation of the Bagua Dharma

What are the 8 Laws?

Firstly know that they are really One Law (governed by Law of Conservation) and that these are an "approximation" (governed by Law of Relativity)... countless sublaws exist within them and between them (governed by Law of Polarity), etc... They are not separate pillars but instead fluid streams (governed by Law of Evolution) of forces changing matter and energy back and forth (governed by Law of Vibration). These 8 Laws are so subtle that they blend one into the next quicker than you can think their names (governed by Law of Rotation). They are so profound in meaning and practical that one can use them to bring you anything you truly wish for or believe you can have - or are willing to allow yourself to have - (governed by Laws of Harmony and Cause & Effect).

Four Heavenly Laws

1. Law of Cause and Effect (Karma)
 1. Heaven trigram
 2. God's MO
 1. Has been written about in every language and in every religion on Earth and certainly other planets.
 3. Contains idea of Synchronicity and Dependent Origination
 1. Yi Jing or Book of Changes
 2. Four Noble Truths and 12-linked Chain of Causation
 3. Newton's "Law"
 4. The Golden Rule
 4. Works with Conservation to create all possibilities and probability-clouds in all dimensions, realms, and planes simultaneously.
 5. Cannot be controlled by people directly; the fallacy of almost all mankind and the bane of those stuck in the Lower Six and 7th Realms.
2. Law of Evolution
 1. Wind trigram
 2. Governs chemistry, biology, the 5 elements, change in the laws, and rotation between polarities (yin and yang)
 3. Implies if you are not growing you are dying.
 4. Governs non-linear or Chaos Math or rather is governed with it.

Four Earthly Laws

1. Law of Vibration
 1. Earth trigram
 2. Implies stillness, receptivity, being in tune with the Dao or Heaven's/God's will
 3. Governs Quantum mechanics, the 11 Realms, and in general your happiness.
 4. Works with Law of Resonance (physics) or Harmony (spirit) to control Universe
 5. Is controlled by your attitude and paradigm
 1. Attitude is position and bearing (vector) with respect to thoughts, feelings, and actions.
 2. Paradigm are the habits and systems of belief that form your attitude.
 3. To change vibration, change attitude, to change attitude change your paradigm, to change your paradigm...
 1. emotional shock
 2. constant spaced repetition
2. Law of Rotation
 1. Thunder trigram
 2. Represents turning bad roots to good ones, acting with knowledge, and refinement of the self in

5. Implies that all things have an arc of life
 1. Birth
 2. Waxing
 1. Cultivation
 3. Peaking
 4. Waning
 1. Culmination
 5. Death
 6. Recovery
 7. Rebirth
3. Law of Relativity
 1. River trigram
 2. States there is no constant observer in the Physical Plane
 3. All light, thought and spirit therefore belong to the One (11th Realm)
 4. States that all human/sentient knowledge is limited to cultural dynamics and historical precedence
 5. Supports the need for all people to learn therapeutic methods to they can overcome separateness and achieve Oneness.
4. Law of Conservation
 1. Mountain trigram
 2. States that all mass, energy, data, thought, spirit, power, possibilities that have ever or ever will exist do so all all times.
 3. Implies time is a delusion of consciousness.
 1. Implies the Universe did not undergo a Big Bang and expand, but that accord with the mandate of Tian Ren Di.
3. Implies the possibility of Heaven or Hell in all moments; and enlightenment or ignorance in all moments.
4. It is said that Thunder trigram is called such for at first there is shock, then laughter... enlightenment is thus as easy to have as turning over your palm!
3. Law of Polarity
 1. Fire trigram
 2. Represents knowledge and wisdom, and seeing truth and phenomena As It Is.
 3. Governs yin and yang
 1. Interdependent
 2. Opposing
 3. Mutually generating
 4. Mutually consuming
 5. Mutually regulating
 4. Governs charges and polarities in physics
4. Law of Harmony
 1. Lake trigram
 2. Represents tranquility and peace that come of itself and know no end.
 3. Usually associated with end of life.
 4. Governs happiness
 1. You cannot remain long in contact or near to anyone or anything you are not in vibration with
 2. Thus seek that which you are in vibration with or...
 3. If it is unwholesome,

- it is expanded for us to see it All at once.
4. Implies that the One is a self-contained sphere of existence.
 5. Implies that through the Law of Polarity the One is None and thus the Void is the same as It All thus uniting western and eastern thought.
 6. Is most difficult to fathom, best to study it through fractals and do not try to comprehend it fully... it's incomprehensible, that is why the One constantly says to Himself, "I am I am I am I am, etc..."
- then change your Vibration.
5. Governs transformation
 1. Resonance implies destruction of Yin (matter) into Yang (energy)
 2. Harmony implies construction of psyche (mind-spirit) or Yang into Meaning of Life or Yin
 6. This is associated with the Law of Evolution and Rotation which govern the changes of all things we see and cycles of life and opportunities.

How does the Order Function?

How does E11EVEN work?

Yin Stage of a membership aka Cultivation¹

1. Readings
 1. Bible
 2. Torah
 3. Koran
 4. Yi Jing, Dao De Jing & Chuang Tse
 5. Tripitaka (self selections)
 6. Lotus Sutra & Gosho
 7. Tibetan Book of the Dead
 8. Upanishads & Baghavad Gita
 9. Huang Di Nei Jing
 10. Confucian Analects
 11. Hopi/Mayan Prophecies
2. Commentary
 1. creating a Personal Peace Plan
3. Examinations
4. Engaging in Dialogue in the area of residence with all 11 sects/subjects
5. Community Service
 1. Guardianship for SHARP; protecting HARP org members
6. Apprenticeship
 1. Online (limited)
 2. In Person

Yang Stage (Avatar/Bodhi) aka Movement²

1. Teaching for the Order
2. Lobbying/advocacy
3. Setting policy for [SHARP \(Society for the Hammer & Anvil Revolutionary Project\)](#); a non-violent group that represents organizations that...
 1. Advocate freedom and the Constitution of the USA (or other countries which guarantee human rights).
 2. Advocate pro-environmental policy and changing our economic system to un-enslave nature from Man and save our species from the brink.
 3. Refute evil and violence.
4. Traveling to engage in dialogue.
5. Writing treatises.
6. Building other "Temples" of E11EVEN
 1. online

2. physical temples
 3. clinics of healing
 4. writings
 5. sermons
 6. discourses
 7. discussion groups
 8. etc...
7. YOU are the temple itself. Whither you walk, trust in yourself and your own **good** nature.

SRC

Sep 18, 2010

1 - Cultivation corresponds to the Mountain trigram, or stillness or Law of Conservation.

The Academy of the Order

As of current the "Academy" is a set of principles. Over time this will evolve to a Curriculum. It will be given here at this Temple. After a time a physical place will be set for the first physical temple. This will be the first location of the Academy.

In due time this Academy will grow and there will be a raising of funds and donations. Upon a sustainable and pure land following the Tian Ren Di mandate, the Academy will be permanently established.

This is the Prophecy. It is not a mystical divination... it is a logical sequence of events that come as a result of application of intelligence and reason. Intuitive knowledge, though valuable, is not necessary here - only a little imagination.

The Principles

1. We are all One.
 1. Know this as the first gate of True Knowledge. All scientific knowledge and other subknowledges of Man are subservient to this One fact.
 2. Thus if you hate one another, then you hate yourself and you hate the One.
 1. The Ten Commandments say: "... Worship no other before Me... Love thy Neighbor as Thyself ... "
 3. To have Oneness means to love and be loved, have compassion and seek the compassionate.
2. All human knowledges can be placed onto the 'grid' of the M x N matrix; where they intersect Truth is found
3. The 11 Realms and 8 Laws serve to 'translate' religious scripture and knowledge from one culture to another.
4. The 11th Realm is One; there is no other outside the One, thus the One is Null and Void, and so we are empty within; so fulfills the Law of Polarity.
5. The 8 Laws are not separate from each other but regulate one another and regulate the One Law.
 1. If you cannot understand them all, understand Relativity (danger), Vibration (escape), Polarity (truth) and Harmony (correct life)...
 2. If you cannot understand all of these, or wish to keep it simple, then understand Polarity and Harmony.
 3. If you understand even Harmony, your Karma will be Divine.
6. The Laws cannot be bent or broken - you may fight them, but to your sickness, toil, and death.
7. The 4 Heavenly Laws are not your province - know them that you may be Saved.
8. The 4 Earthly Laws are your responsibility - know them that you may be Enlightened.
9. The 7th & 8th realms are expedients to the 9th; the 9th Realm is access to the 10th Realm (via the Bodhi Way); the 10th Realm is access to the 11th realm - there is no shortcut to permanent access, except death; suicide is not access because it is denial of responsibility of this pathway.
10. You must teach, share, convert, and uphold these 8 dharma/laws - whatever your religion may be or the presentation of these values may sound like in your culture; you must cultivate the self and forgo the UnLaw to achieve the Meaning of Life.¹

11. If you do this and make your pact with God to be a Vessel of the Law(s), you will be protected here and in the afterlife - even Hell would not keep you from the 11th Realm; if at death you should choose to come back rather than stay, you will encounter this again... for you are constantly the high aspect of the One recognizing itself and repeating the one incantation² of consciousness and truth... "I am I am I am I am" etc...

Treatise on Walking the Path

From Cultivation to Motivation

Introduction

To be sure, one should understand that one does not cultivate solely and separately and then "arrive" at Motivation. Rather, one cultivates and cultivates, growing from a seed to a sapling, planting good roots, then from a sapling to a tree, and continues even beyond that to gathering enough merit, virtue, wisdom, knowledge, and essence to bear fruit. At this point, the person has become a fruit-bearing tree and this stage of life, until death, is known as Motivation.

One continues to cultivate, continues to grow all one's life, just as a tree never ceases growing and reaching for the Sun, which of course is the penultimate representation of the Heaven trigram itself (pure Yang).¹ In fact the Chinese character for Yang is the same as the Sun.²

Thus we see that for a time in life - usually at youth until maturity, but not limited to then - one should enter the path of striving (just as a sapling battles weeds, ferns, shrubs, and vines for supremacy) and advance the Yang of the spirit.

Once this path has been cultivated, the tree spends some time in maturation and ripening, hardening and testing one's 'bark' against the winds and storms of life and then when the Summer of life comes, bear fruit.

The path of striving thus continues on, bearing fruit, mating yin and yang, until at last the individual ceases to be individual and recognizes the spontaneity of Action.

Fruit no longer fall to the forest floor uneaten and rot away - they fall into hands of those who are hungry... starving even... and the path of non-striving is consummated for however much time one is allotted, as the case may be. This may be only 5 minutes, or it may be 50 years; that is quite individual.

Reader and members - fellow E11EVENists - you must understand that this treatise contains no hard and fast rules, but rather guidelines. Each person and every path is different.

There are those that wish to walk the Forest alone, like an elephant, committing no sin. There are those that enjoy the forest, and blend in tune with it. There are those that meander upon its paths in wonder and awe. There are those that run amok through it in fear and desperation, afraid of its loneliness - for it is lonely.

There are those that seek a way out; those that find a way out; those that know the way out; and those teach the Way out.

These guidelines thus must form a relative sameness between different persuasions, vagaries of thought, and biases of culture and historical view in order to be interchangeable and exchangeable, and enable the E11EVENist to move about freely. And they are relatively the same between lay persons and "spiritual

professionals' as it is the religion of one's persuasion that should provide the basis for refinement; not the Order itself.

What follows therefore is not based on any scripture, sutra, or parable, but upon Universal Law, and in particular, the sublaws³ of education and refinement:

- 5/90/5 Rule
 - 95/5 is OK
- Tathagata⁴ Curve
 - 11 Realms

The 95/5 Rule is a basic statement that uses the Bell Curve to define the various capabilities, interests, and divisions of groups. In essence, 5% of any group cannot understand the topic that unites them, 90% don't understand (half want to, half don't), and 5% do understand.

The Law of Polarity immediately insinuates that of these 5% that do understand, again they may be divided up again (and again and again) until at last you arrive at the 10th Realm, which is the penultimate of "coming and going" where one perceives the forwards, backwards, up, down, center, and outside of the argument with clarity and precision AND one can act upon it.

The Tathagata Curve explains the spiritual energy from the exponential perspective. This diagram, not ironically, is displaying Kinetic Energy of a mass approaching the speed of light, here set at "1", which acts as an asymptote and explains why only the Tathagatas, who are near to it, can open the door to the 11th Realm. This means Jesus, Buddha, Ghandi, Mother Theresa, and whoever else you see evidence of being able to open the door for others and exhibiting living in Nirvana (Oneness). The AUC or Area under Curve represents the sum total of energy they contain... as you can see the Tathagata has as much energy allocated to him as all the other 9 realms combined... and this is a mathematical function (ratio) of the Universe... such that at any given time, someone somewhere is in the 10th realm, and together with the 5th-9th are offsetting the great amount of negativity and woe we see in our news and on our streets today.

Reader, you must clearly understand that one experiences all the 10 Realms daily and within each other, as a vibration within a vibration... but what you Resonate with or Harmonize upon - that which is your

base - is your primary Realm. You should seek to know this average state in yourself and in others, and seek to raise all. This is the vow of the E11EVENist.

It is not easy - and for that reason one should know that it is wholly dependent on oneself, one's willingness to expend energy upon this task, and one's innate Jing or inborn essence of ability. Also, one's inherited Karma (caste, class, and Jing) will affect life conditions and health conditions to influence this Path. You cannot be blamed for the "arrival" only for the journeying. Much as a traveling cannot be blamed for the sinking of his ship or being besought by highwaymen and waylayers.

This has led many to comment, "It's not the destination but the journey that matters."

This is a positive sentiment, but clearly erroneous. Both equally matter. You do not set out upon a journey to wander aimlessly (if you wish to accomplish anything and achieve potential), but to find your Destination. Some idly imagine that Fate will carry them all the way to a Destiny, and aim to "float like a leaf on the river of life". This is fine until the river ends up in a dry desert lake. Everyone has the opportunity to guide their Destiny as a captain can choose his port of call. But the storms... this you cannot control.⁵

Before entering the First Gate (the Gate of 5 Gates), let me clearly make known the manner of changing Karma.

As the

past->paradigm->beliefs->thoughts->feelings->actions->results->past->paradigm

And we cannot change the past; and this illustrates that past=future (Karma); then clearly **the only way to affect one's Karma is to change one's paradigm(s).**

The only way this is done is through changing a Vibration (lit: changing your tune) which is an attitude of belief and thought. The difficulty lies in *how* this is done; especially given most people are partially or completely (depending on their Realm) controlled by their emotional mind and thus always miss the opportunity to make the change.

These are the only two ways to change your Tune:

1. Emotional shock aka realization
 1. Thus the Zen idea of Satori
 2. Thus the act of "Voice-hearing"
 3. Thus the conceiving of a desire for salvation or bodhi.
2. Constant-spaced-repetition aka Hard Work!
 1. Thus the path of Cultivation.

The ignorant wait for the former, the smart bet on the latter, the Wise utilize both with increasing frequency and efficacy.

One can, and has the right, to delay the tilling of the field, but must, as a consequence suffer the bitterness of a Winter unprepared. This has been said in every religion and we can also see it in life as well with old and careworn people who have no one to care for them in their latter years. That is surely not the Meaning of Life! We are meant to find our potential just as a lotus is meant to bloom and a ship to reach its harbor.

Article 1 - the Five Gates

I will briefly summarize them now, then explain each in some relative detail... as much as possible without initiating dogma.

1. Ignorance Is :: thus existence in the Lower 6 Realms
2. Awareness of Ignorance :: thus Ignorance of Danger
3. Awareness of Danger :: thus Ignorance of Escape
4. Awareness of Escape :: thus Ignorance of the Way
5. Awareness of the Way :: thus Escape through Mastery

Mastery and refinement, through the Formula⁸ is not a Gate... it is the Gate of no-Gate, "the Way that can be walked is not the Way".

Let us use an example. If you desired to be famous, perhaps, in music, you must reach approximately 50% of ears. If you wanted to be a musician in the US, then, you must reach 150 million ears. That means you are going to be one of 938 people who figured out the Way to famousness... roughly about the size of Hollywood's most active celebrities.

But of those 938 only about 48 or so will become immortally famous - Clint Eastwood or Michael Jordan, etc...

Thus, to be an E11EVENist, first recognize the size of the community you wish to affect, and then you will know how hard you must work. In my community, for example, I will have to work 10 times harder than my future community... but since I wish to affect 100 times this community, I must work 1000 times harder than I need to... so the Tathagata Curve prediction is accurate.

Now, as for the individual gates.

Wood Gate⁹

When one is in youth, one is essentially innocent, ignorant, and pure. It is only through interaction with the environment and learning to sow bad roots that one comes to change this. Yet, as we enter the second Gate (almost all cases unknowingly) our Yang nature is penetrated and evolves. By puberty we begin to have the desires and still we have not exited Ignorance. It is true that we are essentially aware and learning of 'adult' things - drugs, sex, work, relationships, etc... - but our fundamental Ignorance of ourselves remains because our parents, even the best of them, cannot tell us who we are. The riddle to our Selves was postulated at conception, thus how could they know the answer?⁹

The key to understanding this Gate is that it is the largest number of people in all age categories and in any group. It is the first 95%. 5% cannot physically know themselves; they may be mentally challenged, mentally ill, physically ill, etc... but the rest live in Ignorance out of ignorance of being in Ignorance.

If people were fundamentally honest with themselves, they could pass through this Gate; thus we know the first skill to teaching the Way to Escape... self-honesty.

The primary tool to developing this skill is critical thinking, because children are deficient in critical thinking skills, their intuition is quite useless for development; only for 'small things' of no consequence to their long-term life.

To develop critical thinking skills and self-honesty are hard work for the vast majority of people. Even through this Gate we see that it does not guarantee Escape... in fact, with many people it leads to an Arrogance of presumption. Young people - usually men - group together in throngs on forums and the internet pouring out vehement messages of hatred, name-calling, and discrimination because they suppose they have knowledge. But even the strongest critical thinker, if he does not pass through the second Gate... what use is he? Better to remain quiet and cultivate.¹⁰

The best method to helping a disciple or friend in this regard is challenge. Never rest as long as you can in helping them see themselves and be honest with themselves. However one must not fail to see one's own planks in the eyes; and also not destroy confidence or self-esteem. A moment of humility is one thing... depression is totally different; the difference is in setting oneself on high to keep them down, and this is rooted in Darkness.

River-Mountain Gate

Just as we see that a swift river running through the mountain is a danger to a rafter... so is the river of life when one is 'caught up' in the desires, vices, and behaviors of one's ill-designed Karma. Without refinement, the river cuts, bangs, crashes, splurches, falls, stagnates, and in general has no fluid nature... it is raw and unrefined.

This corresponds to the time when one must realize that you are ignorant and in danger of losing the Meaning of Life; not because it will be lost like Atlantis in one fell swoop... but because a minute turns to an hour, to a day, to a week, a month, a year, a decade, and a lifetime. Without having started, having put off the MOST important business of sentience, one cannot finish. The course of work is already quite long; why delay?

Generally speaking, it is better if a person is young when they reach this Gate; especially better to do so before getting married and having children, which would naturally cause some slowing of self-development to focus on the inherent problems of the relationship and the 'salvation' of children.

But, technically speaking a person can enter the 7th Realm at any age, any time. The more time one has to commit to the teachings of one's faith, martial art, sport, etc... that refines one's nature, the more likely of passing through the next Gate.

Fully 95% of the first 5% or 99/100 people will not pass this Gate. If you are working with your sangha/community of followers, if you can help 100 people in your 100... then another 900 elsewhere must go without. It is a sad fact, but also a function of the Tathagata curve and also of consciousness. Do not fight the rule... and do not be saddened at this balance. It is not your responsibility.

The key skill, therefore, here is consummation of self-honesty and refinement of seeking behavior. Many people seek - and seek outside - endlessly without luck. Here the story of [Acres of Diamonds](#)' is most apt to remind us that we have paths all around us.

Indeed the forest floor looks to the walker to be dangerous and obscured, but upon inspection one will see it is all dirt and gaps everywhere. The paths can go anywhere, and nowhere. Already in your life is the Way if you can see it.

Occasionally the Sangha you grew up in is unhealthy for you, and you have to seek elsewhere... and using the 8 Laws, you will certainly get what you need.

Having entered the 7th Realm, "when the student is ready the Teacher will appear."

Earth Gate

The innate meaning of the previous gate is stillness of a mountain... the mountain is the highest, grandest manifestation of Earth. Indeed it is the mountain you see through the dark canopy above and want to climb which guides your heart.

The Earth Gate is setting one's Vibration. It is pure 7th Realm, without the mistakes and regressions of falling back into one's old ways again. One always experiences the Lower 6 Realms... but to be moved by them, this is the bane of 99/100 people.

But for that 100th person, the reward is sweet, the air fresh. Emerging from the dark forest, one sees he/she is at the Root of the great mountain. It is a long climb to the top of one's faith, community, and mastering doctrines. One is in fact not quite sure how to climb to the top... and searches again outside for help.

The 8th Realm types - arhats, worthies, gurus, hermits, etc... - will tell you to search within yourself. This you can do, and risk not passing the next Gate. Or you should more likely clearly discern those around you and find the 1/1000 person who can help you because they actually are upon a high ledge and taking good perspective. The other 95% of those like you... they are climbing just as you are.

Once again, the view is nice, the air clear... many will not leave the mountainside, or will sit upon their plateaus and admire their work. This is their right, and they incur no judgment from anyone below or above! Those in the forest are jealous... those climbing know the work is hard.

The key skills in the climber's tool-belt are these:

- humility - ask for help, you will need it!
- willingness
- good solid work ethic
- clarity of Vision - working with one's self-honesty this is a key to guiding life
- endurance and perseverance
 - Parable of the Sower
 - Beware of 'paper walls'
 - Remember the Razor's Edge

Remember... most paths will carry you to the top if you have the right guide. If you have the wrong guide, you may fall off a precipice (ruin), into a ravine (suffering/entrapment), or not have your ropes tied off above you (betrayal). Choose well.

Lightening Gate

Lightning has the image of fire and of thunder... a flash of brilliance or illumination, and the Thunderous roar of spontaneous action consummating your newly forged Karma.

Those who say you cannot grasp: ask them when forging oneself in the fire, you apply the hammer... "do you let loose the hot sword!?"

Of course not, this is a dangerous time when the refinement is like as not to fail or be abandoned. If your life could be described as a medicinal cooking - 95% of people ruin the herbal decoction (or meal) here.

Remember... they are not to be blamed. They will see this Gate, and having gone as far as their teacher could go... or that they are willing to go, they gather at their plateaus and enjoy the view.

This is also important because having discovered that there is Escape from the dark forest of Ignorance, they lend a hand to those below, and help while those in the next level are busy with the final climb.

It is important to rest here and not go on without cessation. But it is important not to rest here forever; the joints will cool, the sweat dry, and the spirit wane for the climb ahead, which is 10 times the journey thus far.

So fully 9,999/10,000 of those who reach the 8th Realm do not leave it... and reaching below to aid others, they are often dragged back into the work. Very much of the time they exhibit the telltale signs of frustration, cynicism, and giving up on mankind.

As it happens this is the mistake that prevents the opening of the last Gate.

So we see that the skills are much the same, but even more intense:

- Searching for more skilled sages, doctrines, texts, and clarification of meaning
- Humility
- Dissatisfaction with the life of Striving.
- Ultimate Endurance

Refining oneself with constant, daily patience... one comes to leave behind frustration with others... ceasing to see them as separate and seeing the demons and enemies within oneself not as opponents but sparring partners and revelations of Enlightenment.

Your fundamental nature which has been mixed with yin can be sublimated (transformed without intermediate steps) to true Yin, which will nourish the Yang spirit back to its Original Face and vitality. You will cease to see your idiosyncrasies as problems so much as course work itself.

Water Gate

Having discerned one's nature clearly, penetrated one's faith with power, one now passes through a gate (usually later in life, it just depends on the efforts hitherto) of non-regression. One experiences the Lower Realms, but are not stopped by them. One is a student, but not under anyone. One is enlightened but not arrogant; instead one is pleasant to be around and friendly without and within.

Now approaching the peak, you come to a point of ponderance... "How to sit upon the peak and not fall down the other side?"

This ponderance of the Gate of No-Gate is key to the rest in one's goodness... you do not rest; you are not "arrived" you are "ready".

The mountain, you find, is a grain... and above you lies the rest of the mountain of the 10th Realm. You are able to help others and still climb the mountain, for you are now so few in number the journey upwards is quite unlike before but instead wide and open, and the view nice. Though your climb up Everest is paled by the climb up Olympus Mons to come, having come so far... why be daunted now? There is nothing to fear. It is time to become a Motivator.

Article II - The Various Doctrines and Scriptures

Without debating them and citing them, I want to make it clear to E11EVENists the reality of the M x N Matrix.

There is no end to this Matrix. Even upon our planet were it to magically be filled, there are other worlds, other cultures, other dimensions, etc... where the Matrix is continually renewed in empty, uncharted lands of knowledge. In fact, it is 95% mystery at all times.

Where the smaller subsets, series, etc... of knowledge cross: this is the wisdom of truth contained within all doctrines.

But we are not speaking of these same qualities, but of the multitudes of varying theses written over the last 5,000 years.

Here's another Truth: some of these are more efficient at guiding the climbing of the mountain than others. But none is more "right" than any other. To a person within their culture, the most familiar doctrine may be most useful and in another it would be another. Even still people are born out of place, out of time, even in the wrong body... and thus they will find doctrines and ways of other lands/cultures to be of more use.

The important thing here for the E11EVENist is that once one is a Motivator, or when practicing it during Cultivation, one is not to work solely with people of one's particular cohort of Vibrations. But instead one should seek to aid all others in finding the best doctrine, cohort, and Sangha for them. A hike is more fun with a friend, and a Sunday stroll increased by good conversation.

Do not be greedy or chincy; not helping those of varying beliefs... aid them and be a friend in the orchid room. Only by that method can you enter the Gate of No-Gate.

However, though all faiths/paths have a doorway - however meandering the path - they are certainly not all equal in potency. It is my advice to seek the most potent, and increase your potency thereby and also through refinement of faith, attitudes, reduction of fear, actions, and a good supporting cast.

Most importantly, however, is to not stay satisfied in the 8th Realm if you wish to be a Motivator... this is counterintuitive. Nobody will look up to the quitters forever... and you can really only help one or two with your ropes here. Those at the peak leave long ropes that go everywhere... nets even... but in the 8th Realm one is quite impotent.

From this newfound perspective of the 9th and 10th Realms, one will see all the mountains of the chain, and not simply the rock in one's face. These mountains, no matter their shape, hue, size, smoothness, volatility, etc... they are all still mountains, and therefore worthy climbs for those upon them. Some will avalanche, and some will explode... so choose a mountain that is firm and smooth if you can... but really it is inconsequential to the climber who reaches the Summit Road.

Article III - the "End" of Cultivation

One thing that will become very clear to you once you enter the path of the Motivator - and in fact it is (as said above) the key aspect holding the door shut firmly - is that the formula to the 10th Realm requires you to help others.

"You have to do it by yourself; but you can't do it alone."

It is a fact that the energy it requires to be a normal human is quite small (only by summation of population does it equal the great ones). To reach the upper realms requires increasing effort and sacrifice, and often loneliness and struggle. But the primary thing separating those of the 8th and 9th Realms is merely the volition to Act.

The separation of the 9th and 10th Realm is about power and constancy of application of Principle. But the 8th to 9th Realm: that is solely about choice. Thus just as the Voice-hearer feels a painful relief upon entering the 7th Realm... seeing the light at the edge of the dark forest as it were... those receiving the "bodhicitta" or vow of attainment for all beings it is a relieving pain. The former gave one escape and

excuse to be separate from one's community for a time. The latter gave one responsibility for one's community once again; and the pain of seeing this community after such a time can be traumatic and difficult.

This is where the Ultimate Endurance becomes necessary.

The other key here is to have thoroughly invested in one's Theoretical Education so that when one enters Motivation one is prepared for the shock of brutal truth in Life.

At this point Cultivation becomes more and more refinement of the sword - hammering it flat and sharp:

- Powers of Observation
- Powers of Persuasion
- Patience
- Fortitude
- Dialogue over debate
- Maturity

Article IV - Teaching Others

In general the Guidelines are a short list of precepts, but here I wish to enumerate some broader concepts.

Firstly one's faith - especially if it is potent - should have a list of Peaceful Practices or ways to deal with one's sangha and other people, and share/proselytize. But, these are general practices for Order of E11VEN:

1. No condemnation, judgment, nor condoning (of that which is incorrect in your view); in other words, be impartial.
2. Affirm Oneness, no matter the difficulty (this is a test of maturity and patience).
3. Be compassionate and Love
4. Have 'relative' detachment.
 1. Follow your faith's guidelines here, and what is correct for you as a lay person or professional.
5. Share when asked; teach when ready
 1. When you are ready.
 2. When they are ready.
6. Use expedients... teach according to their:
 1. Needs
 2. Abilities
 3. Biases
 4. Culture
 5. Interests
7. Do not expect much in general.
8. Realize that of the 5% you reach:
 1. Some will be 33% of their potential
 2. Some will be 66% of their potential
 3. Some will be 100% of their potential
 4. This is not under your control; it's how they get the lifestyle they need.
9. When asked of your faith, patiently explain it; do not expect much.
10. When asked of 11:11, say "Yes I am Aware and more importantly I know where to find it."

11. If they ask beyond that... then share a 11:11 temple or this Temple; but do not expect much.

Article V - Motivation

Thus the doorway henceforth has been to Act. Now once one acts, one must do so with conviction, power, and force of personality.

Do not waste your time by apologizing, being small, acting small, or avoiding the Elephant in the Room.

It is obvious to others you are gifted... and to not share is greedy. If you do not share you may cost another needy friend or patient years of struggle in the forest. Then they may find a bad teacher!

When the opportunity arises, move vigorously forward, advancing all Yang to the point of utter ruin to the enemy: Ignorance.

But when a person resists, and repels... this is a sign that you should stop the advance. Real in your line, gather yourself up. There are other people, other ones in need: address them.

Learn to teach those who have earned it, not those whom you think deserve it. But... teach others to earn your time.

Speaking of time, one should be compensated for one's time:

- monetary
- trades of goods and services
- acquiring students or others time
- new contacts
- knowledge and wisdom shared

One should be compensated well: if you live well, you will earn well.

Moreover do not fight for compensation and respect, that is clingy behavior.

If people do not respect you, do not respect themselves, do not do as they promised, and say as they mean in their hearts: sigh and think, "Isn't that interesting?"

That is all one can do.

Once you begin to act - do not apologize: there is no one over you anymore that you have not placed there. If someone asserts their dominion over you: realize they likely have none.

But fear not! Engage them and all peoples in dialogue - tirelessly - and in activity and sharing of knowledge and wisdom that way all will be benefited from your benevolent demeanor. You will greatly enrich your Sangha now that you are a Motivator... all the more so if you refine your powers and learn from great Mahasattvas and [their texts](#)

Be fruitful, and enjoy your work... do not work in something you do not enjoy, and do not do something which contradicts this vow to aid others and Oneness.

But above all: enjoy the Act of helping; after all it's why we are all here in the first place.

Thank you,
Shifu Careaga

Add files

Comments

SRC

R

Ramon Careaga

Sep 20, 2010

11 - At the heart of his lecture was a parable Conwell heard while traveling through present-day Iraq in 1870:

There was once a wealthy man named Ali Hafed who lived not far from the River Indus. "He was contented because he was wealthy, and wealthy because he was contented." One day a priest visited Ali Hafed and told him about diamonds.

Ali Hafed heard all about diamonds, how much they were worth, and went to his bed that night a poor man. He had not lost anything, but he was poor because he was discontented, and discontented because he feared he was poor.

Ali Hafed sold his farm, left his family, and traveled to Palestine and then to Europe searching for diamonds. He did not find them. His health and his wealth failed him. Dejected, he cast himself into the sea.

One day, the man who had purchased Ali Hafed's farm found a curious sparkling stone in a stream that cut through his land. It was a diamond. Digging produced more diamonds — acres of diamonds, in fact. This, according to the parable, was the discovery of the famed diamonds of Golconda.

Reply

R

Ramon Careaga

Sep 20, 2010

10 - This doesn't mean one shouldn't use one's rights and freedoms to expression and free speech. But it is important not to overstate a matter, or over assert a thing. I myself, at this period was in fact 180 degrees different from now. I was brash, brazen, arrogant, atheist, and full of certainty that I was right. But by opening my heart, my ears, and doubting my own wisdom, I came to see my inherent dangers and through the martial art found the Way. After much stumbling through that path... only then was I able to escape the forest.

So I do not judge from a position of ignorance of this refinement: I myself epitomized the activities of an arrogant person asserting his correctness in ignorance. If I had not changed I certainly could not have met my wife, nor have harmonized yin and yang. I would be a wholly different person.

Reply

R

Ramon Careaga

Sep 20, 2010

9 - indeed parents themselves are often trying to find the solution to themselves when they have children. In fact, most have not even Harmonized with their spouses and found that special Tune that welds them into one heart... and thus the years of child rearing can totally change the tune for each and people often go through mid-life crises due to this. It is a natural course of the Law of Harmony.

Reply

R

Ramon Careaga

Sep 20, 2010

8 - Wood because the trigram is Wind, which associated with Spring, which is associated with the Wood element; reaching, grasping, working hard to break through above. The wind has an image of yin stripping away Yang from below: this is the danger of striving and wearing oneself out.

Reply

R

Ramon Careaga

Sep 20, 2010

7 - As it happens, my goal is pretty on par with the celebrity math done above, that is I wish to affect the entire US community as an E11EVENist.

Reply

R

Ramon Careaga

Sep 20, 2010

6 - study (7th) + practice (8th) + teach (9th) = attainment (10th)

Reply

R

Ramon Careaga

Sep 20, 2010

5 - I apologize for the number of euphemisms, but it is not easy to make the matter clear without a lot of verbiage, except through imagery.

Reply

R

Ramon Careaga

Sep 20, 2010

4 - Tathagata means one who comes a goes freely. Synonym: Thus Come One.

Reply

R

Ramon Careaga

Sep 20, 2010

3 - sublaws meaning not the 8 Universal Laws but some partial aspect of them, often combined with parts of some or all 8 Bagua Dharma (laws)

Reply

R

Ramon Careaga

Sep 20, 2010

2 - literally the sunny side of a hill with the radical of the Sun, and shady side of a hill is Yin, but contains the radical for the Moon.

Reply

R

Ramon Careaga

Sep 20, 2010

1 - Yang is characterized by the unbroken line, and Heaven by three unbroken lines (trigram). The Yang referred to here is the spirit and essence derived from the Divine, which is pure and unsullied.

General Guidelines

1. Study, practice, and teach - whatever faith you have (and whatever sect you fall into/under).
2. When you meet one another, as you inevitably will, you can identify yourselves via the recitation of 11-11-11
 1. Those who are called will know OF it.
 2. Those who are awake will know it by name and meaning.
 3. Those who are within it will know it period.
3. Go into the throngs and masses and share...
4. Do not open the door to 11-11-11, let it be instead a person who has heard of it and their curiosity has led them to you.
5. Share but do not expect much.
6. Realize that struggle is faith and growth... do not lament, you are knocking on the door of Enlightenment!
7. Do not engage in frivolous debate over tiny details and unimportant trivialities and eccentricities. Thus the Law of Relativity (which having a body dictates you cannot have ultimate View) is aka the River trigram; before one knows it, he is already in danger of drowning [in his own delusions and karma].
8. Seek to aid others find the sects and belief systems THAT BENEFIT THEM... not your own personal agenda and belief system...
 1. Love your friends and those in your Vibrational cohort... and guide them and befriend them and guard them from error.
 2. Take pity and compassion on your enemies and guide them away from yourself but towards their own cohorts and do not see them with enmity but Love.

9. Engage in work that brings you health and happiness, and above all value family, for it is the first of all communities. Do not engage in work that violates the One Law!
 1. Once you know of your living in Sin and sowing bad Karma... stop!
10. Enjoy Life and the ride... it is after all a drug you took to enjoy mystery and enjoy not knowing - you are part of the One who has no beginning, no end, and is all data and all Qi... thus you fulfill a need to exist for a time as a unique flower, and enrich the great garden; when you have enjoyed this drug to the fullest, return to the One having achieved the Meaning of Life!
11. And above all study (7th) + practice (8th) + teach (9th) = 10th

Students studying Daoism (Taoism) may also find it handy to read all of the following:

- **Book of History**
- **Spring and Autumn Annals**
- The Warring States
- **Huang Di Nei Jing - Yellow Emperor's Inner Classic**
 - **Acupuncture Classic**
 - Pulse Classic
 - Shang Han Lun
 - **Pi Wei Lun**
- **Bing Fa - the Art of War**

- **Biography of Sun Tzu (Sun-zi)**
- **Sun Bin Bing Fa**
- **Tai Kung's 6 Secret Teachings**
- **Questions and Answers of Tang TaiTsong**
- **Three Strategies of Huang Shihkung**
- **Wu Tzu (Wu Qi Bing Fa)**
- **Wei Liao Tzu**
- **Ssu-ma Fa - Marshal's Art of War**
- **The 36 Strategems**
- **Zhuge Liang's Way of the General**
- **Guiguzi (not yet translated)**
- Romance of the Three Kingdoms
 - **Vol 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6**
- **Journey to the West**
- **108 Heroes - The Outlaws of the Marsh**

- **Myths and Legends of China**
- **Confucius' Lun Yu - the Analects**
 - **Multilingual**
 - **Doctrine of the Mean**
 - **Da Shui - The Great Learning**
 - **Legge's Translation**
 - **Complete Confucianism**
- **Mencius' Writings**
- **Book of Rites**

- **The Book of Filial Piety**
- **The Book of Odes**
- **Taoist Medical Gymnastics (Gung Fu)**

Visioneer

Shifu Careaga's Vision is a society that is sustainable, self-supporting, values natural and human resources, and government that is not engaged in corruption and destruction of liberty and the environment. As a Chinese medical practitioner and teacher of the Bagua Dharma, his sincerest hope and compassion is a disease reduced and stress reduced society.

"It is said in the classics that there are three main evils. Evils of the society and family, evils of the body, and evils of the psyche. Our society shows corruption on all three levels. Our society does not respect the family nor even know the Odes which guide family life. Thus divorce is now greater than 50% and many children are neglected or abused. Our bodies are over-stressed by emotions, nutritional deficiency, and overwork as well as normal daily pathogenic attack. Our children are fed garbage in the stores and schools, and parents do not know who to trust as an authority, despite the existence of Indian, Chinese, and Japanese classics which have been proven efficacious in both regards. Our psyches are bombarded by nonsense

in marketing, junk news-media, and shallow entertainment that corrupts our view of humanity and hurts our self-esteem." -Shifu Careaga

Therefore his Vision unfolds in three main areas:

I - Natural and Holistic Medicine; teaching society and individuals time-proven values in health and nutrition

II - Spiritual Expansion and awareness-evolution; explaining the Laws that unite faith with science and math.

III - Environmental advocacy, of policies, of sustainable agriculture and new ways of looking at nature and human relations with it, and of combining I & II with III for a rounded experience.

In addition, there are individual projects that support and fulfill this Vision by filling in missing gaps.